

REPORT ON POLICY ENVIRONMENTS FOR DIGITALISATION IN EUROPE

30 SEPTEMBER 2025

POLICY ENVIRONMENT ANALYSIS: ANTONIO R. HURTADO (UCO), MARÍA MAR DELGADO-SERRANO (UCO)

AKIS ANALYSIS: PIERRE LABARTHE (INRAE)

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17235435](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17235435)

Status: approved by the EC

Funded by
the European Union

CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement n. 101060179. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

D6.2 REPORT ON POLICY ENVIRONMENTS FOR DIGITALISATION IN EUROPE

Project name	Maximising the CO-benefits of agricultural Digitalisation through conducive digital ECoSystems
Project acronym	CODECS
Horizon Europe Topic ID	HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-22
Project ID	101060179
Website	www.horizoncodecs.eu
Document Type	Deliverable
File Name	D6.2 Report on policy environments for digitalisation in Europe
Status	Final
Dissemination level	Public
Date of creation	30 September 2025
Keywords	Digital literacy, digital uptake, farming technologies, digital ecosystems, digitalisation.
Authors	Policy Environment Analysis: Antonio R. HURTADO (UCO), María Mar DELGADO-SERRANO (UCO) AKIS Analysis: Pierre LABARTHE (INRAE)
Work Package Leader	WP6 - BSC
Project Coordinator	University of Pisa

**Funded by
the European Union**

CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement n. 101060179. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This license enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator.

Content

Executive Summary	3
Acknowledgements	5
List of Acronyms	6
1. Introduction	8
2. Methodology	9
2.1 Analysis of Policy Environments	9
2.2 AKIS Models for Digitalisation	13
2.3 Country Profiles.....	14
3. Policy Insights from Previous Projects	14
3.1 Contributions from DESIRA	14
3.2 Policy Recommendations from Previous Projects.....	15
4. Domains and Pathways of Agricultural Digitalisation	19
4.1 Four Domains of Agricultural Digitalisation	19
4.1.1 Digital Communication and Knowledge Exchange	19
4.1.2 Government-Farmer Interface.....	19
4.1.3 Operational Efficiency and Productivity	20
4.1.4 Transparency and Market Connectivity	20
4.2 Evolution of Farm Digital Maturity.....	21
4.2.1 Initial Stage (Familiarisation).....	21
4.2.2 Adoption Stage (Standalone Tools).....	22
4.2.3 Integration Stage (Connected Systems).....	22
4.2.4 Smart Farming Stage.....	23
5. Policy Tools for Digitalisation in Agriculture and Rural Areas	23
5.1 The Common Agricultural Policy	23
5.2 CAP National Strategic Plans.....	25
5.3 Other Policy Levers	31
6. Insights from Interviews with Policymakers and Experts	34
6.1 Digitalisation in CODECS Countries.....	34
6.2 Agricultural Digitalisation in CODECS Countries	36
6.2.1 Frontrunner: Strengths and Challenges Ahead	37
6.2.2 Advanced Performers: Progress and Bottlenecks	38
6.2.3 Growing Performers: Building Momentum and Addressing Gaps	42

6.2.4	Early-Stage Performers: Structural Barriers and Opportunities.....	44
6.3	Digitalisation in the CAP National Strategic Plans.....	48
6.4	Other Policy Areas Influencing Digitalisation in Agriculture	52
6.5	Cross-Cutting Insights on Digitalisation Drivers, Barriers, and Enablers	53
6.5.1	Contextual Conditions and Regional Endowments.....	53
6.5.2	Farmer Motivations and Behavioural Drivers	54
6.5.3	Systemic Barriers.....	56
6.5.4	Digitalisation and Technology Management	57
7.	AKIS, Living Labs, and Intermediaries in the CODECS Countries	58
7.1	Insights from Former Research Projects	59
7.2	Insights from the AKIS Mapping Exercises Implemented in CODECS Living Labs	59
7.3	Insights from a Qualitative Survey with Innovation Intermediaries	62
8.	Final Remarks.....	64
	References.....	70
	Annexes	73
	Annex 1: Interview Guide – Policymakers at EU Level	73
	Annex 2: Interview Guide – Policymakers at EU, Extra EU and National Level	75
	Annex 3: Country Values for the Four Pillars of Agricultural Digitalisation	77
	Annex 4: EU-Funded Initiatives with Relevant Policy Recommendations	78
	Annex 5: Methodology and Results on Innovation Intermediaries for Digital Innovation for Farmers.....	96
	Annex 6: Country Profiles	107

Executive Summary

This CODECS report on policy environments for digitalisation in Europe (Deliverable 6.2) establishes a baseline to understanding how European and national policies shape the digital transformation of agriculture and rural areas in the different countries analysed. Drawing on the review of policy recommendations from past projects, current European Union (EU) and national policy initiatives regarding digitalisation in agriculture and rural areas, and interviews with policymakers and experts across 15 EU Member States and three candidate countries, the report identifies progress made, challenges ahead, and the systemic conditions that will determine the future trajectory of digitalisation in agriculture, both in general and specifically for each country. This analysis is complemented by an examination of the AKIS system, focusing on the relationship between two interconnected policy domains: AKIS policies and the instruments that support the sustainable digitalisation of agriculture, such as living labs. The AKIS analysis is undertaken from the perspective of innovation intermediaries, which are deemed as central in both domains. Country profiles including agriculture data, digitalisation facts and AKIS analysis have been drafted for each country. All these insights provide the basis for Deliverable 6.3 (*Policy Recommendations and Toolbox*), to be delivered in Month 48 of the project.

Key Findings

- **Agricultural digitalisation is conditioned by the broader digital landscape.** The level of agricultural digitalisation largely mirrors a country's overall digital advancement and is conditioned by multiple, interconnected divides in connectivity, skills, and farm size.
- **A clear, proactive policy vision and context-specific policies are essential.** Many digital technologies can contribute to improve food security, green transition, productivity, sustainability, and resilience in agriculture. Farmer uptake requires proactive and coordinated policies to steer investments, supported by robust EU-level regulation on data and cybersecurity to build trust and ensure digital sovereignty. Adoption pathways are influenced by factors as diverse as geography, farm structure, markets, and culture. A layered policy architecture is needed: strategic guidance and funding at EU level, enabling frameworks at national level, and granular programme design at regional and local level.
- **A narrow perspective risks underestimating the transformative potential of digital technologies.** A meaningful assessment requires a clear understanding of the four pathways where digital technologies can have an impact: digital communication and knowledge exchange, government-farmer interface, operational efficiency and productivity, and transparency and market connectivity.
- **Digitalisation is a multi-stage process.** The adoption of digital technologies in farming is not uniform and can be understood as a process with four stages that depend on affordability, digital skills, and a supportive ecosystem: initial stage (familiarisation), adoption stage (standalone tools), integration stage (connected systems), and smart farming.
- **A systemic and interdependent challenge.** Digitalisation in agriculture is shaped by multiple, interconnected factors. Interviews conducted with policymakers and experts consistently showed that no single lever (such as technology, policy, finance, skills, advisory support, or infrastructure) can deliver results in isolation. Success depends on a coherent and synergistic approach across all these domains.
- **The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is a key lever, with challenges.** For the first time, the CAP requires Member States to include a digital strategy in their National Strategic Plans. This has prompted crucial engagement with the topic. Digitalisation is integrated through eco-schemes, investments, and advisory services. However, the CAP is also seen as a source of increased bureaucracy, and its digital interventions are dispersed and challenging to evaluate.
- **The central role of governance and institutions.** Effective digital transformation requires more than just technical solutions; it demands good governance and strong institutional capacity. This is essential across all policy layers to ensure alignment, responsiveness, and the continuity of digitalisation efforts over the long term.

- **AKIS skills and advisory services are a critical bottleneck.** Improving digital literacy among farmers and advisors is a key challenge. Current advisory systems are often fragmented, lack digital expertise, and are not prepared to meet new demands. A transformation towards effective, holistic, independent support to farmers requires an alignment of representations of Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) between policy makers, researchers and intermediaries.

Key Policy Insights from Past Projects

A total of 30 projects were identified that included policy recommendations that relate, directly or indirectly, to digitalisation in agriculture or rural areas. Their reviewed converged on six thematic areas critical to advancing agricultural digitalisation: infrastructure and connectivity; data and governance; AKIS, skills, and capacity building; political, financial, and legal frameworks; tools and technologies; and social aspects. Remarkably, **over the past 10 years the core recommendations have changed little**, pointing not to a knowledge gap but to an implementation gap. This suggests that the priority should shift towards consistent execution at scale, stronger coordination across policies and funds, clear standards, and systematic monitoring of outcomes.

Insights on Digitalisation Drivers, Barriers, and Enablers

Digitalisation in agriculture depends on the **interplay of multiple factors**. The analysis highlights a set of persistent barriers that must be addressed together to achieve an inclusive digital transition in European agriculture:

- **Connectivity:** Urban-rural and field-level connectivity gaps remain critical, limiting access to services, data, and precision tools. Coverage, affordability, and reliability vary widely, and the last mile to fields is often unmet.
- **Structural:** Small farms, which make up the majority of EU holdings, face higher barriers to investment and risk exclusion from CAP incentives. Larger farms and small but specialised (organic, green houses, etc.) farms are better positioned to adopt advanced technologies.
- **Generational:** Younger farmers are generally more digitally literate but less present in the sector, while older farmers often lack the time or willingness to engage in training.
- **Institutional:** Advisory systems and public administrations are often fragmented, have limited capacity, and are insufficiently prepared to support the highly dynamic digital transition.
- **Governance:** Coordination gaps across ministries and programmes lead to inconsistent rules and delivery, even in frontrunner and advanced performers.
- **Data use and ownership:** Limited granular data, unclear rights, limited access to open data, and uneven consent practices reduce farmers' control and willingness to share.
- **Limited trust slow down adoption:** Low confidence in the performance, reliability, safety, and vendor neutrality of digital tools slows technology adoption. Farmers also have a limited trust in administrations, perceiving data sharing as an additional control or punishment mechanism.
- **Interoperability:** Incompatible systems and weak standards prevent seamless data exchange within farms, within public agencies, and between public and private platforms.
- **Digital literacy and skills:** Persistent gaps among farmers, intermediaries, and public officials limit uptake and effective use of digital solutions, with small farms and vulnerable groups most affected.

The Need for a Proactive and Coordinated Approach

Strong leadership and strategic guidance are needed at the EU level, **with clear coordination mechanisms across national, regional, and local levels** to ensure alignment and minimise fragmentation. Long-term, regionally adapted funding and performance approach to agricultural digitalisation would help ensure that efforts are coherent, effective, and fair across farming systems. The **CAP and agricultural administrations are central** to this agenda. CAP interventions should align with wider programmes to reduce duplication and unlock synergies, with digital objectives embedded consistently across instruments and tracked with shared indicators. At the same time, greater legal clarity within the EU competition framework is needed to ensure that collective farmer initiatives (such as data pooling and cost-sharing) can proceed without fear of breaching antitrust rules.

Acknowledgements

The Policy Analysis of this deliverable draws on the views of a diverse array of European, national, and regional stakeholders from the agriculture and digitalisation sectors. Representatives from Belgium, Czechia, Estonia, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland, Scotland, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, the EU-funded QuantiFarm project, the Directorate General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI), the Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (DG CNECT), the Joint Research Centre (JRC), and the Broadband Competence Office (BCO) Network were interviewed.

We would like to thank all the policy makers and experts who took the time to share their views on digitalisation in agriculture and all the CODECS partners who facilitated their reach. We would also like to acknowledge the continuous support of the project coordinator, Professor Gianluca Brunori, the CODECS ethical team, and to WP6 coordinator Emils Kilis from the BSC. Special thanks to María Alonso Roldán for their support in the initial stages of Task 6.1.

At the AKIS analysis, we are very grateful to the Living Lab members for their contribution and to the colleagues who participated to task T6.2: Livia Ortolani, Gianluca Brunori, Leanne Townsend, Niamh Mahon, Irina Ugorenko, Emils Kilis, Alexia Gobrecht and Andrea Knierim. Special thanks to Beatriz Herrera for the joint work on WP3 data and her careful review of section 7.

List of Acronyms

AECC	Agri-Environmental Climate Commitments
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge Information System
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMS	Agricultural Monitoring Systems
BCO	Broadband Competence Office
BSC	Baltic Studies Centre
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
D	Deliverable
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
DESI	Digital Economy and Society Index
DG AGRI	Directorate General for Agriculture and Rural Development
DG CNECT	Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology
DG DIGIT	Directorate-General for Informatics
DIAS	Copernicus Data and Information Services
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DSS	Decision Support System
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
EAGF	European Agricultural Guarantee Fund
EC	European Commission
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership or Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
EO	Earth Observation
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
ESF+	European Social Fund Plus
EU	European Union
FAS	Focal Action Situation
FaST	Farm Sustainability Tool
FFIS	Future Farming Investment Scheme
FMIS	Farm Management Information Systems
FNS	Food and Nutrition Security
FTTP	Fibre to the premises
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
H2020	Horizon 2020

IACS	Integrated Administration and Control System
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IPARD	Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance in Rural Development
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KIBS	Knowledge and Intensive and Business services
KTIF	Knowledge Transfer and Innovation Fund
LEADER	Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rurale
MAP	Multi Actor Platform
NIS	Network and Information Systems
NSP	National Strategic Plan
NSRF	National Strategic Reference Framework
R&I	Research and Innovation
RDP	Rural Development Programme
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility
SAOS	Scottish Agricultural Organisation Society
SCAP	Serbia Competitive Agriculture Project
SFT	Smart Farming Technologies
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SRDP	Scottish Rural Development Programme
T	Task
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
UCO	University of Cordoba
VHCN	Very high capacity network
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

Agricultural digitalisation represents a profound transformation, moving beyond the simple conversion of analogue processes to a broad socioeconomic, ecological, and technical transition. It is reshaping how value is created and distributed across farms, value chains, and rural communities. From a policy perspective, this transition must be strategically aligned with goals of food security, climate change mitigation, resilience, inclusion, and environmental stewardship to ensure its benefits are maximised and potential costs are contained (Rolandi et al., 2021). This report adopts this strategic perspective, examining digitalisation not merely as a technological upgrade but as a key driver of transformative change in the agricultural sector.

It is important to distinguish between digitisation (the technical act of converting information and operations into digital form) and digitalisation (the wider social and economic shifts triggered by that act) (Autio, 2017). These changes, which include new practices, institutions, and relationships, extend far beyond the farm gate. Therefore, effective policy must consider the entire context in which these technologies operate. Concepts such as digital ecosystems and the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) offer practical frameworks for action by connecting technology, data, infrastructure, governance, advisory services, and end-users in a holistic manner (European Commission, 2019)

The opportunities presented by this shift are significant. Digital tools can enhance productivity, improve efficiency and work quality, reduce pressure on natural resources, enable better market integration, and lower administrative burdens. They can also broaden access to knowledge, strengthen peer-to-peer learning, and forge more direct links between producers and consumers. Furthermore, they can boost generational renewal, making the sector more attractive to youngsters. However, without proper governance, digitalisation can also introduce economic, social, and environmental risks, particularly for vulnerable groups and regions. Public policy must therefore build foresight and monitoring capacity to steer technological development and adoption toward shared sustainability objectives (FAO, 2021; Trendov et al., 2019).

Realising these opportunities requires a comprehensive approach to these systemic challenges: diversity, complexity, and timing. First, digitalisation can expand the freedom of actors to achieve their goals, but only if access, power dynamics, and other enabling conditions are supportive. Second, given the inherent differences across farms, landscapes, and value chains, a “one-size-fits-all” solution is rarely effective because the costs, benefits, and perceptions of digital tools vary. Third, as technologies interact with social, ecological, institutional, and technical systems, successful outcomes depend on how well these components function together within a digital ecosystem. Fourth, adoption often requires coordinated changes in software, hardware, connectivity, skills, and organization, and asynchronous moves can increase costs and hinder scaling. To address these challenges, policy needs robust ways to diagnose readiness and target support (Apostol & Hernández-Rodríguez, 2024; Rolandi et al., 2021).

Navigating this complex transition requires a shift in policy focus from merely promoting technological adoption to actively cultivating a conducive environment for equitable and sustainable digital transformation. The central challenge for policymakers is not to predict which specific technology will prevail, but to build adaptive systems that can harness innovation while mitigating its disruptive potential. This involves moving beyond a narrow, productivity-centric view to embrace a multi-dimensional approach that values social cohesion, environmental regeneration, and economic resilience as equally critical outcomes of the digitalisation process (McFadden et al., 2022).

To translate these ideas into practice, the CODECS **Work Package 6 (WP6)**, *Policy Analysis and Roadmap*, aims to develop an evidence-based policy strategy for sustainable digitalisation under alternative future scenarios and to deliver policy recommendations. Coordinated by the Baltic Studies Centre (BSC), this WP comprises four tasks: Task 6.1 (T6.1), *Analysis of Policy Environments in the EU*; Task 6.2 (T6.2), *AKIS Models for Digitalisation*; Task 6.3 (T6.3), *Policy Foresight Exercise*; and Task 6.4 (T6.4), *Policy Recommendations*. This **Deliverable 6.2 (D6.2)**, *Report on Policy Environments for Digitalisation in Europe*, consolidates the work from **T6.1** and **T6.2**. Coordinated by the University of Córdoba (UCO), this report builds on the interim Deliverable 6.1 (D6.1), *Draft Report on Policy Environments*, submitted at Month 18 (March 2023), by integrating additional evidence and analysis to provide a comprehensive final assessment of policy environments as the conclusive output of these tasks at Month 36 of the project (Sept 2025).

2. Methodology

2.1 Analysis of Policy Environments

Led by the University of Cordoba (UCO), **Task 6.1 (T6.1), Analysis of Policy Environments in the EU**, ran from month 1 to month 36 and had the objective of describing, comparing, and assessing EU policy environments for digitalisation in agriculture and rural areas by: (i) reviewing policy insights and recommendations from relevant past projects; (ii) examining EU and national policy initiatives related to digitalisation in agriculture and rural areas; and (iii) conducting targeted interviews with policymakers and experts at EU, non-EU, national, and regional levels to describe, compare, and contrast different policy environments. These three core activities are described below. An initial analysis was submitted in month 18 ([D6.1 Draft report on policy environments](#)). This document builds on that analysis, follows the same methodology, and complements and updates the results.

(i) Review of policy insights and recommendations from relevant past projects

The analysis began by drawing on the knowledge base generated by the H2020 project [DESIRA](#) (Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas), which served as a key point of departure (see Alonso-Roldán et al., 2023). DESIRA's extensive policy analysis on rural and agricultural digitalisation across both European and national contexts provided a strong foundation for the identification of key implementation challenges, structural constraints, and governance gaps (Section 3.1). Building on this base, the CODECS project extended its review to include a broader set of EU-funded projects that addressed digitalisation in agriculture and rural development. These additional sources offered complementary perspectives, which were systematically examined to identify relevant insights for the policy analysis. This two-step approach ensured both continuity with prior research and a comprehensive understanding of the evolving policy landscape.

As part of this review, an initial list of past EU-funded projects related to digitalisation in agriculture and food systems was compiled using the Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) portal. For this purpose, we applied an adaptation of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) method (Figure 1), using different combinations of the keywords “digitalisation”, “digitalization”, “agriculture”, “agricultural”, “farming”, “policy”, “rural”, “brief”, “guidelines”, and “recommendation” in the CORDIS Search interface. The results were filtered by Project Deliverables and Report Summaries as these two collections are where policy recommendations are generally stored. After several iterations, the searches that yielded a manageable number of relevant results were ‘digit*’ AND ‘agr*’ AND ‘polic*’ AND ‘recommend*’ (570 results), ‘digit*’ AND ‘polic*’ AND ‘rural’ AND ‘guidelines’ (213 results), ‘digit*’ AND ‘agr*’ AND ‘polic*’ AND ‘rural’ AND ‘guidelines’ (187 results), ‘digit*’ AND ‘agricult*’ AND ‘polic*’ AND ‘recommend*’ (153 results), ‘digit*’ AND ‘agr*’ AND ‘polic*’ AND ‘rural’ AND ‘brief’ (51 results). The duplicates were discarded, and a qualitative screening of the remaining projects was performed through a review of the information available on the CORDIS database (Project Description, Objective, and list of Deliverables) and the project websites that were still accessible. A total of 147 projects were retained due to their potential relevance for our study, and three other projects were added based on information received during the interviews with policymakers and experts. A full text review of the relevant outputs of the resulting 150 projects was then conducted to identify recommendations relevant to our project. here recommendations were available, they were examined and categorised based on their relevance to the objectives and thematic scope of the CODECS project. In addition to formal policy outputs, other useful resources (such as strategic roadmaps, guidance documents, and position papers) were also taken into account to enrich the analysis. The findings from this review are presented in Section 3.2.

Figure 1: Overview of project identification, selection, and inclusion process.

(ii) EU and national policy initiatives regarding digitalisation in agriculture and rural areas

EU policy initiatives related to the digitalisation of agriculture and rural areas were systematically mapped and analysed as part of this task. The aim was to capture both established and emerging areas of relevance within the evolving policy landscape, with particular attention to developments at the EU level. This analysis was guided by the expertise of the UCO team and closely aligned with the operational scope of the 20 CODECS Living Labs, each of which focuses on a specific Focal Action Situation (FAS). The thematic priorities of the living labs informed the selection of relevant policy areas and enabled the identification of links with specific EU policies, strategies, and regulatory frameworks (see example below). This approach ensured that the policy review was grounded in real-world challenges and supported a contextual understanding of how digitalisation is addressed across different governance levels.

Living Lab Focal Action Situation Problem	Policy Areas	Policies and strategies
Decrease transaction costs and increase environmental, social, and economic benefits of virtual and physical market-place interactions between buyers and sellers in a defined geographical space	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture and rural development • Digital single market • Environment and sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) • Cohesion Policy • Digital Single Market Strategy • EU Digital Innovation Hubs • E-Commerce Directive • EU Green Deal • Farm to Fork Strategy

Additionally, we examined the Common Agricultural Policy National Strategic Plans (CAP NSPs) of the EU countries participating in CODECS: Belgium (Flanders), Belgium (Wallonia), Czechia, Estonia, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Spain. Since the NSPs are published in national languages and the most up-to-date versions are hosted on national government websites, we employed GDPR-compliant DeepL Pro translation software (DeepL, n.d.) to access and analyse the relevant content. This allowed for consistent and accurate extraction of information regarding digitalisation strategies, planned interventions, target indicators, and policy instruments. The translation process was complemented by targeted keyword searches and cross-referencing with official summaries to ensure fidelity and context-specific understanding across different language versions. The translated CAP NSPs were reviewed to evaluate the strategic orientation and planned interventions related to digitalisation, applying a comparative lens to capture variations in national approaches, reflecting differing levels of digital readiness, farm structure, and rural infrastructure, but also different country ambitions. This activity was also informed by insights from interviews with policymakers and experts, conducted under activity (iii) below. These semi-structured conversations offered contextual understanding that helped guide the selection and interpretation of key policy documents. In particular, they shed light on the rationale behind certain strategic choices in the CAP NSPs, the practical implementation challenges faced by public administrations, and the evolving priorities in digitalisation policy. This input proved instrumental in identifying which documents and policy areas warranted closer examination and enabled a more nuanced reading of the formal texts. In this way, the interview findings served as a complementary source of evidence that enhanced the depth and relevance of the documentary analysis.

The findings from this analysis are presented in Section 5.

(iii) Interviews with policymakers and experts at EU, non-EU, national, and regional levels

Semi-structured interviews were conducted using two versions of an interview guide that was developed and refined through a participatory process involving CODECS project partners (see Annex 1: Interview Guide – Policymakers at EU Level, and Annex 2: Interview Guide – Policymakers at EU, Extra EU and National Level). A preliminary list of interview topics was tested during the 2023 CODECS General Assembly in Almería, in group discussions with partners who were organised according to their areas of expertise, including digital technologies, the CAP, agriculture, and other fields relevant to agricultural digitalisation. Feedback from this exercise informed the final structure and thematic focus of the guide, ensuring its relevance and adaptability across diverse national and institutional contexts.

The selection of interviewees was based on a combination of criteria, including relevant expertise, availability, familiarity with project partners, and proficiency in either English or Spanish, which were the working languages of the UCO team. CODECS partners suggested suitable candidates who were then contacted to arrange interviews. In some cases, additional interviewees were identified through snowball sampling, where initial participants recommended other experts or policymakers with relevant knowledge. This process supported the collection of rich and comparative insights into the expert views on the state of digitalisation in the agriculture sector and how digitalisation is addressed within the CAP and related policy frameworks across a range of governance contexts.

The identified profiles for interviewees included:

- **Profile 1:** Policymakers and staff involved in drafting or implementing the CAP NSPs, particularly the digitalisation aspect.
- **Profile 2:** Experts in digitalisation in agriculture, including advisors, researchers, tech developers and providers.
- **Profile 3:** Individuals with experience related to the CODECS Living Labs.
- **Profile 4:** Representatives of EU institutions, agriculture unions, cooperatives, associations, etc. involved in digitalisation efforts at the EU, national, and regional level.

Between February 2024 and September 2025, a total of 101 interviews were conducted with policymakers and experts as part of this task. These included representatives from 15 EU Member States (Belgium, Czechia, Estonia, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Spain), three non-EU countries (North Macedonia, Scotland [United Kingdom], and Serbia), and institutions at the EU level. Efforts were made to ensure broad coverage across the 18 CODECS partner countries, while also

capturing a diversity of institutional perspectives and levels of engagement with digital policy. The number of interviews conducted in each country varied, generally ranging from four to six, depending on national contexts and stakeholder availability. In addition, 11 interviews were held with representatives of European Commission (EC) departments and agencies, and further insights were obtained through two meetings with the leaders of the policy-related task of [QuantiFarm](#), a sister EU-funded project currently underway. Some EU level experts were interviewed twice to know the evolution of the sector between D6.1 and D6.2. Interview participants represented a wide spectrum of stakeholders in the fields of agriculture and digitalisation. These included government officials such as former ministers, senior policy officers, and heads of digital inclusion divisions, as well as representatives from agricultural research centres, rural support services, economic development agencies, technology developers, cluster organisations, incubators, farmers, farmer associations and cooperatives, and sectoral lobbying institutions.

Participation in the interviews was entirely voluntary. Prior to each interview, participants received the interview guide and an information sheet prepared by the CODECS ethics team outlining the treatment of personal data in the project. Consent forms were signed to confirm their agreement to participate. All interviews were recorded with participants' permission and rewatched in full to ensure accurate annotation of key insights. Interviews were not transcribed, nor text analysis developed. These annotations were then organised into thematic categories, and the findings were synthesised and integrated across Sections 4, 5 and 6. The information presented for each country in Section 6 was discussed with and validated by the respective CODECS partner.

Comparative analysis of country conditions for agricultural digitalisation

Since agricultural digitalisation is shaped by many interacting factors that vary widely across countries and regions, it became clear that a comparative view was needed to gain a broad understanding of relative progress and the conditions that enable it. Narrow assessments that focus on a single tool or stage risk missing this complexity, so we adopted a broader lens to reflect multiple domains of change across the sector. At the same time, the absence of standardised farm level statistics limits a fully objective comparison, which led us to adopt a pragmatic and transparent approach to bring different signals together into a common baseline.

Accordingly, in the analysis phase, to compare the level of digitalisation across CODECS countries on a common basis, we combined the qualitative insights gained through interviews with four quantitative pillars. The first was each country's overall digital readiness, based on the 2022 Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) composite index, which is the last published version (European Commission, 2022). The second and third pillars reflected structural constraints that, according to interviewees, tend to slow the adoption of technology. These were measured by the share of small and very small farms (Eurostat, 2022) and the ratio of farm managers younger than 35 years old versus older than 55 years old (European Commission, DG AGRI, n.d.a). And the fourth pillar was related to the agriculture specific momentum in each country, captured through five CAP NSP target indicators normalised by the number of farms to balance for sector size (see Annex 1: Interview Guide – Policymakers at EU Level Country Values for the Four Pillars of Agricultural Digitalisation). The following indicators were selected given its direct or indirect relation with the boost of digitalisation in the agriculture sector:

- **R.1 (Knowledge and innovation):** Target number of individuals benefiting from advice, training, knowledge exchange or participation in EIP operational groups supported by the CAP.
- **R.2 (Linking advisory and knowledge systems):** Target number of advisors receiving support to be integrated into the AKIS.
- **R.3 (Digitalisation of agriculture):** Target number of farms receiving support for digital agricultural technologies under CAP.
- **R.28 (Environmental or climate performance through knowledge and innovation):** Target number of individuals benefiting from advice, training, knowledge exchange or participation in EIP operational groups supported by CAP to deliver better environmental or climate-related performance.

Scores were constructed by first applying min-max normalization (0 to 100) for each raw indicator to ensure comparability across scales. Pillar scores for digital readiness, farm size structure, and demographic structure are the simple averages of their normalised indicators, with the farm size structure pillar inverted so that lower shares of small farms receive higher scores. For agriculture-specific momentum, R.1, R.2, and R.28 were divided by the number of farms, while R.3 was used as a fraction. Missing values were conservatively imputed with the

median across countries for the respective indicator. Each adjusted R indicator was then normalised to 0 to 100, and a weighted average was calculated with 55% for R.3 and 15% for each of R.1, R.2, and R.28. The composite score was calculated as a weighted sum: 60% derived from DESI, 25% from farm size structure, 10% from demographic structure, and 5% from agriculture-specific digital momentum.

$$\text{Composite} = 0.60 \times \text{Digital readiness} + 0.25 \times \text{Farm size structure} + 0.10 \times \text{Demographic structure} + 0.05 \times \text{Agriculture-specific momentum}$$

Pillar weighting prioritises foundational readiness while still accounting for sector structure and recent activity. DESI received 60% because it captures the economy-wide enablers of digital uptake in agriculture, including connectivity, human capital, and digital public services. These inputs are prerequisites because, without them, farm-level tools and services cannot scale. Farm size structure, based on standard output as a better indicator of economic capacity for our purposes (as opposed to physical size), was given 25% as a direct proxy for the capacity to adopt and sustain digital solutions. Larger and more consolidated organisations typically have better access to capital, skills and advisory support, and potentially higher turnover, which raises the affordability, feasibility, and return on digital investment. Demographic structure contributed 10% because a higher share of younger managers is associated with faster adoption and experimentation, but demographics change slowly and should not outweigh system readiness or structural capacity. Furthermore, most of the older farmers will leave the sector in the next few years. This moderate weight recognises its importance while keeping the focus on enabling conditions. Lastly, agriculture-specific digital momentum received 5% because CAP NSP indicators capture recent activity and mobilisation. They reflect policy intent and planned mobilisation, not necessarily realised adoption or outcomes, and they can be sensitive to reporting practices and partly driven by the same enablers already reflected in DESI. Due to constraints in data availability and comparability, this analysis was restricted to the CODECS EU Member States.

The resulting composite scores, presented in Section 6.2, provide a comparative view of each country's stage of agricultural digitalisation that closely reflects the perspectives of the policymakers and experts interviewed (Section 6.3). Table 1 below summarises the pillars, weights, indicators and the rationale for their selection.

Table 1: Agricultural digitalisation composite score pillars, indicators, and weights.

Weight	Pillar	Indicator set	Why it matters for ag-tech uptake
60%	Overall digital readiness	DESI 2022 composite index	Broadband, skills and e-services create the basic conditions for ag-tech uptake.
25%	Farm size structure	% of very-small & small farms (standard output ≤ 24,999 EUR)	Larger farms are typically better placed to invest in precision equipment.
10%	Demographic structure	Ratio of farm managers <35 years old versus 55+ years old	Younger farm managers are generally more likely to adopt digital technologies.
5%	Agriculture-specific momentum	R.1, R.2, R.3, R.28 (R.1, R.2, R.28 scaled per farm; blanks = sample mean; R.3: 55%, Other Rs: 15%)	Signals the policy intent toward digital tools (it reflects government intentions, not actual investments, adoption, or use).

2.2 AKIS Models for Digitalisation

Led by the National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement, INRAE), **Task 6.2 (T6.2), AKIS Models for Digitalisation**, was

carried out from month 12 to month 36 and aimed to understand the role of innovation intermediaries within AKIS from the perspective of CODECS Living Lab participants. It also sought to integrate results from WP3 into policy discussions. Accordingly, an empirical three-step approach was used to progressively focus on innovation intermediaries:

Step 1: Review of policy documents and results of twin EU projects (AgriLink, i2connect, LIAISON, PRO AKIS) to extract information about expected relationships among AKIS, digitalisation, and innovation intermediaries.

Step 2: Synthesis of WP3 findings, based on a mapping exercise conducted in 19 CODECS Living Labs, in which participants identified the AKIS actors with whom they interact. A total of 330 actors were mentioned.

Step 3: Survey of a subset of the identified actors (n = 45) across four countries (Germany, Italy, Latvia, and France) to understand perceptions of AKIS policies and living labs, and to examine the roles of intermediary organisations, their resources, and the services they provide. The questionnaire was designed and fielded using the EUSurvey tool (European Commission, 2025a) in the languages of the surveyed countries (see Annex 1: Interview Guide – Policymakers at EU Level).

The findings of this analysis are presented in Section 7 and in the AKIS factsheets within Annex 6: Country Profiles. The content of these factsheets is derived from the corresponding national reports of the i2connect project.

2.3 Country Profiles

The analysis of policy environments and AKIS models for digitalisation required assembling, for each country, a comparable baseline on the socioeconomic context, the main features of agriculture and rural areas, and the state of digitalisation. Developed in parallel with Sections 2.1 and 2.2, these country baselines were compiled through desk research using a common template to ensure consistency and support comparison across countries. General socioeconomic data were obtained from Eurostat (n.d.b, n.d.c), the European Union (n.d.), the World Bank (n.d.), and the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE, n.d.). For the state of agriculture and rural areas we used data from the EC's Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (European Commission - DG AGRI, n.d.a), Eurostat (n.d.a), Krajnc (2017), Unión de Pequeños Agricultores y Ganaderos-UPA (2022), and the World Bank (n.d.). Data about the state of digitalisation in the CODECS countries was drawn from the EC's Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (European Commission - DG CNECT, 2024a, 2024b, 2025a, 2025b, n.d.), and the EC's Directorate-General for Economic and Financial Affairs (European Commission - DG ECFIN, n.d.). Each country profile includes a section based on the AKIS descriptions developed by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect, reflecting our synthesis of their work. The complete set is presented in Annex 6: Country Profiles. Due to constraints in data availability and comparability, country profiles were developed only for the CODECS EU Member States.

3. Policy Insights from Previous Projects

3.1 Contributions from DESIRA

The DESIRA project, which concluded in May 2023, conducted national policy analyses on rural and agricultural digitalisation in 15 countries¹ (11 of which were also examined in CODECS), revealing several challenges related to policy implementation and impact assessment (Alonso-Roldán et al., 2023). Among the key issues identified were an urban-rural digitalisation gap, limited availability of rural and agricultural data, difficulties in conducting ex post evaluations of policy impact, the fast pace of technological change, and coordination challenges among policy actors. The analysis also highlighted the role of limited digital skills in slowing the uptake of digital technologies across the rural, agriculture, and forestry sectors. Moreover, the research showed a significant influence of EU policies on digitalisation, rural development, and regional development on the national policies

¹ Austria, Croatia, Finland, Flanders (Belgium), France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Scotland, Spain, and Switzerland.

supporting rural digitalisation.

Across the 15 countries, all developed policy strategies in key areas, including:

- **Infrastructure:** All countries deployed broadband programmes, initially prioritising easily accessible areas and later expanding to rural and less profitable locations in line with European objectives. However, high-speed connectivity in rural areas and at the farm or field level remains limited in most countries.
- **Digital competencies and literacy:** Recently gaining political attention, most countries have introduced strategies to enhance digital literacy, addressing dimensions such as age, gender, and education. Standalone national strategies in France, Italy, Poland, and Spain aimed at improving digital skills, though not specifically targeting rural areas. Skill gaps among farmers and rural residents continue to hinder the adoption of digital technologies.
- **Rural digitalisation:** Countries follow different approaches. Greece, Hungary, and Spain implemented dedicated agriculture digitalisation strategies, while Italy, Austria, Germany, and Latvia integrated rural digitalisation objectives within broader rural development ones. These strategies typically consider agriculture as one component among several rural priorities.
- **Digital trust:** In line with Europe's Digital Future strategy, national policies addressed key issues such as cybersecurity, interoperability, and data governance. All countries transposed the European Network and Information Security (NIS) Directive into national legislation, although levels of cybersecurity maturity varied. While interoperability guidelines were present across all countries, implementation challenges remain. The agricultural sector in particular continues to face complex barriers in these areas.

Overall, DESIRA's cross-country analysis showed that while EU-level strategies provide an important common direction, national implementation remains uneven, shaped by differing priorities, capacities, and institutional contexts. Persistent gaps in connectivity, skills, and trust (particularly in rural and agricultural settings) continue to limit the pace and scope of digital adoption. By revealing these systemic challenges and their links to both national and EU policy frameworks, DESIRA provided a valuable evidence base for the design of more targeted, coherent, and inclusive digitalisation strategies that can better serve rural communities across Europe.

3.2 Policy Recommendations from Previous Projects

The initial list of projects screened on D6.1 was revised and updated as follows. From a total of 152 EU-funded projects reviewed in depth (Figure 2), 30 included policy recommendations that relate, directly or indirectly, to digitalisation in agriculture or rural areas (see Annex 4: EU-funded initiatives with relevant policy recommendations Annex 4:). A further 15 were not aligned with CODECS but produced outputs of interest to the topic: AURORAL, BESTMAP, DataBio, DRURAL, FOSTER, I4MS, MATILDE, ROBS4CROPS, RUBIZMO, RUSTIK, SURE-Farm, SYNCHRONICITY, and VICINITY. Another 15 projects are still under way and are expected to deliver policy recommendations, or their relevance remains to be seen: AgRibot, AGRO-WELL, BEATLES, DAISY, DIGI-Rangeland, FLIARA, ForestAgriGreenNudge, FUTURAL, GRANULAR, HASHTAG, INSPIRE, QUANTIFARM, RURALITIC, SUS-SOIL, and TECHCOACH. The remaining 92 were discarded.

Figure 2: EU-funded projects and initiatives reviewed

The main recommendations made in the 30 relevant projects can be organised into the following topics:

Infrastructures: Different projects underscored the importance of connectivity and stable and reliable connections in the rural areas at the farm level (DESIRA, FAIRshare, GRASSCEILING, IoF2020, NEFERTITI, OPEN DEI) as a first and essential step for digital transformation. SHERPA, WIRE2018, and Interreg Alpine Space Smart Villages recommended investing and developing digital infrastructures according to the needs and the technological possibilities of farmers. The latter project supports the role of smart villages in the smart transformation of mountain, rural and peripheral villages. The development of secure platforms where farmers can manage their data appropriately is a demand in the EU FOOD 2030 and SUPREMA projects. GRASSCEILING recommends prioritising underserved communities by investing in gender-responsive, socially inclusive infrastructure (including digital access), recognising connectivity and digital literacy as essential for enabling rural women to participate in emerging economic sectors and innovation ecosystems.

Data and data governance: Even if some projects, such as AGRICORE, have found increases in farmer reliance on data and models, most of the project recommendations highlight that important changes and advances are still needed. Aspects such as facilitating access to public and open data, establishing clear rules on data ownership and usage of shared data, ensuring and facilitating data protection and privacy and farmer’s consent, advancing the standardisation of data, or the need for data sharing are mentioned in the recommendations of projects such as DESIRA, EU FOOD 2030, IoF2020, NEFERTITI, OPEN DEI, SHERPA, and SmartAgriHubs.

Other aspects mentioned include the need for granular data adapted to farm realities (AGRICORE) and the establishment of data spaces and interoperable solutions to increase trust and transparency along the supply chain (OPEN DEI). TOOLS4CAP further argues that interoperability challenges should be addressed in a combined manner spanning both agri-food information and communication technologies (ICT) solutions and the data requirements of CAP monitoring and implementation; it also stresses that clear technical definitions within guidelines are critical for transparency, inclusivity, and adaptability, fostering a collaborative, data-driven approach to achieving CAP sustainability targets. SmartAgriHubs likewise emphasises creating data spaces and advancing interoperability, alongside developing robust semantic standards and agrifood-specific vocabularies/ontologies to enable data sharing.

NIVA suggested developing and agreeing upon semantic and technical standards for enhancing data exchange. Interoperability standards and interconnection of data to provide transparency and reliable and traceable information are demanded by projects such as DEMETER, DESIRA, and EU FOOD 2030. SUPREMA underscored the need for quality control, (cross) validation, and transparency of the models used in the agriculture system, which are crucial topics given the growing importance and plurality of models and modelling approaches. The need for adapted models to individual needs and characteristics is also highlighted.

Additionally, GRASSCEILING highlights that data scarcity is especially problematic in areas critical to policy design for rural areas (such as social security, farm diversification, and innovative farming practices) and

recommends integrating gender-specific variables into major EU data and monitoring frameworks to close these gaps.

AKIS, skills, and capacity building: The need to increase digital literacy and skills in different actors is a common recommendation in many projects. AKIS and advisory services play a key role in reaching this goal. Public and independent advisory services are needed, and advisors must upskill and reskill their digital knowledge. Farmers demand independent, well-trained, and updated advisory services, as well as inclusive approaches to give answers to their different needs (AgriLink, DESIRA, FAIRshare, GRASSCEILING, OPEN DEI). Advisory services must tackle the digital training of advisers from updated knowledge to new approaches to training and advising based on demonstration activities and the use of harmonised methodologies on the performance of smart farming technologies (Smart-AKIS). New ways of providing information on digital technologies should be provided, such as specific training campaigns, field trials, demonstrations, and demo farms (FAIRshare, IoF2020, NEFERTITI, OPEN DEI, Robotics4EU). Specialised competence centres providing technical assistance and need-based services dedicated to crucial sectors identified at the local level (e.g. agriculture, forestry, and also tourism and leisure as complementary sectors) should be established (SHERPA). SuMaNu recommended the use of digital tools to control the use of fertilisers.

Digital technologies advance at a very high speed and are expensive. To boost technology adoption, farmers need access to updated and easy-to-understand information on the different existing options and access to funds. Innovation/digital ecosystems are needed as supportive environments aiming at promoting a culture of innovation (NEFERTITI) and promoting the creation of spaces for the co-design of locally adapted digital strategies that include members and organisations from civil society, policy, tech providers and researchers (SHERPA).

Smart-AKIS advocates farmer-centred solutions and the use of digital tools tailored to farm size. It also underlines the need to review and update educational curricula at all levels to mainstream smart farming and digital technologies. DESIRA and SALSA highlighted concerns about the need to ensure that digital tools are both accessible and affordable for smaller-scale producers. In parallel, digital and informal knowledge-sharing tools (e.g., WhatsApp and LinkedIn) are seen as valuable to extend learning beyond formal sessions by increasing visibility, widening access to training, and fostering online communities and networks (GRASSCEILING).

SHERPA calls for sustained investment in the continuous development of basic digital competences in rural areas, with particular attention to the digital inclusion of low-skilled and vulnerable groups (e.g., migrants and refugees, the elderly, the hard-to-reach), to ensure the process benefits the whole society. SALSA likewise encourages building digital skills among both younger and older farmers. GRASSCEILING advocates expanding access to high-quality training, upskilling, and reskilling for women in emerging green and digital sectors, alongside targeted efforts to build their capacity to engage in digital innovation, access online services, and adopt smart and green agricultural technologies. Overall, changes are needed across the education continuum, from university programmes to vocational training, to address the broadening range of needs in ICT in agriculture and accelerate the digital transformation of farming practices.

Political, financial, and legal frameworks: The projects recognise that ensuring connectivity and skills acquisition is a national responsibility, even if it should be promoted at the EU level. Hence, national, regional, and local policies have a very important role in addressing these aspects and ensuring that enough funds and political will are allocated together with efforts to reduce bureaucracy and create friendly and easy-to-use environments (FAIRshare, IoF2020) and integrate commercial and public software to decrease the burden of filling applications, providing mandatory statistics or using aggregated datasets in farming management (NIVA). The role of both CAP pillars in boosting digital transition for competitiveness and promoting sustainability is proposed by several projects (EO4AGRI, NIVA, Smart-AKIS, SUPREMA).

Different aspects are mentioned in relation to the legal frameworks needed to support digital transformation and digital technology adoption: aspects such as interoperability standards, transparency and trust among agrifood actors and technological providers, and data interconnection to provide reliable and traceable information need to be regulated (DEMETER, EU FOOD 2030).

NEFERTITI proposed specific Public-Private Partnerships or agreements that provide targeted funding for digital facilities and combine different types of funding, while Rural SMEs demanded providing direct financial support to farmers through dedicated programmes, including e.g., vouchers, grants for innovation and transformative projects or subsidised loans aiming at reducing the risk for significant digital investments, and WIRE2018

demanded the alignment and simplification in the use of funding instruments. SmartAgriHubs proposed shifting from subsidising product/equipment acquisition to a process-oriented approach based on equipment + advice/service acquisition. The need for financial support for farmers and the importance of sustaining small-scale farmers in their digital transformation pathway are proposed by OPEN DEI, Robotics4EU and SHERPA projects. The MATS project raises a specific concern related to the fact that intellectual property rights on digital tools and platforms are in the hands of providers that have positions of dominance, creating a new barrier to farmers' access.

Tools and technologies: Technologies cannot be the end but the means for specific aims (DESIRA, INSPIRE). Technological/ICT offers need to be tailored according to the specific farmer's need (SmartAgriHubs). The last decades have seen an amazing advance in the development of digital technologies. However, LIAISON acknowledges the EU innovation gap and claims for investments, research and innovation (R&I) and political will to address it. The technologies that have a bigger impact on the agricultural sector are precision farming, robots, artificial intelligence (AI), big data, Internet of Things (IoT), blockchain, and data-based solutions (agROBOfood, DEMETER). IoF2020 project supports the reusability of IoT components.

Other relevant tools are the advances in earth observation (EO) and data gathering triggered by Copernicus and Sentinels satellites. However, using these tools requires high-level computing skills. Projects such as EO4AGRI, and NEFERTITI advocate for better and easier-of-use information tools, claim for the EC to provide algorithms for Agricultural Monitoring Systems (AMS), develop a knowledge database shared among the EU Member States, incorporate references in AMS regulations regarding conditionality and urge EC leadership in conditionality and agri-environmental schemes, proposing more suitable EU legislation for Copernicus Sentinels, updating EC Regulations to lower monitoring approach requirements, improving standards for "GeoTag" tools, endorsing initiatives for in-situ data collection tools, promoting education for EO end-users, and emphasising follow-up actions by DG AGRI and the Joint Research Centre (JRC) on Copernicus Data and Information Services (DIAS) production capabilities. Other projects, such as NIVA, recognise data from Farm Management Information Systems (FMIS) and precision farming more broadly as valuable and appropriate tools for managing CAP payments. They also promote data exchange between commercial agricultural software and government information systems as a means to support greater technology adoption.

As an emerging, strategically important field for the EU and the agri-food economy, AI is drawing increasing attention. In this regard, the CoRoSect project recommends prioritising human rights protections alongside safety, strengthening oversight of provider self-classification, and issuing detailed guidance and inclusive codes of conduct, especially for high-risk systems already deployed and for human-robot collaboration in the workplace. It urges the EC to facilitate sectoral codes and cross-border data sharing through technical and semantic interoperability, and to review and refine the AI Act after it enters into force. Furthermore, it argues that, beyond horizontal rules, policymakers should develop sector- and use-case-specific ethical guidelines and practical tools (e.g., impact-assessment methods) that also cover environmental impacts and non-human life.

Social aspects: EU FOOD 2030 calls for responsible R&I and greater use of social sciences and humanities in the digital transformation, including research to understand why farmers distrust data sharing and trials that involve individual farmers as participants. It also urges that farmers and the wider sector help design digital technologies and policies. DEMETER echoes this, while SmartAgriHubs stresses focusing on farmers' needs and expectations (the weakest link in the chain) and delivering services that are needed rather than deploying digital tools for their own sake. FAIRshare, HubIT and OPEN DEI underline the importance of clearer communication and awareness raising about opportunities in the sector. Along similar lines, YOUNG FARMERS recommends using digital communications to tailor messages to young people's evolving motivations, highlight opportunities in digital agriculture such as innovation capacity and geographical flexibility, and run targeted campaigns for groups like young women to present farming and rural life as attractive careers. HubIT also recommends closer attention to ethics in data processing, stronger risk assessment, and the integration of ICT and social experts when designing tools and building knowledge. DESIRA proposes an ethical code for digitalisation, and Robotics4EU campaigns for responsible robotics by engaging a wide range of actors in policy making and in the development of product safety, data, ethics and sustainability.

4. Domains and Pathways of Agricultural Digitalisation

4.1 Four Domains of Agricultural Digitalisation

A meaningful assessment of digitalisation in a country's agricultural sector requires a clear understanding of the diverse areas where digital technologies can have an impact. Too often, analyses focus narrowly on a single aspect, such as the use of digital tools like mobile apps, sensors, or decision support systems (DSS) and online platforms, while overlooking equally important aspects such as access to efficient e-government services, the uptake of precision farming practices, or the digital transformation of agricultural value chains, among others. This narrow perspective risks underestimating both the complexity and the transformative potential of digital technologies. Drawing on insights from our interviews with policymakers and experts, the literature, and researchers' expertise, this study identifies four overlapping domains (digital communication and knowledge exchange, government-farmer interface, operational efficiency and productivity, and transparency and market connectivity), that together reflect the complex nature of digital transformation. This framework supports a more nuanced evaluation of digitalisation and can inform the design of targeted interventions to address gaps across the agricultural ecosystem.

4.1.1 Digital Communication and Knowledge Exchange

The proliferation of basic handheld devices, most notably smartphones and tablets, has impacted significantly the landscape of agricultural communication. In many contexts, their use marks the first step in the digitalisation of farming systems via video-streaming channels, which allow farmers to share and obtain practical insights on various topics, including crop management innovations, irrigation, and pest management. Similarly, simple mobile applications and messaging services deliver real-time weather forecasts, pest and disease alerts, and market-price information directly in the field, accelerating decision-making and reducing response times to emerging challenges.

Smartphones and tablets also foster two-way knowledge exchange among farmers and other AKIS members. Social media forums and dedicated chat groups allow farmers to exchange insights and expertise, while live video calls help bridge the gap between technology providers, experts, and end users. For instance, extension officers can conduct remote diagnostics through the analysis of photographs of crop symptoms, while agribusiness advisors can host live demonstrations of equipment operation. These interactive exchanges amplify traditional extension services, extending their reach, tailoring support, and reducing the need for costly field visits.

Beyond communication and knowledge exchange, this initial layer of connectivity familiarises users with electronic information flows and lays the foundation for the use of more advanced digital tools. The blending of informal peer exchanges with professional advisory content fosters continuous learning, reinforces trust in digital tools, and helps bridge gaps in regional extension capacity, ultimately accelerating the diffusion of these technologies across diverse farming contexts.

At the next stage of digitalisation, device-based apps enable farmers to log yields, soil test results and input expenditures, generating digital records that support decision making, optimise resource use, improve operational efficiency, and enhance environmental performance. These data streams can feed into dashboards accessed by cooperatives and government agencies, improving the targeting of subsidies, credit schemes and training programmes, and supporting evidence-based policy design and participatory research.

4.1.2 Government-Farmer Interface

The use of digital technologies for payments, compliance and advisory services plays a central role in the modernisation of agriculture by transforming paper-based, time-consuming processes into streamlined, user-friendly services that benefit both farmers and public authorities. These tools improve government-farmer interactions by enabling the direct submission of subsidy claims, reporting of regulatory data, and access to tailored guidance via online portals or mobile apps, thereby reducing administrative delays, cutting transaction costs, and minimising errors. Digital channels also foster transparency and trust by letting farmers track the status

of payments and compliance, while providing authorities with more accurate, timely insights into policy uptake and impact, thus paving the way for more responsive, data driven agricultural governance.

The interoperability of registries and data flows is a key element of agricultural digitalisation due to its role in transparency, responsiveness, and efficiency improvements. When land use, subsidy, environmental and farm-management databases can communicate seamlessly, administrative processes (such as CAP applications, compliance checks and subsidy payments) become faster, more accurate and less burdensome for both farmers and public authorities. Real-time data exchange enables integrated decision-making across agencies (for example linking environmental risk assessments directly to payment eligibility), supports effective monitoring and evaluation of policy measures, and lays the groundwork for advanced services like precision-farming advisory tools. Interoperable systems foster trust among stakeholders by ensuring data consistency and reducing opportunities for error or fraud, while also opening the door to innovative public-private partnerships and regional data-sharing platforms that can leverage local strengths and needs.

4.1.3 Operational Efficiency and Productivity

Digitalisation drives measurable efficiency gains in operations and administration. Moving processes such as CAP applications, subsidy tracking, and audit processes to digital registries, e-filing tools and automated grant-management systems, helps farms, cooperatives and governments to reduce paperwork, minimise errors, and accelerate compliance. When these systems are connected, they lay the groundwork for real-time data sharing across multiple stages of the value chain.

In production, digital technologies (such as advanced sensors, satellite imagery, and AI-driven decision-support systems) can significantly optimise seeding, nutrient and pest management, and irrigation scheduling, helping increase yields while safeguarding environmental resources. Soil-moisture and nutrient probes feed data into analytics platforms, allowing farmers to apply water and fertilizers with precision, while satellite-linked advisory tools convert those inputs into actionable recommendations for planting dates, pest control and harvest timing. Furthermore, the integration of robotics and autonomous machinery helps address labour shortages and standardise routine tasks, integrating on-farm technologies into daily operations to support sustainable, resilient and competitive farming.

Delivering these gains requires high quality data capture at field and farm level, smooth device-to-platform connectivity, and integration of sensor and machine data into farm management and advisory dashboards. Where farmers log yields, soil tests and input costs, these records can feed cooperatives and public agencies, improving the targeting of support measures and advisory services and enabling evidence-based policy design. Interoperability is key to realising operational efficiency gains by linking devices, apps, and farm systems and aligning data formats and identifiers, so that information flows readily into the analytics and reporting tools already used by farmers and support institutions.

4.1.4 Transparency and Market Connectivity

Beyond the farm gate, digital tools create visibility and traceability across logistics, storage, processing and sales. For instance, Global Positioning System (GPS)-enabled fleet tracking, blockchain-backed provenance systems and IoT connected storage facilities provide real-time views of product movement and condition, reduce post-harvest losses and strengthen consumer confidence. Integrated Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems and cloud-based exchange hubs align orders, inventory, quality checks and compliance reporting among cooperatives, processors and distributors. E-commerce portals, Customer Relationship Management (CRM) solutions and social-media analytics help farmers reach new markets, engage directly with consumers, and tailor offerings to local or niche demand.

To achieve end-to-end transparency and market connectivity, these tools must link data across many independent organisations. They depend on shared data models, consistent identifiers, open APIs, and permission rules that allow verification without exposing sensitive commercial information. Strong interoperability between registries and operational systems improves accuracy and speed, supports integrated decision-making across institutions, and fosters trust among stakeholders, which is essential when multiple actors record and verify product information along the chain. Cybersecurity and data security are therefore additional key

considerations to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of data exchanges and protect participants from misuse or unauthorised access.

4.2 Evolution of Farm Digital Maturity

The limited availability of updated data on agricultural digitalisation, combined with differing interpretations of what “digitalisation” entails (Parida et al., 2019), makes it difficult to assess the level of digital advancement within a given country or region. However, our research and interview insights point to a sequence of identifiable stages along the digitalisation journey in agriculture, closely linked to technology uptake and development (see Figure 3). The adoption of digital tools depends on factors such as affordability (including public funding availability and the perceived return on investment, with machinery typically more expensive than software), digital literacy, and the preparedness of the broader enabling environment. This includes political and legislative frameworks that foster trust in digital ecosystems, as well as AKIS systems that promote awareness and facilitate uptake. As technology adoption advances, systems become more complex, incorporating a wider range of software and hardware, which in turn drives demand for more specialised solutions. This complexity leads to the generation of increasing volumes of data, highlighting the need for greater interoperability among digital tools and more advanced ICT skills among the data users. Moving toward more advanced, integrated systems also introduces institutional and structural challenges, particularly around the establishment of common data standards, open architectures, and governance mechanisms that foster transparency, trust, and equitable access across the digital ecosystem, and that explicitly address clearly perceived needs.

Figure 3: Stages of digitalisation in agriculture (Source: updated from Alonso-Roldán and Delgado-Serrano, 2024).

4.2.1 Initial Stage (Familiarisation)

In this phase, farmers first encounter digital tools through everyday technologies like smartphones, social media and mobile internet, which they use to check weather forecasts, monitor market prices and engage in peer-to-peer exchanges about emerging issues. Informal marketing and sales channels (such as e-commerce portals, online marketplaces or direct-to-consumer social-media storefronts) also provide an accessible entry point, allowing producers to experiment with digital sales and gauge consumer demand. These informal channels lower the barrier to digital engagement through their easy integration into the existing routines of farmers, consequently

building their confidence in online resources. In parallel, some farmers begin using simple digital substitutes for traditional paperwork, such as spreadsheets to record input use or scanned documents to archive invoices and certificates. These low-complexity tools introduce farmers to digital workflows in familiar formats. Similarly, mandatory online filings (for example e-CAP submissions and digital compliance reporting) serve as structured introductions to government portals and workflows, leading users to navigate digital forms and dashboards. Additionally, the use of online government services and digital tools for everyday tasks, including healthcare, education and tax administration, helps build farmers' familiarity with digitalisation. Together, these experiences demystify technology, spark demand for further support and lay the groundwork for deeper integration of more sophisticated systems. However, significant barriers remain, including limited access to computers and software, unreliable internet, and gaps in digital skills. As a result, many farmers depend on cooperatives and farmers' associations to complete required online procedures, which limits their autonomy and slows the uptake of new technologies.

What changes at this stage?

- Confidence grows as farmers see quick wins from simple, low-friction tools embedded in daily routines.
- Informal peer networks and AKIS/extension actors often provide crucial first-line support.

"Everybody has a smartphone. So, if you have a smartphone, it's sure that you have a certain degree of digitalisation in your life."

4.2.2 Adoption Stage (Standalone Tools)

In this stage, farmers start introducing individual digital tools into specific parts of their operations. They explore specialised applications, such as nutrient management calculators, and deploy basic sensors like soil moisture probes, livestock robots and collars, or simple yield monitors. These tools support decision-making by enabling more accurate input adjustments and more precise monitoring of field and animals' conditions. At the same time, many farmers begin adopting electronic record-keeping systems, including digital diaries, spreadsheets, and entry-level farm management software. These systems allow them to log activities, inputs, and outputs in a more structured and accessible way. Although often used in isolation and not yet connected to broader digital ecosystems, such tools represent a significant step toward operational digitalisation. This gradual adoption process is frequently supported by training programmes, pilot initiatives, or extension services, and helps farmers build the familiarity and confidence needed for future system integration. Adoption is accelerated by market and consumer demand, by shortages of essential resources such as water or labour, and by the availability of tailored solutions offered by cooperatives, companies, or associations. Barriers to moving beyond this stage include the limited availability or high cost of context-specific tools that depend on collaborative approaches, as well as data governance challenges related to use, ownership, and interoperability.

What changes at this stage?

- Productivity gains from precision input application (irrigation, fertiliser, pesticides) start to appear.
- Farmers' digital literacy improves, revealing new concerns around data governance, ownership, and interoperability (topics that will intensify in the next stage).

"The more digitalisation progresses, the more new issues arise."

4.2.3 Integration Stage (Connected Systems)

In this phase, farmers gradually move beyond the use of isolated tools towards the establishment of integrated digital ecosystems, linking farm management software platforms with on-farm sensor networks, machinery telemetry, and compliance modules. Big farms, input intensive sectors, or those with higher return on investment, such as greenhouses or intensive livestock production, are more common to adopt these technologies. Also at this stage, regional platforms collect, aggregate, and anonymise data from multiple operations, merging it with advisory inputs and official records to identify trends in input usage, environmental impacts, and regulatory compliance. This integration enables more precise planning (such as aligning irrigation schedules with weather forecasts and verifying subsidy eligibility and deadlines), fostering collaborative decision-making among farmers,

extension agents, and public agencies. Moreover, it empowers farmers to plan with greater accuracy, reduce resource waste, and maintain compliance of rules and market demands without constant manual oversight. Barriers to move beyond this stage relate to interoperability, standardisation and harmonisation of protocols, cybersecurity and availability of reliable advisory systems.

What changes at this stage?

- Data begins to flow across systems, enabling semi-automated workflows and reducing manual oversight.
- Governance (ownership, access rights, standards) and neutrality of advice become central strategic issues.

“Precision farming does not necessarily mean smart farming; the second demands data interoperability.”

4.2.4 Smart Farming Stage

In this stage, farms evolve into largely self-managing systems powered by interconnected IoT devices, advanced analytics, and autonomous equipment. Arrays of sensors continuously collect detailed information (such as soil moisture levels or emerging pest pressures) which machine learning algorithms interpret to adjust irrigation rates, planting densities, or pesticide applications in real time with minimal human intervention. Robots and drones execute commands with high precision, freeing farmers from routine tasks and enabling them to focus on strategic management. Satellite data and digital twins boost evidence base decision making. This integrated digital environment not only enhances resource efficiency and yield outcomes but also strengthens resilience through the prediction of potential threats well in advance (like extreme weather events or disease outbreaks), thus making possible the implementation of preventive measures to safeguard both productivity and environmental sustainability. This stage involves high hardware and software costs, a need for advanced IT skills, and rapid technological change. Only a small share of European commercial and integrated farms can sustain such investments, so uptake remains limited across most sectors.

What changes at this stage?

- Human oversight shifts to supervising autonomous processes and strategic decision-making.
- Interoperability standards and open data architectures become non-negotiable to avoid lock-in and ensure independent advisory services.
- Advanced cybersecurity protocols are needed to protect farm operations.

“Using machinery from different manufacturers and being tied to their advisory services, rather than being free to share farm data with independent advisors, remains a challenge”

5. Policy Tools for Digitalisation in Agriculture and Rural Areas

The digital transformation of agriculture, rural areas and the wider agri-food sector depends not only on technological innovation but also on a supportive policy environment. A range of EU policy levers related to rural development, funding, regulation, infrastructure and advisory systems play a critical role in creating the conditions for digital uptake, guiding investment and ensuring that digital tools contribute to broader economic, environmental and social objectives.

5.1 The Common Agricultural Policy

The **CAP is the primary funding and policy instrument for agricultural digitalisation**, supporting farmers through both financial assistance and capacity building. It is financed through two complementary funds that are often referred to as the two pillars of the CAP, each with a distinct focus (European Commission - DG AGRI, n.d.b). The European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF), or Pillar I, primarily supports direct payments to

farmers and market related measures. Its aim is to provide income stability, ensure food security and support key sectors through instruments such as basic income support for sustainability, payments to young farmers and targeted aid for specific products or regions. Pillar II, the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), supports broader objectives linked to the sustainable development of rural areas. It cofinances a wide range of measures that promote the competitiveness of agriculture and forestry, encourage sustainable land management and foster the balanced development of rural economies and communities. Through this fund, Member States support farm modernisation (including digitalisation), training and knowledge transfer, and local development initiatives.

Within the CAP Pillar II, **a set of instruments provides support for farmers' needs across technology uptake, environmental performance, advisory support, skills development, and local collaboration**, so help is available from first investment through everyday use. Investment support under rural development measures helps farmers adopt digital tools. **Eco-schemes** and **Agri-Environmental Climate Commitments (AECC)** reward the use of technologies that deliver environmental benefits, for example farm management information systems and precision farming. The CAP also strengthens capacity by requiring Member States to provide advice on digital issues and to use the **Farm Sustainability Tool (FaST)** for optimal nutrient management at field level. Member States can fund knowledge exchange and training to build digital skills, and they can use cooperation measures such as the European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (**EIP-AGRI**) **Operational Groups**, the ***Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rurale (LEADER)*** program, and **smart villages** to spread solutions in rural communities. Furthermore, the CAP supports the digitalisation of agriculture by leveraging data from the **Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS)** to enable evidence-based policymaking, foster the development of a digital ecosystem with innovative services and tools, support R&I, and promote interoperability and data accessibility.

Digitalisation within the current CAP is promoted through three key mechanisms: eco-schemes, investments, and knowledge-sharing or advisory services. **Eco-schemes** symbolise the policy shift introduced in the 2023-2027 programming period, based on the green transition and placing sustainability high on the political agenda and rewarding practices such as reduced ploughing or more sustainable spraying, but only when farmers can provide detailed electronic logs. **Investments** under CAP Pillar II continue to play a central role in supporting digitalisation, with eligibility increasingly tied to sustainability objectives. In parallel, Member States have shown strong interest in embedding digitalisation within **knowledge-sharing and advisory services** under their CAP NSPs, recognising the importance of targeted support for skills development and informed decision making among farmers.

These efforts also contribute to the cross-cutting objective set out in Article 6(2) of Regulation (EU) 2021/2115. In this context, Member States are required to describe how digitalisation is integrated within their AKIS systems, including cooperation between advisory services, research actors, and CAP networks. This reflects a broader shift from traditional advisory models toward more integrated and dynamic systems capable of supporting innovation in a rapidly changing agricultural landscape. While digitalisation may not always be the central focus of AKIS, it frequently features prominently within their activities and strategic priorities. Effective AKIS depend on collaborative networks that promote good governance, trust, openness, diversity and long-term relationships. Current CAP funding instruments are well placed to support this transition by encouraging collaborative and demonstrative approaches, which have proven effective in fostering the uptake of new technologies.

The evaluation of both the extent of the digitalisation efforts of Member States and the impact of the CAP is significantly constrained by the current **absence of reliable baseline data, inconsistencies in how digitalisation expenditures are recorded, and variations in the definition of what qualifies as digitalisation-related expenses**. Although data on the overall state of digitalisation in Member States are published annually by the EC through the Digital Decade DESI visualisation tool (European Commission, n.d.), no equivalent data are available specifically for rural areas or the agricultural sector. Furthermore, while R.3 (Digitalisation of agriculture: Target number of farms receiving support for digital agricultural technologies under CAP) is considered the most direct indicator of digitalisation in the CAP NSPs, other target indicators also capture relevant aspects of digitalisation efforts. These include R.1 (Knowledge and innovation: Target number of individuals benefiting from advice, training, knowledge exchange or participation in EIP Operational Groups supported by the CAP), R.2 (Linking advisory and knowledge systems: Target number of advisors receiving

support to be integrated into the AKIS), and R.28 (Environmental or climate performance through knowledge and innovation: Target number of individuals benefiting from advice, training, knowledge exchange or participation in EIP Operational Groups supported by the CAP to deliver better environmental or climate-related performance).

Beyond funding levels, **this CAP period has put digitalisation firmly on the policy agenda** and encouraged a more strategic use of instruments (e.g. payment follow-up, digital notebook). The challenge now is to ensure consistent uptake by national administrations and farmers, and to strengthen tracking and monitoring, since the existing indicators may not be well suited to capture digital progress and there is no robust baseline against which to assess change. A clear view of actual expenditure will be important not only to evaluate the effectiveness of planned interventions, but also to understand patterns of uptake, identify gaps across regions or farm types, and inform adjustments to future programming and policy design. In the meantime, the overall direction appears positive, with broader coverage of digital interventions and growing attention to how they are delivered and measured.

5.2 CAP National Strategic Plans

For the current CAP period (2023-2027), all Member States were required to include a **digitalisation strategy** in their **CAP NSPs**, as part of the broader obligation to support the modernisation of agriculture and rural areas. This requirement reflects Article 114 of Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, which mandates that each plan outline a strategy for the development and use of digital technologies to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of CAP interventions (European Union, 2021). The **scope and depth of the digitalisation strategies within the CAP NSPs vary considerably** across Member States, ranging from brief overviews to detailed frameworks, reflecting each country's prior experience with digitalisation in agriculture and agriculture policy priorities.

In their NSPs, Member States with more advanced digital economies have focused on high-technology solutions, including investments in precision farming and the development of national agricultural data platforms. In contrast, countries with a higher proportion of small-scale farms and limited digital infrastructure have prioritised foundational interventions such as expanding rural broadband, offering basic digital skills training, and deploying digital tools to streamline administrative processes. This flexibility, which is a core feature of the new CAP framework, has led to a diverse set of strategies in which the ambition and scope of digitalisation are tailored to the specific contexts and starting points of each country. Importantly, even in the absence of prescriptive legal requirements, the process of developing these strategies has encouraged Member States to reflect on the role of digitalisation in agriculture and to establish a baseline framework that was previously lacking in many cases.

Although the full effects of implementation are only beginning to materialise after preparatory work in 2022 and the start of implementation in 2023, all NSPs analysed include some dedicated measures to support the uptake of digital technologies, develop digital skills, and improve the use of data in the agricultural sector. At the planning stage, Member States signalled the allocation of approximately six billion euro for digitalisation over the course of the programming period. This figure represents an **indicative commitment**, and the extent of implementation remains to be assessed in order to determine which interventions have been prioritised by governments and actually adopted by farmers. Nevertheless, the planned amount constitutes one of the largest sources of funding directly available to farmers for digital adoption, reinforcing the central role of the CAP as the primary instrument for the advancement of digital technologies in farms, complemented by R&I support under Horizon Europe.

Overview of CAP NSP Targets in the CODECS EU Member States

Table 2 shows the country-by-country targets for R.1, R.2, R.3, and R.28 alongside the number of farms, highlighting both the scale of planned outreach and the uneven distribution of ambition and reporting across Member States. It should be noted that R.3 is a direct indicator of efforts for agricultural digitalisation, whereas R.1, R.2, and R.28 encompass digitalisation-related initiatives and are therefore included in this analysis. R.40 (target number of "smart villages" strategies supported) was reviewed as well, but the lack of values for most countries makes the distribution incomplete and limits a balanced interpretation across the group.

Across Table 2, a clear split can be observed between absolute scale and per farm intensity. Some countries set very large raw totals for the number of people reached, but when adjusted per farm, the intensity picture shifts. For instance, under **R.1**, Spain leads with 1,329,127, followed by Hungary with 736,210. Belgium's totals are

lower in absolute terms but translate into very high intensity once divided by its smaller farm base: about 10.14 people per farm, well ahead of Hungary at 3.17 and Ireland at 2.30, with a close group that includes Spain at 1.45, Estonia at 1.42, Czechia at 1.38, Germany at 1.33, Slovenia at 1.15, and the Netherlands at 1.04. Lower intensities appear for France at 0.35, Italy at 0.38, Greece at 0.39, Slovakia at 0.54, Latvia at 0.34, and Poland at 0.10. This contrast between volume and intensity is one of the defining patterns in the data.

Advisor integration shows even sharper divergences. Estonia stands out with about 0.585 advisors per farm under **R.2**, far above the rest, indicating a strategy that concentrates on embedding advisory capacity relative to the size of the farm base. By contrast, Poland reports a very large raw advisor total of 103,332 but this equates to about 0.079 per farm, illustrating how scale does not automatically imply high density when farm numbers are large. Several other countries register lean advisor ratios near or below one hundredth per farm, reinforcing the broad spread in approaches to building AKIS capacity.

On **R.3**, the share of farms receiving digital support ranges from more than half of farms to just a few per thousand. The pattern shows a small group planning very broad diffusion across farms, a middle group aiming for selective but visible uptake, and several countries positioning digital support as a small component. The contrast between Belgium (52.28%) and Greece (26.08%) at the top and countries with fractions below 1% (Germany, Ireland, Czechia, Latvia, Poland, and Italy) underscores very different starting points or prioritisation paths for digitalisation in this period.

For **R.28**, the per farm lens shows the relative intensity of planned environment and climate-related knowledge actions. Belgium again leads with about 5.22 target individuals per farm, followed by Hungary at 1.90 and Ireland at 1.80. Germany is at 1.07, with Slovenia at 0.79 and the Netherlands at 0.62. Most others lie below 0.5 per farm, including Estonia at 0.40, Spain at 0.30, France at 0.18, Greece at 0.16, Slovakia at 0.12, Italy at 0.11, Latvia at 0.10, Czechia at 0.06, and Poland at 0.02. Because R.28 counts individuals reached through advice, training, knowledge exchange or EIP group participation focused on better environmental or climate related performance, these per farm ratios indicate how intensively programmes aim to mobilise people on that agenda relative to their farm base.

Using “per farm” intensity (instead of “per farmer” intensity) provides a better assessment of the programmes’ reach for these interventions. The objective of R.1, R.2, and R.28 is ultimately to transform farm businesses by facilitating the adoption of digital tools and practices. Since a holding is a single business unit typically governed by one primary manager, the most policy-relevant question is: “What is the average number of people reached per business?” This “per farm” average directly estimates the penetration of the measure into the agricultural sector’s business fabric. In contrast, a “per farmer” average would answer a different question: “What is the average number of people reached per individual working in agriculture?” This metric is less meaningful for evaluating these specific CAP measures because it is diluted by the varying labour structures of different holdings. A large, corporate farm with many employees would disproportionately inflate the denominator for a country, making a successful program appear to have low penetration simply because the agricultural workforce is large. The “per farm” average is therefore a more robust and consistent indicator of how effectively the support is being disseminated to the core decision-making units (the farms themselves) across different Member States.

Table 2: CAP NSP indicators relevant to agricultural digitalisation and farm counts by country.

Country	R.1 Knowledge and Innovation	R.2 Linking Advisory and Knowledge Systems (AKIS)	R.3 Digitalisation of Agriculture	R.28 Participation in EIP Operational Groups	Number of Farms	R.1 Per farm	R.2 Per farm	R.3 (fraction)	R.28 Per farm
Belgium	365,099	3,618	52.28%	187,878	36,000	10.1416	0.1005	0.5228	5.2188

Country	R.1 Knowledge and Innovation	R.2 Linking Advisory and Knowledge Systems (AKIS)	R.3 Digitalisation of Agriculture	R.28 Participation in EIP Operational Groups	Number of Farms	R.1 Per farm	R.2 Per farm	R.3 (fraction)	R.28 Per farm
Czechia	39,991	480	0.67%	1,625	28,910	1.3833	0.0166	0.0067	0.0562
Estonia	16,180	6,653	1.16%	4,590	11,370	1.4230	0.5851	0.0116	0.4037
France	139,488	-	-	-	393,030	0.3549	-	-	-
Germany	350,000	1,000	0.95%	280,000	262,780	1.3319	0.0038	0.0095	1.0655
Greece	206,154	6,594	26.08%	82,461	530,750	0.3884	0.0124	0.2608	0.1554
Hungary	736,210	14,640	7.69%	441,726	232,060	3.1725	0.0631	0.0769	1.9035
Ireland	299,412	10,176	0.91%	234,927	130,220	2.2993	0.0781	0.0091	1.8041
Italy	431,868	16,070	0.10%	120,000	1,133,020	0.3812	0.0142	0.0010	0.1059
Latvia	23,383	304	0.49%	7,133	68,980	0.3390	0.0044	0.0049	0.1034
Netherlands	54,991	2,108	-	32,500	52,640	1.0447	0.0400	-	0.6174
Poland	127,209	103,332	0.30%	25,244	1,302,330	0.0977	0.0793	0.0030	0.0194
Slovakia	10,509	492	3.36%	2,300	19,630	0.5354	0.0251	0.0336	0.1172
Slovenia	83,336	510	4.28%	57,186	72,470	1.1499	0.0070	0.0428	0.7891
Spain	1,329,127	8,259	2.47%	273,282	914,870	1.4528	0.0090	0.0247	0.2987

R.1 (Knowledge and innovation): Target number of individuals benefiting from advice, training, knowledge exchange or participation in EIP Operational Groups supported by the CAP.

R.2 (Linking advisory and knowledge systems): Target number of advisors receiving support to be integrated into the AKIS.

R.3 (Digitalisation of agriculture): Target number of farms receiving support for digital agricultural technologies under CAP.

R.28 (Environmental or climate performance through knowledge and innovation): Target number of individuals benefiting from advice, training, knowledge exchange or participation in EIP Operational Groups supported by CAP to deliver better environmental or climate-related performance.

Agriculture-Specific Momentum in the CODECS EU Member States

Table 3 below presents a composite estimate of momentum behind agricultural digitalisation in the CODECS EU Member States, obtained by normalising each adjusted indicator from Table 2 to a 0 to 100 scale and computing a weighted average that assigns 55% to R.3 and 15% to each of R.1, R.2 and R.28. The countries were then ranked by the overall composite, and the indicator composites shown alongside reveal which dimensions drive each position. This ranking should be read as **a measure of relative ambition and planned intensity** rather than realised performance, especially where entries are missing. A short country-by-country analysis follows.

Table 3: Country overview of agriculture-specific momentum (normalised 0-100).

Country	R1 Normalised	R2 Normalised	R3 Normalised	R28 Normalised	Ag-Specific Momentum
Belgium	100	16.6	100	100	87.49
Greece	2.9	1.5	49.8	2.6	28.43
Hungary	30.6	10.2	14.5	36.2	19.56
Estonia	13.2	100	2.0	7.4	19.21
Ireland	21.9	12.8	1.6	34.3	11.21
Slovenia	10.5	0.6	8.0	14.8	8.28
Germany	12.3	0	1.6	20.1	5.76
Spain	13.5	0.9	4.5	5.4	5.46
Netherlands	9.4	6.2	(*) 2.0	11.5	5.19
Slovakia	4.4	3.7	6.2	1.9	4.92
Czechia	12.8	2.2	1.1	0.7	2.96
France	2.6	(*) 1.6	(*) 2.0	(*) 3.0	2.20
Poland	0	13.0	0.4	0	2.16
Latvia	2.4	0.1	0.7	1.6	1.03
Italy	2.8	1.8	0	1.7	0.94

* No target reported in the country's CAP NSP. The median across this indicator was imputed as a conservative proxy.

In absolute terms, **Belgium** sets very large targets across the board: 365,099 people under R.1, 3,618 advisors under R.2, and 187,878 people under R.28, with digitalisation support planned for 52.28% of farms under R.3 out of a farm base of 36,000. This points to a programme that combines broad knowledge and innovation actions, substantial integration of advisors, and a very wide digital push across farms. On intensity, Belgium's per farm figures are striking: 10.1416 people per farm for R.1, 0.1005 advisors per farm for R.2, and 5.2188 people per farm for R.28. Taken together these numbers signal very dense engagement with farmers on knowledge and on environmental or climate related actions, supported by a comparatively high advisor presence and an unusually

broad adoption of digital technologies. Remarkably, however, two points extend the Belgium reading beyond the national numbers. First, the national digitalisation share of 52.28% under R.3 is the net of a very high share in Flanders at 80.71% and a very small share in Wallonia at 0.21%. The country level figure therefore masks a split in planned digital reach that is almost all located in Flanders. Second, the remarkably high Belgium per farm intensities for R.1 and R.28 are driven by the Flemish figures rather than being evenly distributed. Using the regional farm counts, Flanders targets about 19.39 R.1 beneficiaries, 0.191 advisors under R.2, and 9.98 R.28 beneficiaries per farm, while Wallonia aims about 0.0037, 0.00077, and 0.0015 respectively. In short, Belgium's high national ratios reflect an intensive Flemish programme rather than a balanced effort across both regions.

Greece sets targets of 206,154 people for R.1, 6,594 advisors for R.2, and 82,461 people for R.28, against a farm base of 530,750. Under R.3, digitalisation support is planned for 26.08% of farms, the second highest share among the CODECS countries. On a per farm basis, Greece is below the median on R.1, R.2, and R.28, with 0.3884 R.1 beneficiaries, 0.0124 R.2 advisors, and 0.1554 R.28 beneficiaries per farm. Overall, this points to moderate reach on knowledge actions relative to the farm base, lean advisor density, and targeted environment or climate-related engagement, while digital technologies are planned for about one quarter of farms.

At raw level, **Hungary** sets large targets on knowledge and on environment or climate-related actions, with 736,210 people under R.1 and 441,726 under R.28, alongside 14,640 advisors under R.2. Digitalisation support is planned for 7.69% of farms under R.3, and the farm base is 232,060. On intensity, Hungary targets 3.1725 beneficiaries per farm for R.1, 0.0631 advisors per farm under R.2, and 1.9035 beneficiaries per farm for R.28. This profile signals dense engagement with knowledge and with environment or climate-related actions relative to the farm base, a solid advisor presence, and digital support planned for a meaningful share of farms (the third largest share among the CODECS countries).

Estonia's overall targets are 16,180 people under R.1, a very large 6,653 advisors under R.2, and 4,590 people under R.28, with digitalisation planned for 1.16% of farms under R.3 from a base of 11,370. The standout figure is the advisor count, which is high in absolute terms given the small farm base, pointing to a programme centred on building advisory capacity. On intensity, Estonia aims 1.4230 people per farm for R.1, an exceptional 0.5851 advisors per farm for R.2, and 0.4037 people per farm for R.28. This shows a strategy that couples solid knowledge actions with very dense advisor integration and a meaningful but selective push on environmental or climate-related knowledge. However, the planned number of farms receiving support for digital agricultural technologies remains modest in scope (just under the median).

Ireland's raw targets are 299,412 people for R.1, 10,176 advisors for R.2, and 234,927 people for R.28, with digitalisation planned for 0.91% of farms under R.3, against a farm base of 130,220. On a per farm basis, Ireland aims 2.2993 beneficiaries for R.1, 0.0781 advisors under R.2 (the fourth largest among the CODECS countries), and 1.8041 beneficiaries for R.28, while the breadth of support for farm digitalisation is comparatively modest in absolute reach (the fifth lowest in the cohort). The figures indicate strong people-focused activity and a comparatively dense advisor integration for the farm base, while support for digital technologies is planned for only about one farm in a hundred.

Slovenia targets 83,336 people for R.1, 510 advisors for R.2, and 57,186 people for R.28, with digitalisation support planned for 4.28% of farms under R.3 (the fourth highest in the dataset, though still far below the very broad coverage planned in Belgium and Greece). Relative to 72,470 farms, this equates to 1.1499 beneficiaries per farm under R.1, 0.0070 advisors per farm under R.2 (the third lowest among CODECS countries), and 0.7891 beneficiaries per farm under R.28. Taken together, these figures indicate broad reach of knowledge actions relative to the farm base, very lean advisor density, and particularly intensive engagement on environment or climate-related knowledge, while the planned digital support for farms, although modest in overall share, is well above the median among CODECS countries.

Germany sets large totals for knowledge and environment-related actions with 350,000 people under R.1 and 280,000 under R.28, alongside 1,000 advisors under R.2, and digitalisation support for 0.95% of farms under R.3. Against a base 262,780 farms, this equates to 1.3319 R.1 beneficiaries and 1.0655 R.28 beneficiaries per farm, indicating roughly one person reached per farm on both agendas, while R.2 stands at 0.0038 advisors per farm (the lowest among CODECS countries). Taken together, these figures indicate strong per farm engagement on knowledge and environment-related themes, a very lean presence of CAP-funded advisory services, and a modest scope of support for the digitalisation of farms (just below the CODECS median).

Spain sets very large raw totals with 1,329,127 people for R.1, 8,259 advisors for R.2, and 273,282 people for R.28. Digitalisation support is planned for 2.47% of farms under R.3, and the farm base is 914,870. On a per farm basis, Spain aims 1.4528 beneficiaries under R.1, 0.0090 advisors for R.2 (the fourth lowest among CODECS countries), and 0.2987 beneficiaries under R.28. Altogether, this profile shows strong reach on knowledge actions relative to the farm base, low-density support for advisory services, environment or climate-related engagement at the median among CODECS countries, and digital technologies planned for roughly one farm in forty (just above the CODECS median).

The **Netherlands** establishes a target of 54,991 people for R.1, 2,108 advisors for R.2, and 32,500 people for R.28. With a farm base of 52,640 this corresponds to 1.0447 beneficiaries per farm for R.1, 0.0400 advisors per farm for R.2, and 0.6174 beneficiaries per farm for R.28. Interestingly, the Netherlands does not set a target number of farms receiving support for digital agricultural technologies under CAP for R.3. Given the country's leading role in agricultural digitalisation, several explanations are plausible and consistent with this observation. One is design choice, since substantial effort is visible in knowledge actions and in environment or climate related knowledge, which suggests digitalisation could be delivered through those measures rather than as a standalone target to avoid double counting where digital components are embedded in other actions. Another possibility is timing or accounting, with the target defined elsewhere, reported later, or addressed through non-CAP instruments. A further explanation is that uptake is expected to proceed without explicit CAP targeting, reflecting a national tendency to move ahead without waiting for government support. The Dutch CAP NSP does not state which of these applies and simply records that no R.3 target is given for the period.

Slovakia plans to support 10,509 people under R.1, 492 advisors under R.2, and 2,300 people under R.28. With a farm base of 19,630, equates to 0.5354 beneficiaries per farm for R.1, 0.0251 advisors per farm for R.2, and 0.1172 beneficiaries per farm for R.28. In addition, Slovakia sets a target of 3.36% of farms receiving support for digital agricultural technologies under R.3. This profile suggests advisory support density just above the CODECS median, modest reach on knowledge actions and on environment or climate-related activity, and support for digital technologies planned for about one farm in thirty.

In total terms, **Czechia** targets support for 39,991 people under R.1, 480 advisors under R.2, and 1,625 people under R.28. With a farm base of 28,910, this corresponds to 1.3833 beneficiaries per farm under R.1, 0.0166 advisors per farm under R.2, and 0.0562 people per farm under R.28. Digitalisation support is planned for 0.67% of farms under R.3, the fourth lowest among CODECS countries. Overall, Czechia's profile shows above median reach on knowledge and innovation actions, below median advisor density under CAP, very modest environment or climate-related engagement (the second lowest in the cohort), and a low level of digitalisation support for farms (the fourth lowest).

France sets a target of 139,488 people supported under R.1 and provides no targets for R.2, R.3, or R.28. The number of farms in the country is 393,030. In absolute terms, this means the only quantified commitment for France in this analysis concerns knowledge and innovation actions captured by R.1 (the third lowest among CODECS countries). The absence of targets for the other indicators could reflect a design choice to embed digital and environment or climate-related actions within other measures, a timing or accounting decision with targets defined elsewhere or to be published later, or reliance on instruments outside CAP. The French CAP NSP does not specify which applies and simply records no targets for R.2, R.3, or R.28 for the period.

Poland's total targets are 127,209 people for R.1, a very large 103,332 advisors for R.2, and 25,244 people for R.28, with digitalisation support planned for 0.30% of farms under R.3. With a farm base of 1,302,330, the profile is dominated by advisor integration, while digital support covers a very small share of holdings. Per farm, Poland aims to benefit 0.0977 people under R.1, 0.0793 advisors under R.2, and 0.0194 individuals under R.28, placing the country third in the cohort for advisor density under CAP. By contrast, the R.3 share is the second lowest in the group (only about three farms in a thousand), and per farm reach on both knowledge and innovation (R.1) and on environment or climate-related actions (R.28) are the lowest among CODECS countries.

Latvia's overall targets are 23,383 people under R.1, 304 advisors under R.2, and 7,133 people under R.28, with digitalisation support planned for 0.49% of farms under R.3. Against a farm base of 68,980, this is a very modest plan. Per farm, Latvia aims 0.3390 beneficiaries for R.1, 0.0044 advisors under R.2, and 0.1034 beneficiaries under R.28. Within the CODECS group, Latvia sits near the bottom on each of the four indicators, with modest reach on knowledge and innovation actions (second lowest for R.1), very lean advisor density under CAP (second

lowest for R.2), limited environment or climate-related engagement (third lowest for R.28), and low planned digitalisation with only about five farms support for every one thousand (third lowest for R.3).

Lastly, **Italy** plans to benefit 431,868 people under R.1, 16,070 advisors under R.2, and 120,000 people under R.28, with digitalisation support planned for 0.10% of farms under R.3. Against a very large base of 1,133,020 farms, this corresponds to 0.3812 beneficiaries per farm under R.1, 0.0142 advisors per farm under R.2, and 0.1059 beneficiaries per farm under R.28. Overall, Italy shows advisor density under CAP (R.2) just below the median, and the fourth lowest per farm reach on both knowledge and innovation (R.1) and on environment or climate-related actions (R.28). The very low target of about one farm in a thousand receiving support for digital technologies (R.3) places the country at the bottom for agriculture-specific momentum among CODECS countries.

In closing, while the CAP NSP indicators reviewed in this section provide a structured view of planned actions and per farm intensities, **early signals on the performance of Member States remain inconclusive**. As noted in section 5.1, the absence of reliable baseline data, inconsistencies in how digitalisation expenditures are recorded, and variation in what qualifies as digitalisation related expenses make it difficult to assess progress, to judge whether limited CAP spending reflects prior investments, and to determine whether countries are using other funding sources to support agricultural digitalisation. Where data exist, such as R.3, reported outcomes have not yet reached the scale originally anticipated, and a clearer picture is expected once all Member State reports are submitted and reviewed. Preliminary information indicates that eco schemes and AECCs have been used to promote the uptake of precision technologies aimed at environmental benefits, although these budgets have generally been limited. The main instrument to advance digitalisation continues to be investment support under rural development measures, which accounts for most of the planned spending on digital tools.

5.3 Other Policy Levers

The digital transition is currently one of the most strategic cross-cutting frameworks in the EU, mobilising multiple tools and funding streams to address the complexity of digital policy and generate spillovers across sectors. In agriculture, turning this agenda into results will require concerted action. Although the CAP is a key support instrument for digitalisation in agriculture, this transformation involves more than the adoption of technology at farm level and depends also on broader enabling conditions such as connectivity, skills development, data governance, interoperability, and R&I. To meet these interconnected needs, the EU draws on a range of complementary policies and funding programmes that work together to support the digital transformation of the agri-food sector.

The broader EU funding landscape includes, among others, the **Digital Europe Programme (DEP)** for technology development and deployment, **Horizon Europe** for R&I, the **Connecting Europe Facility (CEF)** to improve connectivity, and the **Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)** for a wide range of reforms and investments, including large scale infrastructure and small-scale projects for SMEs. In addition, the **European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)** promotes a smarter and more balanced Europe by financing investments in digital infrastructure, support for SMEs, and digital skills development. The **European Social Fund Plus (ESF+)** focuses on human capital, providing resources for training and skills development to ensure that farmers and rural communities have the digital literacy and technical expertise needed to adopt new technologies. And the **LIFE Programme**, which supports environment and climate action, contributes by funding digital solutions with clear environmental benefits, such as smart irrigation systems or tools to monitor and reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

Established as the central component of NextGenerationEU, the EU's response to the economic and social impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, the **RRF** has been an important instrument for digitalisation in agriculture and rural areas in several EU Member States, primarily by treating connectivity as critical economic infrastructure. By allocating unprecedented funding through national recovery plans (such as Spain's España Digital 2026 agenda or Italy's PAC Italia 2), it has provided substantial funding to expand high-capacity broadband and 5G networks into rural "white zones", thereby addressing the fundamental connectivity gap that has long hindered adoption. Furthermore, its strategic use has incentivized Member States to bundle digital infrastructure with targeted

investments in agricultural innovation, funding everything from precision farming technologies and AI-driven solutions to smart irrigation systems and digital skills training for farmers.

This diversity of programmes gives national and regional authorities the flexibility to match funding sources to specific policy goals and implementation needs. Governments select programmes based on their alignment with the specific **type of intervention**, the **scale and scope of investment**, the characteristics of the **target population or region**, and the **administrative structures** available to deliver results. Some instruments are better suited for farm level or sector specific support, while others are designed for cross-sectoral infrastructure, innovation, or skills development. Strategic coordination across these programmes is essential to avoid duplication, close investment gaps, and ensure that public resources are used effectively, although this is not always achieved in practice. When combined thoughtfully, these instruments create a more coherent and resilient framework for advancing the digital transition in agriculture and the wider agri-food system. For instance, although the CAP can support infrastructure, most countries rely on other funds that are better suited to large scale connectivity investments.

Beyond funding, a set of complementary measures play a critical role in building trust and advancing digitalisation across the wider agri-food system. For instance, recent cross sector initiatives have introduced a stronger framework for data use and sharing in support of the EU's digital economy, with direct implications for agriculture. A key example is the **European Data Strategy** launched in February 2020 to develop a single market for data across the EU. This strategy is supported by two major legislative instruments: the Data Governance Act and the Data Act. The **Data Governance Act** establishes mechanisms for the voluntary sharing of data that cannot be classified as open data due to concerns related to privacy, intellectual property or commercial confidentiality. It also promotes the use of trusted data intermediaries to facilitate secure exchanges and protocols for data harmonisation. Complementing this, the **Data Act** strengthens rights for individuals and businesses to access data generated by connected devices and Internet of Things applications. This is particularly relevant for the agriculture sector, where improved data access can support the uptake of smart farming technologies and the development of new services. In parallel, the **Open Data Directive** seeks to increase the availability and reuse of public sector information. Its latest revision introduced the concept of **high value datasets**, including geospatial, earth observation and meteorological data, which are especially important for agricultural applications. These datasets must be made freely available in machine readable formats and accessible through standardised digital tools, helping to lay the foundations for more interoperable and data driven innovation in the sector. Building on these, the **Common European Agricultural Data Space** aims to provide a secure, trusted, and interoperable environment for cross-EU data sharing across the agri-food sector.

An important driver of progress in agricultural digitalisation is the growing demand for simplification, as expressed by farmers, policymakers, and other agri-food stakeholders in a recent CAP evaluation (European Commission, 2025b). Although many digital tools are already in use, adoption often reaches a plateau due to persistent interoperability challenges across public and private systems. These barriers limit farmers' ability to integrate technologies beyond their local context, create inefficiencies, and constrain broader uptake. To address this **at the public sector level**, the **Interoperable Europe Act**, which entered into force in April 2024, requires both EU institutions and Member States to assess the compatibility of new legal acts and digital systems. A formal review process has been introduced within EU institutions to ensure that systems and data are interoperable, harmonised where necessary, and aligned with a digital-by-default approach. Managed by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Informatics (DG DIGIT), the Act is supported by the **Interoperable Europe Portal**, which shares effective solutions to encourage alignment across administrations. Furthermore, the **legislative proposal 2025/0236(COD)**, presented in May 2025, calls for **each Member State to designate an interoperability governance authority** responsible for developing and implementing a roadmap to achieve and maintain interoperability and seamless data exchange. Together, these measures aim to induce a significant cultural and institutional shift that removes structural barriers to digitalisation and ensures public sector organisations across the EU operate within a more integrated and digitally coherent framework for CAP implementation.

This strategic emphasis on data and interoperability forms part of a broader policy push that recognises digitalisation as a central enabler of the EU's long-term vision for agriculture and food systems. Adopted in February 2025, the EU's **Vision for Agriculture and Food** places digitalisation at the heart of competitiveness, resilience and sustainability. It identifies four priorities guiding the path to 2040: building an attractive sector,

strengthening competitiveness and resilience, future proofing agriculture and its communities, and promoting the value of food while fostering vibrant rural areas. The vision responds to mounting pressures, including geopolitical tensions, challenges with generational renewal, persistent farm income difficulties, and the accelerating effects of climate change. It therefore highlights the need for strong enablers. Digitalisation is seen as a key driver of change, with the potential to improve economic performance, reinforce competitiveness and resilience, and support sustainability goals (European Commission, 2025c).

A central action from the Vision is the development of an **EU Digital Strategy for Agriculture** to address barriers to the digital transition, including high costs, limited capacity building, issues of trust and uneven connectivity. To inform this strategy, the EC conducted two complementary studies. The first is a foresight exercise led by the JRC through workshops across the EU, which explores the long-term implications of digitalisation for farmers and rural communities, sets out a value-based vision to guide the transition, and proposes policy options to reduce risks and capture opportunities (Barabanova & Krzysztofowicz, 2023). In parallel, the Commission carried out a survey-based study to establish a baseline for the adoption of digital tools in EU agriculture, compare progress across Member States and assess whether a digital divide is emerging. Data collection took place from June to September 2024 and covered about 1,440 farmers in nine countries, namely France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Poland, Spain, Greece and Lithuania, covering multiple sectors (Tur Cardona et al., 2025). There is substantial overlap between the countries covered in this report and those in CODECS. A quick review of the report, released only days before the submission of this deliverable, shows strong alignment between our research and its findings.

An emerging area of interest concerns the growing potential of AI in agriculture. In April 2025, the EC announced its **AI Continent Action Plan**, which aims to position the EU as a global leader in AI by improving access to high quality data and promoting adoption across strategic sectors, including agriculture (European Commission, 2025d). As part of this initiative, two complementary strategies were proposed: the **Apply AI Strategy** and the **Data Union Strategy**. The Apply AI Strategy seeks to accelerate the deployment of AI in key sectors, with agriculture explicitly identified as a priority. Public consultation on the strategy has recently concluded, and adoption is expected by the end of 2025. In parallel, the Data Union Strategy aims to foster a more integrated internal market for data and to scale up AI development across the EU. Its consultation period closed in July 2025, with adoption also planned for later in the year. Complementing these policy drives, the **EU AI Act** (landmark legislation that entered into force in August 2024) establishes a risk-based framework that bans unacceptable-risk systems and imposes strict requirements on high-risk applications, with most provisions taking effect between 2025 and 2026. It will also capture agricultural use cases where AI forms part of the safety components of regulated machinery. Together with the forthcoming EU Digital Strategy for Agriculture, these initiatives signal a stronger push to operationalise AI on farms and across agri-food value chains.

Another area of growing interest is cybersecurity, which is becoming integral to agriculture and food systems as connected machinery, on-farm sensors, farm management software, satellite services, and digital platforms for logistics and payments create more points of exposure. According to Angelica Marotta (MIT researcher) presentation in [CODECS Knowledge Accelerator](#) event, one out of seven ransom demands are targeting the agrifood sector. Disruptions from cyberattacks can halt operations, compromise traceability and safety data, and erode trust, so resilience must be strengthened across farms, cooperatives, processors, traders, and public services. The **EU's Cybersecurity Strategy for the Digital Decade**, presented in December 2020, provides a comprehensive plan to build resilience to cyber threats and ensure that citizens and businesses benefit from trustworthy digital technologies. Within this framework, the **NIS2 Directive** establishes essential risk management and incident reporting duties for a wide range of sectors. This is complemented by the **Cyber Resilience Act**, which sets horizontal security requirements for all products with digital elements, ensuring that connected hardware and software are secure by design throughout their life cycle.

Efforts to digitalise the agri-food value chain are also impacted by a wide range of EU policies and regulations related to e-government, health, food safety, and environmental protection. These frameworks cover areas such as primary production, hygiene standards, packaging, labelling, and quality control. Other related domains including animal welfare, plant health, biosecurity, fertiliser and pesticide use, and nutrition labelling are also subject to specific regulatory requirements. Many of these areas are directly linked to transparency, traceability and sustainability, which are core objectives of the **European Green Deal** and the **Farm to Fork Strategy**, and stand to benefit significantly from digital technologies. In addition, several EU regulations governing digital markets and online transactions also affect the agri-food sector. These include the **Directive on Contracts for**

the Supply of Digital Content and Digital Services (Directive (EU) 2019/770), the Digital Services Act, and the Digital Markets Act.

6. Insights from Interviews with Policymakers and Experts

6.1 Digitalisation in CODECS Countries

The interviews with policymakers and experts revealed a complex picture of digitalisation across EU member states and candidate countries, reflecting a wide spectrum of approaches, achievements, and ongoing challenges. While many noted substantial progress in national digitalisation efforts, they also pointed to the COVID-19 pandemic as a critical accelerator that catalysed rapid deployment of digital solutions and services across various sectors. Public administration, CAP compliance, and service delivery were cited as areas of progress, alongside a broader uptake of digital technologies by businesses and citizens. Despite these gains, interviewees highlighted persistent differences between countries, driven by structural conditions such as the urban-rural connectivity gap, uneven digital skills, and unequal access to transformation initiatives, as well as by farm size, orography, demographics, and absorptive capacity at farm level. They also drew attention to emerging challenges gaining prominence in policy discussions, including the need for greater interoperability, robust data governance frameworks, and improved cross-border collaboration to support an integrated digital ecosystem across the EU.

In addition, the interviews with EU-level experts highlighted the significant impact of policy in driving the digital transition, noting that without a clear EU framework, progress across Member States would likely have been slower and less coordinated. They highlighted initiatives such as the Digital Data Act, the Digital Governance Act, and the Digital Markets Act as instrumental in helping countries address complex challenges like data sharing and interoperability. Member States that have taken proactive political decisions to advance digitalisation were seen as having advanced more quickly and achieved more tangible results compared to those adopting a more cautious approach. The interviewees also underscored the importance of mobilising both public and private investment to meet the ambitions of national and EU digital agendas. Connectivity was described as the backbone of digital transformation, particularly in rural and underserved areas. While the urban-rural digital divide is gradually narrowing and is increasingly viewed as a short-term issue, persistent challenges such as high investment costs and regulatory constraints, including limits on electromagnetic emissions, continue to hinder progress in some regions.

This qualitative evidence aligns closely with the findings from the analysis of DESI data, providing a more comprehensive picture of the state of digitalisation across the CODECS countries. Figure 4 presents the overall DESI scores for these countries, using the most recent year for which a complete aggregate ranking is available (European Commission, 2022). Although individual DESI indicators have been updated through 2024, the 2022 composite remains the latest harmonised benchmark, giving a consistent snapshot of each country's relative level of digitalisation at the start of the decade. The results reveal a sharply differentiated landscape of digital readiness across the 15 CODECS EU member states, with composite scores ranging from 67.4 for the Netherlands at the top of the table to 38.9 for Greece at the bottom, against an EU-27 average of 52.3 points. When viewed together, these data sort the countries into **four performance tiers** that are shaped not only by their aggregate scores but also by contrasting strengths and weaknesses across the index's four pillars: Connectivity, Digital Public Services, Human Capital, and Integration of Digital Technologies. The interviews with policymakers and sector experts corroborated this tiered pattern, highlighting the disparities in the quality of infrastructure, use of e-government services, availability of digital skills, and technology adoption by SMEs.

The top tier is formed by the Netherlands, Ireland, Spain and Estonia. At its head stands the Netherlands with a composite score of 67.4, which is driven by the strongest connectivity, human capital, and business uptake of digital technologies, along with the second highest score in digital public services among the CODECS countries. Ireland follows with 62.7, pushed above all by exceptional human-capital performance and high degree of integration of digital technologies by businesses. Spain's third position with a score of 60.8 is driven by near-ubiquitous connectivity, a digitally mature public administration, and human capital and business adoption of digital technologies that are at levels above the EU-27 average. Estonia completes the group with 56.5, largely

thanks to EU-leading e-government services that compensate for a relatively modest connectivity score (one of the lowest in the EU, despite significant improvements achieved between 2020 and 2025).

The second tier comprises Slovenia, France, Germany and Belgium, which are clustered around the EU average with composite scores between 50.3 and 53.4. All four enjoy solid foundations, yet each one of them shows distinct shortcomings that hold back its overall performance. Slovenia’s balanced profile is held back by below EU average digital skill levels. France combines robust connectivity, human capital and public service digitalisation with a comparatively weak score for business adoption of advanced technologies. Germany mirrors France in the quality of connectivity infrastructure but records below the EU-27 average in digital skills, use of e-government services, and business uptake of digital technologies. Belgium, conversely, shows high performance in that same corporate dimension but its connectivity trailed the EU average in 2021 (it has since improved, closing significantly the gap with the leaders). For all four, addressing digital skills bottlenecks and accelerating SME digital uptake are the most pressing items on the policy agenda.

Figure 4: DESI Aggregate Score of CODECS Countries (2022).

The third tier consists of Latvia, Italy, Czechia and Hungary, which sit in the 43.8 to 49.7 range and present more uneven profiles. Latvia stands out for its strong performance in digital public services, but rural connectivity gaps and very low levels of digital transformation of businesses drag down its composite score. Italy’s multi-billion-euro tax incentives for industrial modernisation are reflected in its strong business digitalisation score, yet the country still records some of the weakest human capital metrics among its CODECS peers. Czechia’s composite score of 49.1 reflects a balanced performance, with each of the four pillars sitting close to the EU average (52.3) and none straying markedly from the reference values. Lastly, although Hungary’s connectivity is close to the EU average, the country struggles with particularly low scores in digital skills, e-government services, and business digitalisation. Common threads for this cohort include the need to accelerate infrastructure development beyond large cities and boost basic digital literacy among older and low-income groups.

Finally, Slovakia, Poland and Greece constitute the fourth tier, with composites between 38.9 and 43.4. Their scores cluster around the EU-27’s bottom quartile across all four DESI pillars, thus suggesting a digital landscape that is broad yet still relatively shallow. Slovakia shows a broadly balanced but modest digitalisation profile, with all four DESI pillars scoring slightly below the EU average; while progress has been steady in recent years, the country still faces challenges in digital skills development, business adoption of advanced technologies, and the deployment of digital infrastructure in rural areas. Poland enjoys robust fixed line internet connectivity and has steadily improved across all DESI pillars over the past five years, yet its population’s digital skills remain limited, and businesses are still slow to adopt advanced technologies. Lastly, Greece, despite recent gains in e-government and parts of connectivity supported by Recovery and Resilience Facility funding, still records subpar results in digital skills and business digitalisation.

Taken together, the insights obtained from the interviews and DESI data reveal that digital skills have become the decisive dividing line in the EU's digital landscape. Countries that have resolved connectivity challenges are competing on the depth of advanced talent, while those still expanding their digital infrastructure must simultaneously address human capital gaps. At the same time, slow adoption of digital technologies by businesses (especially SMEs) remains a major limiting factor in most CODECS countries, thus highlighting the need for policies that leverage digital transformation as a driver of productivity and competitiveness.

6.2 Agricultural Digitalisation in CODECS Countries

As described in more detail in Section 6.5, the level of agricultural digitalisation is shaped by a range of factors, including level of connectivity, human capital, governance, topography, economic conditions, absorptive capacity, farmer demographics, farm size structure, and the prevalence of specific subsectors. Thus, for example, adoption tends to be higher in subsectors such as horticulture, row crops, and high-volume greenhouse production, where returns on investment are strong and market requirements (including buyer and supply chain standards) call for digital tracking and traceability. In the livestock sector, uptake increases with farm intensity, with large dairy farms in Germany and the Netherlands frequently cited as examples of advanced digital use. High-revenue farms, such as those in Italian viticulture or Spanish greenhouses, are generally more willing to invest in digital solutions, particularly when cultivating high-value crops that justify the cost of specialised equipment and data-driven management. Environmental and physical conditions, such as water scarcity or poor soil quality, can also drive adoption by increasing the need for greater efficiency and precision. Likewise, younger farmers tend to be more open to digitalisation, driven by their familiarity with technology and their interest in innovation, sustainability, and data-informed decision-making.

These dynamics play out differently across countries and regions, producing wide variation in adoption. For example, farming practices in the Netherlands are generally highly digitalised, while in countries such as Greece, Poland, and Slovakia, digital adoption remains at an earlier stage, despite notable examples of advanced farms. Regional contrasts are also evident, with farms in northern parts of Serbia, Italy or Germany tending to be more digitally advanced than those in the south. Across all contexts, however, one pattern is consistent: regardless of a country's overall digital development, the agricultural sector typically lags behind other sectors in adopting digital technologies.

Although the absence of standardised farm-level digitalisation statistics limits the possibility of a fully objective assessment, our combined analysis of national digital readiness, indicators related to farm size and farm manager demographics, and indicators related to agriculture-specific momentum (see Section 2.1) enabled us to identify four distinct groups: (i) countries that excel in digitalisation (composite score ≥ 75), (ii) countries that perform well but remain behind the leader (score between 50 and 75), (iii) countries with moderate performance (composite score between 25 and 50), and (iv) countries that continue to face major challenges despite ongoing efforts (composite score < 25) (Table 4).

It is important to note that scores ranging from 0 to 100 reflect **relative performance across countries**, with 0 indicating the lowest observed value and 100 the highest within the sample. These values are **normalised**, meaning they show how each country compares to other CODECS countries, not absolute performance levels. Furthermore, while each country's stage of digitalisation closely reflects the overall perspectives of the policymakers and experts interviewed, the main purpose of this analysis was to identify relative strengths and gaps and to support targeted discussion and action, not to deliver a definitive ranking.

Table 4: Comparative country performance on agricultural digitalisation factors.

Country	Digital Readiness	Farm size Structure	Demographic Structure	Ag-specific Momentum	Composite
Netherlands	100	100	13.00	5.19	86.56
Ireland	83.70	36.60	34.80	11.21	63.41

France	50.60	85.90	73.90	2.20	59.33
Belgium	40.00	95.80	30.40	87.49	55.36
Spain	76.80	23.90	4.30	5.46	52.76
Germany	49.10	70.40	47.80	5.76	52.13
Estonia	61.80	23.90	69.60	19.21	50.98
Czechia	35.90	39.40	73.90	2.96	38.93
Slovenia	50.80	2.80	8.70	8.28	32.46
Italy	36.30	31.00	13.00	0.94	30.88
Latvia	37.90	0	17.40	1.03	24.53
Slovakia	15.90	16.90	82.60	4.92	22.27
Poland	5.70	7.00	100	2.16	15.28
Hungary	17.00	5.60	13.00	19.56	13.88
Greece	0	4.20	0	28.43	2.47

6.2.1 Frontrunner: Strengths and Challenges Ahead

The **Netherlands** owes its frontrunner status in agricultural digitalisation to decades of building solid economic and institutional foundations: an open, innovation-oriented economy; a predictable legal environment; sustained investment in research and extension systems; a robust technology sector; and strong, reliable physical and digital infrastructure. Its relatively small, topographically uniform territory has lowered the transaction costs of nationwide network deployment, enabling near-universal broadband coverage and the early introduction of integrated farm-management platforms that combine sensor networks with regulatory-compliance modules. A low share of small farms, combined with clear governance structures and high social capital, has facilitated broader adoption of digital technologies. The Netherlands also benefits from extensive 5G and very high capacity network (VHCN) coverage, driven by a competitive telecom market that keeps access affordable. High labour costs, time constraints, and a well-educated farming population have created strong incentives to adopt digital tools. In several crop-based sectors, the agricultural value chain is fully digitalised (from production and processing to marketing and traceability) while animal farming is also highly digitalised and approaching the same level.

Digitalisation is embedded in a broader culture of pragmatism, experimentation, and self-reliance. Active multi-stakeholder innovation hubs, supported by funding lines that persist across electoral cycles, provide a favourable testing ground for new technologies and reinforce farmers' absorptive capacity for advanced technologies. More recently, however, some experts note a growing top-down tendency to favour digital innovation through subsidies and pilot projects as a means to address environmental challenges and to align with EU environmental objectives. This high level of adoption is reinforced by a broader national context in which nearly all public services are delivered digitally, creating an environment where digital interaction is the norm. It extends to agricultural policy implementation, as the Netherlands has closely aligned its CAP NSP with its digitalisation strategy, using tools like electronic field logs to support eco-scheme compliance and enable more efficient sustainability practices. The widespread use of digital technologies across both farming operations and

administrative systems enhances efficiency in compliance, monitoring, and support, reinforcing the country's position at the forefront of smart and sustainable agriculture.

Nonetheless, some challenges lie ahead. The growing complexity of data ownership, interoperability, and cybersecurity calls for governance frameworks that can evolve as rapidly as the underlying technologies. As digital adoption deepens, a new challenge is emerging in ensuring that fragmented tools and platforms work together seamlessly. In the vision of the "Farm of the Future", all digital activities (from machinery operation to environmental monitoring) are connected through interoperable, high quality data systems. Rather than burdening farmers with dozens of disconnected apps, the goal is an integrated ecosystem where data flows efficiently across operations. Achieving this vision will require not only technical solutions but also policy push toward strong vertical and horizontal coordination.

The Netherlands:

- Frontrunner in agricultural digitalisation, with widespread adoption across the value chain and near-universal connectivity.
- Favourable farm structure (only 18% of small and very small holdings), well-educated farming population, and a culture that favours innovation, experimentation and self-reliance over top-down intervention.
- Predictable rule of law, sustained investment in research and extension systems, and efficient, digital public administration.
- Challenges include data interoperability and standardisation, effective digital governance, digital literacy and skills gaps in smaller farms, and somewhat fragmented innovation ecosystem.

6.2.2 Advanced Performers: Progress and Bottlenecks

In CODECS' advanced performer countries, agricultural digitalisation is gaining steady momentum, supported by improving infrastructure, rising farmer engagement, and policy frameworks that promote the adoption of digital tools. Connectivity in many core farming areas is growing, and the use of farm management software, e-filing systems, and advisory networks is expanding. These countries are frequently characterised by a mix of medium to large farm holdings that are well positioned to invest in new technologies along with moderate institutional capacity to guide the transition. Digitalisation is also driven by a relative prevalence of high-value crops, rising labour costs, generational renewal in parts of the farming sector, and growing pressure to meet environmental and compliance standards more efficiently. Together, these factors are pushing both producers and policymakers to view digital tools as essential to improve competitiveness and sustainability. However, persistent challenges continue to hold back progress. Fragmented digital platforms limit interoperability, connectivity in rural and remote regions remains uneven, advisory services often lack the reach or expertise to support smaller farms effectively, and connecting high-level technologies with site-specific needs remains difficult. Significant regional differences within countries also affect the consistency of digitalisation efforts, with some areas benefiting from stronger infrastructure, funding, or institutional support than others. Ensuring long-term policy continuity, tailoring digital solutions to diverse farm structures and sectors, and reinforcing coordination across different levels of government are essential for these countries to move closer to frontrunner status.

In **Ireland**, the latest figures place the country third in digital skills, second in IoT use, and first in online shopping within the EU. From a slow start, these strengths have increasingly carried over to agricultural digitalisation. While rural digitalisation strategies have lagged somewhat (for example, broadband rollout), overall digital readiness is strong: high speed connectivity reaches most areas, including many remote rural locations, and the population is well educated with rapidly improving digital skills. For farmers, compliance, payments, and advisory services are increasingly delivered digitally. The push for greater efficiency, profitability, and sustainability, together with the challenges of a shrinking and aging rural workforce, is accelerating adoption, supported by initiatives from the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, Teagasc, and a growing agri-tech sector. Policy priorities around climate-smart farming and consumer demand for traceability also play a role. Importantly, most farms are export-oriented or supply supermarket chains rather than local markets, which creates strong productivity pressures and incentivises the use of digital tools to remain competitive. However, significant challenges persist. The farm structure is highly fragmented, with about 63% of holdings classified as small or very small, which limits scalability. Poor rural broadband remains an issue in some remote regions, although widespread mobile data packages can partly offset this for basic connectivity. Adoption of advanced digital tools is further hindered by high upfront costs and concerns about data privacy and ownership. Limited digital literacy among older farmers,

uneven access to advisory and training services, and the lack of tailored solutions for Ireland's diverse farm types also constrain wider uptake. Notably, some interviewees argued that progress in agricultural digitalisation has occurred largely in spite of CAP rather than because of it, highlighting a perceived disconnect between EU-level support and national-level modernisation efforts.

France is an advanced performer in agricultural digitalisation, largely due to its strong digital readiness, a relatively low share of small and very small farms (28%), and one of the highest ratios of younger to older farm managers (0.22). The push for digitalisation in the country is driven by the urgent need to combine economic and environmental performances, spurred by climate change and the demand for sustainable food systems. Digital technologies offer potential solutions for the optimisation of resources, boosting efficiency, improving animal welfare, and real-time environmental monitoring. A shrinking and aging agricultural workforce, combined with consumer demand for greater transparency, also fuels the adoption of these tools. Strong government support through national or regional recovery plans (e.g., France 2030, Plan de Relance), and a burgeoning agri-tech ecosystem with numerous startups, further accelerate this transformation by fostering innovation and investment. Despite these drivers, important barriers hinder widespread adoption. High initial costs and an unclear return on investment deter many farmers, especially smaller ones. Poor rural connectivity in some regions limits the effectiveness of data-dependent technologies, while a lack of digital literacy and training among an aging farming population presents a steep adoption curve. Concerns over data privacy and ownership also create farmer distrust, compounded by a fragmented agri-tech market that hinders interoperability. Lastly, the diverse nature of French agriculture means that generic digital tools often fail to meet specific farm needs, making broad adoption challenging.

In **Belgium**, the Flanders region has become a European testbed for smart farming. Sensor-equipped greenhouses, AI-powered yield forecasting, and agricultural robotics labs are turning the northern plains into a living lab for data-intensive agriculture. This leadership rests on the EU's second-highest business-sector R&D intensity, strong university-industry ties and a surge of ICT-related patents in 2024, plus a business sector in which around 84% of SMEs already meet at least the EU's basic digital-intensity standard. Flanders alone allocates one of Europe's highest shares of business R&D to ICT and operates the DjustConnect agri-food data space, with over 3,000 registered farmers and horticulturists. A favourable farm structure (only 21% of small and very small farms) and high value-added agri-food production further accelerate adoption. A nationwide network of start-up accelerators and European Digital Innovation Hubs further feeds an agri-tech and deep-tech ecosystem, even as DESI connectivity scores (though historically low) are now catching up rapidly. However, residual rural-urban connectivity gaps, skills deficits among smaller producers, and the tension between financing frontier innovations and maintaining legacy systems continue to demand policy attention. Fibre to the premises (FTTP) currently reaches only about a quarter of households nationally, and mid-band 5G coverage remains uneven, largely due to delays in rural Wallonia, where fibre rollout lagged and strict radiation limits remained in place until 2024. As Flanders accelerates FTTP and 5G densification and Wallonia begins to catch up, Belgium's physical network metrics are expected to better reflect its already world-class digital agriculture capabilities.

Spain's agricultural digitalisation is driven by strong overall digital readiness, including high broadband coverage and increasing access to precision agriculture technologies. Government initiatives – such as the Digitalisation Strategy for the Agri-food and Forestry Sector and Rural Areas and the Strategic Projects for the Recovery and Economic Transformation (PERTE) of both the agri-food sector and the water cycle, funded by NextGenerationEU – actively support this transformation by promoting digital innovation, providing subsidies for precision equipment, and working to reduce the rural-urban digital divide. The push for more sustainable, water-efficient farming, particularly in drought-prone regions, is also accelerating the adoption of smart irrigation, remote sensing, and data-driven crop management. In parallel, the sector is responding to the need to improve competitiveness, productivity, and environmental performance in one of the EU's leading agricultural economies, while addressing structural challenges such as rural labour shortages and tightening environmental regulations. However, Spain faces significant structural and implementation challenges that limit the widespread adoption of digital technologies. Over 70% of farms are classified as small or very small, restricting economies of scale and making it harder to justify digital investments. Inconsistent rural broadband connectivity, high upfront costs for advanced technologies, and concerns around data privacy and ownership further hinder uptake. The digital skills gap, particularly among older farmers, combined with uneven access to training and advisory services, adds to the difficulty. These issues are compounded by a very low ratio of younger to older farm managers (0.06), one of the lowest in the EU, which signals a slow generational renewal and limits the sector's capacity to absorb and

implement digital innovations. Additionally, the fragmented agri-tech market and gaps in interoperability between solutions create barriers to integration, especially across Spain's diverse regional and farm structures.

In **Germany**, agricultural digitalisation is driven by a strong industrial base, robust research institutions, specific skill training and well-developed digital infrastructure in many rural areas. The country benefits from a favourable farm size structure, with a majority of farms (61%) being medium to large in scale, which facilitates investment in advanced technologies. Farmers are motivated by the need to enhance efficiency, sustainability, and animal welfare, while addressing labour shortages and optimising resource use, particularly in fertiliser and pesticide application. Strong government support, including substantial R&D funding and initiatives like the "digital trial fields" launched by the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) in 2019, reinforces this momentum. Germany's global leadership in agricultural machinery and equipment strengthens its position as a key player in agricultural digital innovation. Despite strong structural advantages, Germany faces persistent barriers to scaling agricultural digitalisation. Adoption is uneven, especially among smaller farms that lack financial resources, digital skills, and adequate advisory support. Connectivity gaps in remote rural regions, along with fragmented agri-tech markets and poor system interoperability, further limit progress. The country's complex federal structure adds another layer of difficulty due to the fragmentation of responsibilities and inconsistent regional implementation. Concerns about data privacy, unclear governance, the use of data by government, and excessive bureaucracy (such as lengthy and complex approval processes) undermine trust and slow down the deployment of digital technologies. Local resistance to infrastructure development, often driven by NIMBY (Not In My Back Yard) attitudes, exacerbates these bureaucratic delays, particularly for projects like mobile towers or drone operations that require public approval.

Estonia's agricultural digitalisation is primarily driven by its strong digital infrastructure and a national commitment to e-governance, exemplified by systems like X-Road and widespread e-ID usage, which enable seamless data exchange between public and private sectors. This digital-first policy environment, supported by a well-developed ICT ecosystem and widespread internet access, alongside a commitment to developing network connectivity across the whole of Estonia, allows farmers to benefit from streamlined administrative procedures and advanced digital farm management tools. Highly digitised livestock performance recording systems and resource-optimisation technologies are increasingly used to enhance efficiency, reduce paperwork, and improve overall farm operations. The push for sustainability, improved resource use, and the need to attract a new generation into farming further strengthen this momentum. Estonia also shows high agriculture-specific momentum (the second highest CAP NSP target indicator values among CODECS countries), reflecting strong policy commitment to digitalisation, sustainability, and data-driven farm management. However, Estonia faces significant structural challenges, particularly a very high share of small farms (around 72%) that limits economies of scale and makes it harder to justify investment in advanced technologies. Limited technical capacity among some farmers, concerns over costs, and a lack of tailored solutions for small-scale operations further constrain uptake. In addition, very recent geopolitical developments are also constraining digital and aerial tools: intermittent internet jamming near the eastern border and new restrictions on drone operations in eastern Estonia, together with periodic airspace closures during military exercises, limit farmers' and researchers' drone use, especially when poor weather already narrows flight windows.

Agricultural digitalisation in **Scotland** is driven by targeted public investment in rural connectivity, national strategies promoting sustainable land management, and growing attention to climate resilience. Programmes such as the Scottish Rural Development Programme (SRDP), Future Farming Investment Scheme (FFIS) and the Knowledge Transfer and Innovation Fund (KTIF), and the Climate Change Plan support the use of precision technologies, data-driven decision-making, and smart machinery to enhance efficiency and environmental performance. Scotland's farm structure is generally less fragmented and more commercially scaled than many EU counterparts, which is favourable for digital adoption. Scotland's farm structure is dominated by medium to large-scale commercial farms, particularly in arable regions, while smaller holdings (mainly crofts) are concentrated in the Highlands and Islands. The structure of land ownership is characterised by a high degree of concentration, where a limited number of extensive estates account for most rural land. The country has made notable advances in agricultural data management, with the Scottish Agricultural Organisation Society (SAOS) spearheading a cooperative-based approach to data sharing through platforms like ScotEID, ensuring farmers retain ownership of their data while enabling real-time insights to improve traceability, disease control, and climate monitoring across supply chains. However, significant regional diversity and land concentration present challenges for uniform digital adoption across Scotland. Poor internet connectivity, particularly in remote and

island areas, remains a significant barrier for the implementation of data-intensive technologies and real-time monitoring systems. Smaller farms often struggle with high upfront investment costs, uncertainty around return on investment, and compatibility issues with existing systems. Limited digital skills, uneven access to advisory support, and a lack of standardisation in data-sharing frameworks present additional challenges and affect trust. Scotland's diverse agricultural landscape (from high-tech arable farms to remote crofts) highlights the need for tailored digitalisation approaches that reflect distinct operational realities.

Ireland:

- Strong digital readiness, well-educated farming population, growing agri-tech sector, demand for traceability and sustainability, and national initiatives promoting climate-smart farming and digital innovation.
- Productivity pressures drive adoption, as most farms are export-oriented or supply supermarkets rather than local markets.
- Apps and platforms now cover a wide spectrum of agri-food dimensions, including farm inputs, carbon budgets, veterinary care, traceability, and export competitiveness.
- Challenges include a fragmented farm structure (about 63% of holdings are classified as small or very small); patchy connectivity; high costs; data-related concerns; low digital skills among older farmers; and uneven access to training, advisory support, and funding for digital tools and services.

France:

- Strong digital readiness, support of national recovery plans, strong early-stage agricultural education and apprenticeships system, and an expanding agri-tech startup ecosystem.
- Favourable farm structure (only 28% of holdings classified as small or very small) facilitates investment in digital tools.
- Adoption driven by climate pressure, sustainability goals, labour shortages, and growing consumer demand for transparency and traceability.
- Challenges include high costs, limited connectivity in some rural areas, digital skills gaps, data privacy concerns, and

Belgium:

- Leadership driven by strong momentum in Flanders, where high policy support and active farmer engagement accelerate digital adoption.
- Favourable farm structure, with only 21% of small and very small holdings, supports scalable deployment of digital technologies.
- Strong agri-food innovation system built on sustained R&D investment, sensor-based field applications, living labs, and integrated data platforms like DJustConnect.
- Challenges include addressing regional differences (Flanders vs Wallonia) and rural connectivity gaps, coordinating across governance levels, and expanding digital uptake among smaller farms.

Spain:

- Stands out in connectivity, with significant efforts directed towards rural broadband access. Significant investments in skills training for both people and businesses.
- Adoption encouraged by the need to stay competitive as one of the EU's leading agricultural producers.
- Momentum supported by sustainability goals, smart irrigation, market demands in intensive production, and data-driven farming solutions in response to drought, labour shortages, and environmental pressures.
- Challenges include a fragmented farm structure (over 70% of farms are small or very small), inconsistent rural broadband, high costs, digital skills gaps, and poor interoperability across a diverse farming landscape.

Germany:

- Strong industrial base, robust research institutions, and substantial government support through initiatives like BMEL's digital trial fields.
- Favourable farm structure, where 61% of farms are medium to large holdings (as measured by standard output), supports investment in advanced technologies and digital innovation.
- Momentum further influenced by factors such as evolving sustainability targets, labour shortages, and Germany's global leadership in agricultural machinery and precision farming solutions.
- Challenges include uneven adoption, rural connectivity gaps, fragmented digital systems, complex federal governance, and bureaucracy exacerbated by NIMBY resistance to infrastructure projects.

Estonia:

- Strong digital infrastructure, e-governance systems like X-Road, and a digital-first policy environment that supports seamless data exchange.
- High agriculture-specific momentum reflects strong policy commitment to sustainability, data-driven farm management, and attracting younger generations to farming.
- Challenges include a very high share of small and very small farms (around 72%), limited technical capacity, cost concerns, and a lack of tailored solutions for small-scale operations.

Scotland (UK; former EU Member State):

- Leadership driven by public investment, climate-focused strategies, and programmes like the SRDP and Climate Change Plan that promote precision farming and data-driven land management.
- Farm structure dominated by medium to large-scale commercial holdings, with less fragmentation than many EU Member States, supporting more scalable digital adoption.
- Scotland has made notable advances in agricultural data management, with SAOS enabling farmer-controlled data sharing through platforms like ScotEID to support traceability and climate action.
- Challenges include regional diversity, poor rural connectivity, high costs for smaller farms, limited digital skills, and a lack of standardised, trusted data-sharing frameworks.

6.2.3 Growing Performers: Building Momentum and Addressing Gaps

In CODECS' growing performer countries, digitalisation in agriculture is beginning to gain momentum, supported by pilot initiatives, targeted investments, and early policy alignment with digital transition goals, though systemic adoption remains uneven across regions and farm types. These countries demonstrate encouraging signs in specific areas (such as moderate digital readiness or innovation capacity) but face persistent limitations that prevent systemic progress. The challenges are varied and often country-specific, reflecting a patchwork of partial advances and structural bottlenecks. Some growing performer countries (e.g. Czechia and Italy) benefit from a relatively moderate farm size structure and digital readiness, offering a platform for future progress. Conversely, many continue to lag in agriculture-specific momentum (e.g. Italy), reflecting limited policy focus and a lack of pilot activity at the farm level. In some cases (e.g. Slovenia), good digital infrastructure is offset by highly fragmented farm structures, which constrain economies of scale and slow adoption unless supported by tailored solutions. Others (e.g. Slovakia) face the dual challenge of low digital readiness and a high prevalence of small farms, highlighting the need for foundational investments in broadband, advisory services, and skills development. Even where progress has been made in areas like e-government, this has not always translated into improved connectivity, capacity, or uptake within the agricultural sector. In some cases, weak governance frameworks, limited institutional coordination, and a lack of policy continuity hinder the scaling of digital solutions.

Agricultural digitalisation in **Czechia** is progressing gradually, supported by a moderate farm structure (61% of farms are small or very small) and basic digital readiness, including strong nationwide 5G coverage and steadily improving digital skills. Digitalisation features prominently on the government's agenda, with the creation of the Digital and Information Agency in 2023 to coordinate efforts across ministries. Farmers widely use digital tools for administrative tasks such as subsidy applications, reflecting high digital engagement with public services, although many view these requirements as burdensome and time-consuming. Structural gaps persist, particularly in the rollout of VHCN, the digital transformation of businesses, and weak agriculture-specific momentum, as reflected in low CAP NSP targets. As a result, advisory services remain underdeveloped, investment in farm-level innovation is modest, and coordination across stakeholders is limited, resulting in fragmented progress and limited scaling of successful initiatives. Broader challenges include a persistent bureaucratic culture that continues to slow progress, as digitalisation alone has not been sufficient to streamline processes. Efforts to promote open data and enhance interoperability are underway, but uneven integration across systems still constrains more effective and widespread adoption.

Slovenia is advancing steadily in agricultural digitalisation through strong policy frameworks such as the Digital Slovenia 2030 Strategy, proactive EU-aligned initiatives, and the establishment of a Ministry of Digital Transformation, which together reflect a clear national ambition to enhance competitiveness, productivity, and sustainability. Fixed broadband infrastructure is robust, with around 80% of households connected to VHCN or FTTP, placing the country slightly above the EU average. EU policies like the CAP and the European Green Deal

have played an important role in driving adoption, while cultural factors, such as Slovenians' inclination to compete, further support this momentum. Innovation clusters and initiatives such as the Digital Innovation Hub for Agriculture and Food (DIH AGRIFOOD) are fostering knowledge transfer, pilot projects in precision agriculture, AI-driven advisory systems, and digital twins. However, progress is slowed by structural barriers, including an extremely fragmented farm structure (87% of farms are small or very small, the second highest among CODECS countries) and limited incentives for small farmers, who often sell directly to local markets. Likewise, one of the lowest ratios of younger to older farm managers in the EU (0.07) indicates slow generational renewal, which constrains the sector's ability to adopt and apply digital innovations. Furthermore, high upfront investment costs, limited outreach of advisory services, and gaps in interoperability between digital solutions hinder broader adoption. Digital inclusion also remains a challenge, with less than 50% of the population possessing basic digital skills (an issue more linked to age than to location) which affects both the workforce and the ability to use public services. While internet use is improving, slow changes in digital competences and concerns over data privacy continue to limit uptake.

In **Italy**, agricultural digitalisation is supported by relatively good digital infrastructure, increasing broadband access nationwide, and a growing ecosystem of agri-tech startups (over 400 active startups in 2024, especially concentrated in northern regions like Lombardy and EmiliaRomagna). National initiatives such as the Transition Plan 4.0 and Transition Plan 5.0, which are heavily integrated into the country's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) are boosting funding for technology adoption, particularly in high-value sectors like viticulture and horticulture. Farmers are increasingly recognising the role of digital tools in improving efficiency, productivity, and environmental performance, particularly in response to evolving EU regulations linking funding to sustainability outcomes. However, structural and behavioural challenges continue to limit widespread adoption. With about 67% of small or very small farms, Italy's highly fragmented agricultural sector struggles to achieve economies of scale or justify costly investments. Agriculture-specific momentum is the lowest among CODECS countries, as reflected in Italy's CAP NSP targets, signalling weak policy focus and limited uptake at the farm level. Regional disparities in skills and infrastructure, particularly between northern and southern regions, compound these difficulties. Many older farmers are sceptical of labour-saving technologies, often valuing traditional practices and hard work, while slow generational turnover complicate support schemes intended for younger farmers. Even as the digitalisation of the farm registry becomes compulsory, producers face uncertainty about who collects the data, which software to use, and how data will be integrated. Practical barriers such as poor connectivity in some rural areas, high upfront costs, limited digital skills, and concerns about data use by authorities, data ownership and interoperability further hinder adoption. Importantly, lack of awareness about the benefits of digitalisation (rather than outright resistance) is often the main obstacle. Peer influence, demonstration activities, and communities of practice play a crucial role in breaking this inertia, highlighting the importance of localised support networks to complement national-level initiatives.

Czechia:

- Digitalisation is a government priority, with recent efforts to centralise coordination through the Digital and Information Agency and provide clear guidance.
- Gradual progress supported by moderate farm structure (61% of farms are small or very small), strong 5G coverage, and steady improvement of digital skills.
- High administrative digitalisation with mandatory online tools, though farmers often view them as burdensome and time-consuming.
- Challenges include weak agriculture-specific momentum, urban-rural connectivity gaps, underdeveloped advisory services, fragmented coordination, low trust in digitalisation, and persistent bureaucratic culture that slows adoption.

Slovenia:

- Steady progress supported by strong policy frameworks, EU-aligned strategies, and the creation of a Ministry of Digital Transformation, reflecting clear national ambition for digitalisation.
- EU policies like the CAP and Green Deal, along with a strong cultural drive to compete, have helped sustain momentum in digital adoption in the agricultural sector.
- Robust broadband infrastructure and active innovation ecosystems (e.g. DIH AGRIFOOD) fostering knowledge transfer and pilot projects in digital technologies for agriculture.
- Major structural challenges, including a highly fragmented farm structure (87% of small or very small farms, the second highest in CODECS) and low digital inclusion (basic skills lacking for more than half of the population).

Italy:

- Digitalisation driven by great progress in digital strong infrastructure and digital public services, over 400 agri-tech startups, and national programmes that support investments in digital transition.
- Farmers increasingly recognise the role that digital tools can play in the enhancement of productivity, efficiency, and compliance with evolving EU sustainability-linked funding requirements, but overall awareness of benefits remains low.
- Challenges include a fragmented farm structure (67% of farms are small or very small), and regional and generational divides. Policies and programs often follow rather than lead developments on the ground. Reactive approach undermines strategic coherence, making it harder to align efforts and scale effective solutions across the sector.
- Agriculture-specific momentum is the lowest among CODECS countries, as reflected in the country's CAP Strategic Plan targets, signalling weak policy focus and limited uptake at the farm level.

6.2.4 Early-Stage Performers: Structural Barriers and Opportunities

CODECS' early-stage performer countries face significant structural constraints, but also present opportunities to build momentum in agricultural digitalisation. Progress remains fragmented due to foundational barriers such as limited broadband coverage, underdeveloped institutions, unfavourable farm demographics structure, and a predominance of small, family-run farms oriented toward local markets. These challenges are in some cases compounded by weak governance, siloed and outdated legacy systems, a lack of long-term strategic planning, inefficient administrative procedures, and/or regulatory inconsistencies, all of which limit trust, coherence, and access to financing. An ageing farming population, low digital literacy, and slow generational renewal further constrain demand for technological modernisation, while private-sector engagement is sometimes held back by concerns over transparency and accountability. This group also includes CODECS' EU candidate countries (North Macedonia and Serbia), where these structural barriers are often intensified by political uncertainty, limited administrative capacity, and extended timelines for EU integration, all of which discourage long-term investment, planning and alignment with EU benchmarks. Despite these systemic barriers, signs of progress are emerging. Mobile-first advisory services, e-filing platforms, and pilot sensor deployments are gradually introducing farmers and institutions to digital workflows. Peer-to-peer learning is expanding, while EU-funded programmes such as EIP-AGRI Operational Groups and rural development measures are helping to build technical capacity and support local innovation. A small number of large, corporately owned farms are already deploying advanced technologies to improve efficiency and competitiveness, but overall digital uptake across the sector remains limited.

Latvia's agricultural digitalisation is progressing from a modest base, driven by national policy frameworks such as the "Digital Transformation Guidelines for 2021-2027" and growing recognition of the sector's potential to improve sustainability, productivity, and resilience. The country benefits from well-developed digital public services and a centralised governance model that supports coherent national strategies on digital skills and infrastructure. However, the rollout of 5G, FTTP, and VHCN remains below EU averages, with persistent regional disparities affecting rural connectivity. Latvia also has a low ratio of younger to older farm managers (0.09) and the most fragmented farm structure among CODECS countries, with 89% of farms classified as small or very small, thus limiting economies of scale and discouraging investment in digital technologies. Agriculture-specific momentum remains low, as reflected in CAP NSP targets, the third lowest in the CODECS group. While both policymakers and farmers increasingly view digitalisation as essential, adoption is constrained by underdeveloped advisory systems, limited innovation pilots, and challenges in translating strategy into practice.

Additional barriers include high upfront costs, low digital skill levels (among the lowest in the EU), and concerns about data privacy and interoperability. Despite clear policy intent and improving infrastructure, these systemic issues continue to hinder scalable and inclusive digital transformation in Latvia's agricultural sector.

In **Slovakia**, progress is slow, hindered by low digital readiness (the third lowest among CODECS countries) and a highly fragmented farm structure, with 77% of holdings classified as small or very small, and only around 9% of farms managing about 90% of the land and generating most of the country's agricultural production. While national strategies and policy commitments signal intent, limited follow-through, weak institutional coordination, and underdeveloped e-government services undermine implementation. Digital infrastructure and the uptake of broadband and 5G have improved, but overall network development in rural areas still lags, limiting the deployment of data-intensive technologies. Digital tools are rarely integrated into public services, and uptake remains low due to a shortage of farm-level pilots, insufficient advisory capacity, and a poorly functioning Agricultural Payments Agency with fragmented, often incompatible databases. Additional challenges include high upfront investment costs, persistent digital skills gaps, limited trust in digital tools (especially concerning data privacy), and the low quality of basic infrastructure in some rural areas, where even essentials like water supply may be lacking. Farmers are often discouraged by complex administrative processes, delayed funding disbursement, and procedures widely seen as burdensome and lacking transparency. Although short food chains are seen as promising, barriers to direct market access remain. Broader systemic issues (such as land access skewed in favour of large leaseholders, high staff turnover in the civil service, and a legacy of bureaucratic inefficiency) have further stalled momentum. While the EU is sometimes blamed for the decline of agriculture, interviewees agreed that these trends more accurately reflect long-standing domestic governance gaps. Despite these challenges, Slovakia has the second highest ratio of younger to older farm managers among CODECS countries, suggesting significant potential for digitalisation.

Agricultural digitalisation in **Poland** is gradually advancing, supported by national initiatives such as the Digital Competence Development Programme 2020-2030, the Digitalisation Strategy 2035, CAP NSP measures, and investments through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan. The country benefits from strong fixed internet connectivity (above the EU average) and growing interest in precision farming technologies, particularly among larger, commercial farms. Poland also has a well-established nationwide public advisory system, which plays a central role in supporting farmers with training and information services. However, widespread adoption is held back by persistent rural-urban digital divides, low digital literacy (particularly among older farmers), and limited uptake of advanced technologies by farmers. Smallholders, who account for 84% of all farms, often lack economies of scale, face high investment costs, and have limited access to advisory services and financial support. Many are subsistence farms serving local markets, where the incentives for digitalisation remain low, but efforts to promote short food supply chains are helping to introduce digital tools. While Poland has a strategy for agricultural development, implementation is constrained by institutional fragmentation, governance inefficiencies, and the sector's structural diversity. Additional key barriers include low trust in digital technologies and data privacy concerns. The establishment of a new departmental unit for digitalisation within the Ministry of Agriculture suggests a renewed political focus on this priority. However, this positive step is tempered by another recent reorganisation of the Ministry, which is generating concern among stakeholders. Furthermore, growing resistance from farmers (particularly regarding sustainability-linked CAP requirements) signals the critical need for more balanced and farmer-informed policy development. In addition, some interviewed experts argued that the current situation reflects a policy and funding bias toward large-scale, export-oriented industrial farming, coupled with a relative neglect of small and medium-sized holdings. Despite this, momentum is gradually building, supported by the highest ratio of younger to older farm managers among CODECS countries (an encouraging sign of potential for advancing agricultural digitalisation). The key challenge lies in converting strategic ambition into a coordinated, inclusive, and practical digital transition across all segments of the farming sector.

Hungary's digitalisation of the agricultural sector is guided by national strategies such as the Digital Agricultural Strategy adopted in 2019 and the broader National Digitalisation Strategy (2022-2030) adopted in 2022, both of which aim to establish a cohesive "digital vision" for the sector, including the planned development of a national agricultural data space. The country benefits from relatively good digital infrastructure and ongoing improvements in connectivity, but digitalisation of businesses remains limited, and a persistent divide between urban and rural areas continues to hinder equitable access. Despite adequate policy activity, Hungary's poor DESI standing and unfavourable farm size structure (around 85% of farms are small or very small) pose major barriers. Uptake of digital tools is concentrated among larger farms, while smaller holdings struggle with high investment costs,

limited digital skills, and low economies of scale. These structural constraints are compounded by a low ratio of younger to older farm managers, fragmented advisory systems, weak institutional coordination, low trust and cooperation among farmers, and broader governance vulnerabilities, including bureaucratic inefficiencies and limited administrative transparency. Programmes like the Digital Agriculture Support Program (launched in 2018 under the Digital Agricultural Strategy) provide financial and technical support, particularly for precision farming solutions, but their impact has so far remained modest due to insufficient outreach and implementation capacity.

Greece faces substantial structural and institutional barriers to agricultural digitalisation. It ranks lowest in digital readiness among CODECS countries, has the lowest ratio of younger to older farm managers (0.05), and a highly fragmented farm structure (86% of holdings are classified as small or very small) limiting both economies of scale and the financial capacity to invest in digital technologies. Rural connectivity gaps persist, and digital literacy remains low, particularly among older farmers. Additional challenges include limited trust in digital technologies, concerns over data privacy, fragmented advisory services, and weak policy execution, as strategic plans often lack operational clarity and follow-through. While the Ministry of Digital Governance provides a formal institutional anchor, interviewees suggest that its presence alone has not been sufficient to drive coordinated action across the agricultural sector. Cultural and institutional legacies, such as reluctance among farmers to cooperate and complex administrative traditions, further constrain uptake. Despite these constraints, momentum is growing. Greece has integrated its smart farming ambitions into its broader Digital Transformation Bible 2020-2025, led by the Ministry of Digital Governance, and operationalised them through its CAP NSP, which promotes innovation, precision agriculture, and sustainability. Notably, Greece has set the second most ambitious target among CODECS countries for the number of farms receiving support for digital agricultural technologies under the CAP, signalling strong policy intent to accelerate uptake. These frameworks, supported by EU funding under the CAP and European Green Deal, aim to modernise the sector and improve productivity, traceability, and environmental performance. Precision farming and smart technologies are gaining traction, particularly in better-organised sectors like olive oil, rice, and viticulture, and among younger farmers and cooperatives. While broad uptake remains limited, the expansion of fibre infrastructure and increasing digitalisation among SMEs suggest that targeted support, improved AKIS coordination, and strengthened cooperative models could help unlock Greece's agricultural digital potential.

Agricultural digitalisation in **North Macedonia** is advancing slowly but steadily, supported by EU-aligned strategies such as the National Strategy for Agriculture and Rural Development 2021-2027, the Smart Specialisation Strategy (2023), and EU funding from instruments like Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance in Rural Development (IPARD) and Horizon 2020/Horizon Europe. These frameworks are contributing to enhance competitiveness, sustainability, and rural development while attracting and retaining young farmers. Mobile broadband coverage is high, particularly in urban areas, and marking of parcels and digital subsidy systems have been introduced. However, adoption of digital tools on farms remains limited. The sector is dominated by highly fragmented, family-run farms (an estimated two-thirds of farms today have less than one hectare), making economies of scale and modernisation difficult (Economic Chamber of North Macedonia, 2025). Many plots are irregular and scattered, and there is no clear trend toward consolidation. Digital literacy is low, especially among older farmers, who still rely heavily on in-person support despite being required to file documents online. Institutional and structural barriers continue to hinder uptake. While a new law on advisory services has established a legal basis for improved support, extension systems remain underdeveloped, data platforms lack interoperability, and policy implementation is fragmented. The country's varied topography and distinct regional characteristics complicate national planning and highlight the need for tailored region-specific approaches. Larger enterprises and a handful of cooperatives (encouraged by a new Cooperatives Law) are showing early signs of success, while trust in government is relatively stable, although farmers often expect direct solutions rather than active engagement. North Macedonia's EU candidate status has helped frame reforms and mobilise resources, but long delays in accession have generated scepticism in parts of society. Despite these challenges, the country's absorptive capacity is improving, and early pilots such as the CODECS Remote Agricultural Monitoring and Advisory System (RAMAS) Living Lab are helping to demonstrate the value of smart technologies.

Serbia is making gradual progress in the digitalisation of its agricultural sector. At the policy level, it has committed to national initiatives including its Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence for the period 2020-2025 and the Competitive Agriculture Project (SCAP). With EU and international backing (particularly through instruments like IPARD), Serbia is seeking alignment with EU accession requirements and investing in

productivity, competitiveness, and value-added innovation, including open-data platforms and digital advisory tools. Technologically, the country benefits from widespread mobile broadband and increasing investments in digital infrastructure. However, major structural and institutional barriers remain. Fixed broadband coverage is low (around 18% of households), and rural areas rely heavily on mobile networks, constraining data-intensive applications. Many farmers lack the digital literacy needed to adopt new tools and remain sceptical about data privacy and system complexity. The sector is overwhelmingly composed of family farms (approximately 99.6% of all holdings, occupying about 82% of total agricultural land), most of which are small and fragmented, limiting economies of scale and investment capacity (Miljatović et al., 2025). Digitalisation-related gaps in advisory services, slow disbursement of available funding, and bureaucratic inefficiencies (including delays in e-government implementation and opaque procurement) further hinder uptake. While Serbia's EU candidate status provides strategic direction and financial support, gaps in institutional capacity and governance continue to undermine the full use of EU funds. Nonetheless, initiatives such as SCAP and pilot living labs are helping to familiarise farmers and institutions with digital tools. These early efforts, combined with growing SME digitalisation and renewed policy momentum, suggest an emerging foundation for broader transformation of the agricultural sector in the country.

Latvia:

- Progress driven by national digital strategies and recognition of agriculture's role in enhancing sustainability, productivity, and resilience.
- Strong digital public services and centralised governance enable coherent policy direction, but rural connectivity gaps persist due to slow implementation of 5G, FTTP and VHCN.
- Agriculture-specific momentum remains low, as indicated by the country's CAP Strategic Plan targets (the third lowest in CODECS), suggesting that there is significant room for improvement in both policy push and farmer engagement with digital tools.
- Major structural challenges, including an extremely fragmented farm structure (89% of small or very small farms, the highest in CODECS) and low human capital, with nearly 55% of the population lacking basic digital skills.

Slovakia:

- Policy intent is visible through national strategies and commitments, but limited follow-through, weak institutional coordination, and underdeveloped e-government services undermine implementation.
- Digitalisation progress is slowed down by low digital readiness, fragmented farm structure (77% of small or very small farms), and significant gaps in rural infrastructure.
- Uptake is hindered by high investment costs, digital skills gaps, low trust in digital tools, and administrative procedures that are often seen as cumbersome and unclear.
- Systemic governance issues (including problems with land access, high civil service turnover, and persistent bureaucracy) further weaken delivery and farmer engagement.

Poland:

- Rapid digitalisation progress, particularly accelerated by COVID-19. Digitalisation is a priority, as demonstrated by strong national strategies and EU-aligned programmes, along with above-average fixed internet connectivity and growing interest in precision farming.
- A nationwide public advisory system provides a key support mechanism, offering training, information, and a nationwide network for knowledge transfer and modernisation of the agricultural sector.
- Digital adoption is slowed down by persistent rural-urban divides, low digital literacy (particularly among older farmers), and fragmented farm structure (84% of holdings are small or very small).
- Efforts to align with EU digitalisation standards are underway, but disparities in skills and access remain. Initiatives promoting short food supply chains are helping to introduce digital tools among smaller farms.

Hungary:

- Adequate policy activity, including the Digital Agricultural Strategy (2019) and the National Digitalisation Strategy (2022–2030), aiming to build a unified digital vision and agricultural data space.
- Strong digital infrastructure, but rural-urban divides and limited digitalisation of businesses continue to hinder inclusive progress.
- Digital adoption is largely concentrated among larger farms, while smaller farms (85% of total holdings) face major barriers such as high costs, low skills, and limited economies of scale.
- Progress is further slowed down by fragmented advisory systems, weak coordination, low farmer trust, and governance inefficiencies, which limit the reach and impact of support programmes.

Greece:

- Digitalisation progress accelerated by COVID-19, with significant improvements in public services. Growing momentum despite considerable constraints.
- Major structural and institutional barriers to digitalisation, including the lowest digital readiness in CODECS, highly fragmented farm structures (86% small or very small), low digital literacy, and persistent rural connectivity gaps.
- Farmers' trust in digital technologies is limited, and uptake is further constrained by fragmented advisory services, weak policy execution, and cultural legacies such as complex administrative processes.
- Despite existing challenges, growing uptake in organised sectors like olive oil and viticulture, and among younger farmers and cooperatives, supported by EU funding, expanding fibre infrastructure, and rising SME digitalisation. The second most ambitious CAP NSP target in CODECS for farm-level digital support.

North Macedonia (EU candidate country):

- Agricultural digitalisation progressing slowly, driven by EU-aligned strategies, policy efforts aimed at boosting competitiveness, sustainability, and youth retention in rural areas. Key support from EU funding instruments like IPARD and Horizon 2020/Horizon Europe.
- Improving digital infrastructure, with high mobile broadband coverage and digitised subsidy systems, but adoption remains low due to underdeveloped advisory services, non-interoperable data platforms, and fragmented implementation.
- Structural constraints dominate the agricultural sector, with low digital literacy (especially among older farmers), two-thirds of farms smaller than one hectare in size, fragmented landholdings, and no clear trend toward consolidation.
- Regional disparities and delayed EU accession timelines continue to limit trust and momentum.

Serbia (EU candidate country):

- Gradual progress supported by national strategies aiming to align with EU accession requirements and promote competitiveness in the agricultural sector. Pilot initiatives and rising SME digitalisation signal potential for future scaling.
- Widespread mobile broadband and increasing infrastructure investment, but fixed broadband access remains low (around 18% of households), limiting the deployment of data-intensive technologies in rural areas.
- Agricultural sector dominated by small, fragmented family farms (99.6% of holdings), which face barriers such as limited digital skills, low trust in digital systems, and high costs of adoption.
- Uptake further constrained by fragmented advisory services, slow disbursement of funds, and governance weaknesses.

6.3 Digitalisation in the CAP National Strategic Plans

Interviewees generally view the CAP as a **powerful yet often controversial engine for digital change** across EU's farms. They highlighted that recent changes have significantly altered the digitalisation landscape compared to the previous programming period, introducing new layers of complexity and administrative demand. For many producers, the obligation to meet digital compliance requirements has triggered the adoption of specialised software for the first time. In this sense, the CAP acts as a catalyst since the risk of losing payments has proven more compelling than years of voluntary advice or demonstration efforts. Yet interviewees also underline that these changes have come at a cost. The increase in requirements and bureaucratic procedures has fuelled

frustration across the sector and, in several cases, sparked protests, particularly where farmers feel the pace and pressure of change have exceeded their capacity to adapt.

The present 2023-2027 programming period has intensified that dynamic. While earlier reforms focused primarily on income support, the current CAP makes eligibility explicitly conditional on meeting three interconnected objectives: climate action, environmental stewardship, and digital record-keeping. However, not all farmers welcome the new conditions. Several interviewees noted that farmers are feeling “a lot of pressure”, and some expressed concern that the CAP’s rapid green shift may have gone “too far, too fast”. In addition, stakeholders from Italy expressed concerns about the complexity of their country’s digital strategy, noting its emphasis on investment interventions over knowledge-based approaches, as well as a higher focus on individual investments than on collaborative investments. Scepticism was also expressed by stakeholders in Greece and Slovakia regarding the extent to which these digital strategies are effectively being implemented.

“On paper, everything looks great. There are strategies in place. But the real question is: will they actually be implemented?”

Despite these concerns, there are clear signs that farmers across the EU are actively engaging with the digital transition when appropriate incentives and support structures are in place. Several Member States have integrated precision farming into their CAP NSPs, signalling a shift toward more data-driven and sustainability-oriented approaches. In Belgium (Flanders), for example, a dedicated eco-scheme specifically targeting precision farming for plant production has been introduced, offering ongoing support to farmers and replacing the one-off payments previously funded under CAP Pillar II. To qualify, farms must meet competitiveness and sustainability criteria, including standards related to climate, environmental impact, and animal welfare. The Netherlands offers another illustrative case, where, according to an interviewee, eco-scheme payments are directly linked to digital data submissions. A grower who uploads GPS tagged files documenting fertiliser application can earn an additional 250 euro per hectare, but the bonus disappears without the data trail. These examples underscore a broader trend: **data are becoming the currency that unlocks higher payments.**

In parallel, farmers across the EU are increasingly using CAP funds for precision farming technologies. For instance, the *Agriculture 4.0* initiative in Poland, launched in autumn 2023, saw a substantial response, with 150 million zlotys (approximately 35.3 million euros) allocated within the first eight hours primarily for purchasing tractors equipped with satellite feeds. A similar programme in Italy (finished in late 2023) was partly funded by the CAP and enabled a notable proportion of farmers to acquire internet-connected farm machinery, resulting in approximately 8-10% of the Italian agricultural surface being digitalised.

However, practical challenges continue to hinder effective implementation. In some Member States, lengthy approval and disbursement procedures significantly reduce the impact of digital investment support. In Serbia, for instance, farmers may wait up to a year for funding approval, while in Slovakia, delays can extend to up to two years before payments are received. Administrative inefficiencies (such as fragmented or incompatible databases within the agricultural payments agency, overly complex procedures, and opaque processing practices) further discourage participation. As a result, a portion of available EU funds sometimes remains unused. In fast-moving areas like digital technology, such delays not only reduce interest but also risk making investments obsolete by the time funding is delivered. Moreover, long disbursement timelines can strain farm cash flows, making it harder for smaller holdings to bridge the financial gap between purchase and reimbursement.

At the same time, farmers are increasingly seeking guidance on suitable technologies, applications and investment costs, as many lack the time or digital literacy to independently evaluate options. In Italy, for example, the Rural Development Programmes (RDPs) offer free digitalisation courses, yet participation remains low, indicating a need for more accessible formats and support mechanisms better tailored to farmers’ needs and expectations.

As for the **agricultural advisory services**, their structure varies widely across the EU, reflecting different national policy choices and historical developments. In the Netherlands, advisory services were largely privatised in the late 1980s and early 1990s, in a move that some experts now view as a strategic mistake, arguing that the government should retain a coordinating role to steer long-term innovation and public-interest outcomes. According to Dutch interviewees, full privatisation has made coordination more difficult, although this gap has been partially filled by a strong culture of networking and the proactive role of the CAP Network in convening a

broad range of stakeholders. In contrast, Poland has maintained a publicly coordinated system, with advisory services overseen by the Centre for Agricultural Advisory Services (CAAS) and delivered through a network of regional Agricultural Advisory Centres covering the entire country. This model is seen as a strength, offering broad territorial coverage and direct engagement with farmers and rural communities. Regardless of structure, effective coordination is essential to ensure that public efforts complement rather than compete with private services, and that existing gaps (especially in digital expertise) are strategically addressed.

Most interviewees highlighted the need to enhance advisory services for digitalisation, which are often fragmented and lack in-depth knowledge. The first step involves upskilling and reskilling both public and private farm advisors in digitalisation. Access to independent advisory services is also crucial, since many farmers are limited to private advice from machinery and equipment providers. At the same time, several interviewees noted that many farmers prefer advisors connected to companies or research institutions because their knowledge is more up to date and they have access to wider networks. As a result, so called independent services will likely not always be fully independent. Achieving a diverse, high quality and sufficiently independent advisory ecosystem requires interoperability of data, robust data governance frameworks, and data literacy among advisors and farmers. Furthermore, public administration should ensure a diverse portfolio of advisors and topics. At present, however, advisory services tend to focus primarily on assisting farmers with administrative processes (such as subsidy applications) while offering limited guidance on technology choices, digital tools, or data-driven decision-making.

“How to transform agricultural advising into AKIS approach as opposed to these agricultural advisory centres trying to have the answer to every problem?”

Digitalisation plays a growing role not only in the objectives of the CAP but also in its **administrative and procedural aspects**, such as funding applications and monitoring systems. While countries like Latvia have required online **CAP funding applications** since 2016, the digitalisation of these processes is still ongoing in others, such as Italy and Slovakia. Transitioning to digital procedures, such as submitting funding applications or reporting crop types for specific plots, has helped reduce administrative errors and streamline payment processes. In Latvia, for example, digitalisation has reduced errors in CAP payment processing by over 95%. However, limited digital skills among public administration staff remain a barrier to progress in several CODECS countries. At the same time, the complexity of CAP procedures continues to frustrate farmers, many of whom are calling for simplification. Tools like the Farm Sustainability Tool (FaST), though well-intentioned, are often described as difficult and time consuming. Moreover, access to CAP funds is uneven. In Italy, only a small share of farms applies due to the sector’s fragmented structure, while in Slovakia, many farmers are reportedly reluctant to apply due to weaknesses in their national administrative system. Even in countries where CAP funding applications are already processed digitally (such as Belgium, Czechia, Germany, Latvia, Netherlands, and Spain) challenges persist in terms of data integration, interoperability, and the underutilisation of collected data.

“Digitalisation is time-consuming, but sometimes public authorities don’t even use all the data that has been collected.”

Monitoring and inspections are becoming increasingly digitised, even in countries where CAP payments have not yet transitioned to digital formats. The current CAP reform has added further complexity by requiring all Member States to develop new algorithms and adopt additional monitoring tools, such as geotagged photographs and electronic field books. These digital monitoring initiatives have only recently been introduced and often operate in the background, meaning many farmers are unaware that such changes are taking place. Reactions to these changes vary across Member States. In Germany, some farmers express concern that increased data usage could lead to tighter control, stronger economic surveillance, and potentially reduced payments. By contrast, Dutch farmers generally view digital monitoring as an opportunity to demonstrate good practices more easily and reduce administrative burdens, particularly when technologies such as GPS systems allow data to be uploaded directly into CAP paying agency systems, accelerating payment processing. According to interviewees, Greek farmers tend not to see data collection as a major issue.

Estonia illustrates what full-scale digital control can look like in practice. With just 1.3 million inhabitants, the country uses satellite imagery to verify 100% of declared surfaces, has digitised all field notebooks, and requires that approximately 60% of land enrolled in eco-schemes be registered online. This kind of system demonstrates how digital tools can streamline administration and bring new forms of sustainability verification into the payment

process. Remote sensing and online portals can reduce the time between application and payment and even allow administrations to support environmental practices (such as the maintenance of species-rich grasslands) that would be difficult to verify through traditional audits. In several Member States, farmers report that digital filing speeds up payment. However, in other contexts, mandatory remote checks are perceived as intrusive, prompting ministries to reassure producers that the primary goal is to simplify procedures, not to increase surveillance. The Netherlands exemplifies this conciliatory approach by promoting digital tools as aids to reduce paperwork, rather than as mechanisms for control.

Despite existing frictions, programs continue to evolve. Estonia has launched a five-year initiative to “give back services” to farmers, including nutrient balance calculators that transform compliance data into actionable management advice. In many Member States, rural development funds (often overshadowed by the headline eco-schemes) act as venture capital for broadband roll outs, test beds and pilot apps that would otherwise struggle to attract private finance. Taken together, these initiatives show that the CAP does more than set conditions; it also funds the infrastructure without which digital ambition would remain hypothetical. Furthermore, the general view among the interviewees was that the CAP has provided long-term stability for the sector, which is an essential condition to enable investment in modernisation, even among smaller holdings. Belgium’s experience illustrates how this sense of security can outweigh scepticism rooted in the legacy of past overproduction.

One important concern raised in the interviews is that European competition law (which was introduced long before sustainability entered the political vocabulary) still treats many forms of farmer cooperation with suspicion. As a result, digital platforms that enable data sharing for collective sustainability benefits often fall into a legal grey area. Neither national nor EU authorities can clearly determine what is allowed, producing “vagueness in the institutional setting” and slowing the adoption of tools that rely on shared datasets.

Overall, most interviewees view the CAP as both a driver and an enabler of the EU’s transition toward digital farming. Its financial incentives encourage even traditionally minded farmers to experiment with digital tools, while its environmental objectives help translate those first steps into more advanced, data-driven practices. However, the same policy framework can feel burdensome or even punitive in contexts where infrastructure is lacking, digital skills are limited, or coordination between institutions is weak. Therefore, the extent to which the CAP accelerates or constrains digitalisation depends less on its overarching goals set in Brussels and more on the local conditions in which it is implemented.

“Some people blame the CAP for the decline of agriculture in our country, but in reality, it has only revealed problems that were already there.”

Looking ahead, interviewees caution that digital agriculture is evolving faster than any regulation can predict. They urge policymakers to “keep an open mind” in future CAP programming periods because the technological landscape ten years from now may look entirely different from today’s assumptions. This uncertainty complicates the design of public programmes: too much rigidity risks locking systems into outdated tools, too much flexibility can undermine accountability, and frequent changes may erode trust among stakeholders. A pragmatic middle ground would involve stronger, more agile collaboration between governments, farmers, and technology developers, allowing regulatory frameworks to adapt in real time to emerging developments. If future reforms can maintain the financial momentum while reducing complexity, clarifying competition for collective data initiatives, and consistently turning compliance information into farmer-oriented services, the CAP will remain a central (if sometimes contested) pillar of the EU’s digital agricultural future.

Lastly, assessing the impact of CAP interventions that support digitalisation remains a challenge. As discussed in Section 5.2, digitalisation efforts in agriculture are often fragmented across multiple policy instruments. At present, we have only a view of planned actions set out by governments, while comparable data on actual performance are not yet available. These initiatives are not always clearly defined as CAP-related and are frequently supported by other funding sources such as DEP, CEF, RRF, ERDF, Horizon Europe, or private investment. This fragmentation makes it difficult to consistently track progress and evaluate impact across Member States.

6.4 Other Policy Areas Influencing Digitalisation in Agriculture

Understanding the broader policy landscape is essential to grasp how digitalisation in agriculture is shaped by policies beyond the agricultural sector. In this regard, interviewees noted that the adoption of digital technologies by farmers is influenced by policy decisions at multiple levels, from regional to EU, and across key areas such as education, infrastructure, and innovation.

Intersecting policies and programmes are a key driver of agricultural digitalisation. In Slovenia, for example, the “Act on Emergency Measures for Mitigating the Consequences of Floods and Landslides” facilitated the deployment of mobile-based stations to improve connectivity in remote areas. In addition, Slovenia is pursuing a data-openness and transparency initiative that would allow users to see who accesses their data, although it faces opposition from some ministries. Other examples include the Digital Success Programme in Hungary, which has improved broadband and e-governance, enhancing rural connectivity. Similarly, education reforms have introduced digital skills into vocational training, while the national AI Strategy encourages innovation in areas like precision agriculture and data analytics. In Estonia, national digital infrastructure initiatives, such as the EstWin broadband programme and the X-Road data exchange platform, have provided the foundation for widespread adoption of digital tools in agriculture, including e-ID-based farm reporting and remote monitoring.

In France, a strong and collaborative ecosystem has been established to advance agricultural digitalisation through initiatives that link public research institutes, universities, farmer collectives, and agri-tech startups. This integrated approach fosters knowledge-sharing and accelerates innovation uptake, while ensuring that CAP Strategic Plan implementation aligns with national priorities in agroecology and sustainability. On the other hand, Dutch policy frameworks integrate digitalisation into rural development via CAP Pillar II programmes like the rural development plan POP3, complemented by EU-funded EIP-AGRI Operational Groups, smart farming accelerators, and the Farm of the Future test facility in Lelystad, demonstrating circular and precision agriculture solutions.

In Czechia, agricultural high schools have been providing IT training for over two decades, significantly enhancing digital literacy among young people entering the farming sector. This early exposure to digital tools has contributed to a gradual cultural shift, making younger farmers more receptive to adopting smart farming technologies and data-driven decision-making. In Germany, the renowned dual education system (run jointly by federal and state education ministries with industry associations) combines classroom learning with practical training and is now integrating digital skills into agricultural apprenticeships (*Landwirt/in*) to prepare the next generation of farmers for a digitised sector, data driven decision making, and more sustainable production. Likewise, in Serbia, the State Institution of Application of Science in Agriculture offers train-the-trainer programmes focused on digitalisation, equipping advisors with the knowledge and skills needed to guide farmers in using digital tools. These programmes play a critical role in cascading knowledge to the farm level, particularly in rural areas where access to up-to-date information and technical support is limited.

In Spain, the digitalisation of agriculture is significantly influenced by a variety of non-agricultural policies and programmes. These include national initiatives like the Programme for the Universalisation of Digital Infrastructures for Cohesion (UNICO), which provides crucial digital infrastructure to rural areas. Regional efforts, such as Andalucía’s Smart Irrigation Programme (a water security and environmental policy aimed at farmers), further promote the adoption of digital tools for environmental and resource management. Additionally, national strategies for AI and innovation, including the National Artificial Intelligence Strategy (ENIA) or the HispanIA 2040 initiative, along with mandatory online platforms for EU subsidy applications, require farmers to engage with digital tools. Taken together, these instruments set incentives and build capabilities for adoption beyond the agricultural policy sphere and highlight the need for policy coherence across sectors and levels of governance.

Successful collaboration across different policy areas has positively influenced the digitalisation of agriculture. Examples mentioned by interviewees include continuous data exchange between the Latvian CAP paying agency and various agencies (such as the State Forest Service or the State Revenue Service) to streamline payment processes. Similarly, government efforts to strengthen the AKIS in North Macedonia illustrate a coordinated approach involving multiple institutions and stakeholders. However, in many countries, such collaborations face challenges due to limited communication among different policy areas or bureaucratic hurdles. In this context, the CAP is generally perceived as overly complex, which discourages engagement from ministries outside the agricultural domain. Government officials tend to focus on their own policy priorities and

show limited appetite for becoming involved in a framework that is viewed as both technically demanding and administratively burdensome. This perception can become a significant barrier to integrated policymaking, ultimately limiting the reach and effectiveness of cross-sectoral digitalisation strategies in agriculture.

6.5 Cross-Cutting Insights on Digitalisation Drivers, Barriers, and Enablers

Digitalisation in agriculture is a **multifactor process**. Interviews consistently show that no single lever (such as technology, policy, finance, skills, advisory support, or infrastructure) can deliver results in isolation. Furthermore, since adoption pathways are influenced by factors as diverse as geography, farm structure, markets, and culture, **one-size-fits-all policies do not work**. Instead, a layered policy architecture is needed: strategic guidance and funding at EU level, enabling frameworks at national level, and granular programme design at regional and local level. Good governance and institutional capacity are essential across all layers to ensure alignment, responsiveness, and continuity. The Netherlands' bottom-up "don't wait for government" culture, Poland's highly diverse farm structure, and Germany's strong regional autonomy illustrate how different the starting points are. These structural differences help explain why the same CAP regulation may act as a catalyst in one place and remain irrelevant in another.

"In some rural areas, even basic infrastructure like water supply is still lacking, so it's no surprise that digitalisation often falls much lower on the list of priorities."

The following summary reflects how the interviewed policymakers and experts perceive the interplay of drivers, barriers, and enabling conditions across the four interconnected areas of digitalisation described in Section 4.1 above: digital communication and knowledge exchange, government-farmer interface, operational efficiency and productivity, and transparency and market connectivity.

6.5.1 Contextual Conditions and Regional Endowments

Digitalisation in agriculture is shaped, and often constrained, by the contextual conditions in which farms and institutions operate. **Regional endowments** such as topography, climate, land fragmentation, soil conditions, water availability, farm structure, demographics, skilled labour and capital availability, presence of cooperatives, and supply chains play a key role in determining which technologies are relevant and the economic case for investing in them. For instance, rugged landscapes or highly fragmented land can limit the feasibility of automated machinery, while more favourable conditions can lower costs and increase returns on investment. These endowments also shape how regions approach the four areas of digitalisation set out in this report.

Well-endowed, flat areas like the Netherlands and Flanders in Belgium, further advantaged by their relatively compact geographic size, often combine near-universal digital coverage with cohesive governance. This creates an enabling environment for seamless farmer-government interaction and accelerates on-farm automation. By contrast, mountainous or fragmented regions face greater obstacles, including higher connectivity costs and physical constraints that often leads to slower and more selective adoption of digital technologies. A good example of this can be seen in remote livestock systems in parts of Scotland and Ireland, where dispersed herds, hilly terrain, and low population density make both connectivity and equipment servicing particularly difficult. Conversely, **resource constraints** can also act as powerful drivers for digitalisation. For example, in Almeria (Spain), greenhouse clusters have implemented a range of digital technologies (including precision irrigation systems, soil moisture sensors, and integrated climate and fertigation controls) as part of a broader strategy to enhance efficiency in a context of chronic water scarcity and to meet stringent market demands for detailed information on the production cycle.

Labour and capital endowments also influence significantly the pace and nature of agricultural digitalisation. Regions with a younger, more digitally literate workforce tend to adopt new technologies more readily, especially where rural youth are actively engaged in farming or agribusiness. These populations are often more open to change and possess the baseline skills needed to operate precision tools, data systems, and automated equipment. In contrast, ageing or less technologically proficient farming communities may lack the digital literacy or appetite for risk required to embrace digital tools, slowing adoption even where infrastructure is available. Access to skilled human capital (such as engineers, technicians, and ICT specialists) also influences whether technologies can be effectively deployed and maintained. Capital availability is equally important. Larger or

better-financed farms are more likely to invest in advanced equipment and services, while smallholders with limited financial resources may find digital tools inaccessible without targeted support. Regions with robust financial institutions and supportive credit systems are better positioned to finance, adopt, and maintain digital solutions, whereas limited access to affordable credit can significantly constrain digitalisation efforts. In such cases, public funding schemes, cooperative financing models, and EU rural development programmes play an important role in bridging investment gaps and enabling wider adoption.

The practical limits of digitalisation are also defined by physical and digital infrastructure. Reliable roads, consistent electricity, and efficient logistics are fundamental for deploying and maintaining equipment. Similarly, stable and fast connectivity is essential for cloud services, enabling remote monitoring, and facilitating real-time data exchange. However, infrastructure alone is not enough. Its true impact depends on **institutional capacity**, which dictates how effectively farmers can utilize available assets and translate them into tangible benefits. When advisory services, research centres, producer organizations, and local authorities are effective, they play a key role in helping farmers navigate technological choices, test new solutions, access necessary finance, and build essential skills. Likewise, innovation hubs, demonstration farms, and active peer networks significantly accelerate learning and problem-solving among farmers. Regions with higher **absorptive capacity** (supported by strong education systems, effective local coordination, and a robust network of skilled advisors) tend to progress more rapidly from basic tools to integrated, data-driven systems. By contrast, where these foundational elements are weak, digitalisation is slower and more uncertain. In such contexts, digital transformation efforts require carefully sequenced support to avoid failed investments and ensure long-term sustainability.

6.5.2 Farmer Motivations and Behavioural Drivers

The motivations driving farmers to adopt digital technologies are diverse, as highlighted by interviewees. For some, digitalisation offers a way to comply with regulatory or market requirements, such as those related to animal welfare and traceability in livestock production. Others view it as a practical response to specific challenges, including rising input costs (prompting interest in tools like precision fertiliser equipment), resource constraints (water scarcity or soil degradation), or labour shortages, which have led to increased demand for automation across the EU. Digital technologies can also support more effective farm management by enabling real-time monitoring, improving decision-making, and optimising resource use, ultimately helping to reduce costs and boost efficiency. Beyond these economic and operational benefits, digital tools are increasingly used to support environmental and climate-related goals, such as reducing emissions or limiting pesticide use. Participation in sustainability schemes, certification processes, or digitalised subsidy systems may also require or encourage uptake. Furthermore, farmers increasingly recognise the need to adapt to evolving market demands and consumer expectations around transparency, traceability, and sustainability, which further reinforces the motivation to invest in digital technologies.

Importantly, digitalisation is not viewed only as a technical or economic improvement. Many farmers see it as a pathway to improve their overall quality of life, by reducing manual and repetitive tasks, alleviating physical strain, and creating space for strategic planning or personal time. In this sense, digital tools may contribute to the long-term sustainability of farming, not only from an environmental and financial perspective, but also in terms of human well-being. However, adoption is unlikely unless farmers are convinced that these technologies will lead to tangible improvements in their day-to-day lives. **Perceived gains in quality of life are often a decisive factor** in embracing digital solutions, even when financial returns are modest.

“Digitalisation has to be there to help farmers do better. Not just to look at how they are doing but to help them do it better. And that focus is sometimes not enough.”

Across regions, **larger market-oriented farms** (often corporate-owned) tend to lead in digital adoption, motivated by their ability to absorb risk and make the most of their size and resources. Professionalised management structures, stronger capital bases, and economies of scale allow them to invest more confidently in new technologies. Their focus on **higher-value crops** adds further incentive, as precision technologies and automation can often deliver faster and more substantial returns. **High-value indoor systems**, such as greenhouse vegetables or specialty berries, are also leading adopters, drawn by the ability to tightly control climate, inputs, and harvest timing to maximise returns on expensive crops. Similar dynamics apply to **intensive indoor animal operations** such as dairy, poultry, or pig farming, where real-time monitoring, sensors, automated

feeding, and milking systems offer an attractive combination of time savings, productivity gains, and cost-efficiency. **Medium-sized producers**, such as those growing higher-value fruits, tend to follow suit, motivated by the potential of real-time data to improve per-hectare yields, optimise input use, build resilience to weather and market volatility, and provide the traceability that buyers and supply chains increasingly require.”

At the other end of the spectrum, **small, family-run farms** face persistent barriers that slow digital uptake. Thin margins make it difficult to justify high upfront investments or ongoing subscription costs, especially when they operate in remote, mountainous, or fragmented landscapes where connectivity is limited. For many, paying a service fee that delivers processed information and dependable support is preferable to financing equipment that can become obsolete quickly and requires maintenance they cannot provide. A service model also offers a clear point of contact when problems arise and keeps tools current with the best available technology. In some CODECS countries, many small landowners lack motivation to work full-time on their farms, which in turn limits the time, attention, and resources they can dedicate to modernisation and digital adoption. Furthermore, many in the older generation place value on long working hours and rely on traditional, experience-based knowledge rather than digital tools. For producers of lower-value staples or those serving local markets, the return on investment in digital technologies often seems unconvincing. Interviewees also noted that **small and medium-sized farmers usually need to pool demand and resources through cooperatives, machinery rings or shared service platforms** to reach the scale required for digital tools and data services, yet collaboration is often limited. Smallholders tend to be reluctant to collaborate because they value autonomy, have diverse needs, and face coordination costs, governance burdens, and the risk of unequal benefits. In parts of Europe, especially former socialist countries, the legacy of forced collective structures has further eroded trust, reinforcing caution toward joint arrangements even when cooperation would lower costs and spread risk. Additionally, concerns over data privacy (particularly regarding yield or soil health records) tend to fuel mistrust toward public authorities and service providers.

Younger farmers and new entrants to the sector are generally more inclined to adopt digital tools, driven by greater fluency in the use of smartphones, digital platforms, and data analytics. They often view these technologies as means to scale up their operations more efficiently, enhance competitiveness, and align with values such as innovation, sustainability, and data-informed decision-making, while also improving their wellbeing. While younger users tend to integrate digital tools more readily into their workflows, older farmers often adopt a more cautious approach, weighing the perceived benefits against the time and effort required to learn and adapt to unfamiliar systems. In some countries, such as the Netherlands, digitalisation has also contributed to attracting people into agriculture by enabling more flexible and modern farming lifestyles. The rise of remote work, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, has further facilitated this trend by allowing individuals to live and work in rural areas, fostering renewed interest in agricultural activity and rural life.

“Digital technologies are making farming more appealing to young people.”

Trust is a fundamental factor that is often overlooked for the successful diffusion of digital solutions. Farmers frequently express concerns about data ownership, privacy, security, and the reliability of digital tools and service providers. Without confidence that their farm data will be handled ethically, securely, and to their benefit, adoption of digital technologies is likely to remain limited. In addition to trusting technology and providers, **trust in public institutions and the legal system is essential**. Farmers need to believe that there are fair, transparent rules in place and that those rules will be upheld consistently. In this context, farmer cooperatives can serve as trusted intermediaries. Organisations such as SAOS in Scotland demonstrate how **collective data governance can safeguard farmers’ rights while promoting shared value**. By aggregating data under transparent and robust frameworks, cooperatives like SAOS help ensure data sovereignty and address concerns around misuse and exploitation. Their efforts show how cooperative approaches to data management can unlock the benefits of precision farming while reinforcing the trust required for wider adoption of digital tools.

“For farmers, what really matters is trust. They want to be sure that the technology works, that the advisors know what they’re doing, and that their data is safe and won’t be used against them.”

Interviewees generally view digitalisation as a means to an end rather than an end in itself. Ultimately, farmers are most likely to adopt digital technologies when they see clear personal or operational benefits, whether by (i) **cutting costs**, (ii) **increasing income**, (iii) **accessing markets**, (iv) **improving quality of life**, or (v)

supporting regulatory compliance and access to sustainability incentives. Peer examples, both online and offline, are among the strongest **behavioural drivers**, helping farmers visualise the value of digital tools in real-world settings. In this sense, demonstration farms, innovation hubs, communities of practice, and farmer rings are widely regarded as effective accelerators of digital adoption. For many small producers, mandatory digital filing for CAP payments acts as a first step into the digital world, but many rely on public agencies, cooperatives, or private service providers to complete these filings because they lack computers, find the procedures complex, or have limited digital skills. Policy incentives, such as CAP digitalisation measures and regional grant schemes, further reinforce adoption by helping cover hardware costs and funding demonstration initiatives. Together, these factors create an enabling environment in which **peer influence and financial support** work hand in hand to **build trust and confidence** in technology investments.

6.5.3 Systemic Barriers

Across the CODECS spectrum, countries report persistent systemic barriers that continue to undermine agricultural digitalisation. While the COVID-19 pandemic and the EU's RRF have created momentum, a key conclusion from the interviews is that **adoption is merely the final link in a long chain**. The real constraints lie in the underlying structural foundations rather than in the visible symptoms, which are often just the expression of deeper issues. Unless the upstream challenges are addressed, downstream progress will remain fragile, fragmented, and unevenly distributed.

Governance gaps are especially pronounced, even in frontrunner and advanced performers. Analysis of the interviews revealed that regulatory frameworks in CODECS countries are generally fragmented, with overlapping or unclear mandates among ministries and agencies leading to policy gaps, duplication, or inertia. These are not merely symptoms of underperformance. Rather, they reflect the structural complexities that are intrinsic to managing a rapidly evolving, cross-cutting domain like digital agriculture within multi-layered government systems. Countries in earlier stages of digitalisation face these challenges more acutely, compounded by opaque decision-making, shifting political priorities, limited strategic foresight, and weak institutional capacity to implement, coordinate, and enforce policies effectively. Without coherent governance structures, long-term digital strategies and roadmaps, transparent procedures, and clear lines of accountability, many initiatives lose momentum or fail to achieve the continuity needed to integrate these technologies into everyday practice.

Data use and ownership is a recurring grey area, with farmers, service providers, and public agencies often unclear about rights and responsibilities, creating mistrust and stalling data-sharing initiatives. This uncertainty extends beyond individual contracts to the broader legal and institutional frameworks that should govern agricultural data flows. In most countries, data governance is fragmented, with no single authority overseeing the collection, use, and sharing of agricultural data, and existing rules consistently lagging behind technological developments. As a result, confusion over who controls, accesses, and benefits from farm-generated data has become a systemic barrier to digitalisation. It discourages farmers from adopting digital tools they often view with suspicion and blurs responsibilities for managing, safeguarding, and sharing data effectively. This reinforces platform lock-in and makes interoperability more difficult. Without clear and enforceable rules on data rights (covering both private and public use), investments in smart technologies risk deepening rather than bridging the digital divide. In this context, opportunities are being missed to develop data-driven solutions that offer tangible **added value for farmers**.

Interoperability remains a central challenge, both within farms and across public institutions. **At the farm level**, while individual digital solutions and sensor networks are proliferating, legacy IT systems and proprietary platforms often trap valuable data in silos. This lack of seamless integration between equipment and software from different suppliers makes it difficult for farmers to combine diverse datasets or fully automate processes, significantly limiting the value they can extract from their digital investments. Similarly, **in the public sector**, poor interoperability between ministries and agencies hampers coordination, data sharing, and coherent policy implementation. The slow progress in applying common standards means that even neighbouring regions within the same country struggle to streamline data flows, which undermines regional benchmarking, complicates the delivery of digital services, and frustrates efforts to build scalable, data-driven solutions for agriculture. Interviewees frequently cited the urgent **need to push for common interoperability standards** as a prerequisite for unlocking the full potential of digitalisation. Despite recent rulings on machine data access and ambitious initiatives under the European Data Strategy, such as the Data Governance Act, which aims to foster

trustworthy data sharing mechanisms, and the Data Act, which seeks to empower users with control over device-generated data and promote interoperability, enforcement remains uneven, and integration efforts continue to lag behind technological potential.

Connectivity, on the other hand, remains a persistent barrier to agricultural digitalisation in most countries despite official claims of near-universal population coverage. These figures often mask an important reality, since most of the population lives in or near urban centres, whereas agricultural activity takes place across vast rural areas where territorial coverage is far less consistent. As a result, large tracts of farmland still lack stable and high-speed connections, limiting the reliability of cloud-based platforms, precision tools, and real-time monitoring systems. In many regions, telecom providers have little commercial incentive to invest in infrastructure where returns are uncertain or minimal. In some countries, efforts to expand coverage are further slowed by local resistance to new installations, such as mobile masts, due to aesthetic, health, or land-use concerns. While satellite services offer potential alternatives, their current cost structure remains out of reach for widespread use at the farm level in some countries, especially among small and medium-sized holdings. Compounding the issue is a lack of granular data, as connectivity monitoring typically focuses on household-level access and fails to capture conditions in the fields where many digital tools are designed to operate. This disconnect continues to constrain adoption, even in countries with otherwise advanced digital development, and highlights the need for more targeted, agriculture-specific infrastructure strategies.

Digital literacy and skills are perhaps the most frequently cited bottlenecks. Many older farmers are reluctant to engage with unfamiliar technology platforms, even if they confidently use basic digital tools on their smartphones in their private lives. While all CODECS countries have introduced initiatives to address this gap, training opportunities are sometimes described as fragmented, not well aligned with practical needs, or delivered at unsuitable times. Effective adoption requires training that spans all three phases (pre-adoption, adoption, and post-adoption) and blends **technical and business skills**. Farmers need support not only in using new technologies, but also in **choosing among options and understanding how these tools fit their business models and long-term strategies**. Importantly, the digital skills gap is not limited to farmers. Public advisory services often lack the capacity to provide tailored digital support or focus primarily on compliance paperwork rather than helping farmers make informed decisions about digital tools, while private consultants are frequently aligned with the interests of specific companies. Rural administrations also struggle to attract and retain ICT professionals, especially those who combine agronomic and digital expertise, leaving many local governments poorly equipped to support digitalisation efforts. A steady flow of skilled professionals and systematic upskilling programmes are essential to prevent large parts of the agricultural sector from falling further behind.

6.5.4 Digitalisation and Technology Management

At its core, agricultural digitalisation is fundamentally a matter of **technology management**, not merely the deployment of digital tools or the adoption of new devices. The successful uptake and integration of digital tools in agriculture requires more than connectivity, infrastructure, and technical literacy. It requires a combination of skills and strategic thinking, both at the level of individual farms and across the broader enabling environment shaped by public institutions and the agri-tech industry.

At the macro level, governments play a critical enabling role by aligning digitalisation with long-term policy goals, fostering cross-sector collaboration, and supporting spaces for experimentation such as living labs, Digital Innovation Hubs, pilot programmes, and regulatory sandboxes. Effective technology management requires **coordinated strategies and long-term investment** in institutional capacity. Yet, digitalisation efforts are frequently fragmented across ministries or shaped by short political and funding cycles, with insufficient attention to how technologies interact with existing agricultural structures, value chains, and rural labour markets. A more strategic approach requires integrating digital investments into broader agricultural policy frameworks, ensuring coherence across sectors, and building governance systems that support continuous learning, adaptation, and scaling. This also requires stronger mechanisms for stakeholder engagement, bringing together farmers, technology providers, advisors, and regulators in a shared process of co-design, implementation, and evaluation.

At the farm level, **business and management skills** are essential to ensure that digital tools align with operational goals, resource constraints, and long-term strategies. This includes the ability to assess return on investment, understand implications for labour and workflows, and adapt business models to take advantage of digital opportunities. Deploying digital tools without the ability to integrate, adapt, and utilise them strategically

not only limits their impact and leads to suboptimal outcomes, but also risks wasting scarce resources and undermining the long-term viability of the farm business. Effective change management is equally important. Introducing new technologies can disrupt familiar routines and requires careful transition. Resistance to change, whether at the level of individual farms or collective structures like cooperatives, cannot be addressed by technology alone. Clear communication, tailored training, and leadership that builds trust are key to building a culture that supports digital adoption and learning.

Crucially, the principle of **appropriate technology** matters and should guide all investments in digitalisation. According to policymakers and experts interviewed, one of the main challenges for farmers in CODECS countries is not access to technology, but the lack of support in assessing what is suitable and sustainable in their specific contexts. Technological innovation in agriculture is largely supply-driven, with digital tools often pushed onto farms without adequate consideration of their relevance, usability, or compatibility with existing practices and systems. Interviewees described cases where farmers purchased technologies that later proved incompatible with their equipment or too complex to integrate into daily operations. Others noted that some tools were not fully ready for commercial deployment, leading to disappointment and eroding trust. These experiences highlight the need for stronger advisory systems, demonstration farms, and peer-to-peer learning networks that focus on critical evaluation and informed decision-making (not just on promoting adoption). Digitalisation should not be treated as an end in itself, but as a means to enhance productivity, resilience, and sustainability in ways that make sense for the farm and the farmer.

In sum, managing digital technologies in agriculture is not about isolated investments or one-size-fits-all solutions, but about building context-specific systems that respond to the realities of farming. This requires sustained, long-term coordination, not only among public institutions and private providers, but also across key dimensions such as infrastructure development, skill building, and evolving market conditions. When technology choices are grounded in actual needs and strategies, and supported by appropriate incentives, strong governance structures, and continuous feedback mechanisms, digitalisation can shift from an abstract policy ambition into a practical enabler of sustainable and competitive agriculture.

7. AKIS, Living Labs, and Intermediaries in the CODECS Countries

This section examines the relationship between two interconnected policy domains: AKIS policies, and instruments that promote the sustainable digitalisation of agriculture, including living labs. The analysis is undertaken from the perspective of innovation intermediaries, which are deemed as central in both domains. In Europe, AKIS now constitutes a significant component of agricultural policy at multiple scales (European, national, and regional). In CODECS, we adopt the definition used in EU policy documents: “*AKIS is a mental construct that comprises the combined organisation and knowledge flows between persons, organisations and institutions who use and produce knowledge for agriculture and interrelated fields*” (Common Agricultural Policy Strategic Plans, Article 102a Modernization, COM 2018/392).

AKIS policies and related instruments can play a key role in supporting a broad spectrum of intermediation activities required for sustainable digitalisation, including technology scanning, testing, evaluation, and dissemination. However, there is a limited understanding of which actors are positioned to implement these activities in practice, for instance by contributing to new policy instruments such as living labs. Since AKIS is a mental construct, discrepancies between how researchers, practitioners, and policy makers conceptualise the intermediary profiles that contribute to AKIS may constrain the effectiveness of AKIS policies. Accordingly, this section seeks to elucidate how living lab participants understand AKIS, with the aim of informing policy debates on sustainable digitalisation in agriculture.

The section is organised into three subsections that progressively zoom in on the profiles and roles of intermediary actors through the lens of CODECS Living Labs. The first subsection reviews recent literature, policy documents, and research project outputs to extract key findings and identify knowledge gaps concerning the interplay between AKIS policies, intermediaries, and digitalisation. The second subsection synthesises findings from CODECS WP3 on how living lab participants portray AKIS and contrasts these portrayals with scientific and policy descriptions. The third subsection draws on survey results from T6.2 of CODECS WP6 to provide a qualitative analysis of the functions, economic models, and networks of intermediary actors identified by living labs participants.

Detailed results, figures, methodological notes, and references for further reading are provided in Annex 1: Interview Guide – Policymakers at EU Level.

7.1 Insights from Former Research Projects

Several projects, such as PRO AKIS (2015) and i2connect (2025), have developed comprehensive descriptions of national AKIS for all EU Member States. These studies provide valuable insights into the diverse structures, historical developments, and policy frameworks of AKIS across the EU, with a particular emphasis on farm advisory services as a key intermediary actor. To synthesise this information, we have developed a series of AKIS factsheets for the countries involved in the CODECS project, which are included in Annex 6 of this report. These factsheets, which are based primarily on i2connect reports, offer concise summaries and structural diagrams of each national AKIS. They illustrate the wide variety of intermediaries operating within these systems, from the perspective of AKIS researchers and experts. They often attribute a central role to farmers' organisations and public institutions. Furthermore, these analyses highlight the significant influence of recent policies (mainly at the European scale) that are explicitly built upon the AKIS concept. This has led to an innovation policy paradigm that places a strong emphasis on coordination and the support of multi-actor networks. This shift is operationalised through various dedicated instruments, including living labs, multi-actor projects, operational groups, and mixed technological networks.

These various AKIS initiatives have increasingly integrated digitalisation into their policy mix debates concerning strategies and instruments. For example, a targeted expert survey commissioned by the European Union Standing Committee on Agricultural Research's Strategic Working Group (EU SCAR SWG) (Geerling-Eiff et al., 2019) advanced three main recommendations: strengthen interactions and networks on digitalisation within AKIS; maintain up-to-date inventories of tools, particularly curated by and for bridging organisations; and expand continuous training for farmers and advisers so they can play central roles in the design, evaluation, and dissemination of digital technologies.

In short, studies on AKIS and digitalisation converge in highlighting the need to better connect farmers and other AKIS actors through instruments that promote networks and knowledge reservoirs. However, these studies remain poorly connected to research examining ongoing transformations in the landscape of innovation intermediaries from a bottom-up, farmer-centric perspective. Such transformations include the emergence of new types of actors, fuzzy boundaries, complex roles, and even situations where intermediaries are unaware of their own contributions (both within and beyond the agricultural sector). These changes are driven by multiple trends, including digitalisation and the growing emphasis on sustainability in public innovation policies, which have given rise to mission-oriented innovation systems. Several publications indicate a persistent knowledge gap regarding which actors are effectively fulfilling intermediation functions, highlighting the need for a "reality check" of intermediaries and their roles (Kivimaa et al., 2019), using bottom-up approaches grounded in practice to better inform AKIS and sustainability policies. Some recent research, based on farmer surveys regarding knowledge sources, has provided initial insights into the evolving AKIS landscape, particularly highlighting the role of bridging organisations, especially those delivering advisory services to farmers.

Drawing on a survey of more than 1000 farmers across 13 European countries, the AgriLink project developed the concept of microAKIS to capture farmers' sources of services and knowledge across multiple innovation domains (Madureira et al., 2022). Despite marked contextual diversity, two core findings emerged: 1) even where national AKIS are highly diversified, farmers typically rely on a narrow set of trusted advice sources when assessing and adopting innovations; and 2) actors that are not typically included in AKIS descriptions play a key role for farmers, including informal sources of advice (peers, retired agronomists) and non-independent or "linked" advisors (companies that sell pesticides, seeds or fertilisers to farmers, start-ups, bookkeepers, etc.). This pattern is also evident for digital technologies, where ICT firms and start-ups have a growing contribution.

7.2 Insights from the AKIS Mapping Exercises Implemented in CODECS Living Labs

In the CODECS project, AKIS is defined as a mental construct, consistent with the EU policy framework. A fundamental implication of this perspective is the critical need to examine the convergences and divergences in

how different actors perceive and represent AKIS. Discrepancies among these representations can lead to inefficiencies, such as the low uptake of policy measures or network failures, as evidenced by research in other sectors. Such findings frequently highlight the need of conducting a diagnosis of the resources, relational structures, and economic models of intermediary actors within innovation systems. An initial exploration of the interrelations between CODECS Living Labs, AKIS policy, and innovation intermediaries was undertaken in WP3 through a mapping exercise. This involved conducting workshops across 19 Living Labs, wherein participants were engaged in the task of visually mapping actor ecosystems and relevant AKIS policies. From this exercise, two main findings can be highlighted about Living Lab participants' representations of AKIS:

a) The mapping exercises confirm the growing role of private firms (ICT, upstream and downstream) in AKIS.

This prevalence is evident in the number of private firms identified by CODECS Living Lab participants as relevant AKIS actors. In total, 330 distinct actors were mentioned and subsequently categorised into six groups: 1) Farmers and farmers' associations, 2) Research and education institutions, 3) Bridging organisations (including advisory services), 4) Public authorities, 5) Private companies, and 6) Family and business networks (see Annex 5).

Notably, private firms were cited more frequently than the traditional AKIS actors that are typically placed at the centre of AKIS analyses, inventories, and policies reviewed in the previous section, such as research organisations and bridging organisations, including advisory bodies. A second key finding is the need to differentiate among private organisations. As expected in living labs focused on digital technologies, agricultural technology companies and start-ups were strongly represented, often more than advisers or researchers. Upstream and downstream supply chain companies were also prominent in AKIS representations, along with financial organisations. Taken together, these findings may hold significant policy relevance, as they highlight a disconnection between the traditional conception of AKIS (which is centred on public authorities, research, and bridging organizations), and the bottom-up perspectives of living lab participants (whose representations place greater emphasis on private firms and farmers).

b) Context and purpose shape the proximity between AKIS actors and living labs.

During the WP3 mapping exercise, a question was introduced to evaluate the perceived proximity between AKIS actors and the CODECS Living Labs. For each actor identified, participants were asked to classify the relationship according to three levels of engagement, as illustrated in Figure 5 below: 1) the actor participates directly in the Living Lab ("in LL"); 2) the actor collaborates with the Living Lab or has clear potential to do so ("Close to the LL"); or 3) the actor influences the AKIS but remains disconnected from the Living Lab's activities ("Not so close to the LL"). In cases where participants hesitated about the position of some actors, they were permitted to select two options. To accurately represent these nuanced responses and avoid double-counting, two additional "in between" categories were incorporated during the analysis phase.

Figure 5: Distance of AKIS actors to the CODECS Living Lab (source: WP3 AKIS mapping exercise)
(Y axis = Number of times a type of actors was mentioned during the WP3 mapping exercise)

Two key results emerge from the analysis. First, some actors are consistently recognised as central to the AKIS while also being well-integrated into (or in close proximity to) the Living Labs. This includes classic actors such as research institutions and, to a lesser degree, advisory services. Farmers themselves are also prominent in both roles, though their representative organisations demonstrate limited participation in Living Labs. ICT firms are another notable example, being widely acknowledged as key AKIS actors with significant involvement in the living labs. Another striking result is the divergence between the prominence of certain actors within AKIS and their limited engagement in Living Labs. Public authorities exemplify this pattern: while they are the most frequently cited AKIS actors across Living Labs, they have a very limited participation in their activities. Overall, these findings suggest a certain segmentation within the landscape: living labs primarily function as co-design platforms where farmers, researchers, and ICT firms collaborate to develop and test digital technologies. In contrast, bridging organisations (e.g., advisory services, institutional networks), public authorities, and consumers are assumed to play a more peripheral role, often being portrayed as potential partners for subsequent scaling or dissemination activities.

However, these aggregate patterns should be interpreted with caution, as they mask considerable diversity among the individual living labs. A closer examination of the actor inventories from each site revealed three distinct typologies of AKIS representation (see Annex 5 for further detail).

Group 1 - Firm-Led Representations of AKIS: The first group comprises the mapping exercises implemented in five CODECS Living Labs of four different countries (Belgium, Czechia, Italy, and Spain). The defining characteristic of this representation is the dominant presence of companies (ICT, upstream, and to a lesser extent, downstream firms). Firms are the most cited actors both within the broader AKIS and as participants within the Labs themselves. This focus aligns with the Living Labs' primary objective of addressing economic objectives such as productivity, efficiency, or value creation. Consequently, these Labs function as hubs for technology development and dissemination through direct collaboration between researchers, industry, and farmers. In this model, traditional bridging organisations of AKIS seem to assume a secondary role.

Group 2 - Policy-Driven representations of AKIS: This group comprises the mapping exercises implemented in five CODECS Living Labs located in five different countries (Estonia, Latvia, North Macedonia, Poland, and Slovenia). This AKIS representation is characterized by the predominant citation of Public Authorities as central AKIS actors. While acknowledged for their indirect influence on digital innovation, they are rarely cited as direct members of the Living Labs. This suggests a representation of AKIS primarily as a public policy instrument, while the Labs themselves operate as more agile platforms

for direct innovation between farmers and intermediaries. Although the five Labs have diverse objectives (e.g., productivity, efficiency, resources, value creation), the prominence of public authorities can be partly explained by the national context of these countries, where the AKIS concept was recently introduced in a top-down manner through CAP reforms, as noticeable in i2connect country reports.

Group 3 - Pluralistic representations of AKIS: The third group comprises the mapping exercises implemented in seven CODECS Living Labs located in six different countries (Germany, France, Hungary, Serbia, Slovakia, and Scotland). This group is characterised by an AKIS representation that more closely reflects the pluralistic perspective often described as a defining feature of these systems in Europe, notably in Germany, France, and Hungary. These countries have sustained public investment in bridging organisations, including networks and farm advisory services such as chambers of agriculture, which helps explain both the prominence of these organisations in AKIS representations and their presence in Living Labs. The centrality of bridging organisations also aligns with the objectives of the seven Living Labs, which more directly incorporate sustainability missions supported by public policies and by the bridging organisations themselves, including the conservation of natural resources and the development of social and human capital in rural areas.

In summary, the mapping exercise reveals a considerable diversity in how AKIS is conceptualised across Living Labs, shaped by their distinct contexts and objectives. A key implication is that such divergent representations may lead to significant discrepancies among actors. These discrepancies, in turn, can hinder the uptake of AKIS-supported measures and reduce the willingness of certain actors to participate. Conversely, they may also create opportunities for certain actors to instrumentalise these measures to their own advantage.

7.3 Insights from a Qualitative Survey with Innovation Intermediaries

Building on the AKIS mapping carried out by the CODECS Living Lab participants in WP3, we then sought to characterise the actors they identified as part of AKIS in a subset of living labs (see Annex 5 for methodological details and results). Four dimensions were combined to characterise intermediaries: 1) the functions they perform (what is their role in supporting digital innovation?), 2) the economic model of these organisations (who benefits from their services and how they engage with them?), 3) their knowledge networks (with whom do they exchange knowledge?), and 4) their relations to AKIS-related policies, including living labs.

To move from identification to characterisation, a structured questionnaire was co-designed to operationalise these four dimensions in a manner that is comparable across cases. For sampling, CODECS Living Labs were purposively used as the sampling frame to capture the range of intermediary functions and KIBS models that contribute to living labs, as well as their relations to other AKIS actors. Consistent with this bottom-up approach, Multiple Correspondence Analysis was applied to identify the variables that account for the greatest share of diversity and inertia across the four dimensions for the intermediary actors identified by CODECS Living Lab participants. The operational choices for each dimension are set out below and mirror the variables used in the subsequent analysis.

- To capture **intermediary functions in digital innovation**, we distinguished among *ex-ante* support services (e.g., network building, awareness raising, information scanning, foresight), *in itinere* support services (e.g., prototyping, brokering, testing, training), and *ex-post* support services (e.g., evaluation, standard setting, intellectual property protection).
- To analyse **economic models of intermediaries**, we used a series of variables derived from the literature on Knowledge and Intensive and Business services (KIBS), which focuses not only on who the clients are, but also on how the services are conceived in both their front-office dimension (level of interactions with clients) and back-office one (investments in R&D).
- To capture the **integration of the intermediary organisations within AKIS**, we asked them whether different types of actors were their major partners for knowledge exchange. We considered the same categories of actors as in WP3: public research, industries, bridging organisations (including advisory services), public authorities, farmers and farmers-based organisations.

- To capture the **relations of intermediaries with innovation public policies**, we used three variables about policy frameworks and funding. From a financial perspective, we asked whether public funds were a major source or revenue of the organisation. From a broader perspective, we asked whether the organisation was integrated in any innovation policy framework (European, national or regional). From a more precise perspective related to digitalisation, we asked how close the organisation was from Living Labs.

A first notable finding is that variables describing intermediary functions explain the largest share of total inertia in the responses. The first axis contrasts organisations that perform intermediary functions with those that do not. Subsequent analysis differentiates three clusters of modalities that most strongly account for variation in organisational positioning and in how their roles are perceived:

The first group is most closely associated with participation in Living Labs. Four key aspects of this group stand out. Regarding intermediary functions, it aligns with *ex-ante* and *in itinere* innovation support services, such as foresight, scanning, testing, and dissemination. In terms of KIBS features, there is substantial investment in back-office capabilities, with limited investment in front office activities aimed at providing personalised advice for farmers. Within AKIS networks, knowledge exchange occurs primarily with private firms in the digital technology sector. With respect to public policies, members of this group not only participate in Living Labs but are also well integrated into other innovation policy frameworks.

The second group is characterised by its contribution to the evaluation of digital technologies. In functional terms, the sole activity associated with this group is *ex-post* evaluation of technologies. Its KIBS profile includes some front office activities, though not highly personalised farmer-oriented services, and these are not typically commercialised to farmers. Its AKIS network is the most diverse, with strong interactions with advisory organisations, public research, and upstream and downstream industries. In policy terms, this group is more distant from Living Labs and broader innovation policy frameworks, yet it nonetheless displays some dependence on public subsidies.

The third group has a distinct profile characterised by minimal investment in intermediary functions alongside strong front office activity. In terms of intermediary functions, this group shows little engagement with any of the five intermediary functions considered in the analysis (foresight, scanning, testing, dissemination, evaluation). Its KIBS features include the highest level of service personalisation and a high share of organisations selling services directly to farmers. In terms of AKIS network, it shows the weakest ties to other actors. Regarding public policy, it is also the most distant from Living Labs, innovation policy frameworks, and public financial support.

The Multiple Correspondence Analysis reveals some complementarities across three groups of variables defined by intermediary functions, KIBS economic models, AKIS networks, and links to innovation policy. The first group reflects the role of Living Labs in co-design and testing of digital technologies, with emphasis on foresight and testing, supported by investments in back-office capabilities, close relations with firms in the ICT sector, and participation in innovation policy instruments. The second group corresponds to more traditional R&D activities aimed at the evaluation of digital technologies, characterised by ties with public research and bridging organisations, as well as with industry, and supported by public funds. The third group comprises organisations that provide advisory services to farmers, often on a fee-based basis, but with limited engagement in other intermediary functions and weak connections to public funding and policy instruments.

These results suggest complementary yet potentially fragmented roles within the AKIS: Living Labs develop and test digital technologies; multi-actor R&D projects evaluate them; and Farm Advisory Services support farmers in deciding whether and how to adopt these technologies. However, this functional specialisation also presents a risk of disconnect or segmentation, which is a concern already noted in earlier studies. This risk is further illustrated by the perception among some Living Lab participants, who view AKIS primarily as a domain of public authorities and Living Labs as instruments for engaging with industry. A key challenge is how to better bridge actors involved in scanning and evaluating digital technologies with those providing personalised advisory services to farmers. Further analysis and policy dialogue are needed to assess these dynamics across scales (particularly national and regional levels) as data from WP3 indicate significant variation across contexts.

8. Final Remarks

The comparative analysis conducted across the 18 CODECS countries indicates that **there is no single trajectory toward agricultural digitalisation**. Distinct pathways arise from the interaction between several factors, including governance, physical geography, economic conditions, connectivity, human capital, farmer demographics, farm size structure, and the characteristics and prevalence of the specific subsectors. A comprehensive and coherent policy framework is therefore essential to steer the sector through the twin green-and-digital transitions.

Digitalisation in agriculture is the final link in a long sequence of reforms and investments. It is more readily achieved where **foundational conditions** are strong, including sound governance, reliable connectivity, effective institutions, a skilled labour force, competitive markets, and access to finance. Equally important is the development of **absorptive capacity** at farm, regional and national levels, namely the ability to identify, acquire and integrate new knowledge and technologies and to adapt routines accordingly. Without such foundations, attempts at digitalisation are like placing a roof on weak walls, consuming resources, failing to deliver durable gains, and risking deeper disparities. Among the CODECS countries, the Netherlands illustrates how multiyear programming, a stable civil service, an educated population, well established agriculture markets and coherent funding streams can gradually build absorptive capacity. In contrast, countries where strategies shift with each election cycle or remain largely aspirational often struggle to move from vision to implementation.

“When we joined the EU, we had a law that protected the stability of civil servants. That law doesn’t exist anymore. Now there’s high turnover in the civil service, and we can’t keep institutional memory in our government.”

The most effective policies for driving digital uptake are not those that simply push technology, but those that foster a competitive environment where farm modernisation is a natural response to opportunity and pressure for improvement. A **focus on structural improvements** such as increasing farm profitability, strengthening producer organisations, improving value chain logistics, and building farmers’ business and digital skills can help governments and markets generate strong and sustained demand for the benefits that digital tools offer. This perspective is supported by the observation that, with few exceptions, there is a good correlation between countries’ performance on the DESI dashboard for the Digital Decade and the European Innovation Scoreboard, as both reflect the same underlying structural conditions that support broad digital readiness as well as agricultural digitalisation.

From our analysis, several insights emerge to guide future policy development. They are not prescriptive blueprints, but foundational considerations derived from the diverse experiences of the countries studied. These insights also provide the basis for D6.3 (*Policy Recommendations and Toolbox*) of CODECS, to be delivered in Month 48 of the project, which will include: (i) key messages, (ii) forward-looking digitalisation scenarios, (iii) guiding principles for sustainable digitalisation, (iv) a set of policy tools, and (v) the integration of target group perspectives on policy uptake and digital capacity-building. These **key learnings** are presented below.

Agricultural digitalisation largely mirrors the broader national digital landscape and is conditioned by multiple, interconnected divides

The pace and pattern of digital adoption in agriculture vary not only between urban and rural areas but also across regions, farm sizes, education levels, generations, and idiosyncrasies. These differences reflect disparities in connectivity, digital skills, access to advisory services, investment capacity, trust, and readiness for change within farms and local institutions. Where these foundations are strong, uptake is faster; where they are weak, progress lags. Without targeted efforts to address structural barriers (such as poor broadband infrastructure, limited access to digital training, and gaps in institutional capacity) digitalisation risks reinforcing existing inequalities between regions, farm types, and rural communities.

Strengthening data governance, improving interoperability, and building trust around data sharing at the EU and national levels are critical steps toward unlocking the full value of digitalisation across the agricultural sector. Robust data governance is a strategic enabler of agricultural digitalisation. This requires addressing a complex set of challenges, including data ownership, privacy, cybersecurity, and quality. Establishing clear, universal standards for data exchange is essential to ensure seamless communication between technologies from different

providers. Furthermore, transparent and equitable protocols are needed to govern how companies and government entities access and use farmer data. This includes fair mechanisms for data certification and valuation to ensure farmers are appropriately compensated for the information they generate. Simultaneously, promoting open access to non-sensitive data for research and public good initiatives requires careful safeguards to mitigate risks, such as the misuse of sensitive economic information or cybersecurity risks. Ultimately, a well-governed data ecosystem is the critical enabler that will allow digital tools to deliver on their promise of improved efficiency, profitability, and sustainability for all stakeholders.

Interoperability needs a strategic policy push given its central role in unlocking the full potential of digital tools in agriculture, enabling seamless data exchange across systems, platforms, and stakeholders. A strategic approach is needed to develop and promote common standards and ontologies, ensure compatibility, and avoid fragmentation, creating the foundation for more efficient, integrated and farmer-friendly digital ecosystems. At the same time, this approach must strike a balance between setting shared rules and preserving the flexibility needed to foster innovation and diverse technological solutions.

“You don’t want to end up with one hundred applications on your cell phone. You want tools that work together and can share data among them.”

Digitalisation is essential to address current EU challenges, but farmers uptake requires a clear vision and context-specific policies

The potential of digital technologies in agriculture exceeds their current uptake. While digital technologies hold significant promise to improve food security, green transition, productivity, sustainability, and resilience in agriculture, their actual uptake on the ground remains limited. Many tools (such as precision farming systems, farm management platforms, and data-driven decision support) are available but underused due to barriers like cost, complexity, lack of skills, or insufficient advisory support. Unlocking the full potential of digitalisation requires not only technological availability but also targeted political and funding efforts to build user capacity, demonstrate value, and adapt solutions to the real needs of farmers and rural communities.

Policies play a crucial role in agricultural digitalisation, but their effectiveness depends on design and delivery that reflect regional conditions. Since digitalisation is deeply context-dependent and shaped by local conditions and capacities, a one-size-fits-all approach is usually ineffective. Instead, a targeted approach is needed, combining a shared EU vision and framework with local policy adaptations. This means developing region-specific assessments and technology roadmaps to tailor tools, training, and support to local conditions while staying aligned with broader EU goals. When combined with long-term, multi-cycle funding instruments, these place-based strategies offer a powerful means to overcome the fragmentation that often hinders progress in more diverse and structurally complex territories.

“You can’t apply the same recipe everywhere. What works in one region won’t always work in another. Policies should reflect the reality of the region, its geography, its people, and the way farming is done locally.”

Digitalisation in agriculture is a long-term process that requires systemic solutions and coherence among policies

The digital transformation of agriculture is not a quick fix but a gradual, long-term process that demands coordinated action across multiple dimensions. Systemic solutions are needed to address structural challenges (such as fragmented governance, limited interoperability, uneven digital skills, and inadequate connectivity) ensuring that technological innovation and adoption is embedded within broader institutional, social, and economic frameworks. Progress is the result of disciplined sequencing, consistent implementation, and continuous monitoring and learning.

“In some rural areas they still lack reliable water and sanitation. So, for them digitalisation is probably not the first priority.”

Coherence is also essential both across funding instruments and between national and regional policies. While initiatives such as RRF, ERDF, CAP, DEP, and Horizon Europe aim to advance various aspects of digitalisation, their impact on agriculture is yet to be quantified and will need future assessment. Countries and

regions with more advanced digital ecosystems tend to align national and regional strategies for agriculture, digital, data, and skills; use joint programming and shared standards; and coordinate implementation across ministries to reduce siloed approaches. They also typically acknowledge and actively build on the strategic guidance and obligations set out by the EC in support of the digital transition.

“We didn’t wait for the CAP to tell us what to do. We knew we had to modernise our agriculture, and we’ve been driving that change ourselves.”

Agricultural policies need to enhance digital readiness providing evidence, skills, and trust

Digital readiness is shaped by evidence, skills, and trust. Robust, granular data is the essential foundation for designing and evaluating effective agricultural digitalisation policies. Access to robust statistics, including farm-level surveys and harmonised indicators, is crucial for informed and proactive policymaking. However, the lack of consistent, granular data on digitalisation at the farm level is a persistent major barrier for the design and evaluation of digitalisation policies in agriculture. Existing indicators often miss differences across farm types, regions, and subsectors, leaving decision makers with an incomplete picture of digital readiness and use. Without reliable baselines and ongoing monitoring, strategies risk being misaligned with actual needs and progress is hard to measure. Building coherent data systems that combine regular farm level surveys with harmonised indicators is needed for more targeted support, better evaluation, and timely course correction.

Building digital skills across AKIS is a central challenge. Accelerating technology uptake requires enhancing digital skills, which is a significant hurdle particularly among older farmers. More engaging and accessible learning models, such as demonstration farms, peer-to-peer learning, and video-based modules, can help increase adoption. In parallel, AKIS actors including advisory services, public agriculture administrations, and education institutions must upskill and reskill to stay current with technological advances and adapt services to a data-driven sector. User-friendly platforms, transparent data practices, and clear communication of public procedures help build trust and make adoption easier.

“We need to promote digital literacy in the public administration. That would be the starting point for the development of good policies and programs.”

Policies should support trust in digital tools, identifying and facilitating the turning of available technologies into solutions that are compelling, usable, and affordable for farmers, since one of the main gaps in agricultural digitalisation lies in the “last mile” from technology developers to farmers. Technology adoption reflects practical factors such as perceived usefulness, a sense of autonomy and control (particularly with automated systems, where a fear of error can be a significant deterrent), the time and difficulty required to learn how to use it, and trust in the technology and its providers. Overall, uptake depends more on the fit with farm workflows and integration with existing machinery and data than with the novelty of the tools. Adoption stalls where interfaces are complex, language and accessibility barriers persist, after sales support is weak, interoperability and data portability are limited, and financing conditions place greater risk on smaller farms. By contrast, it is higher where connectivity is dependable, advisory and peer networks are active, returns are clear and measurable, and after sales service is reliable.

“Too many times farmers have adopted technologies that didn’t work for them. Some technologies were not ready for the market and others did not fit their farms. Each time this happens, trust goes down.”

Agricultural administrations should turn to farmer-centred approaches and understand their needs

Policies that promote the digital transition should be perceived by farmers as supportive rather than controlling or punitive. Small farms, which make up the majority of Europe’s agricultural holdings, often remain excluded from CAP funding mechanisms, limiting their access to digitalisation incentives. In contrast, larger farms, particularly those in intensive production systems, are typically better positioned to invest in innovation and digitalisation, exacerbating existing disparities. Policies to close this gap call for proportionate eligibility thresholds, simple access routes, and recognition of cooperative models such as shared ownership and pooled subscriptions. It also requires trusted advisory support from public administrations, clear rules on data use, and

digital services that reduce paperwork and save time. When farmers experience concrete gains in daily decisions, record keeping, and market access, digital tools are adopted as a help rather than seen as a burden.

Policies should also prioritise farmer-centred design and support clear, practical information and dissemination about appropriate technologies. Since digitalisation is a multi-stage process with specific support needs at each phase, policies should reflect this complexity by promoting affordable, tailored solutions, prioritising appropriate technologies that fit the operational realities of different farm types and skill levels, and supporting the development of the new competencies needed for effective use. Strengthening collaboration between farmers and technology developers is key to ensuring that tools are user-friendly, accessible, and aligned with real-world needs. In this context, mobile applications are often preferred by farmers over desktop-based solutions, as they are more familiar and offer greater flexibility and ease of use in daily farm operations. Prioritising intuitive, mobile-friendly design helps bring technology closer to small farmers and facilitates more consistent engagement.

“I am adopting these technologies because they make my life easier, not because somebody tells me that I should do it”

Securing the future of agricultural digitalisation requires sustained investment to empower the next generation of farmers. This means integrating digital skills into vocational training, agricultural curricula, and lifelong learning programs. However, digital skills alone are not enough. A solid foundation in business and management skills is equally essential to ensure that new farmers can evaluate return on investment, adapt business models, and integrate digital technologies effectively and sustainably. Beyond education, these efforts will need to be supported by generational renewal policies aligned with digitalisation goals, including incentives for land transfer, improved access to finance and infrastructure, and targeted advisory support. Ultimately, combining robust, modern education with enabling policies will be essential to foster a digitally competent and resilient new generation.

“Digitalisation will happen anyway if we work with young farmers. But there are fewer people studying agriculture and fewer young people who want to be farmers. Austria is the only EU country that shows a positive trend in generational transition.”

Changes in farmer idiosyncrasy will boost the usefulness of agriculture digitalisation

Collaboration among farmers expands access to digital tools. Technology uptake increases when farmers organise through cooperatives, producer organisations, buying groups, or machinery rings to aggregate demand, negotiate better terms, and secure ongoing support and maintenance. Pooling resources helps reduce costs and spread risk, enabling models such as subscriptions, shared ownership, and cooperative purchasing. Shared ownership improves equipment utilisation, while cooperative-bundled subscriptions can include training, troubleshooting, and data management, which builds trust and consistent use. These collaborative arrangements also support peer learning and promote consistent data practices, which together increase technology adoption and help distribute the benefits of digitalisation more widely across farm types and regions. However, many farmers are reluctant to adopt these approaches, and in some countries the legacy of central planning and compulsory collectivisation complicates efforts to build cooperation.

“Most farmers prefer to do everything on their own, even knowing that it’s not very efficient.”

Transitioning from owning devices and technologies to paying for services helps the digital transformation of agriculture by lowering entry barriers for farmers and cooperatives, especially small and medium-sized ones. Instead of making costly upfront investments in machinery, sensors, or digital platforms, often beyond their financial reach, farmers can access these tools through service-based models such as monthly fees, or “as-a-service” arrangements. This shift enables continuous updates, technical support, and scalability, ensuring that users benefit from the most recent innovations without bearing the risks of obsolescence. Moreover, service models foster stronger connections between technology providers and end-users, as providers have an ongoing incentive to ensure functionality, training, and adaptation to local needs. By making advanced digital solutions more affordable, adaptable, and user-friendly, service-based approaches accelerate widespread adoption and contribute to a more inclusive digital transformation in agriculture.

Digitalisation offers promises for all types of farm holdings

The benefits of digitalisation extend beyond large-scale, professionalised or integrated farms, offering transformative benefits also for small farms, short food supply chains, and the resilience of local food systems. For medium-sized and large farms, advanced systems such as precision machinery, drones, and big data analytics enable efficiency gains, cost reduction, and sustainability improvements. For smallholders, digital tools can provide affordable access to weather forecasts, market prices, precision input use, and advisory services that increase productivity and resilience. Digital platforms also foster inclusion by linking farmers of all scales to markets, cooperatives, and financial services. Digital technologies can also support the transition toward more localised, short food supply chains by improving traceability, logistics, and direct-to-consumer sales. These tools enable producers to better manage inventories, optimise distribution, and connect with nearby consumers, making local food systems more viable and competitive.

Digital tools support rural vitality and reduce exposure to long supply chains, thereby decreasing vulnerability to external shocks. In this context, agricultural policies have a vital role to play in strengthening long-term food security, particularly in the face of mounting global challenges such as climate change and geopolitical tensions. By strategically aligning digitalisation efforts with support for resilient, regionally anchored food systems, policymakers and governing bodies can help safeguard access to food while fostering sustainability, inclusiveness, and socioeconomic dynamism in rural areas.

“Digitalisation can make short food supply chains stronger and more efficient, helping farmers connect directly with consumers and making food systems more secure across the EU.”

Public–private collaboration is key to boost agricultural digitalisation

Joint public–private undertakings offer a powerful mechanism for advancing agricultural digitalisation by leveraging resources, expertise, and incentives that neither sector can provide alone. Public institutions can create an enabling framework through supportive policies, infrastructure investment, and research funding, while private companies bring innovation, technical know-how, and market-driven solutions. This collaboration is necessary from building basic connectivity services to advanced decision-making tools. Targeted public-private efforts are needed to ensure that robust infrastructure extends beyond urban centres into rural and agricultural areas. This includes addressing not only the urban-rural divide, but also the persistent connectivity gap between households and agricultural fields. While rural broadband coverage has improved, remote and hard-to-reach areas continue to face significant challenges, especially in some countries. The growing diversity of connectivity technologies (including satellite) offers promising solutions, but their deployment in most remote areas requires coordinated public-private action. Policy frameworks are needed that promote structured collaboration with telecommunications and energy providers as well as innovative financing mechanisms to reach white spots and areas affected by persistent market failure.

Joint undertakings can co-develop digital platforms, ensure interoperability of technologies, and foster inclusive business models that reach smallholders as well as large-scale farms. These partnerships also reduce risks for early adopters, accelerate scaling, and help align digital tools with broader sustainability and food security goals. In this way, public–private collaboration acts as a catalyst for faster, more equitable digital transformation in agriculture.

“Areas with more population are more likely to get infrastructure because there is demand. There is little interest in investing in areas that are abandoned.”

Discrepancies in representations of AKIS and its intermediary actors could lead to inefficient public policies, including systemic network failures

The CODECS project, consistently with both academics and EU perspectives, conceptualises AKIS as *mental constructs*, i.e. as representations of the actors, relations, resources, and institutions involved in knowledge exchange in the agricultural sector. Hence, it is crucial to understand the representations of different actors or social groups that contribute to digitalisation. Evidence reveals that there are important discrepancies in AKIS representations among researchers, policymakers and Living Lab participants. These differences are influenced

by the regional context as well as by the specific objectives of the Living Labs, and the degree to which sustainability issues are integrated.

A closer examination through the lens of specific Living Labs and the intermediaries collaborating directly or indirectly with them revealed a potential distribution of roles among: 1) actors involved in co-designing and testing digital solutions, 2) actors evaluating them, and 3) actors advising farmers on their use. The first group is well integrated into policy frameworks, participates in Living Labs, and interacts with IT firms. The second is connected to a plurality of intermediary actors and benefits from public R&D funds. The third group, however, operates largely outside AKIS policy and interactions, but being the closest to farmers is the one that provides the most personalised advisory services.

This pattern should be interpreted with caution as it is based on a small sample of actors. It can be seen as a form of functional complementarity within innovation systems, but it may also be a sign of segmentation between the innovation support embedded in EU policy frameworks and the day-to-day advice available to farmers. These findings point to the need for debate about how to anchor AKIS policy discussions in the realities of farmers' practices, networks, and resources. A promising avenue for such debates would be to give bottom-up perspectives a stronger role in the policy arenas where the AKIS policy mix (strategies and instruments) is designed and evaluated.

In closing, **strong leadership and strategic guidance** are needed at the EU level, with clear coordination mechanisms across national, regional, and local levels to ensure alignment and minimise fragmentation. The experience of cohesion policy (infrastructure investment, institution building, and multiannual programming) shows that sustained, place-based funding can drive convergence. A similar long-term, regionally adapted funding and performance approach to agricultural digitalisation would help ensure that efforts are coherent, effective, and fair across farming systems. The **CAP and agricultural administrations are central** to this agenda. CAP interventions should align with wider programmes to reduce duplication and unlock synergies, with digital objectives embedded consistently across instruments and tracked with shared indicators. At the same time, greater legal clarity within the EU competition framework is needed to ensure that collective farmer initiatives (such as data pooling and cost-sharing) can proceed without fear of breaching antitrust rules.

References

- Alonso-Roldán, M., Delgado-Serrano, M.M. (2024). Draft report on policy environments (D6.1). CODECS project. European Commission.
<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e50ac0fe69&apld=PPGMS>
- Alonso-Roldán, M., Delgado-Serrano, M.M., Brunori, G. (2023). Policy analysis and roadmap (D4.1). DESIRA project. European Commission.
<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5fc6a24be&apld=PPGMS>
- Apostol, S., Hernández-Rodríguez, E. (2024). Digitalisation in European regions: unravelling the impact of relatedness and complexity on digital technology adoption and productivity growth. *Industry and Innovation*, 1-30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13662716.2024.2423731>
- Autio, E. (2017). *Digitalisation, Ecosystems, Entrepreneurship and Policy*. Policy Briefs; Finland Ministry of Trade and Employment: Helsinki, Finland, 2017.
- Barabanova, Y. and Krzysztofowicz, M. (2023). *Digital Transition: Long-term Implications for EU Farmers and Rural Communities*, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg
<https://dx.doi.org/10.2760/093463>
- Central Intelligence Agency. (2024). *The World Factbook*. Retrieved from <https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/> (Accessed: 2 September 2025)
- DeepL (n.d.) DeepL Pro. Available at: <https://www.deepl.com/pro>
- Economic Chamber of North Macedonia. (2025) Ristovski in an Interview for MKD.mk: 'With a Strategic Approach, Macedonia Can Become a Significant Player on the EU Food Market' [Online]. Economic Chamber of North Macedonia, 14 May. Available at: <https://www.mchamber.mk/en/news/index/773> (Accessed: 10 July 2025).
- European Commission. (2019). *Building stronger Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) to foster advice, knowledge and innovation in agriculture*. Retrieved from https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2019-04/building-stronger-akis_en_0.pdf (Accessed: August 27, 2025)
- European Commission. (2022) DESI 2022 composite index [Dataset]. Digital Decade platform. Available at: <https://digital-decade-desi.digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/datasets/desi-2022/charts/desi-composite> (Accessed: 6 August 2025).
- European Commission. (2023). *Recovery and Resilience Facility - European Commission*. https://commission.europa.eu/business-economy-euro/economic-recovery/recovery-and-resilience-facility_en
- European Commission. (2025a). EUSurvey [Online survey tool]. <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/> (Accessed: August 18, 2025)
- European Commission. (2025b). *Study on simplification and administrative burden for farmers and other beneficiaries under the CAP*. EU CAP Network. <https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/publications/2025-05/eu-cap-network-report-study-on-simplification.pdf>
- European Commission. (2025c). *A Vision for Agriculture and Food: Shaping together an attractive farming and agri-food sector for future generations*. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/overview-vision-agriculture-food/vision-agriculture-and-food_en#documents
- European Commission. (2025d). *Communication COM (2025) 165 final: AI Continent Action Plan*. Brussels, 9 April 2025. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/redirection/document/114523> (Accessed: 06 August 2025).

- European Commission. (n.d.) Digital Decade – DESI. Digital Economy and Society Index. Available at: <https://digital-decade-desi.digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/> (Accessed: 06 August 2025).
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development – DG AGRI. (n.d.a). Agri-food Data Portal [Website]. <https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/DataPortal/home.html> (Accessed: 06 August 2025).
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development – DG AGRI. (n.d.b). The common agricultural policy at a glance. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/cap-overview/cap-glance_en (Accessed: 06 August 2025).
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology – DG CNECT. (2024a). Report on the State of the Digital Decade 2024. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/report-state-digital-decade-2024> (Accessed: 06 August 2025).
- European Commission, Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology – DG CNECT. (2024b). Women in Digital Scoreboard 2024: Country profiles. <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/redirection/document/107320> (Accessed: 02 September 2025).
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology – DG CNECT. (2025a). Digital Decade 2025: Country reports. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/digital-decade-2025-country-reports> (Accessed: 02 September 2025).
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology – DG CNECT. (2025b). Digital Decade 2025 report: Country fact pages. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/factpages/digital-decade-2025-report-country-fact-pages> (Accessed: 06 August 2025).
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology – DG CNECT. (n.d.). DESI dashboard for the Digital Decade (2023 onwards). <https://digital-decade-desi.digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/datasets/desi/charts> (Accessed: 01 September 2025).
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Economic and Financial Affairs – DG ECFIN. (n.d.). ECFIN publications. https://economy-finance.ec.europa.eu/ecfin-publications_en (Accessed: 22 August 2025).
- European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE). (n.d.). Gender Equality Index: Digitalisation — Country. <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/thematic-focus/digitalisation/country> (Accessed: 22 August 2025).
- European Union. (2021). Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 2 December 2021 establishing rules on support for strategic plans to be drawn up by Member States under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP Strategic Plans). Official Journal of the European Union, L 435, 6.12.2021, pp. 1–186. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32021R2115> (Accessed: 06 August 2025)
- European Union. (n.d.). EU countries. https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/eu-countries_en (Accessed: 22 August 2025)
- Eurostat. (2022). Farms and farmland in the European Union – statistics, Statistics Explained. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Farms_and_farmland_in_the_European_Union_-_statistics#Farms_in_2020 (Accessed: 22 August 2025)
- Eurostat. (n.d.a). Category: Agriculture. Statistics Explained. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Category:Agriculture> (Accessed: 22 August 2025)
- Eurostat. (n.d.b). *Country facts* [Interactive data tool]. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/countryfacts/> (Accessed: 31 August 2025)
- Eurostat. (n.d.c). Economy and finance. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/explore/all/economy> (Accessed: 31 August 2025)
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). (2021). FAO Strategic Framework 2022–31. Rome: FAO. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/handle/20.500.14283/cb7099en>

- Geerling-Eiff F., Bogaardt M.-J., Burssens S., Kujáni K., Reszkető T. (2019). Exploring digitalisation to enhance knowledge flows in EU AKIS. Report of the CASA project. https://scar-europe.org/images/SCAR-Documents/Reports_outcomes_studies/AKIS3_Report_Exploring_digitalisation_for_future_AKIS_final.pdf
- Kivimaa, P., Boon, W., Hyysalo, S., Klerkx, L. (2019). Towards a typology of intermediaries in sustainability transitions: A systematic review and a research agenda. *Research Policy*, 48(4), 1062-1075. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.10.006>
- Krajnc, A. (2017). Farm Structure Survey, Slovenia, 2016. Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia. <https://www.stat.si/statweb/en/News/Index/6742>
- Madureira, L., Labarthe, P., Marques, C. S., Santos, G. (2022). Exploring microAKIS: farmer-centric evidence on the role of advice in agricultural innovation in Europe. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 28(5), 549-575. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1389224X.2022.2123838>
- McFadden, J., Casalini, F., Griffin, T., Antón, J. (2022). The digitalisation of agriculture: A literature review and emerging policy issues. *OECD Food, Agriculture and Fisheries Papers*, No. 176, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/285cc27d-en>
- Miljatović, A., Tomaš Simin, M. and Vukoje, V. (2025) Key determinants of the economic viability of family farms: Evidence from Serbia. *Agriculture*, 15, 828. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture15080828>
- Parida, V., Sjödin, D. and Reim, W. (2019) Reviewing literature on digitalization, business model innovation, and sustainable industry: Past achievements and future promises. *Sustainability*, 11(2), 391. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11020391>
- Rolandi, S., Brunori, G., Bacco, M., Scotti, I. (2021). The digitalization of agriculture and rural areas: Towards a taxonomy of the impacts. *Sustainability*, 13, 5172. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13095172>
- Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia. (2017, March 29). Agriculture: In 2016, there were 99.7% of family farms in Slovenia [Press release]. <https://www.stat.si/statweb/en/News/Index/6742>
- The World Bank. (n.d.). World Bank Open Data. <https://data.worldbank.org/> (Accessed: 31 August 2025)
- Trendov, N. M., Varas, S., Zeng, M. (2019). Digital technologies in agriculture and rural areas. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). Retrieved from <https://openknowledge.fao.org/items/ba78b670-0947-4e73-ad10-091009c0dfc3>
- Tur Cardona, J., Ciaian, P., Antonioli, F., Fellmann, T., Rocciola, F., Ierardi, I., Crimeni, R., Anastasiou, E. (2025). The state of digitalisation in EU agriculture: Insights from farm surveys. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/4688498>
- Unión de Pequeños Agricultores y Ganaderos (UPA), Fundación de Estudios Rurales. (2022). ¿Cómo es la agricultura y ganadería familiar en España? <https://www.upa.es/Anuario2022/Diptico-Resumen-Anuario-2022.pdf>

Annexes

Annex 1: Interview Guide – Policymakers at EU Level

1. INTRODUCTION TO THE TASK

The *Task 6.1 Analysis of policy environments in the EU*, led by University of Córdoba -UCO-, includes a **selected number of interviews with policy makers at EU level**. These interviews have got the aim of *describing, comparing, and contrasting* the different policy environments.

Ten policy makers at EU level will be interviewed along the duration of this task (month 1 to month 36), including people with different profiles:

Profile 1: Digitalisation experts.

Profile 2: People with experience in digitalisation in agriculture.

Profile 3: People involved in evaluating the CAP National Strategic Plans, especially the digitalisation part.

2. ETHICS

The UCO team will ensure the appropriate treatment of the data gathered according to both CODECS and the University of Córdoba Data Management Plans.

Researchers responsible for the task: Mar Delgado (mmdelgado@uco.es) and Antonio Hurtado (es2rohuc@uco.es)

3. INTERVIEW GUIDE

3.1. Digitalisation in the EU.

To understand how advanced and promoted is digitalisation in the EU.

To identify key policies/policy initiatives that have given a push to digitalisation.

- How would you describe the current state of digitalisation in the EU? Any key dates or milestones in digitalisation? How is digitalisation in the different Member States?
- Can you highlight key policies or initiatives that have significantly advanced digitalisation in the EU?
- In what ways has digitalisation impacted various sectors or areas in the EU?
- What are the major challenges or barriers hindering further digitalisation efforts?

3.2. Role of digitalisation in agriculture.

To understand the views of stakeholders about the role of digitalisation in agriculture and farming.

To which aspects of agriculture is digitalisation contributing the most?

Which type of agriculture/farming is digitalisation currently supporting the most?

- How do you perceive the role of digitalisation in the current agriculture and farming practices within the EU?
- Could you elaborate on specific aspects where digitalisation has made the most significant contributions to agriculture?
- Which types of agriculture or farming practices have primarily benefited from digitalisation, and why?
- What are some potential drawbacks or challenges associated with implementing digitalisation in agriculture?

Co-funded by
the European Union

CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060179. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060179. Views and opinions

Page | 1

3.3. Role of digitalisation in the CAP NSP.

To understand the role of digitalisation in the CAP NSP (e.g., has it got a key role, is it an add-on, an obligation, perhaps?).

- How do you see the role of digitalisation within the CAP National Strategic Plans in the different Member States?
- How is the CAP influencing digitalisation in agriculture in the Member States?
- How do you foresee digitalisation influencing the effectiveness or outcomes of the NSP in the agricultural sector?

3.4. Role of other policy areas regarding digitalisation in agriculture.

To understand the EU policy environment, to identify other policy areas influencing digitalisation in agriculture.

- Aside from agricultural policies, what other policy domains or areas do you believe significantly impact digitalisation in the agricultural sector? E.g., Infrastructure, education, innovation, etc.
- How do these intersecting policies complement or potentially conflict with efforts to enhance digitalisation in agriculture?
- Can you provide examples of successful collaborations between different policy areas that have positively impacted digitalisation in agriculture?

CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060179. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060179. Views and opinions

Page | 2

CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement n. 101060179. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

Page | 74

Annex 2: Interview Guide – Policymakers at EU, Extra EU and National Level

1. INTRODUCTION TO THE TASK

The *Task 6.1 Analysis of policy environments in the EU*, led by University of Córdoba -UCO-, includes a **selected number of interviews with policy makers at EU, extra EU (UK, Serbia, North Macedonia) and national levels**. These interviews have got the aim of *describing, comparing, and contrasting* the different policy environments.

Five policy makers per partner country will be interviewed along the duration of this task (month 1 to month 36), including people with different profiles:

Profile 1: People involved in drafting or implementing the CAP NSP, especially the digitalisation part (only EU countries).

Profile 2: People with expertise on digitalisation in agriculture.

Profile 3: People with experience regarding the CODECS Living Labs.

Profile 4: People involved in the digitalisation in general at national level.

2. ETHICS

The UCO team will ensure the appropriate treatment of the data gathered according to both CODECS and the University of Córdoba Data Management Plans.

Researchers responsible for the task: Mar Delgado (mmdelgado@uco.es) and Antonio Hurtado (es2rohuc@uco.es).

3. INTERVIEW GUIDE

3.1. Digitalisation in the country. (All interviewees)

To understand how advanced and promoted is digitalisation in the different countries.

To identify key policies/policy initiatives that have given a push to digitalisation.

- How would you describe the current state of digitalisation in your country? Any key dates or milestones in digitalisation? How is digitalisation compared to other EU countries?
- Can you highlight key policies or initiatives that have significantly advanced digitalisation within your country? Policies at any level: EU, national, regional, local.
- In what ways has digitalisation impacted various sectors or areas within your country?
- What are the major challenges or barriers hindering further digitalisation efforts?

3.2. Role of digitalisation in agriculture. (Only agri experts)

To understand the views of national stakeholders about the role of digitalisation in agriculture and farming.

To which aspects of agriculture is digitalisation contributing the most?

Which type of agriculture/farming is digitalisation currently supporting the most?

- How do you perceive the role of digitalisation in the current agriculture and farming practices within your country?
- Could you elaborate on specific aspects where digitalisation has made the most significant contributions to agriculture?
- Which types of agriculture or farming practices have primarily benefited from digitalisation, and why?

CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060179. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060179. Views and opinions

Page | 1

- What are some potential drawbacks or challenges associated with implementing digitalisation in agriculture?

3.3. Role of digitalisation in the CAP NSP. (Only CAP experts, EU countries)

To understand national perceptions on the role of digitalisation in the NSP (e.g., has it got a key role, is it an add-on, an obligation, perhaps?).

- How does your country view the role of digitalisation within the Common Agricultural Policy's National Strategic Plan (CAP NSP)? Is digitalisation considered a pivotal component of the NSP, or is it perceived as an additional feature or obligation?
- How is the CAP influencing digitalisation in agriculture in your country?
- How do you foresee digitalisation influencing the effectiveness or outcomes of the NSP in the agricultural sector?

3.4. Role of other policy areas regarding digitalisation in agriculture. (Only agri experts)

To understand national policy environments, to identify other policy areas influencing digitalisation in agriculture.

- Aside from agricultural policies, what other policy domains or areas do you believe significantly impact digitalisation in the agricultural sector? E.g., Infrastructure, education, innovation, etc.
- How do these intersecting policies complement or potentially conflict with efforts to enhance digitalisation in agriculture?
- Can you provide examples of successful collaborations between different policy areas that have positively impacted digitalisation in agriculture?

CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060179. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060179. Views and opinions

Page | 2

CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement n. 101060179. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

Page | 76

Annex 3: Country Values for the Four Pillars of Agricultural Digitalisation

Country	DESI 2022 Composite Index	Agriculture-Specific Momentum	% of Very Small and Small Farms (up to 24,999 EUR Standard Output)	Ratio Farmers <35yo vs 55+
Belgium	50.31	87.49	21%	0.12
Czechia	49.14	28.43	61%	0.22
Estonia	56.51	19.56	72%	0.21
France	53.33	19.21	28%	0.22
Germany	52.88	11.21	39%	0.16
Greece	38.93	8.28	86%	0.05
Hungary	43.76	5.76	85%	0.08
Ireland	62.74	5.46	63%	0.13
Italy	49.25	5.19	67%	0.08
Latvia	49.71	4.92	89%	0.09
Netherlands	67.37	2.96	18%	0.08
Poland	40.55	2.20	84%	0.28
Slovakia	43.45	2.16	77%	0.24
Slovenia	53.37	1.03	87%	0.07
Spain	60.77	0.94	72%	0.06

Annex 4: EU-Funded Initiatives with Relevant Policy Recommendations

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
1	AGRICORE	Agent-based support tool for the development of agriculture policies	The EU-funded AGRICORE project aims to use an agent-based approach to improve on traditional methods with modelling and information and communication technology (ICT). It will use computational modelling to simulate farmers' actions as autonomous or collective entities, with contexts ranging from local to global scales. Artificial intelligence, Big Data, cloud services will be involved in the process. This open-source tool will permit more efficient, optimised policies with its predictive and monitoring capabilities while ensuring transparency and constant improvement.	1 Sep 2019 - 29 Feb 2024	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/816078 https://agricore-project.eu/
2	AgriLink	AgriLink. Agricultural Knowledge: Linking farmers, advisors and researchers to boost innovation.	AgriLink aims to enhance sustainability transitions in European agriculture by analysing and enhancing the role of farmer advice in eight areas of	1 Jun 2017 - 30 Nov 2021	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/727577 https://www.agrilink2020.eu/

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			innovation that address the challenges identified in the Strategic Approach to EU Agricultural Research & Innovation.		
3	agROBOfood	agROBOfood: Business-Oriented Support to the European Robotics and Agri-food Sector, towards a network of Digital Innovation Hubs in Robotics	The agROBOfood project aims to accelerate the sector's digital transformation through the adoption of robotic technologies. To boost the uptake of robotic solutions, it will establish a sustainable network of digital innovation hubs (DIHs).	1 Jun 2019 - 29 Feb 2024	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/825395 https://agrobofood.eu/
4	CoRoSect	Cognitive Robotic System for Digitalized and Networked (Automated) Insect Farms	The CoRoSect project focused on the connection of research on bionomics and the life cycle of insects with new robotics tools and protocols for the automatisisation of insect farming. The project's objectives included establishing innovative integrated cognitive robotics ecosystems to replace operations demanding manual labour or	1 Jan 2021 - 31 Mar 2024	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101016953 https://corosect.eu/

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			continuous human supervision.		
5	DEMETER	Building an Interoperable, Data-Driven, Innovative and Sustainable European Agri-Food Sector	The EU-funded DEMETER is a large-scale project deployed in 18 countries, 15 of which are EU Member States. The project will analyse data obtained from a wide range of actors (production sectors and systems) to provide an integrated interoperable data model enabling optimal resource management in the European agri-food sector.	1 Sep 2019 - 31 Aug 2023	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/857202 https://h2020-demeter.eu
6	DESIRA	Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas	The DESIRA project will develop a methodology - and a related online tool - to assess the impact of past, current and future digitalisation trends, using the concept of socio-cyber-physical systems – which connect and change data, things, people, plants and animals. Impact analysis will be linked directly to	1 Jun 2019 - 31 May 2023	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/818194 https://desira2020.eu/

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			<p>the United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals and will contribute to the promotion of the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation. Involving 25 partners across Europe, the consortium will organise 20 Living Labs and one EU-level Rural Digital Forum. The project will ultimately contribute to policy development across the EU.</p>		
7	EO4AGRI	Bringing together the Knowledge for Better Agriculture Monitoring	EO4AGRI will combine Copernicus satellite observation data with exploitation of associated geospatial and socio-economic information services to improve operational agriculture monitoring from local to global levels. The project will support the implementation of the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), focusing on the CAP2020 reform, the requirements of	1 Nov 2018 - 31 Oct 2020	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/821940

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			<p>Paying Agencies, the Integrated Administration and Control System processes, and specifications of data-driven farming services in interaction with farmers, farmer associations and agro-food industry. EO4AGRI will consider EC investments employment into Copernicus Data and Information Access Services to assess information concerning land use and agricultural service needs.</p>		
8	<p>EU FOOD 2030 Project Family</p>	<p>Collaboration of five EU Horizon Projects (<u>FoodSHIFT2030</u>, <u>FUSILLI</u>, <u>FoodE</u>, <u>CITIES2023</u>, <u>FOOD TRAILS</u>)</p>	<p>The EU FOOD 2030 Project Family is a collaboration of five EU Horizon projects coordinating synergistic cross-project initiatives towards a sustainable transformation of the European food system aligned with European Commission's FOOD 2030 and Farm to Fork Strategy.</p>		<p>https://foodshift2030.eu/eu-food-2030-project-family/</p>

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
9	FAIRshare	Farm Advisory digital Innovation tools Realised and Shared	The EU-funded FAIRshare project will engage, enable and empower the independent farm advisor community by sharing digital tools, services, expertise and motivations. The project will allow advisors to integrate digital tools in diverse advisory and farming contexts across the EU.	1 Nov 2018 - 31 Oct 2023	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/818488 https://www.h2020fairshare.eu/
10	GRASS Ceiling	Gender Equality in Rural and Agricultural Innovation SystemS	GRASS Ceiling is a multi-actor project which aims to empower rural women and increase the number of socio-ecological innovations led by women in agriculture, the rural economy and rural communities. The project aims to contribute to advancing the UN's goals on gender parity, realise the EU gender equality strategy, and achieve the goals of the Green Deal, the Farm to Fork strategy, the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas, and the European Pillar of Social Rights.	1 Jan 2023 - 31 Dec 2025	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101083408 http://www.grassceiling.eu/

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
1 1	HubIT	The HUB for boosting the Responsibility and inclusiveness of ICT enabled Research and Innovation through constructive interactions with SSH research	The EU-Funded HubIT project aims to improve Horizon 2020 by ensuring ICT-related innovations remain responsible and inclusive. To do so, they plan to develop a hub that will help the social sciences and humanities, and ICT disciplines co-create a vision of inclusivity.	1 Sep 2017 - 28 Feb 2021	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/769497 https://www.hubit-project.eu/
1 2	INSPIRE (H2020)	Towards growth for business by flexible processing in customer-driven value chains	The main focus of this project is the development of innovative business models creating flexible networks through the use of intensified processing that would promote more local production in Europe within the 5 years after the end of this study. Expected outcome of this project would be the description of the current European landscape and link between intensified processing and flexibility, development of innovative business models for different sectors in general, and providing a guideline to	1 Sep 2016 - 31 Aug 2018	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/723748 https://www.inspire-eu-project.eu/

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			measure the performance of such novel models under different scenario		
13	Interreg Alpine Space Smart Villages	Smart digital transformation of villages in the Alpine Space	Alpine rural communities often lack a good provision of services as well as a favourable climate for entrepreneurship and social innovation. Digitalisation is a promising approach to counter the situation but remains unexploited. SmartVillages unlocked the potential of local actors to make their region a more attractive place to live and work through new forms of stakeholder involvement, by bringing together policy makers, business, academia and the civil society. Finally, the transfer of the project results to the policy level contributed to improve the political framework conditions for digital innovation, for both the organisational / societal part and	Apr 2018 – Oct 2021	Smart Villages Policies: Past, Present and Future (published 4 Feb 2021): https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/4/1663

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			the technical part.		
14	IoF2020	Internet of Food and Farm 2020	The EU-funded IoF2020 project will lead the charge in accelerating the adoption of Internet of Things (IoT) technology. With a consortium of 73 partners, including Wageningen University & Research and previous key project partners, IoF2020 aims to foster a symbiotic ecosystem of farmers, food industry stakeholders, technology providers, and research institutes.	1 Jan 2017 - 31 Mar 2021	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/731884 https://www.iof2020.eu/
15	LIAISON	Better Rural Innovation: Linking Actors, Instruments and Policies through Networks	LIAISON aims to make a significant and meaningful contribution to optimising interactive innovation project approaches and the delivery of EU policies to speed up innovation in	1 May 2018 - 30 Apr 2022	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773418 https://liaison2020.eu

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			<p>agriculture, forestry and rural areas. Researchers, policy advisors, actors from interactive innovation projects, initiatives and networks, farm/forestry advisors, decision-makers and administrators will jointly investigate the design and implementation of interactive innovation project approaches. Looking with the eyes of a larger number of interactive innovation initiatives we will assess the infrastructure of H2020 and Rural Development Programmes at the project, national and European levels.</p>		
16	MATS	Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable	<p>The EU-funded MATS project will explore how to improve trade at private sector, national, EU, African and global levels. Specifically, it will carry out case studies on 15 countries to understand the conditions for sustainability as</p>	1 Jul 2021 - 31 Dec 2024	<p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/10100075 1 https://sustainable-agri-trade.eu/</p>

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			<p>food is traded from surplus to deficit areas. The findings will shed light on the interactions between agricultural markets, trade, investments, policy, environmental sustainability and human well-being. With this information, the project will design a new benchmark in trade policy analysis.</p>		
17	NEFERTITI	Networking European Farms to Enhance Cross Fertilisation and Innovation Uptake through Demonstration	<p>NEFERTITI focuses on creating added value from the exchange of knowledge, actors, farmers and technical content over the networks in order to boost innovation uptake, to improve peer to peer learning and network connectivity between farms actors across Europe, thus contributing to a more competitive, sustainable and climate-smart agriculture.</p>	1 Jan 2018 - 30 Sep 2022	<p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/772705</p> <p>https://nefertiti-h2020.eu/</p>
18	NIVA	A New IACS Vision in Action	<p>The EU-funded NIVA project is based on interactive planning to ensure faster turnaround,</p>	1 Jun 2019 - 30 Nov 2022	<p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/842009</p> <p>https://www.niva4cap.eu/</p>

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			<p>increased flexibility and further participation of stakeholders. The project is undertaken by nine EU member administrations at national, multi-national and pan-European levels. It aims to accelerate innovation, diminish administrative obstacles, support cooperation in an innovative environment, and increase the flow of information to all stakeholders.</p>		
19	OPEN DEI	Aligning Reference Architectures, Open Platforms and Large-Scale Pilots in Digitising European Industry	The EU-funded OPEN DEI project aims to detect gaps, encourage synergies, support regional and national cooperation, and enhance communication among the Innovation Actions implementing the EU DT strategy. The project aims to compare reference architectures and enable a unified data platform, to create large scale pilots and contribute to a	1 Jun 2019 - 31 Dec 2022	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/857065 https://www.opendei.eu/

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			digital maturity model, to build a data ecosystem and to strive for standardisation.		
20	Robotics4EU	Robotics with and for Society – Boosting Widespread Adoption of Robotics in Europe	The EU-funded Robotics4EU project will apply responsible robotics principles amongst the EU robotics community, envisaging the societal acceptance of (artificial intelligence-based) robotics solutions in the application areas of healthcare, inspection, maintenance of infrastructure, agri-food and agile production.	1 Jan 2021 - 31 Mar 2024	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101017283 https://www.robotics4eu.eu/
21	Rural SMEs (Interreg Europe)	Policies to develop entrepreneurship and innovative SMEs in rural areas	To improve the policies on regional support systems for entrepreneurs through exchange of experiences and identification of good practices, implementing the lessons learnt in regional action plans to increase the creation of innovative SMEs in rural areas.	1 Jan 2017 - 30 Jun 2021	https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/ruralsmes/
22	SALSA	Small farms, small food businesses and sustainable food security	SALSA will assess the role of small farms and small food businesses in delivering a	1 Apr 2016 - 31 Jul 2020	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/677363

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			sustainable and secure supply of affordable, nutritious and culturally adequate food. SALSA will identify the mechanisms which, at different scales, can strengthen the role of small farms in food systems and thereby support sustainable food and nutrition security (FNS).		
2 3	SHERPA	Sustainable Hub to Engage into Rural Policies with Actors	SHERPA project aims to create long-lasting science-society-policy interfaces that engage in developing policy recommendations at European, national and regional levels, and in designing concrete proposals for future research agendas that fill knowledge gaps and meet the needs of rural actors. SHERPA will gather relevant knowledge and use results of past and present research projects (from FP6, FP7, H2020 and other funding streams) to engage stakeholders in discussions in 40 Multi-Actor	1 Oct 2019 - 30 Sep 2023	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862448 https://rural-interfaces.eu

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			Platforms (MAPs) around 20 EU Member States, and at EU level.		
24	SmartAgriHubs	Connecting the dots to unleash the innovation potential for digital transformation of the European agri-food sector	The EU funded SmartAgriHubs project will create a network of digital innovation hubs (DIHs) to boost the adoption of digital solutions by the sector by consolidating, activating and extending the existing ecosystem. The project will integrate technology and business support in a local one-stop-shop method involving all regions and stakeholders in Europe.	1 Nov 2018 - 30 Nov 2022	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/818182 https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/
25	Smart-AKIS	European Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) towards innovation-driven research in Smart Farming Technology	Smart-AKIS is the Thematic Network focusing on Smart Farming. Smart-AKIS has researched farmers' interests and needs vis-à-vis Smart Farming, disseminated Smart Farming technologies (SFTs) through an online platform, and involved more than 900 stakeholders in 7 EU Member States.	1 Mar 2016 - 31 Aug 2018	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/696294 https://www.smart-akis.com/

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
26	SuMaNu (Interreg Baltic Sea Region)	Sustainable Manure and Nutrient Management for reduction of nutrient loss in the Baltic Sea Region	SuMaNu is a platform project which aims to analyse and synthesize approaches to sustainable manure and nutrient management promoted by four international projects. These are Interreg Baltic Sea Region projects Baltic Slurry Acidification and Manure Standards, Interreg Central Baltic project GreenAgri and BONUS Programme project BONUS PROMISE.	Oct 2018 – Sep 2021	https://balticsumanu.eu/
27	SUPREMA	Support for Policy RElevant Modelling of Agriculture	Sectoral policies are becoming more and more interrelated. Hence, there is a need to improve the capacity of current models, connect them or redesign them to deliver on an increasing variety of policy objectives, and to explore future directions for agricultural modelling in Europe. SUPREMA comes to address this challenge by proposing a meta-platform that supports	1 Jan 2018 - 30 Jun 2020	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773499 https://suprema-project.eu/

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			modelling groups linked already through various other platforms and networks. SUPREMA should help close the gaps between expectations of policy makers and the actual capacity of models to deliver relevant policy analysis.		
28	Tools4CAP	Innovative Toolbox empowering effective CAP governance towards EU ambitions	The overall ambition of Tools4CAP is to support the design, implementation and monitoring of the CAP by stimulating Member States to adopt methods and tools adapted to their needs. It will provide tailor-made solutions, including modelling tools, participatory decision-making and multi-governance tools, as well as new data and monitoring solutions.	1 Jan 2023 - 31 Dec 2026	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101086311 https://www.tools4cap.eu/
29	WIRE2018	Smart Choices für innovative regional ecosystems. The Power of Connectivity, Entrepreneurship and Science & Research.	WIRE 2018 will cover two intersecting issues: digitisation and its impacts on R&I, economy and society, and Alpine challenges. The	1 Feb 2018 - 31 Jan 2019	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/814427 https://www.wire2018.eu/page.cfm

	PROJECT	FULL NAME OF THE PROJECT	SHORT DESCRIPTION	DURATION	WEBSITE
			overall aim of the conference is to raise awareness about the importance of regional innovation ecosystems allowing regional stakeholders to obtain synergies with multilevel policies.		
30	YOUNG FARMERS	What can digital communications do for generational renewal in farming?	The EU-funded YOUNG FARMERS project explored the digital communication transformation to develop new ideas to engage more young people in agriculture and guide generational renewal policies.	1 Jul 2021 - 30 Jun 2024	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/895185

Annex 5: Methodology and Results on Innovation Intermediaries for Digital Innovation for Farmers

This annex presents with more details the results and methodology, figures, references, and the questionnaire specifically used for the task T6.2.

Extended presentation of section 7 (methodology and results) with references

This section deals with the relations between two potentially interconnected policies: Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) policies on the one hand, and instruments for sustainable digitalisation (including Living Labs) on the other hand, from the perspective of innovation intermediaries that are claimed to be central for both policies. AKIS are now an important component of agricultural policies in Europe, at various scales: European, national or regional. In Codecs, we have opted for the definition close to the one in EU policy documents²: “AKIS is a mental construct that comprises the combined organisation and knowledge flows between persons, organisations and institutions who use and produce knowledge for agriculture and interrelated fields”. AKIS policies and related instruments play a key role in supporting various actors that could contribute to the evaluation of digital technologies to the benefit of farmers and the wider community.

However, there is a lack of knowledge and understanding about who the intermediary actors are that could actually (co)produce and disseminate knowledge about digital technologies. As AKIS is a mental construct, potential discrepancies between the AKIS representations of researchers, practitioners and policy makers about the profiles of intermediaries that actually contribute to AKIS could hinder the effectiveness of AKIS policies. This section describes the different perspectives of AKIS, (including policy documents, Living Labs and intermediary actors) to foster policy debates on sustainable digitalisation of agriculture. A major aim of this task was to contribute to understand the innovation intermediaries’ perspective.

This section is organised with three sub-sections, which enable to “zoom-in” on the profiles and roles of intermediary actors through the lenses of Codecs Living Labs. The first sub-section reviews some recent literature, policy documents and outputs of research projects to extract key findings and knowledge gaps about the relations between AKIS policies, intermediaries and digitalisation (with links towards further reading). The second sub-section proposes a synthesis of Codecs WP3 findings about how Living Lab participants actually portray AKIS in contrast with scientific or political description of AKIS. The third sub-section, based on a result of a survey (implemented in the task 6.2 of Codecs WP6), proposes an exploratory analysis of the functions and resources of the intermediary actors acknowledged by LL participants.

Insights form former expertise and research projects

There are various elements that attest the importance of the AKIS concept at the European Scale. 1) Since 2010, a specific working group has been set up to support the exchanges between practitioners, researchers and policy makers from EU Member States (MS) about AKIS (the SCAR-AKIS-SWG). This group has produced various reports on AKIS, with policy recommendations³. 2) AKIS has gradually been incorporated into the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP, Knierim et al. 2015), first with policy instruments targeting farm advisory services in a rather restrictive way (between 2003 and 2015, Labarthe and Beck 2022) and in the latest PAC with an explicit requirement for Member States to present an overall strategy for their AKIS (Sutherland et al. 2023). 3) There have been strong investments in research projects aimed to describe and better understand the structures, functions and processes within AKIS. These research projects had various outcomes about the roles and relations of intermediaries within AKIS.

- From the point of view of the infrastructures of AKIS, several projects, including PROAKIS in 2015 and I2Connect⁴ in 2025, have proposed descriptions of AKIS at national levels for every EU country. They enable to understand the variety of AKIS structures, histories and policies. We provide an appendix with factsheets proposing brief summaries of these national descriptions for the countries involved in

² Article 102a Modernization, COM 2018/392.

³ <https://scar-europe.org/akis-documents>

⁴ <https://i2connect-h2020.eu/resources/akis-country-reports/>

CODECS. There has been many comparisons and discussions about the diversity of intermediaries involved in AKIS across countries, including in policy arenas.

- From a policy perspective, this AKIS perspective has resulted in a conception of innovation policies where a very strong focus is put on supporting multi-actor networks, with various tools and instruments (Living Labs, multi-actor projects, Operational groups, mixed technological networks, etc.). A recent review implemented in the frame of the project Liaison revealed the multiplicity and complementarities between these sets of instruments (Fieldsend et al. 2021).
- These various AKIS initiatives have started to build connections with digitalisation policies. This is for instance the case of a specific survey that was commissioned by the EU-SCAR-SWG to a group of experts⁵. Three main recommendations were highlighted: the need for more interactions and networks about digitalisation within AKIS, a need to keep inventories of tools⁶ especially by and for bridging organisations, and a need to continue training farmers and advisors so that they can play a key role in the design, evaluation and dissemination of digital technologies.

It is striking to note that many of these studies are hardly connected to research that highlights the effects of digitalisation on the profiles and roles of intermediaries, or on innovation processes and systems (Busse et al. 2015, Kernecker et al. 2021). However, various research showed important changes in the landscape of innovation intermediaries, with new ranges of actors, fuzzy boundaries, complex roles and even intermediaries unaware of their contributions (Kivimaa et al. 2019), in the agricultural sector and beyond. This situation is caused by various trends, including digitalisation (Howells 2024), but also the emergence of sustainability issues in innovation public policies that result in mission-oriented innovation systems (Klerkx and Begeman 2020). Different publications state that that we currently lack knowledge about which are the actors that can actually fulfil intermediation functions. In other words, there is a need for a “reality check” of intermediaries and intermediation (Kivimaa et al. 2019) to inform AKIS and sustainability policies. Some recent research, based on farmers’ surveys about their sources of knowledge have highlighted some first important results about the evolution of AKIS landscape, with a focus on bridging organisations (especially the one delivering advisory services to farmers):

- The project AgriLink, based on a survey with more than 1000 farmers in Europe, developed the concept of microAKIS to better understand the sources of service and knowledge of farmers in various innovation areas in 13 European countries (Sutherland and Labarthe 2022, Madureira et al. 2022). Beyond the huge diversity between contexts, two key facts emerged: 1) even in countries with diversified AKIS, farmers tend to rely on a limited number of sources of advice when it comes to assess and adopt innovation; 2) actors that are not typically included in AKIS description play a key role for farmers, including informal sources of advice (peers, retired agronomists) and non-independent or “linked” advisors (companies that sell pesticides, seeds or fertilisers to farmers, start-ups, bookkeepers, etc.). This situation holds true in the case of digital technologies (Konečná and Sutherland 2022, Kvam et al. 2022, Bechtet 2023), with a specific contribution of Information Technology (IT) firms and start-ups.
- Such findings cannot be extrapolated as they are not based on representative sampling at national scales. However, they are partly confirmed by other studies that used other methodologies and conceptual frameworks to capture networks that farmers use when adopting or not innovation (Cofré-Bravo et al. 2019, Klerkx et al. 2017). These studies show the role of industries and linked sources of advice (Paulus et al. 2024); they also demonstrate that linked advisors impact the nature of services provided to farmers, in terms of content and integration of sustainability issues (Wuepper et al. 2021). Other studies show that farmers with alternative production systems, for instance a strong focus on

⁵https://scar-europe.org/images/SCAR-Documents/Reports_outcomes_studies/AKIS3_Report_Exploring_digitalisation_for_future_AKIS_final.pdf

⁶ This inventory was implemented within the Fairshare project: <https://fairshare-pnf.eu/>

agroecology, might rely on different intermediaries, often more informal and local (Šūmane et al. 2018).

In total, these two research areas, the development of multi-actor approaches (Living Labs, etc.) to design and assess digital innovation on the one hand, and research on AKIS and intermediary actors on the other hand, are hardly connected. The aim of the two next section is to better learn about the nature of intermediary actors that are connected (or not) to Living Labs initiatives, such as the ones developed in Codecs.

Insight from the AKIS mapping exercises implemented in Codecs Living Labs (WP3)

In Codecs, we defined AKIS as mental constructions (consistently with EU policy framework). A consequence of such perspective is that it is very important to understand the convergences and divergences in AKIS representations by different actors and from different perspectives. Discrepancies between representations could result in some inefficiencies that are documented by research in other sectors, including the low uptake of policy measures, or network failures (Crespo et al. 2014). Such research often calls for diagnostics about the potentialities of components and intermediary of innovation systems. A first insight on the relation between Living Labs, AKIS policy and innovation intermediaries was provided by WP3 through a mapping exercise. Concretely, workshops were organised in 19 Living Labs and participants were asked to draw ecosystems of actors and AKIS policies. Three main findings can be highlighted about Living Lab participants' representations of AKIS.

a) The mapping exercises confirm the growing role of private firms (IT, upstream and downstream) in AKIS.

This is evident in the number of private firms mentioned among the AKIS actors identified by LL participants. In total, 330 actors were mentioned in the mapping exercise, which were sorted into six categories (see Figure A): 1) Famers and farmers' associations, 2) Research and Education, 3) Bridging organisations (including advisory suppliers), 4) Public authorities, 5) Private companies and 6) Family and business.

Private firms were highly cited, more than the traditional AKIS actors which are placed at the centre in traditional AKIS analysis (Knierim et al. 2015), inventories and policies, such as research organisations or bridging organisations (typically advisory organisations). A second key learning is to disentangle between organisations. Whereas AgTech companies and Start-up are well represented (actually more than advisors or researchers) as one could expect (from the perspective of participants to a LL dealing with digital technologies), upstream and downstream companies of the supply chain are also very well represented. Financial organisations are also present in AKIS representations.

These results could be interesting for policy making by showcasing a form of disconnection between a traditional representation of AKIS centred on public authorities, research and bridging organisations and a representation of Living Lab participants that is more focused on private firms and farmers. This is even more evident when we compare the organisations that actually participate to the LL and organisations that LL participants considered as part of AKIS.

b) The mapping exercises reveal the proximity and role played by different actors regarding Living Labs initiatives.

During the mapping exercise, a question was added to assess how close AKIS actors are from the Living Labs. When citing AKIS actors, Living Labs participants could assess the proximity between these actors and the Living Lab. They had three options⁷ represented on Figure B: 1) the cited actor participates to the LL ("in LL" in Figure B); 2) the actor collaborates to the LL or as the potential to do so ("Close to the LL" in Figure B); 3) the actor has an influence in AKIS but is not close to the LL ("Not so close the LL" in Figure B).

Three results can be highlighted. First, some actors both are considered as key AKIS actors and are well represented in LL or considered as close to the LL. This is the case of some classic actors, like research, and, to a lesser extent advice. This is also true for farmers, but not for famers' organisations that hardly participate to LL. IT firms are also well acknowledged as key AKIS actors. Another striking result is related to actors that are mentioned as key AKIS players but that do not participate to the Living Labs. This is the case of public authorities.

⁷ Some participants hesitated about the position of some actors and pick two options, hence the two categories "in between" that we have added for participants that selected two options, in order to avoid double counts.

They are the most mentioned AKIS actors across Living Labs, but have a very limited participation in LL. Overall, this analysis might give the impression of a segmentation: LL are primarily co-design approaches where farmers, researchers and IT firms collaborate to develop and test digital technologies. Bridging organisations (advice, institutional networks), public authorities or consumers play a more limited role and are portrayed as potential partners for further activities. However, such results might be considered with caution as they hide a strong diversity of situations across LL.

c) The mapping exercise reveals the proximity and role played by different actors regarding Living Labs initiatives.

We are aware that the situation above could be the results of the aggregation of a strong diversity of situations across Living Labs. By having a closer look to the inventories implemented in each Living Lab, we could identify three types of representations of AKIS across Living Labs (Figure C1, Figure C2, Figure C3).

- Group 1 – Firm-led representation of AKIS: the first group comprises the mapping exercises implemented in 5 Living Labs (Figure C1) of four different countries (Belgium, Czech Republic, Italy and Spain). The main characteristic of the representation of AKIS in this group is the strong presence of firms (IT firms, upstream firms, and to a lesser extent, downstream firms). Firms are the most represented actors both in the overall AKIS and in the participation to the Labs. This is coherent with the fact that the aim of the Living Lab relates directly with economic issues: productivity, efficiency, or value creation. The aim of the labs might be to contribute to technology development and dissemination through direct collaborations between researchers, industries and farmers. Traditional bridging organisations of AKIS seems to be rather positioned in second line.
- Group 2 - Policy-Driven representation of AKIS: the second group gathers the mapping exercises implemented in 5 Living Labs (Figure C2) of five different countries of Eastern Europe (Estonia, Latvia, North Macedonia, Poland, Slovenia). The main characteristics of the representation of AKIS in this group is that Public Authorities are the most cited actor of AKIS. However, whereas they are noticed as actors of AKIS that could have indirect effects on digital innovation, they are hardly mentioned as members of any of the 5 Codecs LL of this group. This might be the expression of a representation in which AKIS is primarily seen as public policy instrument supported by public authorities, whereas LL contribute more directly to digital innovation by connecting farmers and intermediaries. The aim of the five LL of the group are diverse (productivity, efficiency, resources, value creation). Hence, the importance of public authorities might be rather partly explained by the national context of Eastern European countries where the emergence of the AKIS concept was more recently introduced in a rather top-down manner in recent reforms of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).
- Group 3 – Policy-driven representation of AKIS: the third group gathers the mapping exercises implemented in 7 Living Labs (Figure C3) of six countries (Germany, France, Hungary, Serbia, Slovakia, Scotland). The characteristics of this group is that the representation better reflects the pluralistic perspective of AKIS that is often presented as the main characteristics of these systems in Europe (Knierim et al. 2015), typically in countries such as Germany, France and Hungary. These countries are also characterised by public investments in bridging organisation (including networks and farm advisory services such as chambers of agriculture, Krierim et al. 2016), hence the importance of these organisations in AKIS representation in these contexts. These bridging organisations are also present in the LL. This might also be related to the aim of the seven Living Labs, which include more directly sustainability missions that are supported by public policies and by public bridging organisations themselves (including the maintenance of natural resources or the development of social and human capital in rural areas).

In total, the mapping exercise reveals the diversity of representation of AKIS across Living Labs, according to contexts and aims of the LL. An implication is that there could be discrepancies in AKIS representations between actors, which could in turn limit the uptake of AKIS measures and the willingness of certain actors to participate, or on the opposite, the ability of certain actors to instrumentalise the measures to their benefits.

Insights from a qualitative survey with innovation intermediaries

As stated in the introduction of this section, a major aim of this task was to contribute to a reality check of innovation intermediaries. Recently, public innovation policies have emphasised the need for better networks and coordination within AKIS, the need for shared knowledge hubs and reservoirs, etc. However, to do so, there is a need to better understand who the intermediary actors within AKIS are, what are these functions, activities and resources. Having better understood the AKIS representation from the perspective of LL participants thanks to WP3 inventory, we next tried to better characterise the actors they mentioned as AKIS actors, for a limited number of Living Labs. To characterize intermediaries, we combined four dimensions: 1) the intermediary functions played by actors, 2) the economic model of these organisations, 3) their knowledge networks, and 4) their relations to AKIS related policies.

To do so, we collectively designed a questionnaire that combine different empirical and theoretical insights from recent research on AKIS and innovation intermediaries (see appendix for the questionnaire and the precise description of the variables):

- To capture the functions played by intermediaries, we relied on two types of literature: a specific literature on innovation support in the agricultural sector (Faure et al. 2019, Sutherland et Labarthe 2022), to distinguish between the stages of innovation when intermediaries are active, and a more generic literature on the functions played by intermediaries, especially the seminal work of Howells (2006). We identified the following functions
 - Ex-ante types of innovation support services: building networks, awareness, scanning information, foresight thinking,
 - In-itinere types of innovation support services: prototyping, brokering, testing, training,
 - Ex-post types of innovation support, services: evaluation, standard settings, intellectual protection (patents), etc.
- To capture the economic model of intermediaries, we used the literature on Knowledge and Innovation Business Intermediaries (KIBS), defined by Consoli and Elche-Hortelano (2010, p. 1303), as “intermediary firms [organisations] specialised in knowledge screening, assessment, evaluation and [which] trade their services in the form of consultancy”. This literature has already been applied to characterise intermediaries in the agricultural sector (Klerkx and Leeuwis 2008). It enables to extract relevant variables already used in former qualitative or quantitative analysis to describe the variety of economic rationale of service providers for farmers (Dhiab et al. 2020, Prager et al. 2016), including:
 - The main source of income of the organisation,
 - The nature of interaction for coproducing knowledge with clients (in our case: farmers): individual one-to-one advice, group sessions, training, remote services, etc.
 - The conception of the productivity of employee’s labour (working with many farmers per advisor versus personalising services for few advisors),
 - The distribution of labour time between these direct interactions with clients (front-office) and time dedicated to updating the knowledge embedded in services (back-office: R&D, scientific watch, staff training, etc.).
- To capture the integration of the intermediary organisations within AKIS, we asked whether and which different types of actors were major partners for knowledge exchange. Following the classification of the main actors already discussed in previous sections and proposed in WP3 inventories, we considered the following actors:
 - Public Research
 - Industries (upstream, downstream and from the digital technologies sector)
 - Bridging organisations, including advisory services (public extension and private advice)

- Public authorities
- Farmers and Farmer Based Organisations
- To capture the relations of intermediaries with innovation public policies, we used three variables about policy frameworks and funding.
 - From a financial perspective, we asked whether public funds was a major source or revenue of the organisation,
 - From a broader perspective, we asked whether the organisation was integrated in any innovation policy framework (European, national or regional),
 - From a more precise perspective related to digitalisation, we asked how close the organisation was from Living Labs.

Before presenting the results, it should be noted that the aim of this analysis is not to provide a representative description of intermediation in European AKIS. This task is qualitative and exploratory. We used a purposive sampling procedure (Etikan et al. 2016) to better understand the role and place of Living Labs within AKIS policies, in the specific case of sustainable digitalisation of the agricultural sector. In other words, we purposely used Codecs Living Labs as a sampling device to understand the types of intermediary functions, and KIBS models that contribute to LL, and their relations to other AKIS actors. We used a bottom-up approach that starts from the Living Lab perspective to identify complementarities, synergies and discrepancies within AKIS. In short, what kind of intermediaries and intermediations do Living Lab attract or not?

Consistently with this bottom-up approach, we did not use a quantitative explanatory model (such as econometrics) nor a classification, but we rather opted for a Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA, Abdi and Valentin 2007). To perform the MCA, we used the packages FactoMinR of the R software (Husson et al. 2007). The aim is not building a typology (as we do not have enough respondents to be representative of national situations) but understanding what variables explain most of the diversity and inertia about the four dimensions mentioned above for the intermediary actors identified by the participants to Codecs LL.

In this current version, we used data from 33 observations, from 3 countries (Latvia, Germany and Italy). This figure can be perceived as low. First, it reflects one of our results: a form of disconnect between LL and AKIS. Hence, it was not easy to reach AKIS actors through LL. Second, as we wanted to stick to our methodology of using LL as sampling device, we did not want to increase the number of observations artificially by using snowball procedures. Third, the size of the sample does not cause any problem with the statistical test that we used, as MCA does not require any minimal size of sample. We were careful with the conditions of the test: we checked that the number of modalities of variables was inferior to the number of observations, and that the number of observations was above 20% for each modality. We also made various tests with different variables to check for robustness. However, the results of the test should not be considered as representative of explanatory but as an image of variables explaining the diversity of intermediaries, KIBS models, and AKIS relations, when considered from the perspective of LL aiming to support a sustainable digitalisation.

A first striking result is that the variables that explain most of the total inertia (first and second axis of the MCA) are variables describing intermediary functions. The first axis opposed organisations that do implement intermediary functions and those that do not. The analysis enables to distinguish three groups of modalities (Figure D) that most explain the diversity of positions and perception of organisations.

- The first group (in red on Figure D) is the one that is the most closely related to participation in Living Labs. Four key aspects of this group can be noted.
 - In terms of intermediary functions, this group correspond to ex-ante or in-itinere innovation support services, such as Foresight, Scanning, Testing or Disseminating,
 - In terms of KIBS features, there are strong investments in back-office, but hardly any investment in front-office for providing personalised advice to farmers,

- In terms of AKIS network, the knowledge exchanges are primarily with private firms from the digital technology sector,
- In terms of public policies, not only the actor participate to Living Labs, but they are also well integrated in other public policy frameworks supporting innovation.
- The second group (in blue on Figure D) is characterised by its contribution to the evaluation of digital technologies.
 - In terms of intermediary functions, the only function associated with this group corresponds indeed to ex-post evaluation of technologies,
 - In terms of KIBS features, this group is characterised by some front-office activities (but not the more personalised for farmers), but which are not commercialised to farmers,
 - In terms of AKIS network, this group shows the most diversified relations, with strong interaction with advisory organisations, public research and industries (upstream or downstream),
 - In terms of public policies, this group is further away from Living Labs and Innovation Public Policies, but nevertheless show some dependency upon public subsidies.
- The third group has some very specific features, characterised by the lack of investment in any intermediary functions but strong front-office activities (in yellow on Figure D).
 - In terms of intermediary functions, this group is indeed characterised by the lack of commitment to any of the five intermediary functions integrated in the analysis (foresight, scanning, testing, dissemination, evaluation),
 - In terms of KIBS features, this group is characterised by the highest level of personalisation of services, and a strong proportion of organisations selling services to farmers,
 - In terms of AKIS network, this group is characterised by the strongest distance with any other AKIS actor,
 - In terms of public policy, this group is also the one further away from LL, innovation public policies or public financial support.

In total, the MCA analysis reveals some complementarities between three groups of variables characterising intermediary function, KIBS economic models, AKIS networks and link to innovation public policies. The first group seems to reflect the role of Living Labs for the co-design of digital technologies, with a focus on foresight and testing, associated to investments in back-office, thanks to relations with firms from the digital/IT sector, and thanks to the participation to instruments of innovation public policy. The second group corresponds to more traditional R&D activities aimed at evaluating digital technologies, with relations with public research, bridging organisations and industries, and with the support of public funds. The third group corresponds to organisations that provide advisory services to farmers (often for a fee), but that are far away from any other intermediary function and from public funds and instruments.

Summary of findings

These results could be analysed as complementary representations of actors about instruments and functions within AKIS: Living Labs to develop and test digital technologies, Multi-actor R&D approaches to evaluate them, and Farm Advisory Services to support farmers in their decision to use or not technologies. But there is also a risk of disconnect and segmentation, which has already been identified in former studies (Dhiab et al. 2020, Klerkx and Proctor 2013, Knuth and Knierim 2013, Labarthe and Nettle 2025). The representation of AKIS from certain Living Lab participants, who associate AKIS as public authorities matter and LL as a device to interact with industries could also point to this risk of segmentation. The question of better bridging AKIS actors involved in scanning and evaluation digital technologies and those proposing personalised services remains open. Some further analysis and policy debates would be needed to assess situations at various scales (including national or regional), as data from WP3 indicate differences across contexts.

Figures

In this section, we present the figures derived both from WP3 and from WP6.

- Figure A presents the number of actors mentioned by LL participants during the mapping exercise according to the categories of AKIS actors (source WP3 AKIS mapping exercise)
- Figure B presents the distance of AKIS actors to the LL (source: WP3 AKIS mapping exercise) (source WP3 AKIS mapping exercise)
- Figure C1 presents the Perception of AKIS across Codecs LL for the group of Living Labs sharing a “Firm-led representation of AKIS”, with indication of the aims of the LL (source: WP3 AKIS mapping exercise)
- Figure C2 presents the Perception of AKIS across Codecs LL for the group of Living Labs sharing a “Policy-driven representation of AKIS”, with indication of the aims of the LL (source: WP3 AKIS mapping exercise)
- Figure C2 presents the Perception of AKIS across Codecs LL for the group of Living Labs sharing a “Pluralistic representation of AKIS”, with indication of the aims of the LL (source: WP3 AKIS mapping exercise)
- Figure D presents the results of the MCA analysis

Figure A: Number of actors mentioned by LL participants during the mapping exercise according to the categories of AKIS actors (source WP3 AKIS mapping exercise)

Legend: Y-axis: number of times this type of organisation was cited during the mapping exercise

Figure B: Distance of AKIS actors to the LL (source: WP3 AKIS mapping exercise)
(source WP3 AKIS mapping exercise)

Legend: Y-axis: number of times this type of organisation was cited during the mapping exercise

- In LL (orange): the actors were mentioned as being part of the LL
- In between (yellow): the actors were mentioned as both being part of the LL and close to the LL
- Close to the LL (dark blue): the actors were mentioned as being close to the LL
- In between (light blue): the actors were mentioned as both being close to the LL and no so close
- Not so close (grey): the actors were mentioned as not so close from the Lab

Figure C1: Perception of AKIS across Codecs LL for the group “Firm-led” representation of AKIS (source: WP3 AKIS mapping exercise)

Legend - Goal of the Living Lab:

Productivity	Efficiency	Resources	Value creation	Social & human capital
--------------	------------	-----------	----------------	------------------------

Legend (Y-axis): number of times the actors was cited as included in the LL (blue line) or as part of AKIS (orange)

Figure C2: Perception of AKIS across Codescs LL for the group “Policy driven” representation of AKIS (source: WP3 AKIS mapping exercise)

Legend - Goal of the Living Lab:				
Productivity	Efficiency	Resources	Value creation	Social & human capital

Legend (Y-axis): number of times the actors was cited as included in the LL (blue line) or as part of AKIS (orange)

Figure C3: Perception of AKIS across Codecs LL for the group “Pluralistic” representation of AKIS (source: WP3 AKIS mapping exercise)

Legend (Y-axis): number of times the actors was cited as included in the LL (blue line) or as part of AKIS (orange)

Figure D: Results of the MCA analysis (source: the authors)

References cited in this annex

- Abdi, H., & Valentin, D. (2007). Multiple correspondence analysis. *Encyclopedia of measurement and statistics*, 2(4), 651-657.
- Bechtet, N. (2023). How do advisory suppliers support farmers in evaluating a digital innovation? A case study on decision support tools for fertilizer application in France. *Journal of Innovation Economics & Management*, 42(3), 73-101.
- Busse, M., Schwerdtner, W., Siebert, R., Doernberg, A., Kuntosch, A., König, B., & Bokelmann, W. (2015). Analysis of animal monitoring technologies in Germany from an innovation system perspective. *Agricultural Systems*, 138, 55-65.
- Cofré-Bravo, G., Klerkx, L., Engler, A. (2019). Combinations of bonding, bridging, and linking social capital for farm innovation: How farmers configure different support networks. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 69, 53-64.
- Consoli, D., & Elche-Hortelano, D. (2010). Variety in the knowledge base of Knowledge Intensive Business Services. *Research Policy*, 39(10), 1303-1310.
- Crespo, J., Suire, R., & Vicente, J. (2014). Lock-in or lock-out? How structural properties of knowledge networks affect regional resilience. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 14(1), 199-219.
- Dhiab, H., Labarthe, P., & Laurent, C. (2020). How the performance rationales of organisations providing farm advice explain persistent difficulties in addressing societal goals in agriculture. *Food Policy*, 95, 101914.
- Etikan, I., Musa, S. A., & Alkassim, R. S. (2016). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American journal of theoretical and applied statistics*, 5(1), 1-4.
- Faure, G., Knierim, A., Koutsouris, A., Ndah, H. T., Audouin, S., Zarokosta, E., ... Heanue, K. (2019). How to strengthen innovation support services in agriculture with regard to multi-stakeholder approaches. *Journal of Innovation Economics & Management*, 28(1), 145-169.
- Fieldsend, A. F., Cronin, E., Varga, E., Biró, S., Rogge, E. (2021). 'Sharing the space' in the agricultural knowledge and innovation system: multi-actor innovation partnerships with farmers and foresters in Europe. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 27(4), 423-442.
- Howells, J. (2024). Innovation intermediaries in a digital paradigm: A theoretical perspective. *Technovation*, 129, 102889.
- Husson, F., Josse, J., Le, S., & Mazet, J. (2007). FactoMineR: An R package for multivariate analysis. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 25(1), 1-18.
- Kernecker, M., Busse, M., Knierim, A. (2021). "Exploring actors, their constellations, and roles in digital agricultural innovations." *Agricultural Systems*, 186, 102952
- Kivimaa, P., Boon, W., Hyysalo, S., Klerkx, L. (2019). Towards a typology of intermediaries in sustainability transitions: A systematic review and a research agenda. *Research policy*, 48(4), 1062-1075.
- Klerkx, L., Begemann, S. (2020). Supporting food systems transformation: The what, why, who, where and how of mission-oriented agricultural innovation systems. *Agricultural Systems*, 184, 102901.
- Klerkx, L., Leeuwis, C. (2008). Matching demand and supply in the agricultural knowledge infrastructure: Experiences with innovation intermediaries. *Food policy*, 33(3), 260-276.
- Klerkx, L., Petter Stræte, E., Kvam, G. T., Ystad, E., & Butli Hårstad, R. M. (2017). Achieving best-fit configurations through advisory subsystems in AKIS: case studies of advisory service provisioning for diverse types of farmers in Norway. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 23(3), 213-229.
- Klerkx, L., Proctor, A. (2013). Beyond fragmentation and disconnect: Networks for knowledge exchange in the English land management advisory system. *Land use policy*, 30(1), 13-24.
- Knierim, A., Boenning, K., Caggiano, M., Cristóvão, A., Dirimanova, V., Koehnen, T., ... & Prager, K. (2015). The AKIS concept and its relevance in selected EU member states. *Outlook on Agriculture*, 44(1), 29-36.
- Knuth, U., Knierim, A. (2013). Characteristics of and challenges for advisors within a privatized extension system. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 19(3), 223-236.
- Kvam, G. T., Hårstad, R. M. B., Stræte, E. P. (2022). The role of farmers' microAKIS at different stages of uptake of digital technology. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 28(5), 671-688.
- Labarthe, P., Beck, M. (2022). CAP and advisory services: from farm advisory systems to innovation support. *EuroChoices*, 21(1), 5-14.

- Labarthe P., Nettle R. (2025). A new dynamics in extension privatisation: exploring the role of “linked suppliers” in Australia and Europe. Presentation at the 27th European Seminar on Extension and Education. Vila Real, Portugal, July 2025.
- Madureira, L., Labarthe, P., Marques, C. S., Santos, G. (2022). Exploring microAKIS: farmer-centric evidence on the role of advice in agricultural innovation in Europe. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 28(5), 549-575.
- Mruštíková Konečná, M., Sutherland, L. A. (2022). Digital innovations in the Czech Republic: developing the inner circle of the Triggering Change Model. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 28(5), 577-600.
- Paulus, M., Herrera, B., Knierim, A. (2024). Who do German farmers trust when making decisions about digital technologies? An analysis of the trustworthiness of innovation actors. *Studies in Agricultural Economics*, 126(3).
- Prager, K., Labarthe, P., Caggiano, M., Lorenzo-Arribas, A. (2016). How does commercialisation impact on the provision of farm advisory services? Evidence from Belgium, Italy, Ireland and the UK. *Land Use Policy*, 52, 329-344.
- Šūmane, S., Kunda, I., Knickel, K., Strauss, A., Tisenkopfs, T., des los Rios, I., ... Ashkenazy, A. (2018). Local and farmers' knowledge matters! How integrating informal and formal knowledge enhances sustainable and resilient agriculture. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 59, 232-241.
- Sutherland, L. A., Adamsone-Fiskovica, A., Elzen, B., Koutsouris, A., Laurent, C., Stræte, E. P., & Labarthe, P. (2023). Advancing AKIS with assemblage thinking. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 97, 57-69.
- Sutherland, L. A., Labarthe, P. (2022). Introducing ‘microAKIS’: a farmer-centric approach to understanding the contribution of advice to agricultural innovation. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 28(5), 525-547.
- Wuepper, D., Roleff, N., Finger, R. (2021). Does it matter who advises farmers? Pest management choices with public and private extension. *Food Policy*, 99, 101995.

Questionnaire

The questionnaire was elaborated jointly between the participants of task T6.2.

It was then diffused by using the tool EU survey.

Below are the screenshots of the different pages of the questionnaire.

Survey on Living Labs for agriculture (European Research Project CODECS)

Disclaimer ✕

The European Commission is not responsible for the content of questionnaires created using the EUSurvey service - it remains the sole responsibility of the form creator and manager. The use of EUSurvey service does not imply a recommendation or endorsement, by the European Commission, of the views expressed within them.

Pages

Presentation of the survey	[Your organisation]	[Role in digital innovation]	[Networks, Living Labs]	[Your services]	[Free comments]
----------------------------	---------------------	------------------------------	-------------------------	-----------------	-----------------

CODECS - Questionnaire on innovation intermediaries for digital innovation for farmers

The aim of this questionnaire is to better understand and acknowledge the role of your organisation in developing and disseminating digital innovation for farmers.

This questionnaire is part of the European project CODECS. CODECS will develop, and turn into concepts, methods, tools, evidence, a vision of "sustainable digitalisation" with the goal of improving the collective capacity to understand, assess and foresee the full range of benefits and costs of farm digitalisation, and to build digital ecosystems that maximise the net benefits of digitalisation.

The questionnaire enables us to also collect your opinion on the role of Living Labs and European innovation Policy in the digitalisation of agriculture.

The questionnaire has 25 questions and can be completed in less than 15 minutes.
Data will be used only for research purposes and will be stored in a secured data repository.

For more information about CODECS project please visit: <https://www.horizoncodecs.eu/>

Responsibility for the survey: Pierre Labarthe, Research at the French National Institute of Research on Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE) pierre.labarthe@inrae.fr

Next

Pages

[Presentation of the survey](#)[\[Your organisation\]](#)[\[Role in digital innovation\]](#)[\[Networks, Living Labs\]](#)[\[Your services\]](#)[\[Free comments\]](#)

General characterisation of your organisation

- In which **country** is the **head office** of your organisation located?

-
- When was your organisation created? (**year of creation**)

-
- How many people work for your organisation? (**number of employees**)

-
- What is the **status** of your organisation?

- A public organisation
- A private company
- An association
- Other

-
- Is your organization **controlled or owned by farmers**?

- Yes
- No

-
- What is the **scale of operation** of your organisation?

- International
- National
- Local

Pages

- Presentation of the survey
- [Your organisation]
- [Role in digital innovation]
- [Networks, Living Labs]
- [Your services]
- [Free comments]

Your contribution to digital innovation for farmers

- At which **stage of innovation process does your organisation operate** regarding digital technologies for farmers. Please rank the three options below

Use drag&drop or the up/down buttons to change the order or accept the initial order.

- :: ↑ ↓ **Initiation Phase** (helping to raise farmers' awareness about digitalisation, building networks, scanning information, foresight thinking...)
- :: ↑ ↓ **Implementation phase** (co-designing the technology, prototyping, testing, brokering, etc).
- :: ↑ ↓ **Dissemination phase** (evaluation, communication, commercialisation, standard settings, etc.)

- Does your organisation **play the following roles** regarding digital innovation?

	Yes, it is a major activity or our organisation	Yes but it is only a minor activity or our organisation	Not at all	The meaning of this function is not clear to me
Foresight & diagnostics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Scanning and information processing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Gatekeeping and brokering	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Testing and validation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Accreditation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Regulation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Protecting the results, managing intellectual property, patents	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Commercialisation and Dissemination	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Evaluation of outcomes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Pages

Networks, Living Labs and Innovation Policies

• Does your organisation **exchange knowledge with the following organisations?**

	Major partner for knowledge exchange	Minor partner for knowledge exchange	Not a partner at all
University and public research institution	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Private research organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consultants and knowledge brokers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Upstream firms (e.g., seed, chemicals, machinery)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Downstream firms (e.g., agrifood sector)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Tech sector (platforms, start-ups, sensors, apps, software)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Public authorities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Farmers' organisations (e.g., cooperatives, associations, unions, applied research stations)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Individual farmers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Public advisory organisations for farmers (e.g., chambers of agriculture, public extension department)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Private advisory organisation for farmers (e.g., freelance advisors, consultancy group for farmers)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

• Do you **participate to a Living Lab for digital innovation for farmers?**

	Major Partners: we are in the Living Lab	Minor Partners: we are close to the Living Labs but only participate in some events	Not a Partner but we know the Living Lab	We don't know the Living Lab
Codecs Living Lab	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Another Living Lab for innovation in agriculture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

• What are **the benefits or limitations of Living Labs to support digital innovation** for farmers?

• Do you **benefit from European, national or regional innovation public policies?**

- Yes
 No

• What is **your perception about the role of national or European AKIS policies?**

Pages

- Presentation of the survey
- [Your organisation]
- [Role in digital innovation]
- [Networks, Living Labs]
- [Your services]
- [Free comments]

Your service activity for the agricultural sector

• What is the **main source of income of your organisation?**

- Selling services (e.g., advice, etc.)
- Software as services (SAAS) or selling apps
- Selling inputs (e.g., seeds, fertilizers, etc.)
- Trading agricultural commodities (e.g., cereals, mils, meat, fruits, vegetables, etc.)
- Selling equipment (e.g., machinery, sensors, etc.)
- Public subsidies
- Farmers' contribution
- Certification

• Who are **your most important clients?** Please rank

Use drag&drop or the up/down buttons to change the order or accept the initial order.

- ☰ ↑ ↓ Farmers
- ☰ ↑ ↓ Farm employees
- ☰ ↑ ↓ Farm advisors
- ☰ ↑ ↓ Public authorities
- ☰ ↑ ↓ Private companies
- ☰ ↑ ↓ Researchers

• Do any of your staff interacts directly with farmers?

- Yes
 No

• How many of your staff work in direct contact with farmers (front of office)?

• Could you indicate the approximate average number of farmers served per advisor/facilitator?

- None
 Less than 25 farmers per advisor
 Between 25 and 100
 More than 100

• How do your staff interact with farmers? Please rank

Use drag&drop or the up/down buttons to change the order or accept the initial order.

⋮	↑ ↓	No interaction
⋮	↑ ↓	Individual 1-to1
⋮	↑ ↓	With groups of farmers
⋮	↑ ↓	Remotely (through apps, software)
⋮	↑ ↓	Social media

- **Do you have advisors dedicated to back-office or R&D tasks** (experimentation, scientific monitoring, R&D projects, etc.)?

- Yes
 No

- **How many people of your staff are dedicated to R&D activities** (back-office: experiments, scientific watch, etc.)

-
- **What are the most important R&D activities that you implement in back-office?** Please rank

Use drag&drop or the up/down buttons to change the order or accept the initial order.

⌵ ⬆ ⬇ Scientific experiments
⌵ ⬆ ⬇ Modelling
⌵ ⬆ ⬇ Reviews
⌵ ⬆ ⬇ Training
⌵ ⬆ ⬇ Codesign / User X

Annex 6: Country Profiles⁸

⁸ Indicators draw on several official sources and close reference years (see Section 2. Methodology). Small differences can appear due to rounding, revisions, or concept differences.

Belgium

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
30,667 km ²	11,832,049	385.8 people/km ²	1.8%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
5,415,520	5.7%	76.1 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
613,984 million EUR	51,810 EUR	0.6%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)				
Agriculture: 44.6%; forest: 22.6%; other: 32.8%				
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops	
1,362 K ha	868 K ha (63.7%)	472 K ha (34.7%)	22 K ha (1.6%)	
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)				
1,080 ha (0.1% UAA)				
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)	
36,000	52,396 EUR/AWU		4%	
Type of Farms (2020)				
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms		
81.76%		18.24%		
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size	
38 ha	37 ha		40 ha	
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)				
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms		
190,142 EUR		428,045 EUR		
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)				
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)
2,250 (6.25%)	5,140 (14.27%)	9,550 (26.52%)	14,780 (41.04%)	4,290 (11.91%)

Labour Force (AWU) (2020)		Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)	
52.09 K		Basic: 29% (EU: 18%)	Full: 23% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)
54.9%	6.3%	0.11	14% (EU: 28%)

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
94.87% (EU: 91.67%)	59.39% (EU: 55.56%)	84.87% (EU: 74.71%)	56.9 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
93.8% (EU: 82.5%)	30.7% (EU: 69.2%)	96.9% (EU: 94.3%)	5.7% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
83.7% (EU: 72.9%)		64.2% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP^{9, 10}

Prioritisation Level

Flanders: Digitalisation is included under need N02 – Innovation (including digitisation), which is assigned a very high prioritisation level in the document. This reflects a strong strategic emphasis on digital technologies as part of the broader innovation agenda, highlighting their importance for the transformation and resilience of the agricultural sector in Flanders.

Wallonia: The NSP assigns a medium prioritisation level (4 out of 7) to Need X.13 – Encourage the use of digital tools. The focus is to support investments for farmers and for the forestry and timber sector to acquire digital tools, to reassure farmers about data protection and ownership when using digital and connected equipment, and to provide clear guidance and advice on both equipment choices and practical use. The Plan also aims to encourage the uptake of digital tools in rural areas, particularly through the LEADER measure.

Description and operational detail of AKIS and digitalisation within the NSPs

Flanders: A multipronged strategy aims to improve the economic and environmental performance of Flemish agriculture by developing future oriented digital skills through training and demonstration projects, raising awareness of precision technologies, and integrating e learning and digital alert systems. Adoption is promoted via platforms such as DJustConnect and Soil Passport, which enhance data interoperability and access to support decision making and sustainable practice. Digitalisation is pursued not only through technology deployment but also by reshaping advisory models, business strategies, and organisational structures. Investment support is provided through the Flemish Agricultural Investment Fund (VLIF) and European Innovation Partnerships, with projects that showcase digital applications in practice. These efforts are reinforced by complementary research under Horizon Europe and national funding schemes, embedding digital transformation within the broader AKIS and CAP intervention ecosystem.

Wallonia: The NSP leverages strong regional connectivity and mandatory e-government tools such as PAC-on-Web, while addressing digital gaps and slow on-farm uptake. Operationally, it aims to mobilise Pillar II investments for digital technologies, with operational groups piloting solutions, and use the AKIS platform to connect advisers and farmers on smart farming, decision support and data protection. Furthermore, through Wallonia's Recovery Plan it rolls out a set of complementary projects, including a Réseau Vitrine and DuraTechFarm to integrate and assess smart farming in conventional and organic systems, data exchange and management platforms via the WalDigiFarm association and the WALLeSMART platform, data security and legislative measures via OpenAgro4.1, the mobile laboratory MOBILAB to demonstrate innovative sensors and analysers, and enhancement of Agromet.be using farmers' connected micro-stations.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

Flanders: Although the alignment with other CAP priorities is not always explicit, digitalisation is not treated as a

⁹ Agency for Agriculture and Fisheries (n.d.). *Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023-2027: general framework*. Retrieved from <https://lv.vlaanderen.be/beleid/landbouwbeleid-eu/gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid-glb/2023-2027-algemeen-kader> (Accessed: 119 September 2025)

¹⁰ Government of Wallonia (n.d.). *CAP Strategic Plan - 2023-2027*. Retrieved from <https://agriculture.wallonie.be/plan-strategique-pac-2023-2027> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

standalone goal. It is systematically embedded to reinforce climate action, biodiversity, resilience, and socio-economic development, reflecting a cross cutting, enabling strategy consistent with the CAP vision for sustainable agriculture. The NSP promotes a coherent and applied digital innovation agenda across innovation, knowledge exchange, and sustainable farm management, closely linked to funding instruments and policy objectives.

Wallonia: Digitalisation is explicitly aligned with multiple CAP priorities. It supports competitiveness and economic resilience by funding smart farming equipment and data platforms, with second pillar aid prioritising digital investments that add value to the green architecture and to farm resilience. It advances environmental and climate goals through decision support for nutrient management and agrometeorology upgrades that steer input reduction and climate smart practices. Furthermore, it contributes to social inclusion and balanced rural development to stimulate digital uptake in rural areas and by addressing the digital divide with Digital Wallonia actions and a strengthened network of public digital access points and mediation services.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

Flanders: Key areas include precision farming, remote sensing and mapping, big data and interoperability, automation and robotics, and smart advisory platforms with e-learning tools. The Plan distinguishes between Precision Agriculture 1.0, focused on parcel level data collection (for example, sensors and GPS mapping), and Precision Agriculture 2.0, which integrates these data into decision support and advisory services. The Soil Passport consolidates field level soil data to enable more sustainable and efficient soil management.

Wallonia: The document highlights the promotion of several specific digital technologies and innovations aimed at modernising Wallonia's agricultural sector. Key technologies include precision farming tools such as GPS-guided systems for mechanical weeding and binning, drones, camera-based systems, RTK precision systems, connected weather stations, and tele-scaling systems for tires to prevent soil compaction. In livestock farming, promoted innovations include robotics for milking and feeding, calving detection sensors, and surveillance equipment. Additionally, the document emphasizes decision-support tools like the REQUAFERT nitrogen advisory tool and the BELCAM satellite imaging platform, which processes Sentinel-2 data to support agricultural management. In addition, the Recovery Plan adds over 12 million euros for initiatives aimed at interoperability, practical demonstration, and integration within the AKIS.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

Flanders: The CAP NSP states that digital infrastructure does not differ across Flemish regions and that broadband coverage is nearly universal, including in rural areas. However, the document acknowledges disparities in digital engagement based on farm size and age, noting that precision agriculture is more frequently adopted by larger farms and that younger farmers are more likely to use digital tools. To mitigate these gaps, the government provides guidance through training and help desks, as well as targeted interventions such as demand-driven education and tailored advice, aiming to ensure that all farmers, regardless of region, sector, or personal familiarity with digital technologies, have equal access to CAP interventions. Demonstrations and peer-to-peer learning are also used to encourage adoption among less digitally experienced farmers.

Wallonia: The document treats digital inclusion and territorial equity as core enablers, recognising that around 20% of residents face access-related digital exclusion, with women, people over 65, and those with lower educational attainment most affected, and that connection quality is weaker in rural areas. The response combines infrastructure, mediation, and place-based action: DW Connect to report connectivity issues, an expanded network of Digital Public Spaces, and Recovery Plan measures that map services, equip households, train mediators, and support local actors. LEADER projects are used to encourage uptake in rural communities, while Digital Wallonia's Giga Region agenda aims to ensure that the benefits of digitalisation, such as smart farming technologies and e-government services, are accessible to all, thereby preventing territorial and social exclusion.

AKIS within the NSP

Flanders: While the term AKIS is not used as frequently as in other NSPs, its functions are clearly integrated into the strategic framework. The document identifies gaps in bridging research outcomes with education and advisory services, particularly in afterschool education and involvement of advisors in EIPs. The AKIS strategy is delineated into four core action areas: strengthening research-practice connections, advancing the competencies and integration of advisors, promoting thematic and cross-border innovation, and supporting digital transition to enhance knowledge dissemination. Multiple interventions are employed to operationalize these aims, including demand- and supply-driven education, demonstration projects, VLIF support, and EIPs. The AKIS framework also emphasizes the importance of networking, centralized access to training information, and improved navigation for farmers through the system.

Wallonia: Wallonia plans to strengthen its AKIS through the creation of a central hub to connect advisors, researchers, and farmers. This platform will include a directory of advisory bodies, a space for events and knowledge exchange, and a library of simplified research reports to accelerate the adoption of new practices. A dedicated administrative unit, funded by

CAP technical assistance, will manage, animate, and continuously refine the platform based on user feedback to identify gaps and overlaps. Complementary measures include promoting independent, conflict-free advice via adviser accreditation, and mobilising the CAP Network to pool expertise, back innovation and Operational Groups, and bridge the gap between research and practice. This approach is further reinforced by synergy with Wallonia's Recovery Plan, which adds initiatives such as pilot farm networking and targeted projects in agroecology, participatory research, forestry skills, biodiversity, and environmental education.

Monitoring and evaluation

Flanders: The NSP sets ambitious targets across several CAP result indicators: under R.1 Knowledge and innovation, 365,013 individuals are to benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in EIP operational groups; under R.2 Linking advisory and knowledge systems, 3,600 advisors will receive support to be integrated into the AKIS; under R.3 Digitisation of agriculture, 80.71 percent of farms are expected to receive CAP support for digital agricultural technology; under R.28 Environmental or climate performance through knowledge and innovation, 187,842 individuals are to benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or EIP participation to improve environmental or climate outcomes; and under R.40 Smart transition of the rural economy, 89 smart village strategies will be supported.

Wallonia: The NSP sets modest targets across several CAP result indicators. Under R.1 on knowledge and innovation, the Plan aims for 86 individuals to benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in EIP operational groups supported by the CAP. For R.2 on linking advisory and knowledge systems, the target is 18 advisors receiving support to be integrated into the AKIS. For R.3 on the digitisation of agriculture, 0.21 percent of farms are expected to receive CAP support for digital agricultural technology. Under R.28, which addresses environmental or climate performance through knowledge and innovation, 36 individuals are targeted to benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in EIP operational groups that improve environmental or climate related outcomes. For R.40 on the smart transition of the rural economy, no target is set.

AKIS Factsheet¹¹

Belgium has a complex political organisation with extensive regional responsibilities. In practice, this decentralisation yields two AKIS: one in Flanders and one in Wallonia. Both comprise a wide range of actors, each with distinct expertise. Both regions use delegated service delivery, with the Flemish and Walloon governments providing institutional support and issuing competitive calls. In Flanders, experimental stations sit at the centre of AKIS, linking applied research with the production sector, alongside the farmers unions. Numerous organisations and institutions are interconnected to varying degrees, making the Flemish AKIS broadly strong and integrated. In Wallonia, the pilot centres, "Collège des producteurs", and many other organisations and institutions form the backbone of AKIS. The region has substantial resources for knowledge exchange and farmer support, but the plurality of providers makes it hard to see who does what. Because of the lack of coherence and resonance between the different Walloon AKIS organisations, the Walloon AKIS can be considered as strong but rather fragmented.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- **About farm advice:** In both regions, a wide range of organisations provide advice and other services to farmers and play a central role in knowledge exchange. An exhaustive list is not feasible given their number. However, a key characteristic is the central role played by various farmer-based organisations, including associations and cooperatives.
- **About public policies:** The Flemish and Walloon governments support both AKIS through institutional funding and competitive calls. Their main tasks are to finance AKIS actors and to monitor and follow up on their activities. In Flanders, institutional support is concentrated on several large organisations, such as the Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), the experimental stations, and the universities. In Wallonia, a larger range of organisations receive institutional support, with the Walloon Agricultural Research Centre (CRA-W), the pilot centres, the "Collège des producteurs" and the farmer unions are the main beneficiaries. Delegation goes a step further in Wallonia, where maintenance of the Walloon CAP Network is outsourced to an external organisation.
- **Some trends:** In both contexts, AKIS policies place strong emphasis on strengthening linkages and knowledge exchange among actors. A key challenge is to further deepen the interface between advisory services and research.

¹¹ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the authors of the report: **Charlotte Lybaert** and **Lies Debruyne**. We thank them for their work. <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/LZ2P52AoT9aXNKe#pdfviewer>

AKIS in Flanders

AKIS in Wallonia

Czechia

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
78,871 km ²	10,900,555	138.2 people/km ²	25.3%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
5,541,179	2.6%	59.9 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
320,742 million EUR	29,440 EUR	0.7%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)				
Agriculture: 45.7%; forest: 34.7%; other: 19.5%				
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops	
3,530 K ha	2,485 K ha (70.4%)	1,003 K ha (28.4%)	42 K ha (1.2%)	
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)				
1,479,074 ha (42.0% UAA)				
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)	
28,910	17,220 EUR/AWU		8%	
Type of Farms (2020)				
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms		
83.57%		16.43%		
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size	
121 ha	37 ha		549 ha	
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)				
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms		
38,918 EUR		967,711EUR		
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)				
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)
11,070 (38.29%)	6,620 (22.90%)	5,920 (20.48%)	3,360 (11.62%)	1,920 (6.64%)

Labour Force (AWU) (2020)	Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)		
94.16 K	Basic: 18% (EU: 18%)		Full: 36% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)
46.1%	9.9%	0.22	12% (EU: 28%)

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
92.19% (EU: 91.67%)	69.11% (EU: 55.56%)	78.52% (EU: 74.71%)	57.1 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
53.9% (EU: 82.5%)	40.6% (EU: 69.2%)	99.1% (EU: 94.3%)	4.5% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
70.8% (EU: 72.9%)		43.1% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP¹²

Prioritisation Level

Digitalisation is given a low to medium level of priority. It is positioned mainly as an instrument to support productivity and environmental outcomes, particularly in relation to precision farming, emissions reduction, and advisory systems.

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

Digitalisation in Czechia's CAP NSP is anchored in national frameworks such as the Digital Czechia strategy and the National Plan for the Development of Very High-Capacity Networks. Digital Czechia is a set of concepts and implementation plans to ensure the conditions for the country's long-term prosperity in a rapidly digitising economy. The National Recovery Plan complements this by improving internet infrastructure, especially in rural areas, and by backing agricultural initiatives like smart and precision farming. Digitalisation is operationalised through specific tools and interventions, such as the integration of digital content in advisory training, the implementation of a Farm Nutrient Sustainability Tool, and investment support for precision agriculture, automation, and robotics. However, these measures are embedded within broader CAP intervention types rather than forming a dedicated digitalisation strategy for agriculture. As such, digitalisation is treated as a functional enabler rather than a standalone policy priority.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

Digital tools are framed as enablers of resource efficiency, climate adaptation, and knowledge-based growth. The document aligns its digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities by emphasizing the role of digital technologies in promoting sustainable agriculture, reducing environmental and climate impacts, and producing quality and safe food. The Plan links digitalisation to climate action through precision nitrogen management and technologies for applying organic and manure fertilisers that lower greenhouse gas and nitrogen emissions. It also supports socio-economic development by improving connectivity in underserved rural areas through infrastructure projects and by encouraging the digital transformation of enterprises. Furthermore, the document highlights the integration of digitalisation in research, innovation, and advisory services as part of broader efforts to strengthen resilience and improve the sustainability of agricultural and rural systems.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

The document promotes digital technologies and innovations under smart and precision agriculture to support sustainable resource management, efficient production, and lower environmental impacts. Supported interventions include tools for emissions monitoring, nutrient management, and remote sensing to guide sustainable practices; automation and robotisation in field operations; precision nitrogen technologies; and systems that apply organic and manure fertilisers directly to the soil to reduce losses and emissions. The Plan also introduces the Farm Nutrient Sustainability Tool as a digital application to be rolled out by 2024. These technologies are advanced through CAP interventions, notably investment support for agricultural enterprises and the work of EIP Operational Groups.

¹² Ministry of Agriculture (2022). *Strategic Plan of the Common Agricultural Policy of the Czech Republic for the Period 2023-2027 (version 1.3)*. Retrieved from <https://mze.gov.cz/public/portal/mze/dotace/szp-pro-obdobi-2021-2027/zakladni-informace/strategicky-plan-spolecne-zemedelske-1.html> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

The NSP identifies digital infrastructure gaps in rural and disadvantaged regions, but digital connectivity is addressed mainly via national and EU-level digital programmes, not CAP funding. Inclusiveness is supported through LEADER and Community-Led Local Development (CLLD), with support for local action groups (LAGs) to tailor solutions to local needs. Section P8.03 on the development of high-speed broadband in rural areas explicitly highlights the urban-rural divide, noting that many small and remote communities remain unattractive to commercial providers, which limits access and slows rural development. Complementing this, Section PX.01 on knowledge and cooperation within AKIS advances digital inclusion indirectly by expanding advisory and training services that build digital competencies, ensuring farmers and rural stakeholders can participate in the digital transformation.

AKIS within the NSP

A moderately detailed framework for AKIS is provided in the document. This framework addresses identified gaps and proposes strategic measures, including the creation of an AKIS Coordination Body, professional training for advisors, and support for European Innovation Partnership (EIP) Operational Groups. These efforts aim to improve knowledge exchange, advisory quality, and innovation uptake. Czechia's plan for 2023-2027 is built around addressing weaknesses identified in a SWOT analysis, particularly the insufficient capacity and topical coverage of independent advisors and weak integration among AKIS actors. Key measures include support under Pillar 2 of the CAP to renew counselling capacities, training to increase advisors' professional competence, and allowing non-accredited advisors to access AKIS. The system aims to foster better cooperation between research and practice, expand training topics, and enhance knowledge sharing through CAP Network activities, EIP Operational Groups, and demonstration farms. Certification of advisory bodies, accreditation of consultants, and the development of informal networks and technology platforms also form integral parts of the strategy.

Monitoring and evaluation

Czechia's NSP sets clear monitoring targets across relevant CAP result indicators. Under R.1 Knowledge and innovation, it aims for 39,991 participants in training or EIP Operational Groups. For R.2 Linking advisory and knowledge systems, the target is 480 advisors supported for integration into AKIS. R.3 Digitisation of agriculture sets a target of 0.67% of farms benefiting from digital support. Finally, under R.28 Environmental or climate performance through knowledge and innovation, 1,625 individuals are expected to benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or EIP participation to deliver better environmental or climate outcomes.

AKIS Factsheet¹³

The uniqueness of the Czech AKIS reflects the national farm structure, where very large farms coexist with many small ones. This wide variability requires advisory services that are diverse and tailored to different topics and farming systems. At the same time, the breadth of farm types and actors within AKIS creates coordination challenges. The EU sets broad requirements for the new AKIS coordination structure, leaving implementation to individual actors. However, limited capacity in some organisations, especially staff and time, hinders the coordination of new activities. Even so, the Czech AKIS is gradually strengthening the connections among its components.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- **About farm advice:** Advisory services, in their current form, were established between 1990 and 1992. Following major changes in the ownership of land and farm buildings after decollectivisation, legal advice and support for transformation issues predominated. The Ministry of Agriculture has since invested in funding, training, and certification schemes to develop farm advisory services. While public AKIS actors still play an important role, recent research indicates that the most important sources of advice are input and machinery suppliers, alongside peers and accredited advisors.
- **About public policies:** The state plays several important roles in AKIS: it supports funding schemes, trains and certifies advisors, sets up knowledge platforms, and sustains public research institutes. EU policy instruments have played, and continue to play, a central role in the dynamics of the Czech AKIS. Some measures have been harder to implement for administrative reasons, notably support for farm advisory services.
- **Some trends:** Two challenges stand out for the further development of AKIS: (1) developing indicators and procedures to delineate and monitor AKIS; and (2) anchoring a complex policy framework in the day-to-day realities of farm advisory services within a fragmented landscape.

¹³ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the author of the report: **Marta Mrnušík Konečná**. We thank her for her work. <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/MPqpgRn3DQaqdc#pdfviewer>

Estonia

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
45,336 km ²	1,374,687	30.3 people/km ²	44.5%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
756,167	7.6%	60.8 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
39,510 million EUR	28,740 EUR	0.6%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)				
Agriculture: 23.1%; forest: 57.1%; other: 19.9%				
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops	
984 K ha	707 K ha (71.8%)	273 K ha (27.7%)	4 K ha (0.4%)	
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)				
424,950 ha (43.1% UAA)				
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)	
11,370	8,055 EUR/AWU		10%	
Type of Farms (2020)				
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms		
65.19%		34.81%		
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size	
86 ha	34 ha		184 ha	
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)				
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms		
18,376 EUR		178,690 EUR		
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)				
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)
6,090 (53.56%)	2,090 (18.38%)	1,820 (16.01%)	1,060 (9.32%)	290 (2.55%)

Labour Force (AWU) (2020)		Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)	
16.63 K		Basic: 17% (EU: 18%)	Full: 32% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)
48.9%	10.4%	0.21	33% (EU: 28%)

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
91.39% (EU: 91.67%)	62.61% (EU: 55.56%)	94.38% (EU: 74.71%)	73.9 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
76.3% (EU: 82.5%)	76.3% (EU: 69.2%)	91.5% (EU: 94.3%)	7.2% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
71.2% (EU: 72.9%)		60.6% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP¹⁴

Prioritisation Level

Digitalisation receives moderate prioritisation. It is not treated as a standalone priority but is embedded within several high priority objectives, mainly those related to AKIS, innovation, and knowledge transfer. Specifically, it features in V0.4 on knowledge transfer and dissemination through the creation of a digital information repository (priority level 1 out of 3); in V5.6 on maintaining soil fertility, which refers to the use of modern digital solutions (priority level 1 out of 3); in V9.8, which aims to develop new modern analytical methods and promote the use of digital solutions (priority level 2 out of 3); and in V9.9 on implementing a holistic AKIS that includes digital tools (priority level 1 out of 3).

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

The document recognises that digital technologies in Estonia's agriculture sector remain underutilised despite significant potential. To accelerate uptake, it prioritises closer cooperation between ICT developers, businesses, researchers, and advisers, with a focus on precision farming and data driven approaches. A central component is the creation of a comprehensive information portal or dashboard that offers structured, user friendly access to training materials, research outputs, and advisory services. These efforts are supported by the national Digital Society Development Plan 2030 and strong e-governance practices, and are complemented by measures that expand rural broadband, foster smart villages through LEADER, and link CAP knowledge transfer with Horizon Europe projects. Overall, the objective is to deliver personalised, timely digital services to all actors across the AKIS.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

Digitalisation is presented as a cross-cutting enabler that supports core CAP priorities, advancing climate action, biodiversity conservation, economic resilience, and rural development. The NSP links digital tools to the sustainable management of natural resources through circular economy approaches and resource-efficient technologies, noting the value of tools such as big data, e-books, and balance calculators for climate and biodiversity-related practices. The development of an integrated AKIS and its digital infrastructure, including a comprehensive information portal, is intended to improve the accessibility and dissemination of knowledge, thereby strengthening the resilience and competitiveness of the rural economy. In addition, the use of digitalisation is encouraged in smart village initiatives under the LEADER programme, linking technological advancement with local socio-economic development.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

Estonia's NSP promotes a broad range of digital technologies to enhance agricultural efficiency, sustainability, and knowledge sharing, particularly through precision agriculture and AKIS modernisation. These include precision fertilisation and spraying equipment, digital soil and nutrient monitoring, e-books, balance calculators, e-advisory platforms, smart irrigation, big data applications, and fertilisation and crop protection recommendation tools. The Plan also advances digital information repositories such as the information dashboard to centralise access to research results, training materials, videos of innovation projects, and adviser databases. Additional focus areas include GIS-based land-use monitoring, traceability

¹⁴ Ministry of Rural Affairs of Estonia. (n.d.). *European Union Common Agricultural Policy Strategic Plan 2023-2027*. Retrieved from <https://www.agri.ee/euroopa-liidu-uhise-pollumajanduspoliitika-strateegiakava-2023-2027> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

systems in the food chain, and digital solutions for manure and water management, all integrated into knowledge transfer, innovation, and environmental actions.

Building on Estonia's strong e-governance practices, the NSP also highlights the role of ICT-based tools such as e-income declarations, e-elections, and e-subsidy applications. It also references participation in Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe initiatives, including ERA-Net ICT-AGRI-FOOD and Agriculture of Data, which support the adoption of ICT in agriculture and food production for improved efficiency and transparency. CAP interventions and national support measures also promote automation, robotics, and digital innovation in rural enterprises, with particular attention to the Smart Village pilot programme, which encourages digital solutions in local communities.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

The document acknowledges the existence of persistent gaps in digital inclusion and territorial equity, especially in rural areas with limited infrastructure. While direct CAP funding does not cover broadband expansion, the NSP aligns with national strategies, including the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) to improve access to high-speed internet in underserved regions. It also emphasises the need for cross-sectoral digital solutions, digital hubs, and shared facilities to ensure that rural populations, including smallholders and young entrepreneurs, are not left behind in the digital transition.

AKIS within the NSP

The NSP notes that Estonia's AKIS is fragmented, in part due to the design of support measures in earlier periods, where sub activities targeted narrowly defined groups. In the new period, the focus shifts to building a common information space across AKIS actors, enabling joint activities, and planning AKIS work more holistically. Relevant information and opportunities will be integrated in a single online information repository. To this end, an AKIS Development Centre will be established to bring together advisory and knowledge transfer activities. The Centre will support the systematic development and long-term sustainability of the AKIS, strengthen cooperation among actors including the CAP network, both within Estonia and internationally. Particular attention will be given to providing diverse training opportunities, ensuring advisor succession, recruiting and training new advisors, and evaluating advisory activities. In line with these objectives, Intervention 0.1 seeks to organise AKIS activities holistically, including knowledge dissemination, advisory support, and digital inclusion; Intervention 0.2 focuses on improving advisory support; and Intervention 0.3 supports innovation cooperation under the European Innovation Partnership (EIP).

Monitoring and evaluation

Estonia's CAP NSP sets clear monitoring targets across knowledge, advisory, digitalisation, and environmental outcomes. For R.1 on knowledge and innovation, the Plan aims for 16,180 participants to benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in workshops under the EIP, covering all AKIS related interventions from advisory services to innovation projects. Under R.2, which links advisory and knowledge systems, the target is to support and integrate 6,653 advisers into the AKIS, including those engaged in both mandatory and voluntary training and knowledge transfer. For R.3 on the digitisation of agriculture, Estonia targets 1.16% of farmers benefiting from CAP support for digital technologies, signalling continued uptake of digital tools and practices on farms. Finally, for R.28 on environmental or climate performance through knowledge and innovation, the Plan foresees 4,590 participants benefiting from activities that address climate and environmental sustainability within the AKIS framework.

AKIS Factsheet¹⁵

The AKIS Centre concept offers a holistic way to assess needs and foster cooperation among AKIS actors. Long-term programming with multiple actors is a major step toward a co-creative mindset in Estonia. The Centre's main objective is to develop and coordinate a coherent AKIS by strengthening the role of advisors, raising awareness of opportunities within the knowledge transfer, exchange, and innovation system, and serving as the central AKIS information point. AKIS coordination is organised around two bodies: the Ministry of Regional Affairs and Agriculture (MRAA) and the Centre of Estonian Rural Research and Knowledge (Maaelu Teadmuskuskeskus, METK).

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- **About farm advice:** After the end of collectivisation, Estonia has provided advisory support to farmers since 1995 and support for group activities since 1997. Support for individual advisors has evolved from county centres and coordination centres to a single national advisory organisation. Estonia's advisory services form a mixed system of publicly supported and private providers. Farmers are free to choose supported advice from an enlisted advisor

¹⁵ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the author of the report: **Hanna Tamsalu**. We thank her for her work. <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/WNpHcoSPZnQEst3#pdfviewer>

or to purchase services on the open market at full cost.

- About public policies:** The EU funding programmes have opened several opportunities for AKIS. The concept of nationwide AKIS coordination offers a holistic way to assess needs and foster cooperation among agricultural and rural stakeholders, including farmers, food processors, local ambassadors, researchers, advisors, and officials. Long-term programming with multi-actor organisations is a major step toward a co-creative mindset among AKIS actors in Estonia. The AKIS Centre (a unit within METK) aims to develop and coordinate a coherent system by strengthening the role of advisors, raising awareness of opportunities within the knowledge transfer, exchange, and innovation system, and serving as the central AKIS information point.
- Some trends:** Several concerns emerged in the i2connect study: the advisory workforce is ageing; stakeholders expect joint action among all those involved in knowledge exchange, advisory, and innovation support, but coordination remains limited; insufficient funding for agricultural and rural research reduces the pipeline of new domestic knowledge for transfer; several stakeholders note that scientific information is not available for producers in a clear and accessible form.

France

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
638,475 km ²	68,401,997	107.1 people/km ²	18.0%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
31,725,232	7.4%	76.1 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
2,919,900 million EUR	42,590 EUR	1.2%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)				
Agriculture: 51.7%; forest: 31.8%; other: 16.5%				
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops	
28,482 K ha	17,046 K ha (59.8%)	10,383 K ha (36.5%)	1,053 K ha (3.7%)	
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)				
8,721,144 ha (30.4% UAA)				
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)	
393,030	33,517 EUR/AWU		8%	
Type of Farms (2020)				
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms		
57.56%		42.44%		
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size	
70 ha	39 ha		111 ha	
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)				
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms		
69,573 EUR		288,669 EUR		
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)				
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)
55,840 (14.21%)	53,760 (13.68%)	104,990 (26.71%)	154,190 (39.23%)	24,240 (6.17%)
Labour Force (AWU) (2020)		Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)		
670.7 K		Basic: 26% (EU: 18%)		Full: 38% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)	
43.9%	9.7%	0.22	21% (EU: 28%)	

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
92.60% (EU: 91.67%)	59.67% (EU: 55.56%)	91.60% (EU: 74.71%)	59.7 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
87.5% (EU: 82.5%)	87.5% (EU: 69.2%)	94.3% (EU: 94.3%)	4.8% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
68.5% (EU: 72.9%)		44.9% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP¹⁶

Prioritisation Level

Digitalisation is given a relatively low level of prioritisation. Although the NSP recognises the relevance of digital tools for farmers, foresters and their employees (T.1) – particularly in relation to innovation, competitiveness, and environmental performance – its strategic and budgetary framing treats digitalisation as complementary rather than central. This is most evident in the prioritisation table, where T.4 (Reinforce the deployment of digital tools) is explicitly classified as a Priority 3 need. This indicates that digitalisation is not considered essential to achieving its core objectives, and that responsibility for advancing digital infrastructure and digital transition lies largely with other national policies, such as France's broadband rollout plans and broader digital economy strategies. Nonetheless, digitalisation appears across specific contexts, including the support for digital solutions in agri-food logistics, traceability, and input efficiency. The NSP mentions the importance of improving farmers' digital skills, supporting digital service companies, and ensuring secure use of digital tools.

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

France's strategy for digitalisation in agriculture emphasizes the development and use of digital tools to enhance production efficiency, autonomy, and ecological sustainability. The government promotes trusted data sharing platforms such as AgDataHub, investment in digital skills and equipment, and training through agricultural education. Connectivity initiatives like the France Très Haut Débit plan aim to ensure broadband access nationwide. The use of satellite data (e.g., Farmstar) and digital advisory tools supports decision-making. Rather than specific aid for digitalisation, France opts for territorialised support schemes aligned with agroecological transition goals, encouraging innovations tailored to diverse local farming needs and ensuring equitable value distribution.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

The digitalisation goals are well aligned with broader CAP priorities such as climate action, biodiversity preservation, and resilience. Digital tools are linked to environmental objectives, like precision agriculture and input reduction, supporting agroecological transitions and enhancing monitoring for emissions, soil health, and biodiversity. The Plan integrates digitalisation with sustainability standards like High Environmental Value (HVE) and organic certification, ensuring that technology contributes to ecological outcomes and environmental performance.

On the socio-economic side, digitalisation is seen as a driver for rural development and knowledge sharing. The NSP supports training, advisory services, and peer learning to bridge technology access gaps, improve human capital, and promote sustainable agriculture. It addresses challenges like generational renewal, farm viability, and rural economic diversification by encouraging digital enterprises and entrepreneurship. Emphasis on inclusive access, especially in remote areas, supports territorial cohesion while positioning digitalisation as a lever for both competitiveness and social equity.

¹⁶ Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sovereignty (2022). *Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2027: approval of the national strategic plan by the Commission*. Retrieved from <https://agriculture.gouv.fr/politique-agricole-commune-2023-2027-approbation-du-plan-strategique-national-par-la-commission> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

The NSP promotes the development and diffusion of digital tools through investments in digital infrastructure, data usage, and the promotion of precision agriculture techniques. This includes the use of digital solutions to optimize logistics, traceability, and production system performance. It encourages the use of connected agri-equipment, digital advisory tools, and farm-level data platforms, emphasizing their role in input reduction, productivity improvement, and risk management. However, while digital innovation is promoted, the Plan also notes that very high-speed broadband access is still underdeveloped in some regions, and broader infrastructure development (like broadband access and data protection) is managed by other public policies outside the NSP framework.

The NSP highlights the importance of innovation systems that include research, training, and advisory services to support the agroecological transition. It encourages knowledge transfer via digital and smart advisory systems, particularly for isolated or underserved territories. Digital tools are also referenced for improving transparency and traceability along the value chain and for strengthening consumer awareness. Strategic consulting that integrates farm and territorial needs is promoted to help develop resilient and sustainable production systems. Although digital deployment is not a top priority in the NSP, the document includes substantial secondary measures to foster adoption.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

Digital inclusion and territorial equity are core considerations. While the NSP does not finance broadband directly, it acknowledges that unequal access to tools and connectivity threatens fair participation in the digital transition. It therefore promotes investments in digital technologies and in digital skills and knowledge for farmers, advisory bodies, SMEs, and rural communities, with special attention to isolated or underserved regions, including overseas territories.

To reduce the digital divide, the NSP includes strategies addressing digital inclusion, territorial equity, and the digital divide. It outlines objectives under the “very high-speed broadband” plan to ensure nationwide digital infrastructure: by 2020, guaranteeing access to good broadband (>8 Mbit/s); by 2022, providing state-of-the-art digital infrastructures; and by 2025, rolling out fibre-to-the-home across France. As of mid-2020, coverage reached 97% for good broadband, 65% for very high-speed, and 52% for fibre optics. Additionally, the “territorial digital cohesion” scheme offers financial support to ensure broadband access for all. The Plan explicitly states that digital rollout facilitates the use of digital technologies in rural and agricultural areas, although some “white zones” still exist. The NSP complements these efforts by focusing on capacity building: training, strategic advisory services, and support for digital innovation at the farm and community level.

AKIS within the NSP

While the term AKIS is mentioned only a few times, the NSP provides a detailed and integrated operational framework, supporting research, training, advisory services, and innovation through strategic and cross-cutting objectives. France’s AKIS consists of a wide array of well-structured public, private, and associative actors who collaborate in networks, programs, and partnerships. It includes organizations such as the National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), agricultural technical institutes, Chambers of Agriculture, and many development actors. Tools like UMTs (mixed technology units), RMTs (mixed technology networks), and European Innovation Partnership (EIP) Operational Groups facilitate cooperation among research, advisory services, and agricultural education. Funding sources include the Special Purpose Account for Agricultural and Rural Development (CASDAR) and contributions from interprofessional organizations. The document states that AKIS governance will be coordinated nationally through existing structures, including a Technical Commission for Agricultural and Rural Development (chaired by the French Ministry of Agriculture, and bringing together professional agricultural organizations and the various players in the French AKIS system) and the National Thematic Group for the implementation of Horizon Europe Cluster 6 (which brings together AKIS players and the national contact points for French participation in Horizon Europe). Efforts will focus on strengthening knowledge dissemination, enhancing cooperation among advisors, and improving connections between research and practice, including in overseas regions through networks like RITA (Agricultural Innovation and Transfer Network). Innovation is frequently referenced throughout the document, particularly in the context of improving environmental performance, supporting the agroecological transition, enhancing farm resilience, and fostering value creation in rural areas.

Monitoring and evaluation

Under the CAP result indicator R.01 (Knowledge and innovation), the NSP sets a target of 139,488 people to be assisted through advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in EIPs. While its narrative and intervention logic also support goals linked to R.02, R.03, and R.28, the official results framework does not include measurable targets for these indicators.

AKIS Factsheet¹⁷

The French AKIS has been developed progressively for almost 150 years. It is characterised by a diversity of organisations, often led by farmers, by a strong involvement of public authorities and by arrangements to promote synergies and achieve common objectives. Over time, there has been a shift from a co-management model between the State and the farmers to a model based on service delegation and contracting. Since the 2000s, environmental and societal issues have become increasingly important within AKIS, as well as the issue of innovation creation and support.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- **About farm advice:** there is a pluralism of advisory actors, with a prominent role of farmer-based organisations, including cooperatives, chambers and associations.
- **About public policies:** There is a strong public support for AKIS, including a national research institute with over 10.000 employees (INRAE) and funding mechanisms that foster cooperation among research organisations, advisory services and farmers, such as the so-called “Mixed technology Network (RMT)”. One of these networks focuses on the digitalisation of agriculture. There is also a major research project on digitalisation.
- **Some trends:** Recent research highlight some transformations, including the growing role of so-called “linked” advisors (i.e. advisors that provide advice linked to other commercial activities), and a growing role of regions in farm advice.

¹⁷ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the authors of the report: **Sylvain Sturel** and **Mikaël Naitlho**. We thank them for their work. <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/TyBtkyY8LTc6npc#pdfviewer>

Germany

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
357,569 km ²	83,445,000	233.4 people/km ²	22.1%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
43,772,213	3.4%	72.0 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
4,328,970 million EUR	51,830 EUR	0.7%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)				
Agriculture: 47.5%; forest: 32.7%; other: 19.8%				
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops	
16,593 K ha	11,657 K ha (70.3%)	4,733 K ha (28.5%)	203 K ha (1.2%)	
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)				
3,315,017 ha (20.0% UAA)				
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)	
262,780	41,634 EUR/AWU		6%	
Type of Farms (2020)				
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms		
83.32%		16.68%		
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size	
63 ha	42 ha		167 ha	
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)				
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms		
112,671 EUR		505,254 EUR		
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)				
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)
41,520 (15.80%)	59,710 (22.72%)	65,590 (24.96%)	75,780 (28.84%)	20,160 (7.67%)
Labour Force (AWU) (2020)		Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)		
469.9 K		Basic: 48% (EU: 18%)		Full: 19% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)	
46.7%	7.6%	0.16	10% (EU: 28%)	

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
92.12% (EU: 91.67%)	52.22% (EU: 55.56%)	63.90% (EU: 74.71%)	49.7 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
77.4% (EU: 82.5%)	36.8% (EU: 69.2%)	99.1% (EU: 94.3%)	5.3% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
79.9% (EU: 72.9%)		58.0% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP¹⁸

Prioritisation Level

Digitalisation is assigned a high prioritisation level, although not as an independent thematic area but as a cross-cutting element embedded within several needs and objectives. It is addressed explicitly under need Q.9, which focuses on knowledge transfer regarding the possibilities and requirements of digitalisation and is given a high priority status within the intervention strategy. Beyond Q.9, digital technologies, including artificial intelligence, are featured as tools to strengthen sustainability, resilience, and competitiveness, notably under B.1, which supports investments for future oriented companies, and B.2, which promotes innovation and cooperation. These references likewise carry high priority ratings, highlighting the strategic weight of digitalisation across the Plan.

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

Germany's CAP NSP embeds digitalisation within its innovation and knowledge architecture and treats it as a core element of modernisation interventions such as EL-0403. The Plan specifies operational uses that enhance resource efficiency and data collection, including precision agriculture applications like automated milking and sensor-based crop management, with explicit links to measurable environmental outcomes and animal welfare. It calls for expanded digital advisory content and farmer-oriented training, and sets objectives to address weaknesses in rural infrastructure by extending broadband and mobile coverage while promoting on farm digital applications and skills development. Instruments include digital experimental fields as testbeds and dissemination hubs and programmes such as Smarte.Land.Regionen and Land.Digital that adapt solutions to rural contexts. Investment support covers autonomous machinery, sensors, and digital platforms, with federal and state programmes, including initiatives such as Agriculture Digital in Bavaria, geared to uptake among small and medium sized farms and to gains in sustainability, environmental protection, and productivity. The strategy also addresses enabling conditions for the digital transition, notably data sovereignty and interoperability, and seeks synergies with EU-level programmes including Digital Europe, Horizon Europe, and Gaia X, particularly through the Data Space for Agriculture and Testing and Experimentation Facilities.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

Digitalisation goals in the NSP are closely aligned with broader CAP priorities, particularly climate action and environmental sustainability. The document links digital approaches to lowering greenhouse gas emissions, improving nutrient efficiency, and protecting soil and water, and it integrates these aims into environmental training and advisory services, including those monitored through indicator R.28. It further situates digitalisation within efforts to monitor biodiversity, optimise input use, and promote the sustainable management of natural resources, in line with the Green Deal and Farm to Fork objectives.

The NSP also positions digitalisation as a lever for rural resilience and socio-economic development. It connects digitalisation to competitiveness and income diversification, particularly for small and medium-sized farms, and highlights pathways such as efficiency gains, cost reduction, and the development of new value chains. The Plan recognises the need

¹⁸ Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Food (n.d.). *CAP Strategic Plan*. Retrieved from <https://www.bmel.de/DE/themen/landwirtschaft/eu-agrarpolitik-und-foerderung/gap/gap-strategieplan.html> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

for equitable access to infrastructure and skills across regions and farm types, aligning with CAP goals on social inclusion and rural vitality. Through vocational training, advisory services, and coordinated innovation networks, it frames digitalisation as a means to strengthen human capital and build the long-term resilience and adaptive capacity of rural economies.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

Germany's CAP NSP promotes a range of specific digital technologies and innovations to modernise agriculture and enhance sustainability. The document highlights precision farming tools, including sensor-based systems, variable rate applications, and site-specific crop and soil management, with the stated aims of optimising resource use, improving input efficiency, and reducing environmental impacts. It also supports the development and uptake of artificial intelligence for real-time monitoring, risk prediction, and smart livestock management, linking these applications to climate resilience and operational efficiency.

The NSP also emphasises the importance of robust data infrastructure and interoperability through initiatives like the EU's Data Space for Agriculture and Gaia-X. It supports digital platforms that enable secure data sharing and integration across advisory, research, and farm systems, and it promotes smart advisory services, e-learning tools, and digital experimental fields to strengthen knowledge transfer and practical innovation. These initiatives are framed through targeted interventions and capacity-building efforts to ensure that digitalisation benefits a wide range of stakeholders while remaining aligned with CAP objectives for sustainability, competitiveness, and rural development.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

The document treats digital inclusion and territorial equity as central to its digitalisation strategy. It recognizes that rural areas often face infrastructure deficits, including limited broadband, and sets out coordination with national and EU digital infrastructure programmes to secure equitable access across regions. It also highlights the importance of reaching small and medium-sized farms, which may lack the capacity or resources to invest in advanced technologies, by providing tailored advisory services, training, and financial support, and it commits to building digital competencies among farmers, advisors, and local institutions. The Plan states that, in implementing measures, care will be taken to avoid neglect of rural areas and to prevent disparities between urban and rural territories.

Initiatives to digitalise rural areas include comprehensive investments in digital infrastructure, such as broadband and mobile network expansion, supported by federal and state funding programmes, with CAP interventions extending physical infrastructure in rural regions. Programmes like *Smarte.Land.Regionen* and *Land.Digital* are cited for the development and implementation of digital solutions tailored to rural needs, including services in education, e-mobility, telemedicine, and work organization. Experimental fields for digitalisation in agriculture and the *GeoBox* infrastructure are used to enable uptake and provide access to relevant agricultural data. Vocational training, e-learning platforms, and inclusive knowledge exchange initiatives are deployed to support less digitally experienced users, while more accessible advisory services and innovation networks are promoted to advance gender equality and regional balance.

AKIS within the NSP

The document elaborates extensively on the institutional architecture, operational coordination, and strategic functions of AKIS. It specifies that the AKIS Coordination Office, within the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL), is responsible for collecting information, facilitating coordination between the federation and the *Länder*, and managing communication with the European Commission. It supports multi-stakeholder exchanges through the organisation of workshops and coordination with entities such as the German Innovation Partnership for Agriculture (DIP), the German Networking Agency for Rural Areas (DVS), and various knowledge platforms like the Federal Office for Agriculture and Food (BZL) and the Federal Centre for Nutrition (BZfE). The Plan also includes references to participatory models such as *Agroecology Living Labs*, which operationalize co-creation with farmers, advisors, and citizens. Furthermore, it details the diversity of advisory structures across the federal states, outlining both public and private models of consultancy, their coordination mechanisms, and the role of training and vocational education institutions.

Monitoring and evaluation

Germany's NSP sets clear monitoring and evaluation targets across key result areas. Under R.1, the Plan aims to reach 350,000 people through CAP funded advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in EIP Operational Groups to improve performance through knowledge and innovation. For R.2, it targets the integration of 1,000 advisors into AKIS, strengthening links between advisory services and the wider knowledge and innovation system. Regarding R.3, the Plan foresees that 0.95% of farms, equivalent to about 2,500 holdings, will receive support for digital agricultural technologies. Finally, under R.28, Germany sets a target of training 280,000 people on environmental and climate-related topics through AKIS-related interventions.

AKIS Factsheet¹⁹

The German AKIS is defined by a decentralised governance model in which the individual states (Länder) are responsible for education and advisory services. This autonomy leads to substantial regional diversity, making it challenging to present a unified AKIS at the national level. However, the German AKIS is strong, with broad participation by public authorities, research institutions, education providers, private enterprises, and many farmer-based and third-sector organisations. Together, these diverse stakeholders contribute to a strong institutional landscape that supports knowledge transfer and innovation. Yet, regional fragmentation points to the need for improved horizontal coordination and stronger linkages between research and practice to foster cohesive knowledge flows.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- **About farm advice:** Germany’s federal states are responsible for implementing advisory services for agriculture, forestry, and horticulture enterprises, resulting in considerable diversity of advisory service providers and structures among the states. While chambers of agriculture, state authorities or private advisory service providers are predominant in some states, various associations and NGOs offer advisory services at the local, state, and national levels.
- **About public policies:** In the CAP NSP for 2023-2027, the federal government has outlined an approach to strengthening the German AKIS, prioritising improved coordination and networking across federal states. To facilitate these efforts, new coordination structures have been established, such as the AKIS coordination office within the BMEL and the AKIS Federal Roundtable (Bund-Länderrunde), which serves as a platform for dialogue and alignment among federal and state-level AKIS activities. Additionally, an AKIS Expert Advisory Board has been introduced, involving key stakeholders from research, advisory, and education sectors to provide strategic insights on knowledge flow and innovation. Through these new structures, the NSP aims to strengthen both horizontal and vertical linkages within the German AKIS, fostering more integrated and efficient knowledge sharing across regions.
- **Some trends:** Improving knowledge flows in the German AKIS requires a wider lens that includes a broader set of actors. Current discussions largely focus on a core group of actors, while private advisory providers (who play a critical role in many Länder) remain underexamined. A fuller understanding will require deeper insight into these private actors so their contributions can be recognised and better leveraged.

AKIS in Bavaria

¹⁹ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the authors of the report: **Sangeun Bae, Fanos Mekonnen Birke, Maria Gerster-Bentaya, Friederike Selensky, Eugenio Giacomelli, Carola Ketelhodt, Margret Kolbeck, Markgr Hartmann, Pablo Asensio, and Andrea Knierim.** We thank them for their work. <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/WMNxF2cR4wrjkoj#pdfviewer>

Greece

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
131,694 km ²	10,397,193	78.9 people/km ²	19.0%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
4,654,775	10.1%	59.3 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
237,573 million EUR	22,560 EUR	2.8%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)				
Agriculture: 44.3%; forest: 30.3%; other: 25.4%				
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops	
5,361 K ha	1,754 K ha (32.7%)	2,475 K ha (46.2%)	1,132 K ha (21.1%)	
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)				
1,707,562 ha (32.5% UAA)				
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)	
530,750	21,628 EUR/AWU		12%	
Type of Farms (2020)				
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms		
99.18%		0.82%		
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size	
5 ha	5 ha		12 ha	
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)				
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms		
13,548 EUR		141,157 EUR		
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)				
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)
335,720 (63.25%)	118,750 (22.37%)	68,270 (12.86%)	7,380 (1.39%)	640 (0.12%)

Labour Force (AWU) (2020)		Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)		
565.4 K		Basic: 5% (EU: 18%)		Full: 1% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)	
64.8%	3.5%	0.05	27% (EU: 28%)	

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
85.48% (EU: 91.67%)	52.40% (EU: 55.56%)	76.25% (EU: 74.71%)	49.3 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
46.1% (EU: 82.5%)	46.1% (EU: 69.2%)	99.8% (EU: 94.3%)	2.5% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
53.4% (EU: 72.9%)		33.5% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP²⁰

Prioritisation Level

Digitalisation is accorded a high level of priority, as reflected in the needs assessment entries that call for improving education services, training opportunities and technological infrastructure (AN 002.10.02), increasing partnerships with high tech companies (AN 024.10.08), expanding investment financing for the development of applications and systems (AN 029.10.11), strengthening education and training of rural residents in digital services (AN 043.08.02), and enhancing the functionality of existing information systems through extensions and upgrades (AN 044.10.17). Taken together, these high priority needs show that digitalisation is seen not as an ancillary or supplementary objective but as a central enabler of modernisation, competitiveness, and efficient service delivery across Greek agriculture and rural development policy.

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

Within Greece's CAP NSP, a SWOT analysis and needs assessment were undertaken, identifying the need to upgrade technological infrastructure and integrate advanced technologies into agricultural production. The programme document translates these findings into a digitalisation agenda that delivers these upgrades and embeds advanced technologies across the sector. The Plan states that it will address the identified needs through increased investment in automation, digital tools, and precision agriculture, including smart irrigation, variable rate fertilisation, greenhouse climate control, remote automation, and information and communication technologies for processing and marketing. Interventions combine financial support for state-of-the-art equipment with structured digital skills training for farmers and advisers, stronger advisory services, and partnerships that accelerate innovation. Knowledge will be disseminated through digital platforms, remote sensing, and broader ICT integration. A flagship project, Digital Transformation of the Agricultural Sector, will create a digital platform (Rural Sector Services and Data Access Portal) to support data-driven decision-making, connect to the AKIS knowledge base, and enhance service delivery. Participation in European digital cooperation initiatives further supports the strategy's alignment with broader EU objectives for rural digital advancement, while targeted actions aim to narrow digital gaps in transition and less developed regions and across the smaller Aegean islands.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

The document integrates digitalisation goals with broader CAP priorities like climate action, biodiversity, resilience, and socio-economic development. For instance, under Specific Objective 2, the focus on digitalisation of agriculture seeks to strengthen competitiveness and market orientation, reinforcing the sector's socioeconomic resilience. The cross-cutting objective further emphasises the use of digital tools to improve systemic interoperability and integrate new management applications, which can streamline operations and enable more efficient resource that supports climate and environmental goals while fostering a more resilient and modern agri-food system. Section 8 makes this alignment explicit, showing how enhanced advisory services and better farmer access to digital knowledge accelerate the uptake of sustainable practices. Accordingly, it prioritises investment in smart technologies for livestock monitoring, irrigation and fertilisation, linking digitalisation to improved climate performance through reduced inputs and optimised resource use, with benefits for environmental sustainability and farm resilience. It also promotes partnerships to pilot digital systems, remote sensing and

²⁰ General Secretariat for EU Resources and Infrastructure (n.d.). *Approval / Modifications - CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027*. Retrieved from <https://www.agrotikianaptixi.gr/category/sskap-2023-2027/sskap-egkrisi-tropopoiiseis/> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

precision agriculture, positioning digitalisation as a means to deliver environmental and climate objectives and to support wider socio-economic progress and adaptability in Greek agriculture.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

The document promotes a range of digital technologies and innovations to modernise Greece's agricultural sector. It prioritises the adoption of new management applications, the integration of information through national digital platforms like gov.gr, and the creation of a core technological platform to support the sector's digital transformation. To strengthen market orientation, it prioritises tools such as platforms for issuing export certificates, business intelligence systems for trade, and portals to promote Greek agri-food products. It also foresees investments in advanced data collection and processing infrastructure, including X-band meteorological radars, telemetry and remote-control stations, unmanned aerial vehicle systems, and capabilities for analysing high-resolution satellite images.

Building on this infrastructure and the associated platforms, the NSP promotes smart applications and precision farming, including systems for monitoring animal health and behaviour in livestock holdings and for precise irrigation and fertilisation based on live environmental data. The document also focuses on integrated information systems for the new CAP, agricultural insurance, and irrigation management. In addition, it encourages partnerships to pilot digital systems, remote sensing applications, precision agriculture, and integrated software for farm level management, underlining a comprehensive approach to digitalisation supported by foundational ultra-fast broadband connectivity and structured digital skills training for advisors.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

The NSP addresses digital inclusion, territorial equity, and the digital divide through several key initiatives. Under the National Broadband Plan 2021-2027, projects such as Ultra-Fast Broadband I and II aim to extend high speed internet to rural and remote areas, including islands and border regions, covering more than 880,000 households and 10,000 public buildings, with particular attention to places facing development barriers, limited-service access, and population decline. Investments also target digital infrastructure for schools, health centres, and public services. Through the LEADER programme, the Plan supports integrated local development in almost all rural areas, promoting social inclusion, quality of life, and smart village initiatives focusing on connectivity, digital services, and innovation. Complementary measures funded by NextGenerationEU and the National Strategic Reference Framework (NSRF) back digital transformation in agriculture, rural education, and public administration. The NSP further provides for farmers' access to digital tools, databases, and mobile applications, and acknowledges differing levels of digital literacy across age groups by providing tailored training and mentoring for older farmers to ensure their full participation in the sector's digital transition.

AKIS within the NSP

The document characterises Greece's AKIS as weak and fragmented, with limited linkages among stakeholders, insufficient national level support, and inadequate advisory services for farmers. In response, it outlines that a restructured AKIS with defined roles is being established to enhance the transfer of knowledge and innovation to agricultural production. The system will be coordinated through a National AKIS Committee and a dedicated AKIS Coordination Body, incorporating stakeholders from advisory services, research, and education. Interventions under Articles 77 and 78 will fund actions such as training, the creation of knowledge repositories, and networking. Additional contributors, including ELGO DIMITRA, the CAP Networks, and the European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) framework, will support education, promote innovation, and facilitate collaboration. The NSP also provides for consultant training, data sharing, and digital interconnection to strengthen advisory capacity and operational synergies.

Monitoring and evaluation

Greece's CAP NSP sets clear monitoring targets across knowledge, advisory capacity, digitalisation, and environmental performance. Under R.1, the Plan aims for 206,154 people to benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in EIP Operational Groups, strengthening sustainable economic, social, environmental, climate, and resource efficiency outcomes. Through R.2, 6,594 advisers are expected to receive support to join AKIS, reinforcing links between advisory services and knowledge flows. For R.3, the strategy targets 26.08% of farms to receive CAP support for digital agricultural technologies, accelerating uptake of tools that improve productivity and resilience. Finally, under R.28, 82,461 people are expected to benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in EIP business groups specifically focused on environmental and climate performance, helping to translate innovation into measurable gains.

AKIS Factsheet²¹

The Greek AKIS is characterised by a high degree of fragmentation, which has constrained its overall effectiveness.

²¹ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the authors of the report: **Alex Koutsouris, Eleni Zarokosta, Eleni Pappa, and Vassiliki Kanaki**. We thank them for their work <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/gFRopn2y4KmEZ4b#pdfviewer>

This fragmentation stems from structural issues, including decentralisation and the separation of research and farmer training functions from the Ministry of Rural Development and Food, coupled with inadequate formal coordination mechanisms. These factors have resulted in weak linkages among core public institutions. Furthermore, collaboration with private sector actors remains largely informal and ad hoc. The fragmented structure of the Greek AKIS has had direct consequences for its ability to address contemporary agricultural challenges. Despite significant public investment in research institutions and universities, the lack of a clear, centralised channel for disseminating new knowledge means that research findings often do not reach farmers in a timely or practical manner. This disconnect is exacerbated by a weak farm advisory service that lacks the resources and formal authority to act as an effective link between academia and the field.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- **About farm advice:** Advice to farmers is provided mainly by private agronomists who run or work in input shops at subregional or local level. In recent years, the launch of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups and the National Farm Advisory System has strengthened the role of independent advisors, raising expectations for more reliable, stable, and robust knowledge flows.
- **About public policies:** The CAP National Strategic Plan (NSP) 2023-2027 is the primary policy framework for supporting AKIS functions and addressing systemic weaknesses. A central pillar of this effort is the newly established National Committee for AKIS, which is designed to serve as the core coordination body. A major challenge for this Committee is to strengthen collaboration across actors, which will require clear leadership and a shared vision to deliver tangible benefits for farmers. Its success is anticipated to establish a robust new framework for advisory services, farmer training, and innovation cooperation, thereby strengthening the foundational connections within the AKIS.
- **Some trends:** Analysis of the i2connect project survey data reveals a consistent pattern of a fragmented advisory landscape. Multiple actors operate within this space, often motivated by the availability of CAP funding, yet they function with minimal interconnection and a lack of back-office support. These entities typically address an excessively broad range of potential clients, rely heavily on fee-based funding models, and predominantly employ a top-down approach. This fragmented and uncoordinated system has resulted in significant gaps in service provision. Large segments of the farming population remain underserved, while others receive guidance only from input shops, which cannot offer impartial advice on pressing operational needs. Consequently, critical opportunities (such as the establishment of a coherent advisory system and the implementation of bottom-up, interactive innovation projects) have been largely missed or significantly delayed.

Hungary

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
93,012 km ²	9,584,627	103.0 people/km ²	26.8%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
4,953,933	4.5%	57.8 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
206,209 million EUR	21,570 EUR	1.6%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)				
Agriculture: 55.6%; forest: 22.5; other: 21.9%				
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops	
5,078 K ha	4,160 K ha (81.9%)	771 K ha (15.2%)	147 K ha (2.9%)	
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)				
1,099,783 ha (22.0% UAA)				
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)	
232,060	9,243 EUR/AWU		10%	
Type of Farms (2020)				
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms		
94.83%		5.17%		
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size	
21 ha	12 ha		188 ha	
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)				
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms		
14,176 EUR		333,781 EUR		
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)				
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)
157,670 (67.94%)	38,890 (16.76%)	24,420 (10.52%)	9,100 (3.92%)	1,970 (0.85%)

Labour Force (AWU) (2020)	Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)		
241.7 K	Basic: 30% (EU: 18%)		Full: 9% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)
64.8%	3.5%	0.05	27% (EU: 28%)

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
93.02% (EU: 91.67%)	58.89% (EU: 55.56%)	84.46% (EU: 74.71%)	51.3 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
86.0% (EU: 82.5%)	79.9% (EU: 69.2%)	85.6% (EU: 94.3%)	4.5% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
57.4% (EU: 72.9%)		65.6% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP²²

Prioritisation Level

Digitalisation is given a high level of prioritisation, embedded within the broader context of innovation, efficiency, and administrative modernisation, and recognised for its transformative potential across agriculture and rural areas. The Plan assigns the highest prioritisation level (1) to interventions related to digitalisation, such as the development of digital infrastructure for agri-food and forestry businesses (CCO.4.4), digital solutions for quality assurance and traceability (CCO.4.5), and support for electronic administration (CCO.4.3). These measures aim to enhance sectoral efficiency, reduce administrative burdens, and support environmental and food safety goals through better data management and traceability.

However, not all digitalisation-related identified needs are given uniformly high priority. For instance, while the development of digital infrastructure is prioritised, other aspects such as personal broadband access (CCO.4.1) and integration of digital sectoral registers (CCO.4.2) are classified with a prioritisation level of 2, and in some cases noted as only in part included in the NSP. This indicates that although digitalisation is recognised as a vital enabler, certain elements (particularly those considered outside the direct remit of the CAP, such as infrastructure development or large-scale database integration) are expected to be addressed through complementary national or EU operational programmes.

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

Hungary's CAP NSP digitalisation strategy builds on the national Digital Agricultural Strategy (DAS 2019-2027) and the Digital Food Strategy (DÉS 2021-2028). It focuses on four pillars: enhancing digital readiness, fostering innovation, digitising public administration, and supporting digital investments in agriculture. Operationally, it advances the linking and streamlining of sectoral databases, promotes the uptake of precision farming tools and decision support systems, and upgrades rural digital infrastructure, including broadband. The Farm Sustainability Improvement intervention and smart village projects are central implementation vehicles, complemented by dedicated support for digital service platforms, innovation partnerships, and rural cooperation. Across measures, the aims are to raise digital competencies, enable farm and food processing investments, and deploy smart rural infrastructure that improves efficiency, traceability, environmental performance, and competitiveness, while making agriculture more attractive to younger generations through modern technology. Digitalisation functions as a cross-cutting objective throughout the Plan, with targeted interventions designed to integrate technology into everyday farm and administrative practice rather than treating it as a separate, isolated initiative.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

The document presents a largely coherent alignment between digitalisation goals and wider CAP priorities, especially those linked to economic resilience and environmental sustainability. Digitalisation is embedded within the AKIS framework to promote knowledge exchange and the uptake of innovative, sustainable technologies. Planned investments in digital infrastructure and tools are explicitly tied to climate mitigation, biodiversity monitoring, and resource efficient production. This technological orientation is positioned as a transversal enabler to enhance productivity, support climate adaptation (e.g., through better forecasting and data collection), and ensure the traceability and quality of food products.

²² Ministry of Agriculture (n.d.). *Hungary's CAP Strategic Plan, 2023-2027*. Retrieved from <https://kormany.hu/dokumentumtar/magyarorszag-kap-strategiai-terve-2023-2027> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

The agenda also connects digitalisation to the socio-economic regeneration of rural areas. Smart village strategies and LEADER-based local development plans incorporate digital tools to improve local governance, service delivery, and economic diversification. However, while digitalisation is thematically cross-cutting, the depth of its integration with biodiversity and ecosystem resilience objectives appears less robust than its alignment with productivity and administrative efficiency. Although digital solutions are proposed for monitoring biodiversity and supporting climate adaptation, the implementation framework suggests these measures are less central than the technologically-driven efficiency gains in production systems.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

The NSP explicitly promotes a set of digital technologies and innovations, with precision farming given a prominent role. The Plan identifies precision agriculture as a key tool for sustainability and competitiveness, highlighting its capacity to optimise input use, reduce environmental impact, and increase productivity. Precision technologies are embedded within broader efforts to modernise production systems and adapt to climate variability, with targeted support for precision soil and nutrient management and environmentally sound plant protection. The development of digital solutions for traceability, certification, and labelling is also encouraged to improve market transparency and enhance food quality assurance. Objectives include the adoption of precision agriculture, the development of farm-level digital tools, and the modernisation of production and post-harvest technologies. The document connects digitalisation directly resource-efficient and market-responsive agricultural practices, aiming to equip farms with the technological capabilities needed for competitiveness and resilience.

Beyond production-focused technologies, the NSP includes measures to strengthen the digital infrastructure of the agri-food sector. This includes the development of digital sectoral registers, electronic administration tools, and smart advisory systems to streamline governance and support evidence-based decision-making. AKIS interventions are designed to enhance the digital competencies of farmers and advisors, promote practice-oriented knowledge transfer, and support innovation networks. Smart village strategies further extend digitalisation to rural development, enabling municipalities to define local strategies around digital tools for services, economic diversification, and environmental management.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

Hungary's CAP NSP incorporates elements of digital inclusion and territorial equity primarily through AKIS and smart village initiatives, seeking to extend digital tools and capabilities to rural and less developed areas and narrow the digital divide. The Plan acknowledges disparities in access to broadband and digital services and, while large scale connectivity investments sit largely with other national programmes, it complements them by supporting local strategies that embed digital solutions in public services, economic diversification, and environmental management. In addition, it targets small-scale and hard-to-reach farmers through staged interventions such as information services, advisory support, and training, supported by the DAS and DÉS to strengthen skills and sector wide infrastructure. While the commitment to digital inclusion is evident, it is more implicit than directly operationalised through dedicated measures for the most disadvantaged groups or territories, relying instead on coordinated efforts via the CAP Network and institutional actors to promote equitable access and participation.

AKIS within the NSP

The document elaborates a comprehensive vision that positions AKIS as a foundational mechanism for achieving its economic, environmental, and social objectives, with a strong emphasis on promoting and disseminating knowledge, innovation and digitalisation across the agricultural sector. The system brings together multiple actors, such as the CAP Network, the Széchenyi Agricultural Knowledge and Accreditation Centre (SZAK), and the National Chamber of Agriculture, to provide professional support, accreditation and continuous knowledge updates for advisers. The CAP Network coordinates training, advisory services, innovation, and digitisation through dedicated support units and promotes synergies among stakeholders. Funding for AKIS interventions is planned to rise from 2.8% to 3.2% of the budget, exceeding 246 million euros.

The AKIS strategy prioritises a farmer-centric that closes the gap between research and practice and promotes technological innovation. Operational measures include the establishment of demonstration farms in secondary and tertiary agricultural education institutions, training advisers with a focus on environmentally sustainable practices, and support for practice-oriented knowledge transfer. The Plan also highlights the role of innovation groups and collaborations between researchers, producers and processors, aiming to improve the responsiveness and practical application of research to farming challenges.

Monitoring and evaluation

Under Hungary's CAP NSP, monitoring and evaluation targets are set across key result areas. For R.1 (Improving performance through knowledge and innovation), Hungary aims for 736,210 people to be advised, trained, involved in knowledge exchange, or engaged in CAP-supported operational groups of the European Innovation Partnership (EIP) to

improve sustainable economic, social, environmental, climate and resource efficiency performance. For R.2 (Connecting advice and knowledge systems), the target is to support the integration of 14,640 advisors into AKIS. For R.3 (Digitalisation of agriculture), 7.69% of farms are expected to receive support for digital agricultural technologies under CAP. For R.28 (Training on climate and environment topics), Hungary sets a target of 441,726 people receiving advice or participating in training, knowledge exchange, or CAP-supported EIP Operational Groups on environmental and climate-related topics. For R.40 (Smart transition for the rural economy), the target is to support 52 smart village strategies.

AKIS Factsheet²³

The Hungarian AKIS has a heterogeneous structure. Alongside several ministries, key actors include advisory providers, education and research institutions, professional chambers, advocacy and farmers' organisations, media and information channels, NGOs, and EU networks. The Hungarian Chamber of Agriculture plays a central role, particularly in representing farmers' interests and in generating and disseminating information. Advisory services, organised under the National Advisory Centre (OSzK), have a prominent role in the transfer of knowledge and the practical application and dissemination of innovations. Within the Hungarian Farm Advisory System, OSzK coordinates, records, and oversees tasks and actors.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- **About farm advice:** The i2connect project identified 168 registered advisory organizations operating in Hungary. Of these, 107 are independent from input material distributors, and 16 are accredited to deliver publicly supported advisory services. Eight organisations operate on a non-commercial basis, but they are not authorised to provide supported advisory services. Advisory organisations are market-based companies or private entrepreneurs who typically operate in a specific geographical area, but often with national coverage. Eligibility for accreditation is strictly regulated. An organisation is only authorised to practice within a specialized field if its employed advisors hold the corresponding official certification. This framework mandates that all advisory services, whether provided by legal entities or natural persons, must be registered in accordance with national legislation.
- **About public policies:** The Hungarian AKIS is characterised by strong state involvement. European policies have significantly strengthened its core components, including funding schemes, accreditation and training procedures, and coordination mechanisms.
- **Some trends:** A key challenge identified is the better integration of educational programmes into the AKIS, particularly within a context where attracting young people to careers in agricultural advisory services and other AKIS roles is difficult.

²³ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the authors of the report: **Gáborné Jakab Ágnes, Varga Zsuzsanna, and Vér András**. We thank them for their work <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/JdHCrJ7AiMLGSnG#pdfviewer>

Ireland

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
69,947 km ²	5,343,805	76.4 people/km ²	35.2%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
2,856,577	4.3%	73.4 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
562,794 million EUR	104,510 EUR	0.9%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)				
Agriculture: 63.1%; forest: 11.5%; other: 25.4%				
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops	
4,620 K ha	471 K ha (10.2%)	4,149 K ha (89.8%)	---	
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)				
1,979,117 ha (44.2% UAA)				
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)	
130,220	25,652 EUR/AWU		11%	
Type of Farms (2020)				
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms		
89.38%		10.62%		
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size	
35 ha	32 ha		61 ha	
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)				
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms		
39,206 EUR		160,280 EUR		
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)				
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)
38,760 (29.77%)	43,320 (33.27%)	30,850 (23.69%)	15,980 (12.27%)	1,320 (1.01%)

Labour Force (AWU) (2020)		Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)	
154.8 K		Basic: 20% (EU: 18%)	Full: 22% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)
55.3%	7.3%	0.13	11% (EU: 28%)

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
98.57% (EU: 91.67%)	72.91% (EU: 55.56%)	90.09% (EU: 74.71%)	73.7 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
87.2% (EU: 82.5%)	73.5% (EU: 69.2%)	89.9% (EU: 94.3%)	6.3% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
73.4% (EU: 72.9%)		64.1% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP²⁴

Prioritisation Level

Digitalisation is an important but not top-tier priority in Ireland's CAP NSP. It is framed primarily through the lens of enhancing competitiveness and knowledge systems. Under Obj2.N1 (Increase efficiency and competitiveness through on-farm investment and the adoption of new technologies), digitalisation is embedded in efforts to encourage the uptake of precision farming and other digital tools, and this need is identified as the highest priority under SO2. Within the cross-cutting objective on AKIS, digitalisation appears again under ObjAKIS.N2, which calls for a review of education, training, and advisory services to reflect new challenges and ambitions, including the need to improve farmer training on digital technologies. Although ObjAKIS.N2 is the second-highest priority within the cross-cutting objective, digitalisation is one component among several, indicating that it is positioned as a supporting enabler rather than a standalone strategic pillar. Overall, digitalisation is prioritised as a key tool for achieving broader goals, especially in competitiveness and knowledge transfer, but it is not highlighted as an independent or primary objective.

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

The NSP identifies, through the SWOT analysis and needs assessment, a slow uptake of digital technologies among Irish farmers and the need to promote tools such as precision farming. It operationalises digitalisation through support for on-farm investment under Obj2.N1, together with advisory and training programmes designed to build digital competencies. Education and advisory services will be reviewed to improve training on digital tools, with the goal of enabling efficient resource use and improved farm management. The Plan places the agricultural digitalisation approach within the national digital framework and emphasises a structured, bottom-up model involving research projects, innovation clusters, and public private partnerships. Within the CAP, digitalisation is promoted through Knowledge Transfer Groups, continuous professional development for advisors, and the On-Farm Capital Investment Scheme, which supports investments in technologies such as electronic identification readers and heat detection systems. The AgriSnap app, developed under the EU funded NIVA project, is cited as a tool for efficient geo tagged photographic submissions. The Skillnet Digital Adoption Programme, the VistaMilk Research Centre, and projects such as DEMETER and Smart Agri Hubs are referenced as part of the broader effort.

The document also details activity outside the CAP, including the National Broadband Plan to address the rural-digital divide and research-led tool development by institutions such as Teagasc and University College Dublin to support farm decision making. The strategy includes support from EU innovation funding and agri-tech accelerators to promote digital transformation. Overall, the NSP provides breadth and operational detail, spanning strategic alignment with the national digital framework, investment in smart technologies on farm, continuous professional development for advisors, and knowledge transfer measures, complemented by wider connectivity, research, and innovation initiatives outside the CAP.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

Ireland's CAP NSP shows a clear alignment between its digitalisation goals and broader CAP priorities, especially in

²⁴ Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine. (2022). *The CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027*. Retrieved from <https://www.gov.ie/en/department-of-agriculture-food-and-the-marine/publications/the-cap-strategic-plan-2023-2027/> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

the context of environmental sustainability and climate action. The Plan positions digital and precision technologies as instruments to enhance resource efficiency, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and support sustainable farming, for example by optimising fertiliser use and improving soil health, thereby contributing to climate mitigation and the protection of natural resources. Within this framing, AKIS is directed towards strengthening digital and technical literacy among farmers and advisors, reinforcing climate smart agriculture and the adoption of environmentally sustainable practices.

The NSP also integrates digitalisation with socio-economic and resilience goals. It treats improved rural broadband as foundational for rural enterprise development, remote work, and income diversification, and advances the development of smart villages as a means to enable community driven, digitally supported local development. These measures are intended to improve quality of life, generate employment, and foster community solutions to environmental and economic challenges. The use of digital tools is further linked to training and knowledge transfer, facilitating access to opportunities and support for young farmers, women, and new entrants.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

The document promotes several digital technologies and innovations. Under the On-Farm Capital Investment Scheme, it identifies tools such as Electronic Identification tag readers, computer information systems, heat detection systems, and ear tags or pedometers as likely investments to support digital farming. The use of satellite data and geotagged photo submissions via the AgriSnap app (developed through the NIVA project) also features prominently. These tools are integrated into new monitoring systems, such as the Area Monitoring System (AMS), to automate compliance checks and reduce the need for physical farm inspections. The Plan also highlights Teagasc software tools, including eProfit Monitor for financial benchmarking, Nutrient Management Planning Online for optimised fertiliser use, and PastureBase Ireland for grassland management.

Beyond these applied tools, the NSP references wider research and innovation activity. VistaMilk is developing next generation electronic monitoring and actuation technologies for the dairy sector, while EU projects such as DEMETER, FairShare, and Smart Agri Hubs provide digital integration platforms, advisory tools, and innovation networks. The inclusion of specific tools, programmes, institutions, and funding streams indicates a high level of operational specificity and a clear roadmap for integrating digitalisation into Ireland's agricultural transformation, reflecting a mature, cross-sectoral approach supported by public and private actors.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

The NSP acknowledges that, despite Ireland's strong performance in the Digital Economy and Society Index 2020, the SWOT analysis identifies low awareness and confidence in using technology within the farming sector, indicating the need for a strategic approach to digital transformation in farming and rural areas. CAP measures aim to provide impartial advisory services with adequate digital knowledge to help farmers navigate the digital landscape and reduce the digital divide, supported by Teagasc's development of digital tools like eProfit Monitor and Nutrient Management Planning Online. The Plan promotes digital inclusion and territorial equity through improved rural broadband under the National Broadband Plan, which targets over 544,000 premises, including a substantial share of farms, and through community led initiatives such as LEADER and the Digital Innovation Programme. These measures are intended to secure equitable access to connectivity and services, enable the development of smart villages, and make advisory services and training programs accessible across all regions to empower rural populations and facilitate inclusive development.

AKIS within the NSP

The document states that Ireland's AKIS is coordinated by the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM), with the objective of strengthening collaboration among researchers, advisors, farmers, and other agri-food actors. It provides for the establishment of an AKIS Coordination Group to enhance synergies across core institutions, including Teagasc, Bord Bia, the Environmental Protection Agency, private advisory providers, and academic institutions. Key planned activities include flexible education and training, improved knowledge transfer, expanded advisory services with continuous professional development, enhanced networking for innovation support, and the promotion of digital transition in agriculture. It identifies Teagasc as having a central role through advisory, research, and training functions, citing the Signpost programme and the ConnectEd programme. The NSP further notes contributions from Bord Bia through the Origin Green programme, the Agricultural Consultants Association, the National CAP Network, and a range of public research organisations. Specific interventions to support AKIS include Knowledge Transfer Groups, European Innovation Partnership (EIP) Operational Groups, continuous professional development for advisors, and a dedicated Innovation Hub under the National CAP Network.

Monitoring and evaluation

Ireland's CAP NSP sets clear targets to track progress on knowledge, advice, and digital uptake. Under R.1 (Enhancing performance through knowledge and innovation), the Plan aims for 299,412 individuals to benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in EIP Operational Groups funded by the CAP. R.2 (Linking advice and knowledge

systems) targets 10,176 advisors receiving support for integration within the AKIS. R.3 (Digitalising agriculture) sets a goal for 0.91% of farms to receive support for digital farming technologies. R.28 (Environmental or climate related performance through knowledge and innovation) specifies 234,927 beneficiaries of CAP-funded advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in EIP Operational Groups focused on environmental or climate-related performance. Finally, R.40 (Smart transition for the rural economy) establishes a target of supporting 200 smart village strategies.

AKIS Factsheet²⁵

The Irish AKIS is notable for the central role of the Agriculture and Food Development Authority (Teagasc), which integrates research, advisory services, and education through seven research centres, seven agricultural colleges, and 52 advisory offices. It serves more than 130,000 farmers and forest owners, employs over 300 advisors, and coordinates 120 demonstration farms. The private sector also plays a major role. The Agricultural Consultants Association (ACA) represents more than 165 offices, employing about 280 agricultural and environmental professionals who provide independent advice to over 55,000 farmers. Private consultants, together with industry advisors employed by input suppliers, make up a large part of the advisory network. In total, these private and industry advisors number roughly 500 professionals and offer services ranging from CAP application support to specialised farm management and innovation advice. Other important AKIS actors include universities and third level institutions, which collaborate on research and education, and the media, which is instrumental in disseminating information to farmers. Farmer representative organisations such as the Irish Farmers Association (IFA) and the Irish Creamery Milk Suppliers Association (ICMSA) are also central to advocacy and knowledge exchange. In recent years, policy has moved toward a more coordinated AKIS approach. The Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM) has strengthened its policy role, notably through the CAP NSP for 2023-2027. The AKIS Coordination Group established in 2023 aims to deepen collaboration among stakeholders to address environmental sustainability, digital transformation, and innovation support.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- **About farm advice:** Ireland maintains a strong advisory service that is publicly supported and integrated with research and education, operating under a mixed funding model. In addition, a similar cohort of private advisors and a smaller cohort of industry advisors provide services directly to farmers. The total number of active advisors varies from year to year with the cycle of CAP scheme funding.
- **About public policies:** In Ireland, publicly funded, mixed funded, and private funded services coexist, giving farmers a choice of provider. While the government is not required to finance all advisory activities, it plays a key role in addressing gaps left by the market. Funded programmes and initiatives, such as joint industry programmes and EIP-AGRI projects, create opportunities for AKIS actors to collaborate.
- **Some trends:** Policies like Food Vision 2030 will further guide AKIS developments, with a strong focus on climate action, biodiversity, and farm-level innovation.

²⁵ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the authors of the report: **Paul Maher, Stan Lalor, George Ramsbottom, Tom Houlihan, and Jane Kavanagh**. We thank them for their work. <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/bcKi9jdCwdo2Q6y#pdfviewer>

Italy

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
302,073 km ²	58,989,749	195.3 people/km ²	27.7%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
25,828,140	6.5%	69.2 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
2,192,182 million EUR	37,180 EUR	2.0%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)				
Agriculture: 44.0%; forest: 32.7%; other: 23.3%				
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops	
12,928 K ha	7,011 K ha (54.2%)	3,530 K ha (27.3%)	2,387 K ha (18.5%)	
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)				
3,523,426 ha (26.9% UAA)				
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)	
1,133,020	32,898 EUR/AWU		6%	
Type of Farms (2020)				
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms		
96.78%		3.22%		
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size	
11 ha	10 ha		38 ha	
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)				
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms		
41,685 EUR		302,042 EUR		
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)				
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)
416,090 (36.72%)	341,440 (30.14%)	256,310 (22.62%)	101,760 (8.98%)	17,430 (1.54%)
Labour Force (AWU) (2020)		Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)		
845 K		Basic: 34% (EU: 18%)		Full: 7% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)	
67.3%	5.5%	0.08	32% (EU: 28%)	

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
88.06% (EU: 91.67%)	45.75% (EU: 55.56%)	61.30% (EU: 74.71%)	49.3 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
70.7% (EU: 82.5%)	70.7% (EU: 69.2%)	99.5% (EU: 94.3%)	4.0% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
70.2% (EU: 72.9%)		63.1% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP²⁶

Prioritisation Level

In Italy's CAP NSP, digitalisation is prioritised mainly as "Complementary", with one notable exception. The specific need E3.2 (Implement and or enhance telematics and digital infrastructure) is designated "Strategic" in mountain and hill areas and "Specific" in plain areas. This reflects Italy's acknowledgement of the digital divide in rural and upland regions and the central role of connectivity in enabling wider CAP aims such as innovation, access to services, and precision farming. While the CAP NSP addresses these interventions in part, they are substantially reinforced through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR).

Several other digitalisation-related needs are also classified as "Complementary", including EA.5 (Promote the use of digital tools) and EA.6 (Stimulate business participation in the development of innovations). These needs support the uptake of digital solutions across the agricultural sector, including the use of precision agriculture, smart farming technologies, and participation in AKIS. While not ranked as top priorities overall, their inclusion and funding highlight Italy's effort to align rural development with broader EU digital transformation goals.

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

The NSP includes an extensive Strategy for Digitalisation built around three overarching objectives: (1) reducing the digital divide, (2) increasing data use, and (3) developing digitised business models, each supported by specific strategic lines and actions. To reduce the digital divide, actions include broadband deployment (e.g., "Italy to 1 Giga" and 5G plans under the PNRR), digitalisation of essential rural services, "smart village" strategies, targeted information campaigns on digital opportunities, and training/advisory activities to boost digital literacy among farmers and AKIS advisors. To increase data use, the Plan promotes open access to research and Operational Group project data, supports interoperability projects and incentives for interoperable platforms, and encourages the collection and sharing of agricultural, geospatial, and environmental data via precision-agriculture commitments and partnerships (e.g., Horizon Europe's "Agriculture of Data"). To foster digitalised business models, actions focus on strengthening the wider ecosystem through Public Administration digitalisation, activating the Digital Innovation Hub network and back-office support services, disseminating information and deploying decision support platforms, and providing capital grants and incentives for acquiring digital tools. The Plan envisages further supporting adoption through on-farm advisory, demonstration events and innovation support services, with continuous governance, monitoring and evaluation frameworks in place.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

Digitalisation goals in Italy's CAP NSP are closely aligned with broader CAP priorities, including climate action, biodiversity conservation, and resilience. The Plan promotes digital tools and infrastructure to enable precision farming, resource-efficient practices, and early warning systems, helping to limit environmental impacts and support adaptation to climate change. Integration with AKIS is used to encourage uptake of climate-smart technologies, improve sustainable input management and strengthen monitoring of emissions and biodiversity indicators, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of

²⁶ National Rural Network (2024). *CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027*. Retrieved from <https://www.referurale.it/flex/cm/pages/ServeBLOB.php/L/IT/IDPagina/24037> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

agri-environmental measures and the Plan's strategic environmental objectives.

On the socio-economic side, digitalisation is aligned with priorities such as rural vitality, youth inclusion, and competitiveness. The Plan highlights that digital infrastructure and services (especially in mountainous and remote areas) are critical to reduce territorial disparities and enable access to innovation, training, and advisory support. Digitalisation is also tied to entrepreneurship (especially for young farmers), job creation, and the modernization of supply chains.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

The document generally promotes the adoption of “new technologies” and “digital tools” within agriculture, emphasising their role in enhancing competitiveness, sustainability, and knowledge exchange. It highlights the importance of digital agricultural technologies as part of a broader modernisation strategy to improve the sector's overall performance.

More specifically, the NSP focuses on systemic digital innovations and infrastructure. It frames digitalisation as a central tool to modernise farms and improve their competitiveness, with a particular emphasis on research, innovation, and the uptake of new technologies. This is realised through specific measures including investments in precision agriculture, support for e-commerce and blockchain technologies, and the promotion of digital tools for improved resource management and supply chain efficiency. While the text does not always list every individual technology, it consistently refers to the broader adoption of precision agriculture, digital platforms, and data systems that support farm management and environmental monitoring. The Plan promotes the establishment and use of interoperable platforms and explicitly mentions the creation of a national data platform as a key initiative. Furthermore, the document underscores the significance of open data, data collection (particularly agricultural, geospatial, and environmental data), and the digitalisation of public administration.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

The NSP places a clear emphasis on closing the digital divide, particularly in rural and mountainous areas. This is reflected in the prioritisation of need E3.2 (Implement and/or enhance telematics and digital infrastructure), which is assigned a “Strategic” level in hill and mountain areas, and “Specific” in the plains. The Plan recognises the need to extend broadband and ultra-wideband in underserved rural zones, improve the quality of ICT services, and strengthen digital skills among businesses and citizens.

To promote territorial equity, the NSP commits to deploying the “Italy to 1 Giga” programme and meeting the EU's Digital Compass 2030 targets so that rural communities have access to the same high-speed connectivity and digital services as urban areas, aligning national and EU instruments to pursue full coverage and inclusion. It also notes that digital infrastructure in these territories will be partly financed through the CAP NSP and complemented by the PNRR and the Development and Cohesion Fund. These investments are intended to achieve full coverage, including “last mile” connections, directly addressing the structural disadvantages faced by less connected rural and upland regions.

AKIS within the NSP

The document provides detailed operational descriptions for AKIS. It outlines a plural, multi-level structure comprising 19 regional AKIS, two provincial AKIS (Trento and Bolzano), and one national AKIS, reflecting Italy's decentralised governance. Interventions are clustered under the Cooperation and Knowledge and Information Exchange, using a systemic and territorial approach that brings together all the relevant actors (advisory services, training bodies, research, businesses, civil society, and public administration). Key operational actions include promoting synergistic implementation of interventions, fostering cooperation among AKIS components (e.g., development of innovation support services via specific cooperative forms), re-framing European Innovation Partnership (EIP) Operational Groups with enhanced participatory modalities, training AKIS practitioners, and assigning the National CAP Network to coordinate networking actions at both national and regional levels.

Coordination mechanisms are designed to align with the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), European Social Fund (ESF), Horizon Europe (notably Cluster 6 and the Pact for Soil Mission), Erasmus+, the PNRR, and the National Research Programme 2021-2027. The Plan also leverages digital platforms such as Copernicus, FADN, FAST and an updated SIAN to improve information flows and the dissemination of innovation.

Monitoring and evaluation

Italy's CAP NSP sets clear monitoring targets across knowledge, advisory services, digitalisation, climate action, and the smart transition of rural areas. Under R.1 (Improving performance through knowledge and innovation), Italy targets 431,868 people benefiting from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in CAP supported EIP Operational Groups to strengthen sustainable implementation across economic, social, environmental, climate, and resource efficiency dimensions. For R.2 (Connecting systems for counselling and knowledge), the Plan supports 16,070 advisors to be integrated within AKIS. R.3 (Digitalising agriculture) aims for 0.10% of farms to receive support for digital farming technologies through the CAP. Under R.28 (Effectiveness of environmental or climate implementation knowledge and innovation), the target is 120,000 people benefiting from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in CAP

supported EIP Operational Groups focused on effective environmental and climate implementation. Finally, R.40 (Smart transition of the rural economy) foresees support for 404 strategies in “smart small municipalities”.

AKIS Factsheet²⁷

The Italian AKIS reflects the complexity of both the national administrative system and the agricultural sector. The former is highly decentralized, with the national government setting general rules that regions then adapt and apply to their territories. The latter is highly varied, shaped by the multiple environmental and socio-economic features of the Italian countryside. As a result, the Italian AKIS is a complex multi-actor and multi-layered system, characterised by a large number of entities operating across multiple governance levels. It features countless actors and stakeholders who work on overlapping topics but maintain specific fields of expertise and areas of competency.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- **About farm advice:** The number and diversity of advisory service providers continues to grow, bringing in new entrants as well as established actors that now support innovation and introduce new advisory topics and methods. A parallel development is the formation of associations among freelancers, who see opportunities to broaden their service offer and provide a holistic advisory approach to whole farm management.
- **About public policies:** The shared responsibilities between national and regional levels on AKIS matters has both benefits and drawbacks. On the positive side, services and skills are widely available across the country. On the negative side, the large number of actors complicates coordination and can slow the diffusion of innovation. This tension between a rich landscape of actors and weak coordination was a central consideration in designing the national AKIS strategy.
- **Some trends:** Italy is witnessing a growing trend of pluralism in the provision of consulting services that, unlike in the past, is more organised, better governed, and more engaged in dialogue with multiple AKIS actors. This reflects stronger organisational structures in both the private and public spheres, and a renewed recognition of private providers as interlocutors by policy makers and other system actors such as researchers and academics. As a result, points of reference are becoming clearer and knowledge flows within the AKIS are more structured.

²⁷ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the authors of the report: **Simona Cristiano, Valentina Carta, Patrizia Proietti, Maria Valentina Lasorella, Concetta Menna, Lucia Tudini, Giuseppina Costantini, and Mara Lai.** We thank them for their work. <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/csFcQJc6r7NacJd#pdfviewer>

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
64,594 km ²	1,871,882	29.0 people/km ²	31.2%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
954,883	6.9%	62.6 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
40,208 million EUR	21,610 EUR	1.3%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)				
Agriculture: 31.7%; forest: 54.9%; other: 13.4%				
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops	
1,970 K ha	1,357 K ha (68.9%)	603 K ha (30.6%)	10 K ha (0.5%)	
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)				
861,575 ha (43.8% UAA)				
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)	
68,980	9,805 EUR/AWU		14%	
Type of Farms (2020)				
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms		
96.04%		3.96%		
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size	
29 ha	21 ha		222 ha	
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)				
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms		
11,694 EUR		212,858 EUR		
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)				
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)
53,680 (77.82%)	7,970 (11.55%)	5,010 (7.26%)	1,940 (2.81%)	380 (0.55%)

Labour Force (AWU) (2020)		Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)	
66.5 K		Basic: 21% (EU: 18%)	Full: 30% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)
60.0%	5.2%	0.09	45% (EU: 28%)

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
92.32% (EU: 91.67%)	45.34% (EU: 55.56%)	80.61% (EU: 74.71%)	51.1 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
68.1% (EU: 82.5%)	61.1% (EU: 69.2%)	71.1% (EU: 94.3%)	4.9% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
59.2% (EU: 72.9%)		48.2% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP²⁸

Prioritisation Level

Digitalisation is assigned a medium priority and is embedded within broader objectives on technological advancement and efficiency. Several identified needs explicitly refer to digitalisation and related innovation processes. In particular, “promoting the use of technology in enterprises, increasing their efficiency and improving digitalisation” carries medium priority under HORIZ V6. The theme is reinforced across other needs with medium or growing priority. HORIZ V4, which promotes access to knowledge and advisory support, and HORIZ V5, which promotes the professional development of consultants, both treat digitalisation as a core element of updated advisory services. In addition, SM2 V8 on the use of new technologies and digital tools and SM3 V2 on encouraging research and the uptake of new technologies are marked as growing priorities, indicating rising strategic importance.

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

Latvia’s digitalisation strategy under the NSP emphasises building farmers’ digital skills, encouraging technology uptake, and supporting investment in digital tools. Interventions such as training, demonstration projects, and advisory services are intended to raise awareness and practical use of digital technologies, especially among small and medium-sized farms. Farmers will be encouraged to use the new digital record-keeping system, the VAAD LIZ Management System (an agricultural system developed by the State Plant Protection Service) to plan and record their field activities. Additional support includes funding for precision technologies in arable and livestock farming, digital trading platforms, and e-services under various investment programs. The strategy also acknowledges broader connectivity goals, including EU targets for rural broadband access, although some infrastructure developments are funded outside the CAP NSP. Complementary national and EU initiatives, such as Horizon Europe and the Recovery and Resilience Facility, support the overall digital transformation.

While the document outlines clear goals and indicative actions, including support for ICT, robotics, and data-driven decision-making, it stops short of detailing implementation timelines, metrics, or specific technologies. Digitalisation is therefore positioned as a cross-cutting priority with practical relevance, while operational details are left to be further developed.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

The NSP treats digitalisation as a cross-cutting enabler that supports multiple CAP priorities, particularly climate action, environmental sustainability, and socio-economic development. Digital tools are promoted to improve resource efficiency, cut greenhouse gas emissions and support precision farming, thereby contributing directly to climate and biodiversity objectives. Smart farming systems, digital record keeping and data driven decision making are linked to eco-schemes and agri-environmental investments, signalling a deliberate alignment between digital uptake and environmental performance. This connection is further reflected in relevant result indicators, including R.3 and R.28.

²⁸ Ministry of Agriculture (2022). *Latvia’s Common Agricultural Policy Strategic Plan for 2023-2027*. Retrieved from <https://www.zm.gov.lv/lv/latvijas-kopejas-lauksaimniecibas-politikas-strategiskais-plans-2023-2027gadamo> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

On the socio-economic side, digitalisation is positioned to strengthen rural vitality and farm resilience, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises. Through investments in digital advisory services, AKIS development, and demonstration farms, the Plan seeks to reduce knowledge gaps and improve competitiveness in lagging rural regions. These actions are expected to increase added value in the agri-food sector, foster innovation, and open new income opportunities, thereby supporting balanced regional development and economic diversification.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

The Plan identifies specific needs (such as the uptake of digital tools, skills development, and the adoption of smart farming) and links them to targeted interventions. These include advisory services, demonstration farms, and eco-schemes that incentivise practices like digital field planning.

Furthermore, the Plan promotes a range of specific digital technologies, emphasising the use of precision agriculture tools, digital field planning software, e-services, environmental monitoring systems, and data-driven farm management platforms. More concretely, Latvia's NSP encourages the adoption of ICT platforms, robotics, and smart farming equipment to boost productivity, reduce input use, and support climate adaptation. The adoption of these technologies is incentivised through interventions under eco-schemes and innovation-focused measures, with the explicit aim of enhancing environmental performance and resource efficiency.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

The document addresses digital inclusion and territorial equity by explicitly acknowledging regional disparities in farmers' and foresters' incomes, as well as differences in digital readiness and access. It outlines targeted strategies to bridge the digital divide, focusing on small and medium-sized farms, less-developed rural areas, and disadvantaged groups. The CAP NSP promotes equitable access to digital advisory services, training opportunities, and demonstration projects across all regions of Latvia, with the goal of ensuring that the benefits of digitalisation are shared broadly and inclusively.

The Plan recognises that the high cost of network construction limits commercial incentives to deploy very high-performance electronic communications networks. It therefore signals the need to expand broadband infrastructure and to promote deployment in areas where market interest is absent or insufficient. The document also highlights that these actions will not be financed under the CAP. Instead, for the implementation of the tasks included in the Electronic Communications and Post Sector Risk Assessment and National Risk Mitigation Plan (ESN Plan), Latvia plans to attract European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and national co-financing, with additional support potentially mobilised from the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) and the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF).

AKIS within the NSP

AKIS is presented as a structural pillar for achieving the CAP's broader objectives. The document describes the system as fragmented and highlights the need for greater integration among stakeholders involved in knowledge generation and dissemination. It proposes targeted measures to improve coordination among research institutions, advisory services, education providers, and end-users. The interventions aim to enhance the quality, accessibility, and territorial reach of knowledge and innovation services. The cross-cutting objective outlines how AKIS will be operationalised, including investment in advisory systems, training for consultants, support for demonstration farms, and the integration of vocational institutions.

To address fragmentation, the Plan foresees the creation of an AKIS Focal Point within the National CAP Network to coordinate activities, disseminate innovations, and improve stakeholder communication. Specific interventions under the NSP include support for training, demonstration projects, individual counselling, and collaborative innovation actions, with an AKIS subcommittee under the CAP Monitoring Committee guiding implementation priorities. Advisors play a central role by communicating farmers' needs to the Focal Point, ensuring a feedback loop that informs future knowledge sharing and innovation efforts.

In addition, the Plan highlights the role of demonstration farms and pilot projects as mechanisms to showcase and disseminate innovative digital solutions. These initiatives are designed to promote hands-on learning and foster practical uptake among farmers, especially in small and medium-sized holdings. The document also stresses the development of advisory services and training tailored to digital skills, ensuring that both farmers and consultants are equipped to implement new technologies effectively.

Monitoring and evaluation

Latvia's CAP NSP sets clear monitoring and evaluation targets across knowledge, advice, digitalisation, and environmental performance. Under R.1, the country aims for 23,383 people to benefit from counselling, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in European Innovation Partnership (EIP) Operational Groups. Through R.2, it plans support for 304 consultants to be integrated into AKIS, strengthening the link between advisory delivery and knowledge systems. For R.3, Latvia targets the digital transition by foreseeing that 0.49% of farms will receive CAP support for digital agricultural

technologies, equal to 345 farms out of 69,930. Finally, under R.28, Latvia expects 7,133 people to take part in knowledge transfer and innovation activities related to environmental or climate performance, supported by CAP.

AKIS Factsheet²⁹

The restoration of Latvian independence in 1990, together with profound political, social, and economic change, has strongly shaped the composition and functioning of today's AKIS. Many AKIS institutions (universities, agricultural schools and research institutes) have long histories dating back to the 19th century and continuing through the Soviet period, with well established research traditions, institutional ties and an accumulated knowledge base. At the same time, post-socialist changes such as privatisation, the introduction of a market economy and the restructuring of agricultural production required a reorganisation of the system. To meet the needs of new farmers, many without agricultural backgrounds, the Ministry of Agriculture and the Latvian Farmers' Federation created the Latvian Rural Advisory and Training Centre in 1991, building an extensive network of advisers across the country. A further milestone was the EU accession process launched in the late 1990s, which drove significant transformations in both agriculture and the AKIS.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- **About farm advice:** There is a broad range of advisory actors, with the Latvian Rural Advisory and Training Centre taking a leading role through its 26 local offices across the country. Farmer NGOs, cooperatives, input suppliers and private independent consultants also play significant roles.
- **About public policies:** Coordination is supported by various multi-actor institutions. More recently, a policy instrument in the form of innovation vouchers has been introduced to promote knowledge exchange.
- **Some trends:** As part of its national innovation policy, Latvia has established business incubators, knowledge transfer centres, industry innovation clusters and other transdisciplinary platforms that facilitate learning, knowledge exchange and support for digitalisation.

²⁹ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the authors of the report: **Anita Dzelve** and **Kaspars Žūriņš**. We thank them for their work. <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/EC8CQ2RrpJw7R2#pdfviewer>

Netherlands

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
37,391 km ²	17,942,942	479.9 people/km ²	6.5%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
10,315,268	3.7%	78.8 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
1,122,459 million EUR	62,380 EUR	1.5%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)				
Agriculture: 53.6%; forest: 11.0%; other: 35.4%				
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops	
1,805 K ha	1,004 K ha (55.6%)	763 K ha (42.3%)	38 K ha (2.1%)	
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)				
N/A				
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)	
52,640	51,775 EUR/AWU		2%	
Type of Farms (2020)				
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms		
89.35%		10.65%		
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size	
35 ha	35 ha		33 ha	
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)				
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms		
342,715 EUR		1,561,584 EUR		
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)				
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)
3,150 (5.98%)	6,440 (12.23%)	9,200 (17.48%)	20,180 (38.34%)	13,680 (25.99%)
Labour Force (AWU) (2020)		Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)		
150.7 K		Basic: 19% (EU: 18%)		Full: 63% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)	
54.7%	4.6%	0.08	5% (EU: 28%)	

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
99.22% (EU: 91.67%)	82.70% (EU: 55.56%)	96.38% (EU: 74.71%)	71.5 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
98.4% (EU: 82.5%)	85.3% (EU: 69.2%)	100.0% (EU: 94.3%)	7.0% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
80.8% (EU: 72.9%)		74.6% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP³⁰

Prioritisation Level

Digitalisation is not identified as a distinct need and is not explicitly referenced under any of the 31 officially listed needs, so no prioritisation level is assigned in the document. This likely reflects the country's already advanced uptake of digital tools. However, the digitalisation strategy positions it as a key enabler of the green transition, data-driven decision making, and greater efficiency and sustainability in farming. Planned actions include investment in data infrastructure, development of digital skills, and the integration of precision agriculture, artificial intelligence and robotics.

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

Digitalisation is identified in the document as a growing and integral part of AKIS and the broader CAP strategy. It is described as playing an increasingly important role in knowledge networks, particularly in improving access to data, facilitating innovation, and supporting sustainability goals. Its delivery is supported through structures such as European Digital Innovation Hubs, the Green Knowledge Network, and national platforms that share knowledge and promote collaborative innovation.

Digitalisation is embedded within the AKIS framework and supports knowledge flows, innovation and the practical application of research via mechanisms such as the European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI), the CAP Network and the National Precision Agriculture Laboratory. The CAP Network is tasked with strengthening connections in the CAP by applying modern (digital) technology and experimenting with new digital opportunities. Specific initiatives include lifelong learning pilots on precision farming and permanent education systems linked to digital content like e-learning modules and wikis. The network support unit is also mandated to strengthen CAP connections by applying modern digital technologies and experimenting with new digital opportunities. Digitalisation is not treated as a standalone priority but is embedded across knowledge-sharing, innovation, and advisory structures as a tool to modernise and improve the effectiveness of CAP interventions.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

The NSP presents digitalisation as a key enabler across CAP priorities, supporting environmental sustainability, climate objectives and economic resilience. It positions digital tools as practical means to improve agricultural practices, facilitating more efficient input use and enabling robust monitoring and data collection. The Plan strategically aligns investments in digital technologies with broader strategies to strengthen farm viability, such as promoting circular agriculture and enhancing biodiversity. These digitally focused investments are eligible for CAP support and are designed to assist farmers (including young farmers) in undertaking the necessary transitions to improve climate mitigation, adaptation, and resource management.

Furthermore, digitalisation is framed as a horizontal objective that strengthens the entire knowledge ecosystem. Deeply integrated within the AKIS, it is intended to streamline information flows and ensure broad access to innovative project outcomes. The NSP also explicitly links digitalisation to enhanced risk management and data-driven decision-making at both

³⁰ Rural Network (2022). *CAP NSP 2023-2027 Program Document, version 1.2*. Retrieved from <https://www.netwerkplatteland.nl/documenten/publicaties/2022/10/28/programmadocument-nsp-qlb-2023-2027-versie-1.2> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

the farm and policy levels. By promoting digital connectivity and the secure exchange of knowledge among stakeholders, the Plan positions digitalisation as a supportive element to achieve overarching goals related to socio-economic development, resilience, and sustainable food systems.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

The document promotes several specific digital technologies and innovations in the context of supporting modernisation, sustainability, and competitiveness in the agricultural sector. It explicitly mentions the use of robotic technology and big data applications in crop protection as methods to enhance input efficiency and reduce emissions, waste, and residues. Techniques such as spot-wise precision application and digital observation of diseases and pests are highlighted as contributing to more targeted use of crop protection products. The Plan also refers to the application of sensor technologies and automation tools in agricultural processes, particularly in the fruit and vegetable sector, where investments in ICT systems, cameras, and other sensors are supported to facilitate automation and data collection.

The NSP backs these technologies through interventions that develop and implement ICT systems for process optimisation and knowledge sharing. This includes digital platforms to secure and unlock knowledge, and communication tools such as webinars and podcasts to disseminate project results and inspire practice. Collaboration with the Green Knowledge Network is used to ensure digital assurance and effective dissemination, while sectoral innovation and research are encouraged through the National Precision Agriculture Laboratory and European Digital Innovation Hubs. The Plan also notes the strong national connectivity, including widespread 4G and 5G coverage and high average internet speeds, which supports the uptake of smart farming and agricultural IoT solutions such as weather stations and soil sensors that provide near real-time data.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

The NSP acknowledges that agriculture contributes to broader societal objectives, specifically naming “goals around social cohesion, liveability and social inclusion.” However, the document does not offer explicit measures to address critical issues such as the digital divide, territorial equity, or digital inclusion for disadvantaged groups. Most substantively, the document highlights that threats of exclusion lie in the design of digital systems and the autonomy of agricultural entrepreneurs in relation to the generation and use of data. It cites the EU code of conduct on agricultural data sharing as a foundation to strengthen the data position and sovereignty of agricultural SMEs vis-à-vis large suppliers. The Plan encourages cooperation among farmers to co-design digital systems so that business autonomy is preserved, for example through digital cooperatives. It also promotes co-ownership of the digital ecosystem, enabling agricultural entrepreneurs to benefit from new revenue models linked to digital innovation, and to capture the added value of processed data both commercially and financially rather than acting solely as data providers and users. Across the sector, the Data Sharing Coalition is developing a system of agreements to formalise these principles, including potential labels or rules of the game.

AKIS within the NSP

The Dutch AKIS is well developed and diverse, widely regarded as a world leader in production-oriented technology and innovation geared towards input efficiency and sustainability. Its strengths include a high level of farmer education, peer-to-peer knowledge development, and the strong integration of advisors and intermediaries. Reflecting this, the NSP outlines the need for a well-functioning AKIS and emphasises the importance of supporting knowledge exchange, innovation, and digital transformation as integral to the sector's modernisation.

However, the NSP also identifies significant weaknesses, such as fragmentation among actors and limited synergies between research, education, and advisory services. In a direct response, the Plan prioritises Need N.31 (“Well-functioning Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System”) as a Category 1, horizontal goal. This is addressed through concrete measures designed to foster cooperation among research institutions, advisory services, and farmers, as well as specific support for digitalisation and innovation. These interventions include the Business Advisory System (BAS) advisor registry, lifelong learning initiatives, and more coordinated knowledge flows through a strengthened CAP Network. Ultimately, the strategy seeks to reduce fragmentation, ensure tailored and integrative farm advice, and promote social learning, cross-sector cooperation, and continuous training for advisors.

Monitoring and evaluation

In the Netherlands' CAP NSP, monitoring and evaluation focus strongly on knowledge and innovation. Under R.1, the Plan sets a target of 54,991 people who will benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in EIP Operational Groups to improve sustainable economic, social, environmental, climate and resource efficiency performance. Complementing this, R.2 aims to strengthen AKIS by supporting 2,108 advisors to become integrated within the system. For R.28, the Plan targets 32,500 people to receive advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participate in EIP Operational Groups specifically related to environmental or climate related performance. Although the narrative and intervention logic also support goals linked to R.3 (Digitisation of agriculture), the official results framework does not set measurable targets for this indicator.

AKIS Factsheet³¹

After public funding for the research-extension-education triptych ended, the Dutch AKIS remained strong but became more fragmented. Although the Netherlands is a frontrunner in innovation and input efficiency, fragmentation stems from a lack of shared vision among AKIS actors. At the same time, the system retains a rich diversity of service providers, brokers and intermediaries. The shift toward a circular agricultural model has widened the gap between public and private interests. To bring these interests closer, the government has introduced a subsidised voucher scheme that enables farmers to obtain advice and training and helps advance a common vision.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- **About farm advice:** The fragmentation of the Dutch agricultural sector led to the demise of the national agricultural extension service in the 1990s. Today, Dutch advisory services are split between sales-driven and independent advisors. Independent advisors are funded either by the government (via a voucher system or other subsidies) or directly by farmers. In contrast, sales-driven advisors are paid through a commission on the products they sell. This has resulted in a market share that is heavily skewed toward commercial advisors.
- **About public policies:** The government's aim to shift to a circular agricultural system has increased the gap between public and private interests. In response, and supported by EU policy, the government is taking action to integrate different networks in a way that accommodates diverse types of Dutch agricultural entrepreneurs. One such action is the voucher system, which allows farmers to receive advice and training. This policy has proven highly successful and has been enthusiastically adopted by both farmers and advisors.
- **Some trends:** A key challenge identified by the i2connect project points is the need to find bridging actors to support interactions and knowledge exchange beyond the duration of innovation projects supported by public calls.

³¹ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the authors of the report: **Peter Páree, Eike Dortmans, Denise van Geel, and Suze van der Velde**. We thank them for their work. <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/NXEMqQNGoieQ3BN#pdfviewer>

Poland

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
311,928 km ²	36,620,970	117.4 people/km ²	39.7%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
18,244,832	2.9%	63.4 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
845,652 million EUR	22,560 EUR	1.7%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)					
Agriculture: 46.3%; forest: 31.1%; other: 22.6%					
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops		
14,176 K ha	11,165 K ha (78.8%)	2,631 K ha (18.6%)	380 K ha (2.7%)		
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)					
1,671,578 ha (11.3% UAA)					
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)		
1,302,330	7,538 EUR/AWU		8%		
Type of Farms (2020)					
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms			
98.89%		1.11%			
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size		
11 ha	10 ha		121 ha		
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)					
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms			
17,483 EUR		301,017 EUR			
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)					
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)	
832,270 (63.91%)	262,300 (20.14%)	165,590 (12.71%)	37,820 (2.90%)	4,360 (0.33%)	

Labour Force (AWU) (2020)		Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)		
1.39 M		Basic: 14% (EU: 18%)		Full: 26% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)	
39.4%	11.0%	0.28	29% (EU: 28%)	

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
87.65% (EU: 91.67%)	44.30% (EU: 55.56%)	67.94% (EU: 74.71%)	47.1 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
83.8% (EU: 82.5%)	77.8% (EU: 69.2%)	89.3% (EU: 94.3%)	4.5% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
69.0% (EU: 72.9%)		51.8% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP³²

Prioritisation Level

Digitalisation is presented as a strategically important yet context-dependent priority, with levels of importance ranging from desirable (+) to critical (+++). Most notably, CS 8.P1 (Improving access to high-performance internet) and CS 8.P11 (Stimulating local development through innovation, digitization and leveraging endogenous potential) hold a critical (+++) prioritisation, showing the importance placed on digitalisation as an enabler of broader rural development. CS 10.P4 (Ensuring access to high-quality high-speed internet infrastructure in rural areas) is likewise critical (+++), reflecting the view that dependable digital connectivity is foundational for modern farming, reducing rural exclusion, and enabling effective advisory and innovation systems. CS 10.P6 (Increase sector innovation through the creation and use of innovative solutions) also carries a critical (+++) rating, highlighting digital tools as essential drivers of agri-food innovation. By contrast, CS 10.P2 (Development of platforms and the use of ICT in knowledge sharing and innovation) and CS 10.P5 (Creation of open collections of public data and their wide use) are rated as required (++) , signalling their enabling role for stronger knowledge flows. All of these needs, with the exception of CS 8.P1, are partially addressed in the CAP NSP. In addition, other identified digitalisation needs target economic resilience and service delivery in rural areas. For example, CS 3.P7 (Use of digitalisation in accessing financial services, information and improving the supply chain) is rated as desirable (+), indicating its supportive role in improving market functioning. This need is not addressed in the document.

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

The NSP states that fixed internet access has improved but significant gaps persist in rural and sparsely populated areas. Accordingly, it sets an objective of universal high-speed broadband for all households by 2030 and embeds measures to promote digitalisation in agriculture within wider national strategies and CAP instruments such as LEADER, alongside investments in farm level digital technologies. The document specifies operational objectives to develop ICT infrastructure, promote digital tools for farm management, enable remote advisory services, and strengthen digital education. It refers to the use of satellite technologies, decision support systems such as eDWIN, and publicly accessible platforms for meteorological and drought data. It also commits to integrating agricultural actors into Horizon Europe and to establishing a Digital Innovation Hub for agriculture under the Digital Europe Programme. The NSP highlights ongoing and planned investments, including those financed by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan and the European funds for digital development. Digitalisation is integrated into local development strategies, notably through Smart Villages, which leverage digital tools to address local challenges and stimulate economic activity. Improving access to high performance internet (CS 8.P1) is identified as a critical need, but it is not addressed within the NSP.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

Poland's CAP NSP aligns its digitalisation goals closely with core CAP priorities, using digital tools as both enablers and accelerators of environmental, economic, and social outcomes. In climate action and biodiversity, digitalisation supports precision agriculture, more efficient input use, and stronger monitoring systems, helping to cut greenhouse gas emissions and ease environmental pressures. Digital advisory platforms and ICT tools are intended to support farmers in adopting

³² Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (n.d.). *Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for the years 2023-2027*. Retrieved from <https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo/plan-strategiczny-dla-wspolnej-polityki-rolnej-na-lata-2023-27> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

sustainable practices, consistent with objectives on climate change mitigation (Specific Objective 4) and soil and water protection (Specific Objective 5), while open data initiatives are expected to improve access to environmental information and reinforce evidence-based decision making and innovation in eco-efficient farming. On the socio-economic front, expanding high-speed internet in rural areas is treated as critical for quality of life, access to services, and support for entrepreneurship and remote work. Smart Villages integrate digitalisation with local innovation and community-led development to strengthen rural economies and counter marginalisation. Combined with AKIS-based digital training, these measures seek to equip farmers and rural communities to adapt to structural change, participate more effectively in value chains, and build long-term socio-economic resilience.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

The document outlines key functional categories of digital tools deemed essential for agricultural modernisation and knowledge exchange. Precision farming is prominently cited for its important role in improving sustainability, productivity, and resource efficiency. The Plan emphasises the implementation of precision agriculture tools, decision support systems, and modern irrigation technologies to help farmers adapt to climate variability and optimise input use. This is supported by references to specific technologies (including milking and feeding robots, the precision application of fertilisers and pesticides, herd management systems, and precision sprayers), all intended to boost production efficiency while minimising environmental impact.

Beyond specific technologies, the NSP signals a broad commitment to fostering a digital ecosystem. This is evident in its promotion of ICT platforms for advisory services, tools for data collection and sharing, and systems enabling remote knowledge exchange, particularly within the AKIS and Smart Villages frameworks. The Plan encourages the application of digital tools in diverse areas such as risk management, contract implementation, and supply chain optimisation, while deliberately avoiding rigid prescriptions of specific technologies. This flexible approach is reinforced by the Plan's emphasis on key enablers like digital advisory systems, open data infrastructures, broadband connectivity, and digital skill-building.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

The NSP explicitly addresses digital inclusion, territorial equity, and the digital divide as core elements of its digitalisation strategy, while acknowledging important gaps. It prioritises expanding high-speed internet in rural areas as a critical precondition for participation in modern agricultural and economic activity (e.g., CS 10.P4 and CS 8.P1). The document also recognises that rural territories face structural disadvantages in connectivity and digital literacy, and it promotes targeted support for disadvantaged groups, including young people, women, and excluded communities, to ensure equitable access to digital tools and services. Initiatives such as Smart Villages and digital skills training are intended to empower local actors, reduce rural marginalisation, and support balanced territorial development, positioning digital transformation as a driver of both inclusion and cohesion.

At the same time, improving access to high performance internet (CS 8.P1) is identified as critical but is not addressed in the NSP, and the inclusion of disadvantaged or excluded rural groups (CS 8.P10) is rated desirable but only partially addressed. The Plan identifies several interconnected challenges in rural areas: higher poverty rates, a skills mismatch in the labour market (exacerbated by events like the closure of state farms), and weak digital skills. These factors are linked to rising professional inactivity and social exclusion. The document also notes additional pressures from migration, highlighting the difficulties faced by those fleeing armed conflict in integrating into new local communities. In response, it calls for activation measures for disadvantaged and excluded groups, including training and advisory offers to support retraining, recognition of existing skills, development of digital competences, and broader knowledge building. It also stresses the importance of strengthening local identity and civic and social participation, with public institutions (for example village community centres) and community organisations – such as sports clubs, Rural Housewives' Circles (KGWs), and Local Action Groups (LAGs) – playing a key role. CAP support is intended to complement measures available under cohesion policy.

AKIS within the NSP

The document describes Poland's plan to strengthen agricultural knowledge exchange and innovation by supporting closer AKIS cooperation, especially via the National Rural Network (KSOW+) and European Innovation Partnership (EIP) Operational Groups. It prioritises stronger advisory and training services for farmers, with a focus on both agricultural production and on-farm processing. Coordination is to be overseen by the Department of Strategy and Development at the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, which will also supervise 12 research institutes. Agricultural advisory units play a central role, notably the Agricultural Advisory Centre in Brwinów and the provincial centres, which are tasked with providing training, advisory, and information services. The NSP also supports the integration of ICT in advisory provision and promotes collaboration with universities, research institutes, and businesses. Targeted interventions, including professional development of farmers and comprehensive agricultural advisory, are designed to address deficits in knowledge and competencies among producers and to improve access to high-quality training and advisory services.

Monitoring and evaluation

Poland's CAP NSP sets clear monitoring targets across knowledge, advisory, digital, environmental, and rural

transformation outcomes. For R.1 (Increase efficiency through knowledge and innovation), the Plan aims for 127,209 people to benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in EIP Operational Groups. Under R.2 (Linking advisory and knowledge systems), 103,332 advisors are targeted to receive support for integration into the AKIS. For R.3 (Digital transformation of agriculture), the target is that 0.30% of farms will receive CAP support for digital agricultural technologies. In R.28 (Environmental or climate efficiency based on knowledge and innovation), 25,244 people are expected to receive advice, training, or knowledge exchange related to environmental or climate performance within the EIP framework. Finally, for R.40 (Smart transition of the rural economy), the Plan sets a target of supporting 18 smart village strategies.

AKIS Factsheet³³

Poland's AKIS brings together many actors, including public administration, research organisations, schools, agricultural advisory services, associations and industry bodies, non-governmental organisations, and enterprises. Coordination is led by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development through the Department of Innovation, Knowledge Transfer and Digitalisation, which serves as the AKIS coordination body (AKIS CB), supported by a broad ecosystem of public and private providers.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- **About farm advice:** A public agricultural advisory system operates as one of the instruments for the delivery of government policy on agriculture and rural development. The system comprises 16 Regional Agricultural Advisory Services and the Agricultural Advisory Centre in Brwinów, with branch offices in Kraków, Poznań, Radom and Warsaw (which hosts the National Rural Network and the National Support Unit). Other key providers include agricultural chambers, producer associations and cooperatives, and private agricultural advisers.
- **About public policies:** The public agricultural advisory network is funded directly from the state budget, which covers about 60-70% of total operating costs (the remainder comes from fee-based services for farmers). Advisory services provided by Agricultural Chambers and sectoral farming organisations are financed through member fees. European policy instruments under the CAP have also been important. In the Rural Development Programme 2014-2020, Measure 16 (Cooperation) was especially relevant to promote innovation, supporting Operational Groups as a policy tool to develop innovative projects through a multi-actor approach bringing together AKIS stakeholders.
- **Some trends:** Poland faces a major challenge in renewing the aging workforce in critical advisory and other specialised agricultural professions.

³³ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the author of the report: **Aleksander Bomberski**. We thank him for his work. <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/fyJcL3NGWKCrpP#pdfviewer>

Slovakia

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
49,035 km ²	5,424,687	110.6 people/km ²	45.8%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
2,779,407	5.3%	59.9 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
130,985 million EUR	24,000 EUR	0.5%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)				
Agriculture: 38.5%; forest: 40.1%; other: 21.5%				
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops	
1,849 K ha	1,323 K ha (71.6%)	509 K ha (27.5%)	17 K ha (0.9%)	
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)				
731,927 ha (38.3% UAA)				
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)	
19,630	17,304 EUR/AWU		9%	
Type of Farms (2020)				
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms		
80.96%		19.04%		
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size	
95 ha	19 ha		418 ha	
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)				
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms		
17,269 EUR		459,554 EUR		
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)				
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)
11,440 (58.28%)	3,710 (18.90%)	2,200 (11.21%)	1,400 (7.13%)	880 (4.48%)

Labour Force (AWU) (2020)		Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)	
41.84 K		Basic: 13% (EU: 18%)	Full: 11% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)
46.5%	11.1%	0.24	19% (EU: 28%)

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
88.87% (EU: 91.67%)	51.31% (EU: 55.56%)	76.15% (EU: 74.71%)	47.2 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
73.0% (EU: 82.5%)	67.8% (EU: 69.2%)	87.9% (EU: 94.3%)	4.6% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
62.9% (EU: 72.9%)		45.8% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP³⁴

Prioritisation Level

Digitalisation is embedded across multiple intervention areas, although not always articulated as a standalone need. Its prioritisation can be inferred from related needs that reference digital tools, smart platforms, and innovation support. Notably, need 10.4, which calls for an AKIS digital platform to improve stakeholder access to information, is rated high priority. Need 10.1, focused on increasing knowledge exchange and innovation, implicitly covers the uptake of digital and smart technologies and is likewise rated high. Broader investment objectives further reinforce the role of digitalisation. Need 2.1, to increase the competitiveness of agricultural holdings through modernisation, carries a very high priority and explicitly highlights new technologies, innovation, and digitalisation. In addition, need 5.5, improving water management and reducing water consumption at farm level, is medium priority and cites the use of smart technologies to automate irrigation timing, while need 8.6, supporting local public infrastructure, basic services, and social life, is high priority and references smart solutions for rural development.

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

Slovakia's approach to digitalisation in the CAP NSP is aligned with the national Digital Transformation Strategy 2030 and is organised around three strands: electronic administration, digital farming, and stakeholder engagement. Acknowledging the digital divide, particularly in rural and less developed areas, the Plan prioritises investment in two foundational areas: high-speed connectivity and the development of digital skills, the latter to be delivered through regional AKIS competence centres.

The core of its digital farming ambition involves the creation of a cloud-based SK Agriculture Data Space. This platform is designed for secure data collection and analysis, enabling the application of advanced technologies like AI, machine learning, and IoT. To translate this into practical tools for farmers, a Farmer Portal and Farmer's Diary are planned to support predictive data use and efficient farm management. Financial support for adopting these technologies, including for precision farming, robotics, and smart forestry, will be channelled through prioritised CAP interventions.

Furthermore, the NSP aims to mainstream digital tools across the sector. For public administration, the goal is to implement a fully electronic system for submission and case management to improve efficiency and access, particularly for smallholders and young farmers. To drive awareness and uptake among stakeholders, initiatives such as the introduction of digitalisation ambassadors and targeted training programmes are also planned.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

The CAP NSP integrates its digitalisation agenda within broader CAP priorities, consistently framing digital technologies as enabling tools for competitiveness, environmental performance, and socio-economic development. While not a standalone objective, digitalisation is embedded across these goals as a key modernising force. This is most explicit under SO2, where it is presented as essential for enhancing the competitiveness of agricultural holdings. Acknowledging the current

³⁴ Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic (2022). *Strategic Plan of the CAP 2023-2027*. Retrieved from <https://www.mpsr.sk/rozvoj-vidieka-a-priame-platby-rybne-hospodarstvo/vlastny-dokument/47-43-1710> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

low level of technological advancement, the Plan emphasises investments in new technologies and innovation to boost productivity and better integrate Slovak agriculture into EU and global markets. Furthermore, the Plan clearly aligns digitalisation with environmental and resilience goals. It highlights digital tools for improving resource efficiency and climate adaptation, calling for systematic advisory support on advanced ICT and the development of an AKIS-linked digital platform to accelerate the uptake of sustainable practices. Ultimately, the digitalisation agenda is strategically positioned to support critical CAP objectives (such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, improving water management, and enhancing biodiversity) by enabling better-informed, technology-supported decision-making across the sector.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

In line with the national Digital Transformation Strategy 2030, the NSP promotes a range of specific digital technologies and innovations primarily through investment interventions. It explicitly highlights precision farming (including technologies for the precise application of pesticides and fertilisers), robotics, and digitalisation operation centres, making these eligible for increased aid intensity under productive investments. The core of this technological push is the planned SK Agriculture Data Space, a cloud-based infrastructure designed to integrate machine learning, AI, IoT, and EO for secure data collection, organisation, and analysis to support advanced farm management.

Beyond hardware, the Plan also promotes essential software solutions, including programs for agrotechnology, ventilation management in livestock farms, and digital applications for marketing and alternative sales channels. Investment interventions are designed to prioritise support for these technologies, a strategy complemented by dedicated financial instruments to encourage innovative practices. This includes support for the latest precision farming-based machinery and digital systems for post-harvest handling.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

While the NSP does not frame digital inclusion or the digital divide as explicit standalone objectives, it demonstrates a clear awareness of these challenges. It identifies key weaknesses such as a workforce shortage in advanced digital skills, a low level of digitalisation across the economy, and the threat of deepening regional disparities. Conversely, it acknowledges strengths like the rapid expansion of mobile broadband coverage and ongoing investment in high-speed infrastructure. The Plan also recognises specific administrative barriers that disproportionately limit smaller farms' access and commits to reducing these burdens. In parallel, it supports modern communication technologies and local capacity building to foster more balanced territorial access to digital services.

To address these challenges, the Slovak NSP places significant emphasis on its plan for an AKIS digital platform. This initiative is designed to achieve three core objectives: improving stakeholder access to information; strengthening coordination among advisory, training, and knowledge transfer services; and integrating existing AKIS components with new digital elements. By providing systematic advice on digitalisation and advanced ICT tools for a wide range of actors, the platform is fundamentally intended to promote a more inclusive and territorially balanced uptake of digital solutions across the agricultural sector.

AKIS within the NSP

The NSP describes a system that is undergoing significant structural changes to address existing fragmentation, lack of interconnection, and insufficient knowledge exchange. The proposed model introduces a centralised architecture integrating vertical and horizontal components through the establishment of a National Competence Centre from 2023, directly managed by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. This central body is tasked with a comprehensive mandate: to coordinate regional structures, advisors, researchers, and the CAP network. Its core functions will include ensuring systematic knowledge transfer, supporting innovation, reducing administrative burdens, and leading the formation of an Innovation and Transfer Centre to pool knowledge and disseminate practical scientific findings. Operationally, it will incorporate training, data collection, consultancy, and the creation of a digital platform interoperable with EU knowledge bases. At the regional level, agricultural competence centres will provide territory-specific support, acting as local contact points for farmers and facilitating both top-down and bottom-up knowledge flows. Advisory services will be professionalised and linked to a continuously updated catalogue managed by the central Competence Centre. To ensure inclusive and systematic coordination, the overall AKIS governance will be reinforced by a Steering Committee comprising actors from research, education, advisory bodies, and the farming sector.

Monitoring and evaluation

Slovakia sets clear targets across four CAP result indicators that are relevant for AKIS and digitalisation. Under R.1, it aims for 10,509 people to benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in CAP-supported European Innovation Partnership (EIP) Operational Groups to improve sustainable economic, environmental, and climate performance and resource efficiency. Under R.2, it plans to support 492 advisers for integration into AKIS. For R.3, Slovakia targets 3.36% of farms benefiting from support for digital agricultural technologies through the CAP. Finally, under R.28, it seeks 2,300 people benefiting from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in CAP supported EIP Operational

Groups specifically focused on environmental or climate performance.

AKIS Factsheet³⁵

The Slovak AKIS promotes knowledge transfer, innovation and technology in agriculture, forestry and rural areas. It brings together the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic (MOARD) and its organisations and agencies; public research and education bodies such as universities, secondary schools and research institutes; private companies and freelancers; farmers; forest owner organisations including associations, chambers and unions; and third sector non-governmental organisations such as EKOTREND, EKOPOLIS, forest certification bodies, and ENGOs. From a legal and institutional perspective, MOARD is the main coordinator of agricultural advisory. In practice, most functions are delegated to the Institute of Knowledge-Based Agriculture and Innovation (IZPI). MOARD has authorised IZPI's AKIS Department to deliver accredited educational activities.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- About farm advice:** Among agricultural advisory providers, the largest group consists of research institutes, followed by academic institutions such as universities and secondary vocational schools. Other key providers include public organisations under MOARD; self-governing bodies such as the National Agricultural and Food Chamber, together with farmers' associations and cooperatives; suppliers of agricultural services including input providers, machinery and technology firms, and IT service companies; and individual advisers and private advisory organisations, including NGOs and non-profit organisations.
- About public policies:** The system operates at four levels: management and methodological, organisational, executive, and target. As of 2020, Slovakia had 184 certified advisers who must meet specific criteria and undergo continuous training. Monitoring of advisory services is carried out by specialised institutions of MOARD.
- Some trends:** Digitalisation is significantly transforming the Slovakian AKIS. This is primarily evident in the wide range of digital training available, which covers topics from new technologies to sustainable farming practices, and in the key role online platforms now play in knowledge exchange.

³⁵ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the authors of the report: **Zuzana Kapsdorferová, Hubert Paluš, Dominika Čeryová, and Matej Čereš**. We thank them for their work. <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/Bco2Yiw9EjEQZd#pdfviewer>

Slovenia

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
20,273 km ²	2,123,949	104.8 people/km ²	43.6%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
1,058,286	3.7%	70.1 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
67,418 million EUR	31,700 EUR	1.0%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)					
Agriculture: 30.3%; forest: 61.3%; other: 8.4%					
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops		
479 K ha	177 K ha (37.0%)	274 K ha (57.2%)	28 K ha (5.8%)		
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)					
117,278 ha (24.2% UAA)					
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)		
72,470	6,428 EUR/AWU		7%		
Type of Farms (2020)					
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms			
99.7%		0.3%			
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size		
7 ha	N/A (Eurostat Agricultural Census data for Slovenia and Spain not comparable with other Member States)				
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)					
Family Farms		Non-Family Farms			
N/A (Eurostat Agricultural Census data for Slovenia and Spain not comparable with other Member States)					
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)					
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)	
47,170 (65.09%)	16,050 (22.15%)	7,560 (10.43%)	1,630 (2.25%)	80 (0.11%)	

Labour Force (AWU) (2020)		Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)		
71.05 K		Basic: 23% (EU: 18%)		Full: 29% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)	
65.3%	4.6%	0.07	20% (EU: 28%)	

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
89.65% (EU: 91.67%)	46.70% (EU: 55.56%)	80.56% (EU: 74.71%)	51.4 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
79.6% (EU: 82.5%)	79.6% (EU: 69.2%)	96.7% (EU: 94.3%)	4.3% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
67.6% (EU: 72.9%)		44.7% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP³⁶

Prioritisation Level

Digitalisation is treated as a horizontal objective, primarily linked to need P29 (Improving high speed broadband coverage in rural areas) and need P37 (Promote digitalisation and competence building in agriculture, forestry and SMEs). Unlike sectoral or thematic needs, these horizontal objectives are not assigned a formal prioritisation level. Nevertheless, they are integrated into the strategic framework and factored into the overall scoring criteria where feasible. Within this framework, digitalisation under P37 is recognised as a cross-cutting contributor to strengthening knowledge creation and transfer. It is partially addressed through several interventions, including Knowledge Exchange and Information Transfer, Training of Advisers, Support for European Innovation Partnership (EIP) projects, and Knowledge Institutions Consortia designed to support the transition to a green, digital, and climate-neutral agriculture. Furthermore, significant digitisation activities are financed externally through the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), notably the E-Agriculture, Food and Forestry project. It is important to note that while P37 is actioned, need P29 (broadband coverage) is not directly addressed within the NSP itself. Overall, the NSP mainstreams digitalisation across all specific objectives. Its presence is evident in relevant intervention clusters, most notably in INVEST 73–74, COOP 77, and KNOW 78.

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

The NSP outlines a comprehensive digital transformation strategy that integrates advanced technologies to enhance productivity, sustainability, and resilience across the agricultural, food, and forestry sectors. Leadership and coordination for these initiatives are centralised under the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food. Key implementation roles are assigned to specific agencies: the paying agency, the Agency for Agricultural Markets and Rural Development (ARSKTRP), is upgrading its systems to implement CAP area-based measures using satellite imagery and geospatial data, while the Public Agricultural Advisory Service (JSKS) is tasked with training farmers and advisers in the practical application of digital tools, from on-farm solutions to remote consultations.

Investment is secured through both the CAP NSP and the Recovery and Resilience Plan (RRP), funding priorities such as smart machinery, research infrastructure, and digital public services. Key tools under development include the Farm Sustainability Tool (FaST) for nutrient management and the eForestry information system. Finally, this digital push is supported by complementary data infrastructure projects, including a data warehouse and integrated information systems. These foundational elements aim to strengthen data analytics, improve policy delivery, and foster inter-agency cooperation, ultimately contributing to a more efficient, transparent, and sustainable agricultural policy framework.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

The NSP aligns digitalisation with core climate and environmental priorities, presenting it as essential for the transition to a green, climate-neutral agricultural sector. This is operationalised through the AKIS, which Chapter 8 states will prioritise content that simultaneously advances both the green and digital transitions. Concrete measures (such as optimising fertiliser use, introducing low-emission practices, and scaling precision agriculture) are explicitly designated to be enabled by digital tools. This link is further institutionalised through Needs P13, P14, P15, and P31, which address climate adaptation, soil protection, and emissions reduction, and reference technology and innovation, positioning digitalisation as a key delivery

³⁶ Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food (2024). *Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2027 (3rd amendment)*. Retrieved from <https://skp.si/skupna-kmetijska-politika-2023-2027> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

mechanism for environmental and climate objectives within the CAP framework.

Concurrently, digitalisation is tied to socio-economic development and resilience. In the context of Smart Villages and broader rural development, the Plan highlights investments in broadband and ICT to stimulate rural employment and improve quality of life, particularly under Needs P27, P28, and P29. Furthermore, capacity building and innovation support under P34 to P37 are framed as horizontal needs that facilitate generational renewal (P23), strengthen competitiveness (P06, P07), and support economic diversification. Taken together, digitalisation is integrated into strategies for income stability, youth engagement, knowledge transfer, and improved access to services, reinforcing its contribution to the CAP's broader socio-economic priorities.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

The document promotes the extensive use of digital technologies and innovations across agriculture, forestry, and food systems, noting that their adoption is already underway. It highlights a wide array of hardware (including robots, drones, sensors, intelligent machinery, geo-positioning systems, and precision measuring equipment), supported by modern ICT such as Big Data, AI, and IoT to optimise agricultural processes. Furthermore, the Plan identifies digital records and registers at farm, sector and national levels as core databases for the planning and implementation of agricultural policy. A significant focus is placed on deploying these technologies for sustainability and environmental objectives, with precision farming featuring prominently. This includes precision and low emission fertiliser equipment, targeted fertilisation and spraying based on soil analysis, planned livestock feeding informed by feed analysis, and enhanced pasture, stable and manure management. These technologies are aimed squarely at reducing methane and nitrous oxide emissions, improving plant health, and optimising resource use.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

The NSP addresses digital inclusion, territorial equity and the digital divide through measures backed by national legislation and programmes. It makes reference to the Law on Promoting Digital Inclusion, which aims to ensure that individuals can competently and safely access, use, and trust digital infrastructure and technologies. The law's objectives include raising awareness of the benefits of digital tools, building trust in technology, improving understanding of safe and responsible use, strengthening digital and entrepreneurial competences, and fostering entrepreneurship based on digital skills. These measures are expressly intended to prevent disparities between population groups.

On territorial equity, the Plan describes a comprehensive approach to closing the gap between rural and urban areas through broadband development. It recognises broadband coverage as a basic prerequisite for rural development and states that all "white spots" without access will be addressed. Although the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) will not finance broadband construction in the 2023-2027 period, funding will be drawn from the Recovery and Resilience Plan (RRP), the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), InvestEU, and the Digital Europe Programme (DEP). The Gigabit Infrastructure Development Plan targets internet connectivity of at least 100 Mbps, upgradable to gigabit speeds, for all households by 2025, and full gigabit connectivity and 5G coverage for all populated areas by 2028. These efforts are coordinated by the Government Office for Digital Transformation and aligned with national and EU digital objectives, ensuring that rural and geographically challenging areas are included in Slovenia's digital transition.

AKIS within the NSP

According to the NSP, Slovenia plans to develop its AKIS into a coordinated system to strengthen knowledge generation, exchange, and innovation, with the ultimate goal of improving the competitiveness and resilience of its agricultural sector. Central to this delivery is the JSKS, which operates regionally under the Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry of Slovenia. This agency is tasked with providing free expert advice on agriculture and rural development, leading knowledge transfer and training, and supporting innovation, including participation in EIP Operational Groups.

The NSP prioritises a user-centred approach, emphasising capacity building, formal and non-formal education, and intergenerational knowledge transfer. A key measure in this regard is IRP38, which supports innovation consortia to drive the transition towards green, digital, and climate-neutral agriculture. Financing for these activities is planned from a blend of national funds, CAP interventions, and the Recovery and Resilience Plan. Implementation will be driven by a set of specific measures, including IRP30 (Intergenerational knowledge transfer), IRP31 (Support for EIP projects), IRP32 (Knowledge sharing and information transfer), and the aforementioned IRP38. The overall system emphasises coordinated collaboration among ministries, public services, and stakeholders, supported by digital knowledge platforms such as the AKIS Knowledge Portal and initiatives like the Ideas Exchange Facility.

Monitoring and evaluation

Slovenia's CAP NSP sets clear monitoring and evaluation targets across knowledge, innovation, and digital transition. Under R.1, the Plan aims for 83,336 people to benefit from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in operational groups of the European Innovation Partnerships supported by the CAP to improve economic, social, environmental, climate, and resource efficiency performance. For R.2, it targets support for 510 extension workers to be integrated into AKIS. Under R.3, 4.28% of farms are expected to receive support for digital farming technologies.

Complementing R.1, indicator R.28 sets a target of 57,186 people benefiting from advisory and learning activities focused specifically on environmental and climate performance. Finally, R.40 seeks to back 24 smart village strategies, advancing a smart transition of the rural economy.

AKIS Factsheet³⁷

The i2connect project found that Slovenia’s AKIS had not yet been the subject of specific analysis. It determined that knowledge, creativity, and innovation are key deficits in Slovenian sustainable development, evident in the following shortcomings: task duplication across knowledge-creating institutions; sporadic cooperation driven by informal expert ties rather than systemic design; slow knowledge transfer to end-users; and a particularly weak feedback flow of practical needs back to the research sphere.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- **About farm advice:** Farm advisory services in Slovenia are centralised and organised within the Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry of Slovenia (CAFS). Core advice across agricultural production is delivered by field advisers in CAFS local offices, supported by specialised second line advisers. By contrast, the private consultancy market remains underdeveloped.
- **About public policies:** Slovenia places AKIS as a central vehicle for knowledge transfer. Current upgrades prioritise stronger innovation, organisational capacity and research. However, the support mechanisms, remain much as before: integrated funding for public services, agricultural education and scientific research, complemented by rural development measures for cooperation and knowledge transfer. Going forward, more effective pathways are needed to move knowledge from research and education, through public services and public agricultural advisory services, to producers.
- **Some trends:** The practical implementation of a comprehensive monitoring system for the Slovenian AKIS continues to present a complex challenge.

³⁷ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the author of the report: **Igor Hrovatičš**. We thank him for his work. <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/REtcZoZSxnxgmFZ#pdfviewer>

Spain

Extension	Population (2024)	Population Density	Rural Population (2024)
505,983 km ²	48,610,458	96.1 people/km ²	18.2%
Labour Force (2024)	Unemployment (2024)	Gender Equality Index (2022)	
24,386,307	11.4%	76.7 (EU: 71.0)	
GDP (2024)	GDP per Capita (2024)	Agriculture's Contribution to GDP (2024)	
1,591,627 million EUR	32,590 EUR	2.4%	

State of the Agricultural Sector

Land Use (2022 est.)				
Agriculture: 53.4%; forest: 37.2%; other: 9.5%				
Utilised Agricultural Area (2022)	Arable	Permanent Grassland and Meadows	Permanent Crops	
24,583 K ha	11,690 K ha (47.6%)	7,782 K ha (31.7%)	5,111 K ha (20.8%)	
Area of Extensive Grazing (% UAA) (2020)				
7,704,239 ha (31.5% UAA)				
Number of Farms (2020)	Agricultural Factor Income (Real) per Full Time Worker (2024)		Share of Direct Payments as a Part of Total Receipts (2023)	
914,870	37,001 EUR/AWU		7%	
Type of Farms (2020)				
Family Farms (50% or More Family Workers)		Non-Family Farms		
87%		13%		
Average Farm Size (2020)	Average Family Farm Size		Average Non-Family Farm Size	
26 ha	N/A (Eurostat Agricultural Census data for Slovenia and Spain not comparable with other Member States)			
Average Economic Farm Size (2020)				
Average Farm Income: 68,696 EUR (2022) (Eurostat Agricultural Census data for Slovenia and Spain not comparable with other Member States)				
Farm Size Distribution (Based on Standard Output) (2020)				
Very Small Farms (<8,000 EUR)	Small Farms (8,000 EUR to 24,999 EUR)	Medium-Sized Farms (25,000 EUR to 99,999 EUR)	Large Farms (100,000 EUR to 499,999 EUR)	Very Large Farms (>500,000 EUR)
449,370 (49.12%)	212,280 (23.20%)	166,830 (18.24%)	72,750 (7.95%)	13,650 (1.49%)

Labour Force (AWU) (2020)		Agricultural Training of Farm Managers (2020)	
826 K		Basic: 20% (EU: 18%)	Full: 4% (EU: 10%)
Share of Farm Managers 55+ Years Old (2020)	Share of Farm Managers <35 Years Old (2020)	Ratio of Farm Managers <35 y.o. vs 55+ (2020)	Share of Female Farm Managers (2016)
66.8%	3.9%	0.06	23% (EU: 28%)

State of Digitalisation at the Country Level

Internet Users (% of Population) (2024)	% of Individuals with at Least Basic Digital Skills (2023)	E-Government Users (% of Population) (2024)	Women in Digital Index (2024)
94.98% (EU: 91.67%)	66.18% (EU: 55.56%)	82.70% (EU: 74.71%)	64.0 (EU: 54.8)
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) (% Households) (2024)	Fibre to the Premises (FTTP) (% Households) (2024)	Overall 5G Coverage (2024)	ICT Specialists (2024)
95.0% (EU: 82.5%)	94.9% (EU: 69.2%)	95.7% (EU: 94.3%)	4.7% (EU: 5.0%)
Digitalisation of SMEs (%)			
SMEs with at Least a Basic Level of Digital Intensity (2024)		AI or Cloud or Data Analytics (2023)	
74.2% (EU: 72.9%)		49.9% (EU: 54.6%)	

Digitalisation in the CAP NSP³⁸

Prioritisation Level

Digitalisation is addressed under cross-cutting need 10.04, which is classified as “Not prioritised” within the national framework. Although it is marked as “addressed in the CAP NSP”, its lack of prioritisation places it outside the three formal tiers that steer intervention focus, namely high (+++), medium (++), and low (+). In practical terms, digitalisation is institutionally acknowledged but does not rank among the needs that receive structured, strategic priority. This is particularly evident when contrasted with need 02.09 (Promoting R&D&I, digitalisation and consultancy), which is explicitly rated as a high priority (+++). This discrepancy suggests that while digitalisation is valued as a component of innovation (R&D&I), it is not deemed a standalone strategic priority for direct intervention in its own right.

Description and operational detail of digitalisation within the NSP

The NSP places digitalisation within the national Digitalisation Strategy for the Agri-Food, Forestry and Rural Areas (2019), which provides the foundational framework, targeting the digital divide, enhanced data use, and innovative business models. This is operationalised by the II Action Plan (2021-2023), which funds non-formal digital training, the AKIS Advisors Platform, competitive grants, and connectivity programs including 5G deployment. Key measures co-funded by the CAP include creating a centralised agri-food data platform (BigMAPA), support for digital entrepreneurship, a FIWARE-based digital innovation hub, and a Digitalisation Observatory to monitor technology adoption. These national efforts are substantially complemented by regional programs, which deploy both CAP and non-CAP funds to deliver targeted training, advisory services, and knowledge networks related to digitalisation. This observatory, often in collaboration with public-private partners like the Cajamar Cooperative Group, tracks the progress of digitalisation across the sector.

Alignment of digitalisation goals with other CAP priorities

The Plan aligns its digitalisation goals with wider CAP priorities by positioning digital tools and innovation as enablers of environmental and climate action. The document links digitalisation to the shift towards more sustainable production models, including organic farming, and to the optimisation of inputs such as fertilisers and phytosanitary products. It also frames digital technologies as supports for climate change mitigation and adaptation, helping to implement changes in production systems that lower greenhouse gas emissions and increase carbon sequestration. Beyond the environmental dimension, the NSP connects digitalisation to socio-economic development by emphasising its role in strengthening competitiveness and market orientation across the agri-food sector. Tools such as blockchain are highlighted for improving product traceability and opening access to alternative marketing channels, expanding opportunities for producers, especially in rural areas. Furthermore, digitalisation is presented as a lever for generational renewal and for the greater participation of young people and women in agriculture, contributing to the revitalisation of rural communities.

Promotion of specific digital technologies or innovations

The NSP presents digitalisation as a means to strengthen competitiveness, sustainability and innovation across agriculture, while making only limited, targeted references to specific technologies. It highlights precision agriculture and so

³⁸ Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (n.d.). *The Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2027 and the Strategic Plan*. Retrieved from <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/pac/pac-2023-2027/> (Accessed: 19 September 2025)

called 4.0 approaches, together with precision livestock farming, as supports for more sustainable and adapted production models that raise efficiency and reduce the use of natural resources and inputs such as fertilisers and pesticides. These methods are framed within wider environmental and climate goals, including emission reduction and resource optimisation. The Plan also describes institutional and technical instruments to foster digital innovation, including a FIWARE-based digital innovation hub, a sector-wide data aggregation platform, and a Digitalisation Observatory to track uptake. Core infrastructures include the Agricultural Holdings Information System (SIEX) for the integration of farm data, alongside tools such as the CAP digital notebook and predictive models like FRUKTIA to improve management and compliance. Blockchain is cited for strengthening product traceability and opening access to alternative markets. Overall, the technologies referenced are diverse but presented chiefly at a programmatic level, with limited technical detail or operational guidance.

Consideration of digital inclusion, territorial equity, and strategies addressing the digital divide

The document incorporates elements addressing digital inclusion, territorial equity, and the digital divide. It frames the digital transition as necessary for the environmental transformation of farms and emphasises the principle of not leaving anyone behind, with a specific focus on small and medium-sized holdings due to their social importance and vital role in sustaining rural communities. The Plan explicitly links challenges in rural entrepreneurship (such as low rates of innovation, gender disparities, limited access to finance, and inadequate infrastructure) to broader issues of territorial equity. A key concern highlighted is the persistent gap in connectivity and the poor dissemination of existing initiatives, which hinders inclusive development.

To address these challenges, the NSP calls for comprehensive advice and knowledge transfer to accompany digitalisation, aiming to ensure equitable access to digital tools across territories and farm sizes. Furthermore, it explicitly links these efforts to broader national initiatives, noting that the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan (PRTR) supports investments in education and training through Component 19 (the National Digital Skills Plan). This component is specifically designed to foster digital skills and provide ICT training to reduce the digital divide and strengthen social inclusion, particularly for staff working with vulnerable groups. This multi-layered approach (combining CAP rural development measures with PRTR-funded digital literacy programmes) reflects a concerted effort to revitalise rural areas by addressing both technological and social barriers to inclusion.

AKIS within the NSP

The NSP outlines a complex, multi-level AKIS designed to enhance knowledge flows and innovation across the agri-food sector. Acknowledging the current system's reliance on regional and informal networks, the Plan explicitly aims to address the lack of a unified national governance structure. Strategic actions to strengthen the AKIS include robust support for European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) Operational Groups, the establishment of thematic programmes for knowledge exchange, and targeted training initiatives with a specific focus on boosting the digital skills of advisors. The Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA) is tasked with coordinating these national efforts. Key instruments led by MAPA include the creation of a national AKIS Advisors Platform and a Digital Innovation Hub (based on FIWARE technology) to foster cooperation between regions and sectors.

To institutionalise this framework, the NSP proposes the establishment of a formal, multi-level governance structure. This envisaged body would incorporate representatives from relevant ministries, research institutions, public and private advisory services, and farming stakeholders to ensure inclusive and systematic coordination. Ultimately, this national framework is designed to be substantially complemented and implemented by regional authorities. The regions are expected to deploy complementary actions (including training, advisory services, and cooperation projects) using both CAP and regional funds, thereby creating a cohesive yet decentralised system to reinforce knowledge creation and transfer on the ground.

Monitoring and evaluation

Spain's CAP NSP sets clear monitoring targets across knowledge, advisory, digital, environmental, and rural innovation outcomes. Under R.1, Spain aims for 1,165,582 people to benefit from CAP-supported advice, training, knowledge sharing, or participation in EIP Operational Groups to improve economic, social, environmental, climate, and resource efficiency performance. For R.2, the Plan targets support for 8,259 advisors to strengthen their integration into AKIS. Under R.3, 2.47% of farms are expected to benefit from support for digital farming technologies. For R.28, Spain sets a target of 208,518 people benefiting from advice, training, knowledge sharing, or participation in EIP operational groups funded by the CAP and related to environmental and climate outcomes. Finally, R.40 foresees support for 160 Smart Village strategies to advance a smart transition of the rural economy.

AKIS Factsheet³⁹

A defining feature of the Spanish AKIS is its decentralisation. This process, initiated following the Constitution of 1978, has transformed the system from a singular agricultural extension model into a heterogeneous, public-private advisory system. Consequently, significant differences now exist between autonomous regions, influenced by the prominence of local AKIS actors and the economic importance of specific agricultural sectors.

Some key characteristics can be highlighted:

- About farm advice:** The advisory landscape in Spain has evolved into a diverse panorama of providers, including producer organizations (e.g., unions, associations, cooperatives), private consulting firms, independent consultants, NGOs, and public entities. The most influential national-level Farmer-Based Organizations (FBOs) and Agri-food Cooperatives operate on a federal model with regional associations, granting them a strong connection and significant influence among farmers.
- About public policies:** The Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA) is progressively developing a multilevel AKIS governance structure that involves all relevant actors. However, significant contrasts persist in advisory systems across different autonomous regions and agricultural sectors.
- Some trends:** Innovation hubs, technology parks, and incubation centres are rapidly developing and connecting diverse nodes within the Spanish AKIS landscape. Advisory networks are expanding at multiple levels. In terms of digitalisation, a key initiative is the e-Agrarian Holding Information System (SIEX), which aims to create interoperability between the various information sources available for the agricultural, livestock, and forestry sectors.

³⁹ This section is based on the AKIS description implemented by the EU projects PRO AKIS and i2connect and reflects our synthesis of the work and views of the authors of the report: **Juan Pedro Romero Trueba, Carlos Salamanca Fresno, Raúl Carbonell Zarco, Natalia Catalina Barral, and Rodrigo Sousa Gómez.** We thank them for their work. <https://meteodocs.llkc.lv/index.php/s/j8aNeigwZEsNre6#pdfviewer>